

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

UC4 : PV potential analysis for public buildings

CIMNE

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Contents of this report

This report contains the results of the PV potential assessment for public buildings in the Zlín region (Czech Republic), using an automated script, given the map outline of each building and LiDAR data for the whole region.

The following figure summarizes the procedure done by the program. The first step is to limit the LiDAR data to the building area (as defined by the cadastre) so that the data belonging to the building is clearly defined. Secondly, only those data points belonging to the building are used to determine all the planes that shape the building rooftop while obtaining their area, azimuth and slope.

A shading study must be done first to assess the PV potential correctly. It is achieved by making a 3D model from the LiDAR points around the building (in a 200m x 200m square) and computing the shade this neighbourhood casts into the building rooftops. This shade is represented in a matrix and is calculated for a sample of points from the roof (about one point per square meter). Finally, with the shading matrix, the solar capacity is estimated using a SAM (System Advisor Model) Python library.

The report in the following pages contains the most important step-by-step results of this program simulation for each building. Firstly, there is a location summary, with an overworld map of the building, a closeup satellite image (as shown on the right), the LiDAR data used for the next steps and some basic information about the building location.

The LiDAR data is a point cloud with the building's x, y and z coordinates. It is used to know the height of each sampled point. Alongside an image of the LiDAR scatter plot, some basic information is displayed in order to give some insight into the quality of the data. As a reference, it is possible to simulate any building with more than 0.5 points/m², although the best results are achieved when point density is above 1 point/m².

With the LiDAR points from the building, a plane identification algorithm is applied to detect the different rooftops. To summarize its functionality, the program samples different planes and sees which ones fit better with the points from the building. A previous stage in which the building was segmented was necessary for complex buildings.

Once these planes are found, a postprocessing algorithm is applied. This postprocessing deletes planes that are too small (or have too few points to be trustworthy), deletes overlaps between planes and pierces holes (e.g. for a heat exhaust).

Finally, with the planes correctly identified, the shading algorithm is applied (for about one point sampled per square meter), and the PV power simulation is applied with the shading matrix. This simulation considers the solar panel to be exactly in the same azimuth and slope of the roof is attached to. The result is a heatmap, as shown on the right, in which it is easy to see which planes have a higher capacity and, within a particular plane, which areas are shaded by the building neighbourhood or by the building itself (in case there is any shading).

The modules used in this simulation are considered to have a peak power of 225 W/m², which is derived from considering a 2 m x 1 m panel with a peak power of 450 W. For this simulation, the standard module type from the PySAM library has been employed, with a module efficiency of 15% and a temperature power coefficient of -0.47%/°C. The inverter efficiency considered is 96% and the total system losses considered for the simulations amount to 14.08%.

The simulation considers the whole plane to be a solar panel, so results should be interpreted as the energy capability per square meter, because most planes will not likely be 100% filled with solar panels.

Buildings summary

Identifier	Municipality	Road	Road number	Latitude	Longitude	Name	Owner	Simulation results
eP-EAZK-001	Hluk	Sokolská	655	48.9891172N	17.5292961E	Kino Hluk	město Hluk	Correct
eP-EAZK-002	Karolinka	Kobylská	391	49.3541422N	18.2310311E	Školní budova	město Karolinka	Correct
eP-EAZK-003	Karolinka	Nábřežní	175	49.3526650N	18.2401997E	Objekt pro charitu	město Karolinka	Correct
eP-EAZK-004	Bánov	-	428	48.9880614N	17.7181519E	Hasičská zbrojnice	obec Bánov	Correct
eP-EAZK-005	Pozlovice	Hlavní	361	49.1210800N	17.7634753E	Šatny pro sportovce	městys Pozlovice	Correct
eP-EAZK-006	Karolinka	Vsetínská	73	49.3514808N	18.2382256E	Objekt občanské vybavenosti	město Karolinka	Correct
eP-EAZK-007	Bohuslavice u Zlína	-	114	49.1634397N	17.6358825E	Hasičská zbrojnice	obec Bohuslavice u Zlína	Correct
eP-EAZK-008	Petrůvka	-	39	49.1070575N	17.8084028E	Kulturní dům	obec Petrůvka	Correct
eP-EAZK-009	Horní Bečva	-	799	49.4320256N	18.2801986E	Objekt TJ Sokol	obec Horní Bečva	Correct
eP-EAZK-010	Liptál	-	81	49.2908314N	17.9227578E	Dům služeb	obec Liptál	Correct
eP-EAZK-011	Zubří	Hlavní	492	49.4663036N	18.0908983E	Sportovní hala	město Zubří	Correct
eP-EAZK-012	Poličná	-	23	49.4641481N	17.9447531E	Drážní domek	obec Poličná	Correct
eP-EAZK-013	Horní Lhota	-	155	49.1547661N	17.8050494E	Kulturní dům	obec Horní Lhota	Correct
eP-EAZK-014	Podolí	-	244	49.0399458N	17.5271575E	Mateřská škola	obec Podolí	Correct
eP-EAZK-015	Topolná	-	204	49.1213142N	17.5402761E	Komunitní dům	obec Topolná	Correct
eP-EAZK-016	Šarovy	-	70	49.1485247N	17.6069619E	Kulturní dům	obec Šarovy	Correct
eP-EAZK-017	Dolní Bečva	-	184	49.4543750N	18.1960239E	Knihovna	obec Dolní Bečva	Correct
eP-EAZK-018	Karolinka	Na Horebečví	635	49.3523917N	18.2496886E	Šatny pro sportovce	město Karolinka	Correct
eP-EAZK-019	Racková	-	166	49.2780256N	17.6250853E	Kulturní dům	obec Racková	Correct
eP-EAZK-020	Dolní Bečva	-	618	49.4524139N	18.1915853E	Sportstadion	obec Dolní Bečva	Correct
eP-EAZK-021	Slavkov	-	114	48.9456653N	17.6118619E	Obecní úřad	obec Slavkov	Correct
eP-EAZK-022	Bohuslavice nad Vlčí	-	130	49.0899983N	17.9297975E	Prodejna a pohostinství	obec Bohuslavice nad Vlčí	Correct
eP-EAZK-023	Horní Bečva	-	655	49.4324694N	18.2883286E	Kulturní dům	obec Horní Bečva	Correct
eP-EAZK-024	Nedakonice	-	33	49.0314153N	17.3857583E	Obecní úřad a hasičská zbrojnice	obec Nedakonice	Correct
eP-EAZK-025	Valašská Bystřice	-	470	49.4141706N	18.1090697E	Hasičská zbrojnice	obec Valašská Bystřice	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-026	Dřínov	-	71	49.2911483N	17.2332933E	Mateřská škola	obec Dřínov	Correct
eP-EAZK-027	Hrobice	-	76	49.2778858N	17.7904214E	Mateřská škola	obec Hrobice	Correct
eP-EAZK-028	Hřivínův Újezd	-	141	49.1207947N	17.6914792E	Prodejna smíšeného zboží	obec Hřivínův Újezd	Correct
eP-EAZK-029	Nový Hrozenkov	-	437	49.3384267N	18.1985775E	Základní škola - budova A a D	obec Nový Hrozenkov	Correct
eP-EAZK-030	Podolí	-	53	49.0422228N	17.5271497E	Základní škola	obec Podolí	Correct

Identifier	Municipality	Road	Road number	Latitude	Longitude	Name	Owner	Simulation results
eP-EAZK-031	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Masarykovo náměstí	128 - 131	49.4575975N	18.1426811E	Městský úřad	město Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Correct
eP-EAZK-032	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Letenská	1918	49.4634569N	18.1433422E	Městský úřad	město Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Correct
eP-EAZK-033	Spytihněv	-	520	49.1427042N	17.4964589E	Mateřská škola	obec Spytihněv	Correct
eP-EAZK-034	Žlutava	-	191	49.1994128N	17.4907114E	Tělocvična	obec Žlutava	Correct
eP-EAZK-035	Uherské Hradiště	Velehradská třída	247	49.0710817N	17.4611850E	Objekt charity	charita Uherské Hradiště	Correct
eP-EAZK-036	Zubří	Sídlištní	1749	49.4643511N	18.0903303E	Lékařský dům	město Zubří	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-037	Zubří	Sídlištní	1748	49.4643358N	18.0907878E	Komunitní dům pro seniory	město Zubří	Correct
eP-EAZK-038	Hluk	nám. Komenského	162	48.9873194N	17.5263836E	Tvrz	město Hluk	Correct
eP-EAZK-039	Holešov	Příční	1475	49.3345072N	17.5773417E	Domov pro seniory	město Holešov	Correct
eP-EAZK-040	Horní Němčí	-	-	48.9412306N	17.6202003E	Čistírna odpadních vod	obec Horní Němčí	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-041	Luhačovice	Uherskobrodská	188	49.0904425N	17.7388822E	Budova technických služeb města	město Luhačovice	Correct
eP-EAZK-042	Korytná	-	297	48.9414072N	17.6656731E	Obecní úřad	obec Korytná	Correct
eP-EAZK-043	Kostelec u Holešova	-	191	49.3734369N	17.5117464E	Základní škola	obec Kostelec u Holešova	Correct
eP-EAZK-044	Luhačovice	Komenského	301	49.099992N	17.7537781E	Mateřská škola	město Luhačovice	Correct
eP-EAZK-045	Luhačovice	Masarykova	137	49.0988092N	17.7557764E	Objekt občanské vybavenosti	město Luhačovice	Correct
eP-EAZK-046	Nedašov	-	370	49.1113136N	18.0628392E	Obecní úřad a kulturní dům	obec Nedašov	Correct
eP-EAZK-047	Štítná nad Vláří-Popov	-	415	49.0692117N	17.9782103E	Kulturní dům	obec Štítná nad Vláří-Popov	Correct
eP-EAZK-048	Velký Ořechov	-	49	49.1098892N	17.6694044E	Základní škola	obec Velký Ořechov	Correct
eP-EAZK-049	Vlčnov	-	186	49.0100961N	17.5802542E	Objekt občanské vybavenosti	obec Vlčnov	Correct
eP-EAZK-050	Zlín	náměstí Míru	12	49.2265694N	17.6661547E	Radnice	statutární město Zlín	Correct
eP-EAZK-051	Zlín	Soudní	1	49.2257686N	17.6631897E	Zámek	statutární město Zlín	Correct
eP-EAZK-052	Zubří	Školní	540	49.4698242N	18.0901939E	Základní škola	město Zubří	Correct
eP-EAZK-053	Horní Němčí	-	350	48.9324072N	17.6238058E	Kulturní dům	obec Horní Němčí	Correct
eP-EAZK-054	Komárno	-	49	49.4339722N	17.7787561E	Obecní úřad	obec Komárno	Correct
eP-EAZK-055	Bezměrov	-	104	49.3288850N	17.3379492E	Kulturní dům	obec Bezměrov	Correct
eP-EAZK-056	Strání - Květná	nám. Em. Zahna	682	48.8850397N	17.7213131E	Kulturní dům	obec Strání	Correct
eP-EAZK-057	Strání - Květná	nám. Em. Zahna	682	48.8850678N	17.7207444E	Restaurace	obec Strání	Correct
eP-EAZK-058	Březůvky	-	1	49.1546367N	17.6987075E	Víceúčelový objekt	obec Březůvky	Correct
eP-EAZK-059	Brusné	-	95	49.3633211N	17.6608828E	Prodejna smíšeného zboží	obec Brusné	Correct

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eP-EAZK-060	Huslenky	-	290	49.3076842N	18.1090558E	Základní škola	obec Huslenky	Correct
eP-EAZK-061	Dolní Lhota	-	129	49.1386089N	17.8112711E	Víceúčelový objekt	obec Dolní Lhota	Correct
eP-EAZK-062	Horní Lideč	-	292	49.1878781N	18.0569481E	Obecní úřad	obec Horní Lideč	Correct
eP-EAZK-063	Otrokovice	Jiráskova	1338	49.2091353N	17.5322158E	Depozitář	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-064	Kašava	-	192	49.3007817N	17.7917519E	Bytový dům	obec Kašava	Correct
eP-EAZK-065	Kašava	-	100	49.2978297N	17.7872581E	Knihovna	obec Kašava	Correct
eP-EAZK-066	Vlachovice	-	260	49.1242439N	17.9394994E	Kulturní dům	obec Vlachovice	Correct
eP-EAZK-067	Kašava	-	217	49.2977658N	17.7880858E	Obecní dům	obec Kašava	Correct
eP-EAZK-068	Nivnice	Sídlíště	870	48.9782986N	17.6479275E	Mateřská škola	obec Nivnice	Correct
eP-EAZK-069	Nivnice	Komenského	101	48.9723050N	17.6487036E	Základní škola - 2. stupeň	obec Nivnice	Correct
eP-EAZK-070	Nivnice	Osvobození	181	48.9755194N	17.6447453E	Základní škola - 1. stupeň	obec Nivnice	Correct
eP-EAZK-071	Pozdřechov	-	192	49.2377222N	17.9521917E	Základní a mateřská škola	obec Pozdřechov	Correct
eP-EAZK-072	Podhradní Lhota	-	175	49.4199192N	17.7952553E	Hasičská zbrojnice	obec Podhradní Lhota	Correct
eP-EAZK-073	Suchá Loz	-	265	48.9700394N	17.7137439E	Hasičská zbrojnice	obec Suchá Loz	Correct
eP-EAZK-074	Břestek	-	14	49.0935933N	17.3543950E	Obecní úřad a domov pro seniory	obec Břestek	Correct
eP-EAZK-075	Slavkov pod Hostýnem	-	189	49.3780539N	17.6711583E	Domov pro seniory	obec Slavkov pod Hostýnem	Correct
eP-EAZK-076	Zlín	Havlíčkovo náměstí	600	49.2275656N	17.7022342E	Krajská hygienická stanice / ředitelství KNTB a.s.	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-077	Prostřední Bečva	-	272	49.4368894N	18.2632211E	Obecní úřad	obec Prostřední Bečva	Correct
eP-EAZK-078	Slopné	-	74	49.1553567N	17.8471656E	Víceúčelový objekt	obec Slopné	Correct
eP-EAZK-079	Bařice - Velké Těšany	-	64	49.2452519N	17.4277228E	Bytový dům	obec Bařice- Velké Těšany	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-080	Vígantice	-	203	49.4405636N	18.1935536E	Obecní úřad	obec Vígantice	Correct
eP-EAZK-081	Holešov	Holešovská	1700	49.3195883N	17.5720039E	Požární stanice	Hasičský záchranný sbor Zlínského kraje	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-082	Holešov	Palackého	524	49.3286908N	17.5726319E	Gymnázium	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-083	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1241	49.2253589N	17.5110836E	Ubytovna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-084	Nový Hrozenkov	-	437	49.3388056N	18.1987378E	Základní škola - budova B	obec Nový Hrozenkov	Correct
eP-EAZK-085	Zlín	Vavrečkova	7040	49.2251286N	17.6587558E	Bařův institut	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-086	Bystřice pod Hostýnem	Holešovská	1737	49.3975350N	17.6603075E	Požární stanice	Hasičský záchranný sbor Zlínského kraje	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-087	Bojkovice	Husova	432	49.0394644N	17.8087575E	Kulturní dům	město Bojkovice	Correct
eP-EAZK-088	Brumov-Bylnice	Sidonie	44	49.0455392N	18.0780497E	Kulturní dům	město Brumov- Bylnice	Correct

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eP-EAZK-089	Valašské Klobouky	Československé armády	259	49.1396353N	18.0092756E	Katastrální úřad	město Valašské Klobouky	Correct
eP-EAZK-090	Boršice	-	176	49.3789556N	17.3563528E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-091	Buchlovice	U Domova	470	49.0864689N	17.3480517E	Domov pro seniory - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-092	Buchlovice	U Domova	470	49.0864689N	17.3480517E	Domov pro seniory - prádelna	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-091
eP-EAZK-093	Buchlovice	U Domova	470	49.0864689N	17.3480517E	Domov pro seniory - kotelna	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-091
eP-EAZK-094	Fryšták	Na Hrádku	100	49.2864478N	17.6835811E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-095	Hrobice	-	136	49.2801389N	17.7913472E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-096	Chvalčov	Javornická	830	49.3992328N	17.6942697E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - hlavní budova - kotelna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-097	Chvalčov	Javornická	831	49.3985833N	17.6947581E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - domeček 1	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-098	Chvalčov	Javornická	832	49.3983703N	17.6944039E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - domeček 2	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-099	Chvalčov	Javornická	833	49.3981469N	17.6940444E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - domeček 3	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-100	Chvalčov	Javornická	834	49.3984647N	17.6938647E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - domeček 4	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-101	Chvalčov	Javornická	830	49.3992328N	17.6942697E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-096
eP-EAZK-102	Chvalčov	Javornická	830	49.3992328N	17.6942697E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - prádelna	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-096
eP-EAZK-103	Chvalčov	Javornická	830	49.3992328N	17.6942697E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - dílny	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-096
eP-EAZK-104	Uherské Hradiště - Jarošov	U Cihelny	259	49.0788128N	17.4864642E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-105	Karolinka	Pod Obecnici	308	49.3543878N	18.2647167E	Domov pro seniory - budova A	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-106	Karolinka	Pod Obecnici	308	49.3543878N	18.2647167E	Domov pro seniory - budova B	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-105
eP-EAZK-107	Karolinka	Pod Obecnici	308	49.3543878N	18.2647167E	Domov pro seniory - budova A - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-105
eP-EAZK-108	Kroměříž	Kojetínská	1126/54	49.3002994N	17.3865825E	Chráněné bydlení - byt č.2	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-109	Kroměříž	Kojetínská	1126/54	49.3002994N	17.3865825E	Chráněné bydlení - byt č.3	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-108
eP-EAZK-110	Kroměříž	Kojetínská	1126/54	49.3002994N	17.3865825E	Chráněné bydlení - byt č.4	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-108
eP-EAZK-111	Kroměříž	Kojetínská	1126/54	49.3002994N	17.3865825E	Chráněné bydlení - byt č. 7	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-108
eP-EAZK-112	Kunovice	Lidická	1502	49.0414300N	17.4686639E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct

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eP-EAZK-113	Kunovice	Cihlářská	526	49.0372386N	17.4742119E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Split in 4 buildings
eP-EAZK-114	Kunovice	Na Bělince	1492	49.0446917N	17.4581947E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-115	Kvasice	Cukrovar	304	49.2439875N	17.4653508E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-116	Kvasice	Parková	21	49.2431178N	17.4739586E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-117	Loučka	-	128	49.1700378N	17.8830458E	Domov pro seniory	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-118	Loučka	-	119	49.1700133N	17.8839036E	Domov se zvláštním režimem	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-119	Luhačovice	V Drahách	1105	49.0964972N	17.7440175E	Domov pro seniory	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-120	Luhačovice	Mlýnská	560	49.0978561N	17.7466767E	Chráněné bydlení - 1.podlaží	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-121	Luhačovice	Mlýnská	560	49.0978561N	17.7466767E	Chráněné bydlení - 2.podlaží	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-120
eP-EAZK-122	Luhačovice	Mlýnská	560	49.0978561N	17.7466767E	Chráněné bydlení - 3.podlaží	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-120
eP-EAZK-123	Lukov	Hradská	82	49.2905731N	17.7300778E	Domov pro seniory	Zlínský kraj	Split in 4 buildings
eP-EAZK-124	Medlovice	-	90	49.0503139N	17.2710567E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-125	Morkovice - Sližany	Nádražní	144	49.2493681N	17.2092217E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-126	Napajedla	Husova	1165	49.1781953N	17.5228033E	Domov pro seniory	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-127	Návojná	-	100	49.1097256N	18.0533428E	Domov se zvláštním režimem	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-128	Nedakonice	-	589	49.0285247N	17.3860483E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-129	Nedakonice	-	590	49.0284922N	17.3860678E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-130	Nedakonice	-	600	49.0287458N	17.3859642E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-131	Nedakonice	-	601	49.0286583N	17.3860900E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-132	Pržno	-	9	49.3877453N	17.9422633E	Domov se zvláštním režimem	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-133	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Julia Fučíka	1605	49.4580733N	18.1476825E	Domov pro seniory	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-134	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Zemědělská	573	49.4609344N	18.1355047E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-135	Slavičín	Školní	276	49.0894914N	17.8787678E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-136	Staré Město	Tyršova	1626	49.0734833N	17.4417853E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-137	Staré Město	Velehradská	2169	49.0819011N	17.4372903E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-138	Uherský Brod	Okružní	1519	49.0270131N	17.6614967E	Domov se zvláštním režimem	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-139	Uherský Brod	Antonína Dvořáka	1248	49.0275689N	17.6385367E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-140	Uherský Brod	Na Dlouhých	1205	49.0284114N	17.6367844E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data

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eP-EAZK-141	Uherský Brod	Slovácké náměstí	2034	49.0196058N	17.6485269E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-142	Uherské Hradiště	Štěpnická	1139	49.0641764N	17.4477953E	Domov pro seniory - velkoodběr	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-143	Uherské Hradiště	Štěpnická	1139	49.0641764N	17.4477953E	Domov pro seniory - maloodběr	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-142
eP-EAZK-144	Uherské Hradiště	Rostislavova	686	49.0642542N	17.4684942E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-145	Uherské Hradiště	Rostislavova	671	49.0645897N	17.4708778E	Chráněné bydlení - byt 1	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-146	Uherské Hradiště	Rostislavova	671	49.0645897N	17.4708778E	Chráněné bydlení - byt 2	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-145
eP-EAZK-147	Uherské Hradiště	Rostislavova	671	49.0645897N	17.4708778E	Chráněné bydlení - byt 3	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-145
eP-EAZK-148	Uherské Hradiště	Rostislavova	671	49.0645897N	17.4708778E	Chráněné bydlení - byt 5	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-145
eP-EAZK-149	Uherské Hradiště	Rostislavova	671	49.0645897N	17.4708778E	Chráněné bydlení - společné prostory	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-145
eP-EAZK-150	Uherský Ostroh	Školní	774	48.9872200N	17.3980139E	Domov pro seniory	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-151	Valašské Meziříčí	Václavkova	919	49.4827331N	17.9645561E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - budova A	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-152	Valašské Meziříčí	Václavkova	919	49.4827331N	17.9645561E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - budova B	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-151
eP-EAZK-153	Valašské Meziříčí	Husova	402/15	49.4691019N	17.9654442E	Poradna - hlavní budova	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-154	Valašské Meziříčí	Husova	404/17	49.4690597N	17.9649383E	Poradna - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-155	Valašské Meziříčí	Žerotínova	1568	49.4717400N	17.9780744E	Domov pro seniory	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-156	Velehrad	Buchlovská	301	49.1059111N	17.3894367E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-157	Velehrad	Nádvoří	305	49.1026050N	17.3965978E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-158	Vsetín	Rokytnice	48	49.3277108N	17.9830192E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-159	Vsetín	Dolní Jasenka	2274	49.3469200N	17.9959644E	Domov pro seniory	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-160	Zašová	-	825	49.4793625N	18.0433064E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-161	Zborovice	Hlavní	1	49.2516208N	17.2815483E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-162	Zlín	Burešov	3675	49.2353117N	17.6903511E	Dětské centrum	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-163	Zlín	Burešov	4884	49.2346461N	17.6896797E	Domov pro seniory - kotelna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-164	Zlín	Burešov	4884	49.2346461N	17.6896797E	Domov pro seniory - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-163
eP-EAZK-165	Zlín	U Náhonu	5208	49.2292375N	17.6760369E	Centrum poradenství	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-166	Zlín	Pod Vodojemem	3651	49.2229236N	17.6771647E	Týdenní stacionář	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-167	Zubří	Hamerská	715	49.4636764N	18.0870250E	Chráněné bydlení	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-168	Nezdenice	-	233	49.0193983N	17.7547231E	Domov pro seniory	Zlínský kraj	Correct

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eP-EAZK-169	Staré Město	Kopánky	2052	49.0790242N	17.4312606E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - kotelna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-170	Staré Město	Kopánky	2052	49.0790242N	17.4312606E	Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-169
eP-EAZK-171	Holešov	Nádražní	525	49.3276925N	17.5700936E	Odborné učiliště	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-172	Holešov	Palackého	437	49.3287664N	17.5712261E	Základní praktická škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-173	Holešov	Bezručova	675/7	49.3306644N	17.5861558E	Základní umělecká škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-174	Kelč	nám. Osvoboditelů	-	49.4766003N	17.8166433E	Odborné učiliště - kotelna, tělocvična	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-175	Kelč	nám. Osvoboditelů	-	49.4774836N	17.8157767E	Odborné učiliště - zahrada	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-176	Kelč	nám. Osvoboditelů	-	49.4773494N	17.8135922E	Odborné učiliště - dílny	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-177	Kelč	nám. Osvoboditelů	1	49.4779500N	17.8158322E	Odborné učiliště - zámek	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-178	Kroměříž	U Sýpek	1306/3	49.2986972N	17.3845272E	Dětský domov	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-179	Kroměříž	Masarykovo náměstí	496/13	49.2970706N	17.3899311E	Gymnázium	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-180	Kroměříž	Pilařova	7	49.2981703N	17.3904739E	Konzervatoř	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-181	Kroměříž	Obvodová	3503/7	49.2953042N	17.4076006E	Obchodní akademie	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-182	Kroměříž	Nábělkova	539/3	49.2942478N	17.3967892E	Centrum odborné přípravy technické	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-183	Kroměříž	Nádražní	3550	49.3017047N	17.4026978E	Střední škola hotelová a služeb - restaurace	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-184	Kroměříž	Kojetínská	-	49.3053489N	17.3824528E	Střední škola hotelová a služeb - budova A	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-185	Kroměříž	Kojetínská	-	49.3051989N	17.3832433E	Střední škola hotelová a služeb - kotelna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-186	Kroměříž	Kojetínská	-	49.3051989N	17.3832433E	Střední škola hotelová a služeb - stáže	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-187	Kroměříž	Na Lindovce	1463/1	49.3021369N	17.3800972E	Střední škola hotelová a služeb	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-188	Kroměříž	Pavláková	3942	49.3012781N	17.3814706E	Střední škola hotelová a služeb - kotelna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-189	Kroměříž	Pavláková	-	49.3014706N	17.3818892E	Střední škola hotelová a služeb - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-190	Kroměříž	Pavláková	-	49.3016944N	17.3822781E	Střední škola hotelová a služeb - škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-191	Kroměříž	Kojetínská	2679/84	49.3036506N	17.3836228E	Střední škola hotelová a služeb - sportovní areál	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-192	Kroměříž	Albertova	4261/25 a	49.2910475N	17.3813786E	Střední zdravotnická škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-193	Kroměříž	1. máje	221/10	49.2961881N	17.3938544E	Vyšší odborná škola pedagogická a sociální a Střední pedagogická škola A	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-194	Kroměříž	1. máje	221/10	49.2961881N	17.3938544E	Vyšší odborná škola pedagogická a sociální a Střední pedagogická škola B	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-193

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eP-EAZK-195	Kroměříž	1. máje	221/10	49.2961881N	17.3938544E	Vyšší odborná škola pedagogická a sociální a Střední pedagogická škola C	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-193
eP-EAZK-196	Kroměříž	Štěchovice	1358/16	49.2999603N	17.3838017E	Vyšší odborná škola potravinářská a Střední průmyslová škola mlékárenská - kotelna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-197	Kroměříž	Štěchovice	1358/16	49.2999603N	17.3838017E	Vyšší odborná škola potravinářská a Střední průmyslová škola mlékárenská - laboratoře	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-196
eP-EAZK-198	Kroměříž	1. máje	209/14	49.2963747N	17.3927122E	Základní škola - škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-199	Kroměříž	1. máje	209/14	49.2963747N	17.3927122E	Základní škola - byt	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-198
eP-EAZK-200	Kroměříž	Františka Vančury	3695/2	49.3009042N	17.3774217E	Základní škola a Matefská škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-201	Liptál	-	233	49.2929928N	17.9307056E	Základní škola a dětský domov - Základní škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-202	Liptál	-	-	49.2925553N	17.9286242E	Základní škola a dětský domov - Hospodářská budova	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-203	Liptál	-	91	49.2923561N	17.9279481E	Základní škola a dětský domov - Dětský domov	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-204	Luhačovice	Hradisko	290	49.0943353N	17.7499458E	Střední odborná škola - dílny	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-205	Luhačovice	Masarykova	999	49.0989281N	17.7547758E	Střední odborná škola - internát	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-206	Luhačovice	Masarykova	101	49.0958669N	17.7476669E	Střední odborná škola - škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-207	Napajedla	Komenského	305	49.1718092N	17.5148711E	Základní umělecká škola	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-208	Otrokovice	tř. Spojenců	907	49.2172508N	17.5122850E	Gymnázium - budova A	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-209	Otrokovice	Školní	726	49.2167336N	17.5124011E	Gymnázium - budova B	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-210	Otrokovice	tř. Spojenců	907	49.2172508N	17.5122850E	Gymnázium - byt	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-208
eP-EAZK-211	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1266	49.2243944N	17.5120281E	Střední průmyslová škola - domov mládeže 1	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-212	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1624	49.2244397N	17.5110725E	Střední průmyslová škola - autodílna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-213	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1581	49.2238700N	17.5108772E	Střední průmyslová škola - budova A	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-214	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1269	49.2241619N	17.5112386E	Střední průmyslová škola - budova B	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-215	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1267	49.2237750N	17.5113656E	Střední průmyslová škola - budova C	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-216	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1268	49.2251639N	17.5117589E	Střední průmyslová škola - domov mládeže 2	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-217	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1582	49.2248219N	17.5113283E	Střední průmyslová škola - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-218	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1270	49.2259011N	17.5115961E	Střední průmyslová škola - sportovní hala	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-219	Otrokovice	Tř. Tomáše Bati	1266	49.2243944N	17.5120281E	Střední průmyslová škola - domov mládeže 1 - kanceláře	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-211

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eP-EAZK-220	Otrokovice	Komenského	1855	49.2121617N	17.5323675E	Základní škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-221	Otrokovice	Školní	806	49.2166686N	17.5121414E	Základní umělecká škola	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-222	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Koryčanské Paseky	1725	49.4664142N	18.1289961E	Gymnázium	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-223	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Zemědělská	500	49.4609686N	18.1364600E	Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - domov mládeže	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-224	Vidče	Hradisko	-	49.4501308N	18.1169525E	Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - kravín	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-225	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Tvarůzkova	-	49.4522764N	18.1482558E	Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - seník	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-226	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	nábřeží Dukelských hrdinů	570	49.4611642N	18.1389536E	Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-227	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Zemědělská	574	49.4609589N	18.1368975E	Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - vila	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-228	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Tyršovo nábřeží	649	49.4583553N	18.1356100E	Základní škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-229	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Pionýrská	20	49.4609369N	18.1423547E	Základní umělecká škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-230	Slavičín	Školní	822	49.0905417N	17.8802092E	Gymnázium	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-231	Slavičín	Divnice	119	49.0992225N	17.9150158E	Střední odborná škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-232	Staré Město	Velehradská	1527	49.0804931N	17.4383050E	Střední odborná škola a Gymnázium - kotelna 1	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-233	Staré Město	Velehradská	1527	49.0804931N	17.4383050E	Střední odborná škola a Gymnázium - kotelna 2	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-232
eP-EAZK-234	Uherské Hradiště	Revoluční	747	49.0695119N	17.4504306E	Střední odborná škola a Gymnázium	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-235	Uherské Hradiště	Jiřího z Poděbrad	313	49.0653497N	17.4634844E	Dětský domov	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-236	Uherské Hradiště	Nádražní	22	49.0670825N	17.4591850E	Obchodní akademie	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-237	Uherské Hradiště	Jiřího z Poděbrad	822	49.0659628N	17.4634169E	Střední škola průmyslová, hotelová a zdravotnická	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-238	Uherské Hradiště	Kollárova	617	49.0664019N	17.4627583E	Střední škola průmyslová, hotelová a zdravotnická - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-239	Uherské Hradiště	Jiřího z Poděbrad	949	49.0658686N	17.4623778E	Střední škola průmyslová, hotelová a zdravotnická	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-240	Uherské Hradiště	Kollárova	617	49.0663183N	17.4621931E	Střední škola průmyslová, hotelová a zdravotnická	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-241	Uherské Hradiště	Tř. Maršála Malinovského	368	49.0640469N	17.4667556E	Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola - A	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-242	Uherské Hradiště	Tř. Maršála Malinovského	368	49.0640469N	17.4667556E	Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola - B	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-241
eP-EAZK-243	Uherské Hradiště	Všehrdova	267	49.0684194N	17.4654647E	Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola - A	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-244	Uherské Hradiště	Všehrdova	267	49.0684194N	17.4654647E	Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola - B	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-243
eP-EAZK-245	Uherský Brod	Komenského	169	49.0231889N	17.6449331E	Gymnázium	Zlínský kraj	Split in 3 buildings

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eP-EAZK-246	Uherský Brod	Na Výsluní	813	49.0290494N	17.6410161E	Střední odborné učiliště - dílny	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-247	Uherský Brod	Na Výsluní	813	49.0291461N	17.6415150E	Střední odborné učiliště - domov mládeže	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-248	Uherský Brod	Svatopluka Čecha	1110	49.0267797N	17.6395369E	Střední odborné učiliště	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-249	Uherský Brod	Svatopluka Čecha	1111	49.0267375N	17.6386814E	Střední odborné učiliště	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-250	Uherský Brod	Vazová	2509	49.0209178N	17.6334928E	Střední odborné učiliště	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-251	Uherský Brod	Větrná	1370	49.0300581N	17.6588153E	Střední průmyslová škola a Obchodní akademie - domov mládeže	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-252	Uherský Brod	Předbranská	415	49.0219133N	17.6509817E	Střední průmyslová škola a Obchodní akademie	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-253	Uherský Brod	Nivnická	1781	49.0027625N	17.6506058E	Střední průmyslová škola a Obchodní akademie	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-254	Uherský Brod	Obchodní	2055	49.0255872N	17.6538567E	Střední škola - COPT	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-255	Uherský Ostroh	Sokolovská	620	48.9856633N	17.3981867E	Dětský domov	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-256	Valašské Klobouky	Brumovská	456	49.1320469N	18.0115675E	Střední odborné učiliště	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-257	Valašské Klobouky	Smolína	16	49.1548417N	17.9967503E	Dětský domov, základní škola a praktická škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-258	Valašské Klobouky	Smetanova	116	49.1417056N	18.0064944E	Základní umělecká škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-259	Valašské Meziříčí	Žerotínova	211/22	49.4710694N	17.9763031E	Dětský domov	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-260	Valašské Meziříčí	Husova	146/2	49.4702183N	17.9688756E	Gymnázium	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-261	Valašské Meziříčí	Palackého	239/49	49.4636683N	17.9674922E	Integrovaná střední škola - COP	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-262	Valašské Meziříčí	Jičínská	97	49.4771881N	17.9728297E	Obchodní akademie a VOŠ	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-263	Valašské Meziříčí	Masarykova	101/18	49.4760308N	17.9716683E	Obchodní akademie a VOŠ	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-264	Valašské Meziříčí	Jičínská	17	49.4771169N	17.9753900E	Obchodní akademie a VOŠ	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-265	Valašské Meziříčí	Máchova	628/10	49.4688694N	17.9758567E	Střední průmyslová škola stavební	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-266	Valašské Meziříčí	Vrbenská	234	49.4742750N	17.9768417E	Střední průmyslová škola stavební - truhlářská dílna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-267	Valašské Meziříčí	Vrbenská	234	49.4741575N	17.9755233E	Střední průmyslová škola stavební - administrativní část	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-268	Valašské Meziříčí	Zašovská	100	49.4762331N	17.9800156E	Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola sklářská - domov mládeže	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-269	Valašské Meziříčí	U Skláren	842	49.4761703N	17.9794700E	Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola sklářská - huť	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-270	Valašské Meziříčí	Sklářská	603/8	49.4765936N	17.9794400E	Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola sklářská - škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-271	Valašské Meziříčí	Křížná	782	49.4722108N	17.9652642E	Základní škola, mateřská škola a praktická škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-272	Vízovice	Chrástěšovská	65	49.2240389N	17.8555981E	Dětský domov	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-273	Vízovice	Tyršova	874	49.2238769N	17.8441533E	Střední škola oděvní a služeb	Zlínský kraj	Correct

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eP-EAZK-274	Vizovice	3. května	528	49.2183650N	17.8497275E	Dětský domov a základní škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-275	Vsetín	nám. Svobody	809	49.3378433N	17.9942944E	Masarykovo gymnázium, střední zdravotnická škola a vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-276	Vsetín	Tyršova	1069	49.3384139N	17.9957617E	Masarykovo gymnázium, střední zdravotnická škola a vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická - část B a C	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-277	Vsetín	Tyršova	1069	49.3388036N	17.9958261E	Masarykovo gymnázium, střední zdravotnická škola a vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická - část A	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-278	Vsetín	Pod Strání	1776	49.3356192N	18.0013308E	Střední průmyslová škola strojnická	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-279	Vsetín	Turkmenská	1612	49.3321842N	18.0014944E	Základní a mateřská škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-280	Vsetín	Podsedy	285	49.3416686N	17.9961722E	Základní umělecká škola - hlavní budova	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-281	Vsetín	Podsedy	285	49.3419753N	17.9963319E	Základní umělecká škola - přístavek	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-282	Zlín	Lesní čtvrť III	1364	49.2182536N	17.6923586E	Gymnázium - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-283	Zlín	Lesní čtvrť III	1364	49.2182536N	17.6923586E	Gymnázium - hlavní budova	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-282
eP-EAZK-284	Zlín	Lazy I	3689	49.2189244N	17.6761828E	Dětský domov	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-285	Zlín	Lazy VI	3696	49.2197881N	17.6819806E	Dětský domov, Mateřská škola, Základní škola a Praktická škola - speciálně pedagogické centrum	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-286	Zlín	Lazy VI	3695	49.2196758N	17.6812269E	Dětský domov, Mateřská škola, Základní škola a Praktická škola - hlavní budova	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-287	Zlín	Lazy VI	3695	49.2196758N	17.6812269E	Dětský domov, Mateřská škola, Základní škola a Praktická škola - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-286
eP-EAZK-288	Zlín	nám. T. G. Masaryka	3669	49.2220439N	17.6650603E	Obchodní akademie Tomáše Bati a Vyšší odborná škola ekonomická	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-289	Zlín	Nad Ovčímou IV	2528	49.2199694N	17.6620028E	Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum odborné přípravy	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-290	Zlín	Růmy	1548	49.2198811N	17.6701506E	Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum odborné přípravy	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-291	Zlín	Růmy	4050	49.2195289N	17.6684281E	Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum odborné přípravy	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-292	Zlín	nám. T. G. Masaryka	2700	49.2196461N	17.6640508E	Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum odborné přípravy vytápění	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-293	Zlín	Růmy	596	49.2196167N	17.6703000E	Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum odborné přípravy	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-294	Zlín	nám. T. G. Masaryka	2700	49.2196461N	17.6640508E	Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-292

Identifier	Municipality	Road	Road number	Latitude	Longitude	Name	Owner	Simulation results
						odborné přípravy příprava teplé vody		
eP-EAZK-295	Zlín	Univerzitní	3015	49.2226283N	17.6675047E	Střední škola gastronomie a obchodu	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-296	Zlín	třída Tomáše Bati	4187	49.2201903N	17.6517564E	Střední průmyslová škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-297	Bystřice pod Hostýnem	Holešovská	394	49.3988967N	17.6640533E	Střední škola nábytkářská a obchodní - škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-298	Bystřice pod Hostýnem	Mlýnská	1425	49.3985178N	17.6665081E	Střední škola nábytkářská a obchodní - internát	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-299	Kroměříž	Štěchovice	1315/7a	49.2990072N	17.3830056E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - domov mládeže 1 - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-300	Kroměříž	Štěchovice	1321/7	49.2992494N	17.3832978E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - domov mládeže 2 - kotelna	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-301	Kroměříž	Štěchovice	1321/7	49.2988717N	17.3834375E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - tělocvična	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-302	Kroměříž	Štěchovice	1321/7	49.2992494N	17.3832978E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - domov mládeže 2	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP- EAZK-300
eP-EAZK-303	Kroměříž	Štěchovice	1315/7a	49.2990072N	17.3830056E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - domov mládeže 1	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP- EAZK-299
eP-EAZK-304	Kroměříž	Štěchovice	1315/7a	49.2990072N	17.3830056E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - byt	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP- EAZK-299
eP-EAZK-305	Kroměříž	Koperníkova	1435	49.3002519N	17.3799661E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - internát A	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-306	Kroměříž	Koperníkova	1435	49.3002519N	17.3799661E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - internát B	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP- EAZK-305
eP-EAZK-307	Kroměříž	Koperníkova	1429/22	49.3010786N	17.3799033E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - laboratoře 1	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-308	Kroměříž	Koperníkova	1429/22	49.3006725N	17.3803028E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - stáje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-309	Kroměříž	Koperníkova	1429/22	49.3010786N	17.3799033E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - laboratoře 2	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP- EAZK-307
eP-EAZK-310	Kroměříž	Koperníkova	1429/22	49.3006200N	17.3795756E	Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-311	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Školní	1610	49.4640158N	18.1276147E	Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel - domov mládeže 2	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-312	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Zemědělská	1077	49.4610511N	18.1331439E	Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel - praktická výuka	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-313	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Školní	1698	49.4646133N	18.1263200E	Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel - teoretická výuka	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-314	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	Svazarmovská	1508	49.4643861N	18.1289958E	Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel - domov mládeže 1	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-315	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	1.máje	1220	49.4610936N	18.1309153E	Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-316	Valašské Klobouky	Komenského	60	49.1402458N	18.0045900E	Gymnázium - hlavní budova	Zlínský kraj	Correct

Identifier	Municipality	Road	Road number	Latitude	Longitude	Name	Owner	Simulation results
eP-EAZK-317	Valašské Klobouky	Komenského	712	49.1393897N	18.0037258E	Gymnázium - domov mládeže	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-318	Valašské Klobouky	Komenského	712	49.1393897N	18.0037258E	Gymnázium - jídelna	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-317
eP-EAZK-319	Valašské Klobouky	Komenského	-	49.1397422N	18.0040881E	Gymnázium - sportovní hala	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-320	Vsetín	Družstevní	1646	49.3389775N	17.9824481E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-321	Vsetín	Bobrky	466	49.3624131N	17.9611089E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-322	Vsetín	Benátky	1779	49.3380986N	17.9833719E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-323	Vsetín	Školní	1824	49.3406172N	17.9881781E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka - šatna_salonky	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-324	Vsetín	Školní	1824	49.3406172N	17.9881781E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka - šatna_učebna	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-323
eP-EAZK-325	Vsetín	Školní	1824	49.3406172N	17.9881781E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka - jídelna	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-323
eP-EAZK-326	Vsetín	Školní	1824	49.3406172N	17.9881781E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka - restaurace	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-323
eP-EAZK-327	Vsetín	Školní	1824	49.3406172N	17.9881781E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka - vodárna	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-323
eP-EAZK-328	Vsetín	Školní	1824	49.3406172N	17.9881781E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka - kanceláře	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-323
eP-EAZK-329	Vsetín	Školní	1824	49.3406172N	17.9881781E	Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka - kryt CO	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-323
eP-EAZK-330	Zlín	nám. T. G. Masaryka	2734	49.2194586N	17.6668906E	Gymnázium a Jazyková škola - škola 1	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-331	Zlín	nám. T. G. Masaryka	2734	49.2194586N	17.6668906E	Gymnázium a Jazyková škola - škola 2	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-330
eP-EAZK-332	Zlín	nám. T. G. Masaryka	-	49.2191906N	17.6671856E	Gymnázium a Jazyková škola - sportovní hala 1	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-333	Zlín	nám. T. G. Masaryka	-	49.2191906N	17.6671856E	Gymnázium a Jazyková škola - sportovní hala 2	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-332
eP-EAZK-334	Zlín	Broučkova	372	49.2247561N	17.7025133E	Střední zdravotnická škola a Vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická - škola	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-335	Zlín	Broučkova	4062	49.2248939N	17.6999989E	Střední zdravotnická škola a Vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická - domov mládeže - kuchyně	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-336	Zlín	Broučkova	4062	49.2248939N	17.6999989E	Střední zdravotnická škola a Vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická - domov mládeže - ubytování	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-335
eP-EAZK-337	Slavičín	Komenského	-	49.0902583N	17.8729508E	Zdravotnická záchraná služba Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-338	Zlín	Peroutkovo nábřeží	434	49.2270650N	17.7031953E	Zdravotnická záchraná služba Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-339	Vizovice	Chrastěšovská	1005	49.2315542N	17.8573436E	Zdravotnická záchraná služba Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-340	Kroměříž	Havlíčková	3549/73	49.2913989N	17.3767356E	Zdravotnická záchraná služba Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct

Identifier	Municipality	Road	Road number	Latitude	Longitude	Name	Owner	Simulation results
eP-EAZK-341	Vsetín	Nemocniční	940	49.3321914N	17.9978997E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-342	Rožnov pod Radhoštěm	nábřeží Dukelských hrdinů	2950	49.4617356N	18.1397889E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-343	Morkovice - Slížany	Nádražní	871	49.2530297N	17.2112692E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-344	Uherský Brod	Partyzánů	2364	49.0300075N	17.6534419E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-345	Valašské Meziříčí	U Nemocnice	1511	49.4632533N	17.9785994E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-346	Bystřice pod Hostýnem	Pod Zábřehem	1690	49.4027469N	17.6818025E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-347	Uherské Hradiště	J.E.Purkyně	1512	49.0648122N	17.4573822E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-348	Buchlovice	náměstí Svobody	881	49.0868414N	17.3364689E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-349	Buchlovice	náměstí Svobody	881	49.0868414N	17.3364689E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje - tepelné čerpadlo	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-348
eP-EAZK-350	Karolinka	Radniční náměstí	42	49.3505833N	18.2374789E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-351	Suchá Loz	-	396	48.9719500N	17.7154478E	Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-352	Valašské Meziříčí	Vsetínská	941/78	49.4637825N	17.9736564E	Hvězdárna - hlavní budova	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-353	Valašské Meziříčí	Vsetínská	237/5	49.4642061N	17.9735681E	Hvězdárna - vedlejší budova	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-354	Uherské Hradiště	Otakarova	103	49.0718319N	17.4577847E	Slovácké muzeum - galerie	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-355	Uherské Hradiště	Smetanovy sady	179	49.0673086N	17.4678431E	Slovácké muzeum - hlavní budova	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-356	Uherské Hradiště	Hradební	227	49.0691017N	17.4632069E	Slovácké muzeum	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-357	Staré Město	Jezuitská	1885	49.0784694N	17.4436947E	Slovácké muzeum - Památník Velké Moravy	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-358	Uherské Hradiště	Štefánikova	1285	49.0705636N	17.4696111E	Slovácké muzeum	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-359	Topolná	-	90	49.1213036N	17.5437217E	Slovácké muzeum	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-360	Topolná	-	93	49.1211558N	17.5432064E	Slovácké muzeum	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-361	Staré Město	Jezuitská	1885	49.0780542N	17.4441586E	Slovácké muzeum - Centrum sv. Cyrila a Metoděje	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-362	Kroměříž	Velké náměstí	38/21	49.2990564N	17.3927533E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-363	Kroměříž	Hanácké náměstí	471/5	49.2931564N	17.3888667E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-364	Rymice	-	104	49.3427253N	17.5324125E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-365	Rymice	-	116	49.3424439N	17.5264867E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Not possible with given data
eP-EAZK-366	Rymice	-	14	49.3418292N	17.5249792E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-367	Rymice	-	3	49.3429725N	17.5279869E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-368	Rymice	-	62	49.3433939N	17.5333303E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Correct

Identifier	Municipality	Road	Road number	Latitude	Longitude	Name	Owner	Simulation results
eP-EAZK-369	Rymice	-	65	49.3434653N	17.5338444E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-370	Rymice	-	6	49.3433489N	17.5268992E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-371	Rymice	-	2	49.3428389N	17.5296750E	Muzeum Kroměřížska	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-372	Lešná	-	1	49.5196839N	17.9297142E	Muzeum regionu Valaško - zámek Lešná	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-373	Valašské Meziříčí	Sokolská	-	49.4706822N	17.9652806E	Muzeum regionu Valaško - kostel sv. Trojice	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-374	Valašské Meziříčí	Zámecká	3/55	49.4784300N	17.9683628E	Muzeum regionu Valaško - zámek Kinských - hlavní budova	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-375	Valašské Meziříčí	Zámecká	3/55	49.4784300N	17.9683628E	Muzeum regionu Valaško - zámek Kinských - přístavek	Zlínský kraj	Equal to eP-EAZK-374
eP-EAZK-376	Vsetín	Horní náměstí	2	49.3406953N	17.9994386E	Muzeum regionu Valaško - zámek Vsetín	Zlínský kraj	Correct
eP-EAZK-377	Vsetín	Jabloňová	231	49.3442658N	17.9962708E	Muzeum regionu Valaško - hvězdárna	Zlínský kraj	Correct

eP-EAZK-001

Location information

Kino Hluk, Sokolská 655, Hluk, město Hluk

48.98912 N, 17.52930 E

Building area: 406 m²

678 LiDAR points (1.67 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	33.5	236.7	2.3	217.7
1	190.9	239.1	26.8	31.2
2	30.3	239.8	5.3	32.6
3	147.2	239.6	26.4	210.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	8.0	0.785
120 - 100	47.8	5.296
140 - 120	147.7	19.631
160 - 140	9.5	1.425
180 - 160	41.6	7.348
200 - 180	46.0	8.568
220 - 200	101.3	21.897
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	401.9	64.949

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	28.6	5.291	3	220 - 200	101.3	21.897
	180 - 160	4.9	0.877		200 - 180	17.4	3.277
	Total	33.5	6.168		180 - 160	6.3	1.058
1	140 - 120	136.7	18.196		160 - 140	9.5	1.425
	120 - 100	46.2	5.111		140 - 120	11.1	1.435
	< 100	8.0	0.785	120 - 100	1.6	0.185	
	Total	190.9	24.091	Total	147.2	29.277	
2	180 - 160	30.3	5.413				
	Total	30.3	5.413				

eP-EAZK-002

Location information

Školní budova, Kobylská 391, Karolinka, město Karolinka

49.35414 N, 18.23103 E

Building area: 132 m²

244 LiDAR points (1.84 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	72.9	480.0	43.5	184.5
1	91.2	480.5	42.9	4.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	91.2	8.584
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	72.9	16.633
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	164.1	25.217

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	240 - 220	72.9	16.633	1	< 100	91.2	8.584
Total		72.9	16.633	Total		91.2	8.584

eP-EAZK-003

Location information

Objekt pro charitu, Nábřeží 175, Karolinka, město Karolinka

49.35267 N, 18.24020 E

Building area: 292 m²

485 LiDAR points (1.66 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	16.7	488.9	40.6	94.0
1	63.3	490.8	40.3	98.6
2	64.0	489.3	5.4	96.9
3	64.4	490.8	40.2	278.2
4	82.9	489.3	4.1	277.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	9.8	1.265
160 - 140	34.4	5.182
180 - 160	118.5	20.193
200 - 180	128.7	23.654
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	291.4	50.295

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	16.7	2.989	3	180 - 160	38.2	6.240
Total		16.7	2.989		160 - 140	16.4	2.416
1	200 - 180	62.1	11.417		140 - 120	9.8	1.265
	160 - 140	1.3	0.200	Total		64.4	9.921
Total		63.3	11.617	4	200 - 180	24.2	4.391
2	200 - 180	42.4	7.847		180 - 160	41.9	7.163
	180 - 160	21.7	3.801		160 - 140	16.8	2.566
Total		64.0	11.648	Total		82.9	14.120

eP-EAZK-004

Location information

Hasičská zbrojnice, - 428, Bánov, obec Bánov

48.98806 N, 17.71815 E

Building area: 215 m²

453 LiDAR points (2.10 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	14.9	298.8	43.2	273.8
1	42.2	298.4	41.0	94.0
2	8.3	296.7	13.9	5.8
3	32.6	298.7	44.0	273.3
4	59.8	299.3	39.1	4.0
5	70.5	299.2	38.5	183.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	24.7	2.379
120 - 100	39.2	4.021
140 - 120	2.8	0.357
160 - 140	16.5	2.528
180 - 160	74.6	12.847
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	3.2	0.687
240 - 220	67.3	15.386
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	228.3	38.205

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	3.3	0.537	3	180 - 160	29.1	4.817
	160 - 140	5.8	0.890		160 - 140	3.5	0.543
	140 - 120	1.7	0.214		Total	32.6	5.360
	120 - 100	0.8	0.092	4	120 - 100	38.4	3.929
	< 100	3.3	0.320		< 100	21.4	2.059
Total	14.9	2.053	Total	59.8	5.988		
1	180 - 160	42.2	7.493	5	240 - 220	67.3	15.386
	Total	42.2	7.493		220 - 200	3.2	0.687
2	160 - 140	7.2	1.095	Total	70.5	16.073	
	140 - 120	1.1	0.143				
	Total	8.3	1.238				

eP-EAZK-005

Location information

Šatny pro sportovce, Hlavní 361, Pozlovice, městys Pozlovice

49.12108 N, 17.76348 E

Building area: 204 m²

313 LiDAR points (1.53 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	179.8	286.3	1.5	211.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	1.9	0.335
200 - 180	177.9	33.753
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	179.8	34.088

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	177.9	33.753
	180 - 160	1.9	0.335
	Total	179.8	34.088

eP-EAZK-006

Location information

Objekt občanske vybavenosti, Vsetínská 73, Karolinka, město Karolinka

49.35148 N, 18.23823 E

Building area: 124 m²

209 LiDAR points (1.68 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	20.3	485.1	43.4	282.2
1	35.5	485.4	32.4	192.2
2	13.1	485.1	41.5	99.0
3	41.7	485.0	32.0	11.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	41.7	4.947
140 - 120	1.6	0.215
160 - 140	18.7	2.854
180 - 160	5.1	0.906
200 - 180	8.0	1.461
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	35.5	8.068
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	110.7	18.451

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	18.7	2.854	2	200 - 180	8.0	1.461
	140 - 120	1.6	0.215		180 - 160	5.1	0.906
	Total	20.3	3.070		Total	13.1	2.367
1	240 - 220	35.5	8.068	3	120 - 100	41.7	4.947
	Total	35.5	8.068		Total	41.7	4.947

eP-EAZK-007

Location information

Hasičská zbrojnice, - 114, Bohuslavice u Zlína, obec Bohuslavice u Zlína

49.16344 N, 17.63588 E

Building area: 141 m²

342 LiDAR points (2.42 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	22.0	259.1	42.9	289.3
1	64.2	259.7	42.0	200.4
2	52.5	259.9	41.9	21.9
3	17.5	258.9	42.3	110.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	54.6	5.648
140 - 120	11.5	1.521
160 - 140	8.4	1.197
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	17.5	3.406
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	64.2	14.476
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	156.2	26.247

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	8.4	1.197
	140 - 120	11.5	1.521
	120 - 100	2.1	0.241
	Total	22.0	2.959
1	240 - 220	64.2	14.476
	Total	64.2	14.476

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	120 - 100	52.5	5.407
	Total	52.5	5.407
	3	200 - 180	17.5
Total		17.5	3.406

eP-EAZK-008

Location information

Kulturní dům, - 39, Petřůvka, obec Petřůvka

49.10706 N, 17.80840 E

Building area: 338 m²

578 LiDAR points (1.71 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	105.8	491.9	38.4	282.1
1	259.0	491.6	20.6	102.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	2.4	0.320
160 - 140	79.3	12.165
180 - 160	32.3	5.309
200 - 180	250.7	48.032
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	364.7	65.826

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	24.0	3.867	1	200 - 180	250.7	48.032
	160 - 140	79.3	12.165		180 - 160	8.3	1.442
	140 - 120	2.4	0.320		Total	259.0	49.474
Total		105.8	16.352				

eP-EAZK-009

Location information

Objekt TJ Sokol, - 799, Horní Bečva, obec Horní Bečva

49.43203 N, 18.28020 E

Building area: 388 m²

772 LiDAR points (1.99 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	183.4	505.1	6.7	22.2
1	198.9	505.2	6.9	202.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	183.4	32.133
200 - 180	198.9	39.679
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	382.3	71.812

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	183.4	32.133	1	200 - 180	198.9	39.679
Total		183.4	32.133	Total		198.9	39.679

eP-EAZK-010

Location information

Dům služeb, - 81, Liptál, obec Liptál

49.29083 N, 17.92276 E

Building area: 153 m²

284 LiDAR points (1.86 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	14.3	431.3	39.7	82.0
1	19.4	431.5	38.9	260.8
2	39.1	431.9	39.1	351.9
3	6.8	432.0	7.7	342.3
4	77.0	431.1	38.9	172.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	35.7	3.347
120 - 100	7.8	0.825
140 - 120	4.4	0.580
160 - 140	12.4	1.886
180 - 160	17.6	2.959
200 - 180	1.7	0.310
220 - 200	2.1	0.443
240 - 220	74.9	17.100
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	156.6	27.450

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	4.1	0.663	2	120 - 100	5.8	0.592
	160 - 140	7.5	1.121		< 100	33.3	3.119
	140 - 120	1.4	0.185		Total	39.1	3.710
	120 - 100	0.7	0.077	3	180 - 160	3.4	0.568
	< 100	0.7	0.066		160 - 140	2.4	0.374
	Total	14.3	2.112		140 - 120	0.5	0.061
1	200 - 180	1.7	0.310		120 - 100	0.5	0.056
	180 - 160	10.1	1.728	Total	6.8	1.059	
	160 - 140	2.5	0.391	4	240 - 220	74.9	17.100
	140 - 120	2.5	0.334		220 - 200	2.1	0.443
	120 - 100	0.8	0.101		Total	77.0	17.543
	< 100	1.7	0.162				
Total	19.4	3.025					

eP-EAZK-011

Location information

Sportovní hala, Hlavní 492, Zubří, město Zubří

49.46630 N, 18.09090 E

Building area: 2905 m²

2867 LiDAR points (0.99 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	85.4	363.1	9.2	95.2
1	384.9	366.5	2.1	5.9
2	348.1	364.0	15.2	276.1
3	587.0	369.4	13.0	275.8
4	579.0	369.4	13.1	96.1
5	321.0	365.5	32.9	96.2
6	187.0	373.6	2.3	275.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	13.1	1.200
120 - 100	30.6	3.352
140 - 120	17.5	2.204
160 - 140	181.8	27.887
180 - 160	1087.6	186.941
200 - 180	1161.8	215.712
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	2492.5	437.296

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	84.4	15.892	3	200 - 180	93.7	17.220
	180 - 160	1.0	0.183		180 - 160	412.2	70.283
	Total	85.4	16.075		160 - 140	81.2	12.274
1	200 - 180	192.5	35.136	Total	587.0	99.777	
	180 - 160	105.0	18.196	4	200 - 180	404.7	75.894
	160 - 140	26.2	3.920		180 - 160	174.3	30.131
	140 - 120	17.5	2.204		Total	579.0	106.025
	120 - 100	30.6	3.352	5	200 - 180	134.0	24.542
	< 100	13.1	1.200		180 - 160	165.8	28.775
	Total	384.9	64.008		160 - 140	21.2	3.330
2	200 - 180	65.5	11.919	Total	321.0	56.647	
	180 - 160	229.4	39.372	6	200 - 180	187.0	35.108
	160 - 140	53.2	8.364		Total	187.0	35.108
	Total	348.1	59.656				

eP-EAZK-012

Location information

Drážní domek, - 23, Poličná, obec Poličná

49.46415 N, 17.94475 E

Building area: 88 m²

190 LiDAR points (2.16 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	42.8	309.6	31.8	88.3
1	52.5	309.6	32.9	268.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	95.2	16.737
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	95.2	16.737

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	42.8	7.588
Total		42.8	7.588

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	180 - 160	52.5	9.149
Total		52.5	9.149

eP-EAZK-013

Location information

Kulturní dům, - 155, Horní Lhota, obec Horní Lhota

49.15477 N, 17.80505 E

Building area: 414 m²

792 LiDAR points (1.91 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	122.9	345.9	0.9	230.1
1	130.0	350.1	36.2	250.6
2	132.5	349.9	35.4	69.8
3	44.9	346.9	1.8	250.1
4	9.3	348.6	25.7	249.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	2.9	0.247
120 - 100	4.3	0.456
140 - 120	27.2	3.641
160 - 140	107.5	15.954
180 - 160	43.8	7.503
200 - 180	253.9	48.359
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	439.6	76.159

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	200 - 180	94.9	17.661	3	200 - 180	19.8	3.632	
	180 - 160	20.2	3.447		180 - 160	23.6	4.055	
	160 - 140	6.2	0.990		160 - 140	1.5	0.231	
	140 - 120	1.6	0.208		Total	44.9	7.919	
	Total	122.9	22.307	4	200 - 180	9.3	1.799	
1	200 - 180	130.0	25.267		Total	9.3	1.799	
1	Total	130.0	25.267					
	2	160 - 140	99.8	14.733				
		140 - 120	25.7	3.432				
		120 - 100	4.3	0.456				
		< 100	2.9	0.247				
Total	132.5	18.868						

eP-EAZK-014

Location information

Mateřská škola, - 244, Podolí, obec Podolí

49.03995 N, 17.52716 E

Building area: 461 m²

806 LiDAR points (1.75 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	68.4	218.1	13.8	35.0
1	73.9	218.2	13.0	215.1
2	132.1	223.6	34.9	215.5
3	146.7	223.2	34.8	35.3
4	14.3	221.1	3.6	208.0
5	7.6	223.5	19.9	305.3
6	8.3	223.5	18.0	140.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	37.1	3.306
120 - 100	47.1	5.279
140 - 120	67.1	8.362
160 - 140	27.1	4.169
180 - 160	65.6	10.713
200 - 180	56.3	10.781
220 - 200	151.1	32.165
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	451.4	74.775

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	44.4	7.211	3	140 - 120	64.1	7.972
	160 - 140	24.0	3.736		120 - 100	45.5	5.102
	Total	68.4	10.947		< 100	37.1	3.306
1	220 - 200	51.5	10.559	Total	146.7	16.380	
	200 - 180	22.5	4.333	4	200 - 180	14.3	2.730
	Total	73.9	14.892		Total	14.3	2.730
2	220 - 200	92.6	20.137	5	180 - 160	7.6	1.230
	200 - 180	18.2	3.470		Total	7.6	1.230
	180 - 160	13.7	2.272	6	220 - 200	7.0	1.468
	160 - 140	3.0	0.433		200 - 180	1.3	0.249
	140 - 120	3.0	0.390		Total	8.3	1.718
	120 - 100	1.5	0.178				
Total	132.1	26.879					

eP-EAZK-015

Location information

Komunitní dům, - 204, Topolná, obec Topolná

49.12131 N, 17.54028 E

Building area: 320 m²

614 LiDAR points (1.92 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	60.7	194.4	34.8	81.1
1	79.9	193.9	32.7	349.8
2	45.8	194.4	33.5	170.6
3	32.4	193.5	33.2	80.5
4	96.3	193.8	34.4	260.6
5	26.8	193.2	37.2	170.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	79.9	9.386
140 - 120	0.9	0.127
160 - 140	8.8	1.316
180 - 160	92.2	15.652
200 - 180	99.8	18.534
220 - 200	8.4	1.796
240 - 220	52.1	11.812
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	342.0	58.622

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	60.7	10.316
	Total	60.7	10.316
1	120 - 100	79.9	9.386
	Total	79.9	9.386
2	240 - 220	25.2	5.680
	220 - 200	8.4	1.796
	200 - 180	5.6	1.059
	180 - 160	2.8	0.494
	160 - 140	2.8	0.416
	140 - 120	0.9	0.127
	Total	45.8	9.571

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	180 - 160	26.5	4.459
	160 - 140	6.0	0.900
	Total	32.4	5.359
4	200 - 180	94.2	17.475
	180 - 160	2.2	0.383
	Total	96.3	17.858
5	240 - 220	26.8	6.132
	Total	26.8	6.132

eP-EAZK-016

Location information

Kulturní dům, - 70, Šarovy, obec Šarovy

49.14852 N, 17.60696 E

Building area: 337 m²

1066 LiDAR points (3.16 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	202.5	233.4	7.8	319.1
1	148.3	233.7	7.5	139.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	13.5	1.839
160 - 140	15.8	2.347
180 - 160	173.3	29.909
200 - 180	148.3	29.254
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	350.9	63.349

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	173.3	29.909
	160 - 140	15.8	2.347
	140 - 120	13.5	1.839
	Total	202.5	34.095

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	200 - 180	148.3	29.254
	Total	148.3	29.254

eP-EAZK-017

Location information

Knihovna, - 184, Dolní Bečva, obec Dolní Bečva

49.45437 N, 18.19602 E

Building area: 344 m²

522 LiDAR points (1.52 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	10.4	435.3	17.9	37.2
1	31.2	438.0	12.0	31.4
2	99.5	441.0	33.2	216.3
3	15.1	440.2	29.8	126.7
4	119.7	441.1	32.2	37.0
5	46.2	440.6	32.4	306.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	12.8	1.146
120 - 100	40.1	4.477
140 - 120	110.8	14.249
160 - 140	20.6	2.984
180 - 160	23.2	3.831
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	114.6	24.542
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	322.2	51.229

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	4.7	0.595	3	220 - 200	15.1	3.139
	120 - 100	5.7	0.632		Total	15.1	3.139
	Total	10.4	1.227	4	140 - 120	79.8	10.141
1	180 - 160	23.2	3.831		120 - 100	27.1	3.029
	160 - 140	5.6	0.854		< 100	12.8	1.146
	140 - 120	1.6	0.205		Total	119.7	14.316
	120 - 100	0.8	0.093	5	160 - 140	15.0	2.130
Total	31.2	4.984	140 - 120		24.7	3.307	
2	220 - 200	99.5	21.403		120 - 100	6.4	0.723
	Total	99.5	21.403	Total	46.2	6.159	

eP-EAZK-018

Location information

Šatny pro sportovce, Na Horebečví 635, Karolinka, město Karolinka

49.35239 N, 18.24969 E

Building area: 443 m²

474 LiDAR points (1.07 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	31.1	488.0	14.7	183.0
1	32.4	489.7	17.4	193.0
2	189.5	489.6	44.0	3.4
3	143.2	490.5	44.1	183.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	189.5	17.175
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	3.2	0.505
180 - 160	6.9	1.215
200 - 180	5.3	1.003
220 - 200	70.4	15.041
240 - 220	120.9	27.546
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	396.2	62.485

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	26.8	5.659	3	240 - 220	120.9	27.546
	200 - 180	2.1	0.412		220 - 200	11.1	2.376
	180 - 160	2.1	0.372		200 - 180	3.2	0.591
	Total	31.1	6.442		180 - 160	4.8	0.843
1	220 - 200	32.4	7.007		160 - 140	3.2	0.505
	Total	32.4	7.007	Total	143.2	31.861	
2	< 100	189.5	17.175				
	Total	189.5	17.175				

eP-EAZK-019

Location information

Kulturní dům, - 166, Racková, obec Racková

49.27803 N, 17.62509 E

Building area: 470 m²

756 LiDAR points (1.61 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	17.0	242.0	42.6	263.8
1	11.8	242.2	41.3	263.2
2	91.1	239.3	9.7	179.6
3	178.6	241.3	37.3	359.5
4	166.3	241.3	37.9	179.5
5	20.6	241.5	41.4	84.2
6	13.2	240.9	41.6	83.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	14.1	1.351
120 - 100	172.3	18.138
140 - 120	9.3	1.210
160 - 140	23.6	3.607
180 - 160	61.2	10.424
200 - 180	34.6	6.655
220 - 200	65.0	13.450
240 - 220	118.5	27.005
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	498.7	81.840

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	180 - 160	14.6	2.581	4	240 - 220	118.5	27.005	
	160 - 140	1.6	0.257		220 - 200	15.9	3.412	
	< 100	0.8	0.078		200 - 180	19.5	3.722	
	Total	17.0	2.916		180 - 160	5.3	0.878	
1	180 - 160	5.9	1.023	160 - 140	7.1	1.082		
	160 - 140	3.9	0.606	Total	166.3	36.099		
	140 - 120	2.0	0.253	5	180 - 160	20.6	3.462	
	Total	11.8	1.883		Total	20.6	3.462	
2	220 - 200	49.1	10.038		6	180 - 160	6.6	1.082
	200 - 180	15.2	2.932			160 - 140	5.1	0.771
	180 - 160	8.2	1.399	140 - 120		1.5	0.193	
	160 - 140	5.8	0.890	Total		13.2	2.045	
	140 - 120	5.8	0.764	3	120 - 100	165.3	17.396	
	120 - 100	7.0	0.742		< 100	13.3	1.273	
	Total	91.1	16.765		Total	178.6	18.669	

eP-EAZK-020

Location information

Sportstadion, - 618, Dolní Bečva, obec Dolní Bečva

49.45241 N, 18.19159 E

Building area: 443 m²

651 LiDAR points (1.47 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	446.0	425.6	9.1	237.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	446.0	87.931
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	446.0	87.931

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	446.0	87.931
Total		446.0	87.931

eP-EAZK-021

Location information

Obecní úřad, - 114, Slavkov, obec Slavkov

48.94567 N, 17.61186 E

Building area: 468 m²

689 LiDAR points (1.47 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	52.1	316.8	18.9	87.2
1	36.6	319.1	39.4	351.7
2	82.5	319.1	28.7	85.8
3	64.4	316.6	18.3	266.6
4	11.6	317.0	14.7	174.2
5	16.9	319.7	27.9	179.1
6	26.5	319.1	28.7	267.6
7	9.7	319.2	28.5	351.3
8	40.7	319.9	29.4	265.7
9	18.8	319.8	28.6	268.5
10	17.1	318.5	27.9	355.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	42.0	3.570
120 - 100	11.6	1.306
140 - 120	10.6	1.342
160 - 140	7.6	1.165
180 - 160	141.9	24.649
200 - 180	146.9	27.072
220 - 200	3.0	0.627
240 - 220	13.3	2.978
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	376.9	62.710

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	45.7	8.371	6	200 - 180	14.6	2.647
	180 - 160	5.6	0.990		180 - 160	12.0	2.070
	160 - 140	0.8	0.128		Total	26.5	4.716
	Total	52.1	9.489	7	120 - 100	5.1	0.570
1	< 100	36.6	3.074		< 100	4.6	0.417
	Total	36.6	3.074		Total	9.7	0.986
2	180 - 160	78.2	13.611	8	200 - 180	24.0	4.401
	160 - 140	4.2	0.658		180 - 160	16.6	2.908
	Total	82.5	14.269		Total	40.7	7.309
3	200 - 180	55.2	10.289	9	200 - 180	3.4	0.618
	180 - 160	9.2	1.615		180 - 160	11.9	2.031
	Total	64.4	11.904		160 - 140	2.6	0.379
4	220 - 200	0.8	0.171		140 - 120	0.9	0.115
	200 - 180	2.5	0.464	Total	18.8	3.143	
	180 - 160	8.3	1.423	10	140 - 120	9.8	1.226
Total	11.6	2.058	120 - 100		6.5	0.737	
5	240 - 220	13.3	2.978		< 100	0.8	0.079
	220 - 200	2.2	0.456	Total	17.1	2.042	
	200 - 180	1.5	0.284				
	Total	16.9	3.718				

eP-EAZK-022

Location information

Prodejna a pohostinství, - 130, Bohuslavice nad Vláří, obec Bohuslavice nad Vláří

49.09000 N, 17.92980 E

Building area: 195 m²

280 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	185.3	333.7	1.6	217.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	4.5	0.759
200 - 180	180.8	34.025
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	185.3	34.784

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	180.8	34.025
	180 - 160	4.5	0.759
	Total	185.3	34.784

eP-EAZK-023

Location information

Kulturní dům, - 655, Horní Bečva, obec Horní Bečva

49.43247 N, 18.28833 E

Building area: 897 m²

1644 LiDAR points (1.83 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	39.3	515.5	4.5	128.5
1	25.0	518.5	5.7	43.6
2	102.7	519.4	33.7	223.9
3	14.2	518.4	33.4	312.4
4	9.9	518.2	23.3	328.0
5	28.5	518.7	34.0	44.0
6	16.0	519.3	28.0	150.8
7	151.4	520.3	5.7	43.7
8	21.2	520.5	32.2	124.9
9	60.7	519.5	33.9	223.9
10	129.9	520.1	34.3	313.8
11	145.7	520.6	33.4	135.5
12	50.9	519.1	34.9	41.6
13	44.7	519.7	34.1	43.8
14	42.3	520.1	17.5	42.7

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	30.9	2.670
120 - 100	41.7	4.602
140 - 120	217.8	28.451
160 - 140	47.0	7.184
180 - 160	116.6	20.398
200 - 180	116.6	21.417
220 - 200	304.0	64.886
240 - 220	8.0	1.769
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	882.4	151.377

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	39.3	7.372	5	140 - 120	28.5	3.820
Total		39.3	7.372	Total		28.5	3.820
1	200 - 180	22.9	4.138	6	240 - 220	8.0	1.769
	180 - 160	2.0	0.360		220 - 200	3.6	0.762
Total		25.0	4.498		200 - 180	1.8	0.326
2	220 - 200	89.5	18.887		180 - 160	0.9	0.143
	200 - 180	7.3	1.414		160 - 140	1.8	0.274
	180 - 160	2.9	0.520	Total		16.0	3.274
	160 - 140	2.9	0.446	7	200 - 180	39.7	7.151
Total		102.7	21.266		180 - 160	97.0	17.125
3	140 - 120	12.8	1.661		160 - 140	10.3	1.541
	120 - 100	1.4	0.167		140 - 120	4.4	0.588
Total		14.2	1.828	Total		151.4	26.406
4	160 - 140	2.3	0.327				
	140 - 120	3.8	0.510				
	120 - 100	1.5	0.159				
	< 100	2.3	0.180				
Total		9.9	1.177				

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
8	220 - 200	21.2	4.387	12	140 - 120	44.1	5.716
	Total	21.2	4.387		120 - 100	3.9	0.424
9	220 - 200	60.7	13.045		< 100	2.9	0.284
	Total	60.7	13.045	Total	50.9	6.424	
10	140 - 120	82.8	10.721	13	140 - 120	38.6	5.076
	120 - 100	24.4	2.697		120 - 100	4.1	0.443
	< 100	22.7	1.928		< 100	2.0	0.194
	Total	129.9	15.347		Total	44.7	5.713
11	220 - 200	129.1	27.805	14	180 - 160	6.3	1.014
	200 - 180	5.5	1.016		160 - 140	29.7	4.596
	180 - 160	7.4	1.235		140 - 120	2.7	0.359
	120 - 100	3.7	0.421		120 - 100	2.7	0.291
	Total	145.7	30.477		< 100	0.9	0.083
			Total		42.3	6.343	

eP-EAZK-024

Location information

Obecní úřad a hasičská zbrojnice, - 33, Nedakonice, obec Nedakonice

49.03142 N, 17.38576 E

Building area: 267 m²

461 LiDAR points (1.73 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	106.6	179.6	4.7	139.3
1	75.1	187.1	37.6	222.1
2	19.6	188.7	36.4	137.2
3	47.5	187.5	37.9	43.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	1.0	0.095
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	56.1	7.163
160 - 140	3.1	0.475
180 - 160	15.7	2.695
200 - 180	98.0	18.670
220 - 200	74.9	16.112
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	248.8	45.210

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	93.8	17.872	2	220 - 200	19.6	4.253
	180 - 160	11.6	1.992		Total	19.6	4.253
	140 - 120	1.3	0.180	3	140 - 120	47.5	6.045
	Total	106.6	20.043		Total	47.5	6.045
1	220 - 200	55.2	11.859				
	200 - 180	4.2	0.798				
	180 - 160	4.2	0.703				
	160 - 140	3.1	0.475				
	140 - 120	7.3	0.938				
	< 100	1.0	0.095				
	Total	75.1	14.869				

eP-EAZK-025

■ Location information

Hasičská zbrojnice, - 470, Valašská Bystřice, obec Valašská Bystřice

49.41417 N, 18.10907 E

LiDAR file was empty

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-026

Location information

Mateřská škola, - 71, Dřínov, obec Dřínov

49.29115 N, 17.23329 E

Building area: 347 m²

678 LiDAR points (1.95 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	68.9	306.4	2.2	113.1
1	49.2	310.1	8.6	109.3
2	95.0	312.3	34.7	108.8
3	79.3	312.6	35.0	289.0
4	33.2	312.1	33.8	17.6
5	42.8	312.1	33.5	198.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	33.2	3.882
140 - 120	16.7	2.212
160 - 140	93.8	14.682
180 - 160	50.1	8.743
200 - 180	131.7	25.004
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	42.8	9.685
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	368.3	64.207

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	68.9	13.040	3	160 - 140	78.2	12.271
	Total	68.9	13.040		140 - 120	1.1	0.153
1	200 - 180	47.2	8.922	Total	79.3	12.424	
	180 - 160	2.0	0.350		4	120 - 100	33.2
2	Total	49.2	9.272	Total		33.2	3.882
	200 - 180	15.6	3.042		5	240 - 220	42.8
	180 - 160	48.2	8.393	Total		42.8	9.685
	160 - 140	15.6	2.410				
	140 - 120	15.6	2.059				
Total	95.0	15.904					

eP-EAZK-027

Location information

Mateřská škola, - 76, Hrobice, obec Hrobice

49.27789 N, 17.79042 E

Building area: 522 m²

814 LiDAR points (1.56 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	45.3	402.5	29.1	5.5
1	6.3	402.4	29.4	96.5
2	41.4	401.1	11.5	275.6
3	29.2	401.9	13.0	273.2
4	15.1	403.3	2.7	297.5
5	22.4	400.7	27.2	103.5
6	72.9	402.9	32.8	183.7
7	106.3	403.2	33.3	274.1
8	20.1	402.7	32.3	5.4
9	65.3	403.7	33.4	94.0
10	19.2	401.5	33.3	94.6
11	50.7	401.2	11.4	2.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.9	0.087
120 - 100	38.8	4.450
140 - 120	36.2	4.498
160 - 140	58.5	8.897
180 - 160	192.5	33.277
200 - 180	94.3	17.286
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	72.9	16.655
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	494.1	85.149

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	25.8	3.147	6	240 - 220	72.9	16.655
	120 - 100	18.7	2.107		Total	72.9	16.655
	< 100	0.9	0.087	7	180 - 160	100.0	17.201
	Total	45.3	5.340		160 - 140	6.3	0.976
1	200 - 180	6.3	1.155	Total	106.3	18.177	
	Total	6.3	1.155	8	120 - 100	20.1	2.343
2	200 - 180	26.2	4.798		Total	20.1	2.343
	180 - 160	11.0	1.915	9	200 - 180	19.5	3.546
	160 - 140	1.7	0.251		180 - 160	42.9	7.527
	140 - 120	2.5	0.327		160 - 140	1.9	0.294
	Total	41.4	7.290		140 - 120	1.0	0.133
3	200 - 180	21.3	3.915	Total	65.3	11.499	
	180 - 160	6.3	1.095	10	200 - 180	14.6	2.671
	160 - 140	1.6	0.237		180 - 160	2.3	0.387
	Total	29.2	5.246		140 - 120	2.3	0.284
4	180 - 160	8.8	1.494		Total	19.2	3.342
	160 - 140	4.4	0.662	11	180 - 160	5.4	0.871
	140 - 120	1.9	0.255		160 - 140	42.5	6.479
	Total	15.1	2.411		140 - 120	2.7	0.353
5	200 - 180	6.5	1.201		Total	50.7	7.703
	180 - 160	15.9	2.786				
	Total	22.4	3.987				

eP-EAZK-028

Location information

Prodejna smíšeného zboží, - 141, Hřivínův Újezd, obec Hřivínův Újezd

49.12079 N, 17.69148 E

Building area: 265 m²

327 LiDAR points (1.24 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	79.4	271.8	0.9	335.6
1	16.5	271.9	4.7	212.8
2	15.0	271.7	1.4	227.4
3	95.8	271.8	0.5	117.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	1.6	0.254
180 - 160	22.2	3.829
200 - 180	182.8	34.153
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	206.6	38.236

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	68.2	12.600	2	200 - 180	12.6	2.376
	180 - 160	10.4	1.783		180 - 160	2.4	0.403
	160 - 140	0.9	0.138		Total	15.0	2.779
	Total	79.4	14.521	3	200 - 180	87.1	16.289
1	200 - 180	15.0	2.888		180 - 160	8.7	1.515
	180 - 160	0.7	0.128		Total	95.8	17.804
	160 - 140	0.7	0.116				
Total	16.5	3.132					

eP-EAZK-029

Location information

Základní škola - budova A a D, - 437, Nový Hrozenkov, obec Nový Hrozenkov

49.33843 N, 18.19858 E

Building area: 1958 m²

2331 LiDAR points (1.19 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	125.5	468.1	33.6	68.5
1	36.4	467.6	31.8	338.6
2	67.2	468.1	32.1	249.4
3	79.8	462.1	34.5	338.2
4	68.4	462.2	31.6	158.4
5	194.5	468.5	32.8	68.6
6	223.7	467.7	34.1	338.3
7	38.6	467.2	31.1	158.7
8	12.9	467.1	30.8	248.5
9	67.3	466.2	29.9	337.8
10	5.6	454.8	12.7	339.5
11	315.2	461.6	3.3	53.1
12	349.9	461.5	29.8	68.5

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	116.3	9.904
120 - 100	297.4	34.347
140 - 120	209.8	27.023
160 - 140	490.7	76.672
180 - 160	290.0	46.966
200 - 180	80.2	15.750
220 - 200	32.2	6.893
240 - 220	68.6	15.336
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1585.2	232.890

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	125.5	19.866	4	240 - 220	47.9	10.709
	Total	125.5	19.866		220 - 200	17.1	3.664
1	140 - 120	32.4	3.963	200 - 180	2.3	0.428	
	120 - 100	3.9	0.460	180 - 160	1.1	0.195	
	Total	36.4	4.423	Total	68.4	14.996	
2	200 - 180	64.2	12.649	5	160 - 140	194.5	30.962
	160 - 140	1.0	0.151		Total	194.5	30.962
	120 - 100	2.0	0.229	6	120 - 100	223.7	26.287
	Total	67.2	13.029		Total	223.7	26.287
3	120 - 100	32.5	3.455	7	240 - 220	20.7	4.626
	< 100	47.2	3.985		220 - 200	15.1	3.229
	Total	79.8	7.440		200 - 180	2.8	0.551
				Total	38.6	8.406	

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
8	200 - 180	10.9	2.123	11	180 - 160	12.4	2.024
	180 - 160	1.4	0.234		160 - 140	105.1	15.694
	140 - 120	0.7	0.083		140 - 120	105.1	13.885
	Total	12.9	2.439		120 - 100	30.9	3.448
			< 100		61.8	5.249	
9	140 - 120	64.3	8.157	Total	315.2	40.300	
	120 - 100	3.0	0.322	12	180 - 160	275.2	44.513
	Total	67.3	8.479		160 - 140	64.5	9.999
10	140 - 120	0.4	0.053		140 - 120	6.8	0.882
	120 - 100	1.3	0.146		< 100	3.4	0.338
	< 100	3.9	0.332	Total	349.9	55.732	
Total	5.6	0.531					

eP-EAZK-030

Location information

Základní škola, - 53, Podolí, obec Podolí

49.04222 N, 17.52715 E

Building area: 385 m²

688 LiDAR points (1.79 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	88.6	205.3	35.1	229.7
1	13.8	206.1	34.3	229.0
2	42.3	204.9	37.0	314.0
3	48.2	204.9	32.1	139.3
4	26.0	204.5	36.5	224.0
5	156.8	205.1	34.1	49.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	20.8	1.778
120 - 100	30.1	3.401
140 - 120	149.0	19.622
160 - 140	15.8	2.354
180 - 160	18.4	3.150
200 - 180	39.6	7.578
220 - 200	102.0	21.408
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	375.7	59.292

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	52.1	10.811	3	220 - 200	15.7	3.327
	200 - 180	19.8	3.816		200 - 180	15.7	2.993
	180 - 160	8.3	1.418		180 - 160	9.3	1.588
	160 - 140	8.3	1.241		160 - 140	7.4	1.112
	Total	88.6	17.286		Total	48.2	9.021
1	220 - 200	8.1	1.696	4	220 - 200	26.0	5.574
	200 - 180	4.1	0.769		Total	26.0	5.574
	180 - 160	0.8	0.144	5	140 - 120	116.1	15.446
	< 100	0.8	0.081		120 - 100	22.6	2.548
Total	13.8	2.689	< 100	18.1	1.513		
2	140 - 120	32.9	4.177	Total	156.8	19.508	
	120 - 100	7.5	0.852				
	< 100	1.9	0.184				
	Total	42.3	5.213				

eP-EAZK-031

Location information

Městský úřad, Masarykovo náměstí 128 - 131, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, město Rožnov pod Radhoštěm

49.45760 N, 18.14268 E

Building area: 425 m²

544 LiDAR points (1.28 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	61.9	389.1	18.3	132.5
1	32.4	389.3	19.3	314.0
2	37.4	389.3	22.3	44.2
3	46.9	388.1	9.9	43.2
4	31.1	389.6	14.7	126.5
5	50.0	388.9	17.2	304.9
6	113.7	389.2	21.8	223.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	4.1	0.368
120 - 100	10.2	1.141
140 - 120	28.1	3.672
160 - 140	71.6	10.812
180 - 160	53.7	9.105
200 - 180	5.3	1.017
220 - 200	200.4	42.001
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	373.4	68.115

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	61.9	12.883	4	220 - 200	24.8	5.043
	Total	61.9	12.883		200 - 180	5.3	1.017
1	160 - 140	23.3	3.588		180 - 160	0.9	0.156
	140 - 120	5.8	0.762	Total	31.1	6.217	
	120 - 100	2.5	0.275	5	180 - 160	15.5	2.535
	< 100	0.8	0.075		160 - 140	21.8	3.311
	Total	32.4	4.700		140 - 120	10.0	1.309
2	160 - 140	19.5	2.864	120 - 100	2.7	0.305	
	140 - 120	11.4	1.492	Total	50.0	7.460	
	120 - 100	3.3	0.360	6	220 - 200	113.7	24.074
	< 100	3.3	0.292		Total	113.7	24.074
Total	37.4	5.008					
3	180 - 160	37.4	6.414				
	160 - 140	7.0	1.050				
	140 - 120	0.9	0.108				
	120 - 100	1.7	0.201				
	Total	46.9	7.773				

eP-EAZK-032

Location information

Městský úřad, Letenská 1918, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, město Rožnov pod Radhoštěm

49.46346 N, 18.14334 E

Building area: 398 m²

412 LiDAR points (1.04 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	117.8	389.5	15.4	296.8
1	197.1	389.5	15.1	116.9
2	25.9	389.8	13.8	291.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	2.7	0.287
140 - 120	11.0	1.449
160 - 140	15.1	2.298
180 - 160	114.9	19.803
200 - 180	197.1	39.254
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	340.7	63.091

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	89.0	15.265
	160 - 140	15.1	2.298
	140 - 120	11.0	1.449
	120 - 100	2.7	0.287
Total		117.8	19.299

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	200 - 180	197.1	39.254
	Total	197.1	39.254
2	180 - 160	25.9	4.538
	Total	25.9	4.538

eP-EAZK-033

Location information

Mateřská škola, - 520, Spytihněv, obec Spytihněv

49.14270 N, 17.49646 E

Building area: 493 m²

872 LiDAR points (1.77 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	489.3	203.3	0.3	319.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	489.3	91.761
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	489.3	91.761

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	489.3	91.761
Total		489.3	91.761

eP-EAZK-034

Location information

Tělocvična, - 191, Žlutava, obec Žlutava

49.19941 N, 17.49071 E

Building area: 489 m²

802 LiDAR points (1.64 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	7.1	284.6	3.7	122.0
1	9.5	283.7	41.3	322.9
2	61.6	284.5	1.9	39.9
3	22.9	280.5	26.1	143.1
4	31.1	281.3	27.3	143.8
5	91.3	284.4	39.0	144.2
6	102.2	283.5	38.3	324.1
7	36.9	284.2	42.9	234.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	38.3	3.053
120 - 100	73.3	8.369
140 - 120	2.2	0.278
160 - 140	6.9	1.012
180 - 160	6.2	1.075
200 - 180	55.8	10.306
220 - 200	101.1	21.556
240 - 220	78.6	17.334
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	362.5	62.983

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	0.5	0.091	4	220 - 200	28.7	6.241
	160 - 140	4.4	0.642		200 - 180	1.8	0.349
	140 - 120	2.2	0.278		180 - 160	0.6	0.109
	Total	7.1	1.011		Total	31.1	6.699
1	120 - 100	9.5	1.072	5	240 - 220	78.6	17.334
	Total	9.5	1.072		220 - 200	12.7	2.759
2	200 - 180	54.0	9.957		Total	91.3	20.093
	180 - 160	5.1	0.875	6	120 - 100	63.8	7.296
	160 - 140	2.5	0.370		< 100	38.3	3.053
	Total	61.6	11.202		Total	102.2	10.349
3	220 - 200	22.9	4.967	7	220 - 200	36.9	7.589
	Total	22.9	4.967		Total	36.9	7.589

eP-EAZK-035

Location information

Objekt charity, Velehradská třída 247, Uherské Hradiště, charita Uherské Hradiště

49.07108 N, 17.46119 E

Building area: 118 m²

146 LiDAR points (1.24 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	18.8	190.9	17.5	51.4
1	55.8	190.6	33.3	227.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	2.2	0.330
180 - 160	16.7	2.749
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	55.8	11.851
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	74.6	14.930

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	16.7	2.749	1	220 - 200	55.8	11.851
	160 - 140	2.2	0.330		Total		55.8
Total		18.8	3.078				

eP-EAZK-036

Location information

Lékařský dům, Sídlištní 1749, Zubří, město Zubří

49.46435 N, 18.09033 E

Building area: 354 m²

122 LiDAR points (0.34 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-037

Location information

Komunitní dům pro seniory, Sídlištní 1748, Zubří, město Zubří

49.46434 N, 18.09079 E

Building area: 380 m²

590 LiDAR points (1.55 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	361.2	362.7	0.1	330.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	4.0	0.627
180 - 160	24.1	4.125
200 - 180	333.1	62.354
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	361.2	67.106

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	333.1	62.354
	180 - 160	24.1	4.125
	160 - 140	4.0	0.627
	Total	361.2	67.106

eP-EAZK-038

Location information

Tvrz, nám. Komenského 162, Hluk, město Hluk

48.98732 N, 17.52638 E

Building area: 976 m²

1303 LiDAR points (1.34 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	43.0	233.6	49.4	20.3
1	113.9	233.3	41.0	113.2
2	133.2	233.5	35.9	298.2
3	155.0	233.1	35.3	119.7
4	138.9	233.4	41.3	292.6
5	129.9	233.1	45.7	199.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	47.2	3.741
120 - 100	1.4	0.144
140 - 120	8.3	1.148
160 - 140	260.7	38.236
180 - 160	1.3	0.222
200 - 180	183.1	36.171
220 - 200	81.9	16.659
240 - 220	129.9	29.214
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	713.8	125.535

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	< 100	43.0	3.379	3	220 - 200	81.9	16.659
Total		43.0	3.379		200 - 180	73.1	14.468
1	200 - 180	110.0	21.704	Total		155.0	31.127
	180 - 160	1.3	0.222	4	160 - 140	137.4	20.175
	140 - 120	2.6	0.357		140 - 120	1.5	0.205
Total		113.9	22.283	Total		138.9	20.380
2	160 - 140	123.3	18.061	5	240 - 220	129.9	29.214
	140 - 120	4.3	0.586	Total		129.9	29.214
	120 - 100	1.4	0.144				
	< 100	4.3	0.363				
Total		133.2	19.153				

eP-EAZK-039

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Příční 1475, Holešov, město Holešov

49.33451 N, 17.57734 E

Building area: 1362 m²

1790 LiDAR points (1.31 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	315.0	240.3	0.1	81.5
1	72.2	233.1	0.6	138.7
2	20.0	239.5	1.9	355.5
3	88.2	256.2	15.3	345.6
4	97.1	256.4	15.6	166.1
5	267.3	256.7	15.4	76.1
6	211.2	256.7	15.6	256.3
7	54.1	257.9	8.2	233.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	13.7	1.561
140 - 120	79.5	10.476
160 - 140	153.9	23.590
180 - 160	422.2	73.489
200 - 180	358.7	66.958
220 - 200	97.1	20.725
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1125.2	196.798

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	151.0	27.643	5	200 - 180	12.6	2.266
	180 - 160	164.0	28.368		180 - 160	198.1	34.669
	Total	315.0	56.011		160 - 140	40.9	6.307
1	160 - 140	10.1	1.467		140 - 120	15.7	2.111
	140 - 120	48.5	6.349	Total	267.3	45.352	
	120 - 100	13.7	1.561	6	200 - 180	164.3	31.235
Total	72.2	9.377	180 - 160		36.9	6.399	
2	160 - 140	16.0	2.414		160 - 140	10.1	1.509
	140 - 120	4.0	0.511	Total	211.2	39.143	
Total	20.0	2.926	7	200 - 180	30.8	5.814	
3	160 - 140	76.9		11.893	180 - 160	23.3	4.053
	140 - 120	11.3		1.505	Total	54.1	9.868
Total	88.2	13.398	4	220 - 200	97.1	20.725	
Total	97.1	20.725		Total	97.1	20.725	

eP-EAZK-040

Location information

Čistírna odpadních vod, --, Horní Němčí, obec Horní Němčí

48.94123 N, 17.62020 E

Building area: 177 m²

17 LiDAR points (0.10 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-041

Location information

Budova technických služeb města, Uherskobrodská 188, Luhačovice, město Luhačovice

49.09044 N, 17.73888 E

Building area: 524 m²

632 LiDAR points (1.21 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	470.4	251.8	2.6	135.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	470.4	90.177
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	470.4	90.177

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	470.4	90.177
Total		470.4	90.177

eP-EAZK-042

Location information

Obecní úřad, - 297, Korytná, obec Korytná

48.94141 N, 17.66567 E

Building area: 995 m²

1170 LiDAR points (1.18 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	247.0	349.9	2.3	328.5
1	61.0	349.5	34.0	59.7
2	82.6	348.9	32.3	240.6
3	244.5	352.5	35.1	330.8
4	27.3	349.3	1.0	47.5
5	257.5	351.7	34.6	150.9
6	22.8	349.3	33.7	62.5
7	18.8	349.8	34.3	241.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	119.7	10.097
120 - 100	174.8	19.770
140 - 120	53.4	6.910
160 - 140	58.7	8.683
180 - 160	111.4	19.307
200 - 180	146.2	27.145
220 - 200	95.4	19.781
240 - 220	201.9	45.019
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	961.5	156.712

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	102.5	18.664	4	180 - 160	12.6	2.116
	180 - 160	95.5	16.640		160 - 140	8.4	1.266
	160 - 140	16.3	2.402		140 - 120	6.3	0.830
	140 - 120	28.0	3.654		Total	27.3	4.212
	120 - 100	4.7	0.543	5	240 - 220	201.9	45.019
Total	247.0	41.903	220 - 200		38.0	8.204	
1	160 - 140	8.3	1.197		200 - 180	2.9	0.579
	140 - 120	10.3	1.303		160 - 140	2.9	0.439
	120 - 100	24.8	2.737		140 - 120	8.8	1.123
	< 100	17.6	1.521	120 - 100	2.9	0.351	
Total	61.0	6.759	Total	257.5	55.714		
2	220 - 200	41.3	8.323	6	160 - 140	22.8	3.379
	200 - 180	38.0	7.401		Total	22.8	3.379
	180 - 160	3.3	0.551	7	220 - 200	16.1	3.254
	Total	82.6	16.275		200 - 180	2.7	0.501
3	120 - 100	142.4	16.140	Total	18.8	3.755	
	< 100	102.1	8.575				
	Total	244.5	24.715				

eP-EAZK-043

Location information

Základní škola, - 191, Kostelec u Holešova, obec Kostelec u Holešova

49.37344 N, 17.51175 E

Building area: 492 m²

1140 LiDAR points (2.32 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	24.8	280.9	36.9	215.7
1	6.0	280.8	5.5	255.4
2	16.8	280.8	22.6	93.8
3	8.8	277.5	32.1	216.2
4	8.4	279.6	40.6	183.6
5	9.7	280.1	18.2	126.7
6	16.6	281.0	35.9	34.8
7	225.8	281.6	35.9	305.3
8	108.2	281.6	36.7	125.2
9	41.7	280.8	36.6	125.2
10	28.5	281.1	35.5	124.8
11	8.0	277.6	32.2	34.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	6.0	0.502
120 - 100	2.3	0.261
140 - 120	250.5	34.483
160 - 140	5.1	0.792
180 - 160	10.7	1.824
200 - 180	36.8	6.974
220 - 200	190.6	39.857
240 - 220	1.2	0.271
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	503.2	84.963

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	24.8	5.419	6	140 - 120	16.6	2.044
Total		24.8	5.419	Total		16.6	2.044
1	< 100	6.0	0.502	7	140 - 120	225.8	31.428
Total		6.0	0.502	Total		225.8	31.428
2	200 - 180	13.5	2.524	8	220 - 200	108.2	22.595
	180 - 160	1.9	0.334	Total		108.2	22.595
	160 - 140	1.3	0.206	9	220 - 200	28.8	5.932
Total		16.8	3.063		200 - 180	7.0	1.322
3	220 - 200	4.7	0.952		180 - 160	4.0	0.680
	200 - 180	4.1	0.787		160 - 140	2.0	0.309
Total		8.8	1.739	Total		41.7	8.243
4	240 - 220	1.2	0.271	10	220 - 200	18.7	3.837
	220 - 200	0.6	0.131		200 - 180	7.3	1.404
	180 - 160	2.4	0.407		180 - 160	2.4	0.402
	160 - 140	1.8	0.277	Total		28.5	5.644
	140 - 120	2.4	0.299	11	140 - 120	5.7	0.711
Total		8.4	1.385		120 - 100	2.3	0.261
5	220 - 200	4.9	0.991	Total		8.0	0.972
	200 - 180	4.9	0.938				
Total		9.7	1.929				

eP-EAZK-044

Location information

Mateřská škola, Komenského 301, Luhačovice, město Luhačovice

49.10000 N, 17.75378 E

Building area: 250 m²

396 LiDAR points (1.58 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	235.5	263.9	0.2	245.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	235.5	44.293
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	235.5	44.293

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	235.5	44.293
Total		235.5	44.293

eP-EAZK-045

Location information

Objekt občanske vybavenosti, Masarykova 137, Luhačovice, město Luhačovice

49.09881 N, 17.75578 E

Building area: 396 m²

641 LiDAR points (1.62 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	229.6	266.3	0.4	156.8
1	141.8	269.9	0.5	316.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	20.3	2.243
140 - 120	2.9	0.405
160 - 140	40.7	6.188
180 - 160	66.8	11.531
200 - 180	240.6	44.832
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	371.4	65.199

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	98.8	18.285	1	200 - 180	141.8	26.547
	180 - 160	66.8	11.531		Total		141.8
	160 - 140	40.7	6.188				
	140 - 120	2.9	0.405				
	120 - 100	20.3	2.243				
Total		229.6	38.652				

eP-EAZK-046

Location information

Obecní úřad a kulturní dům, - 370, Nedašov, obec Nedašov

49.11131 N, 18.06284 E

Building area: 1145 m²

1526 LiDAR points (1.33 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	33.1	387.4	3.7	351.9
1	1056.4	391.4	1.5	168.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	48.3	8.347
200 - 180	1041.2	198.660
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1089.5	207.007

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	4.5	0.813	1	200 - 180	1036.7	197.846
	180 - 160	28.6	5.075		180 - 160	19.7	3.272
	Total	33.1	5.889		Total	1056.4	201.118

eP-EAZK-047

Location information

Kulturní dům, - 415, Štítná nad Vláří-Popov, obec Štítná nad Vláří-Popov

49.06921 N, 17.97821 E

Building area: 820 m²

1528 LiDAR points (1.86 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	38.7	330.7	17.8	252.5
1	125.4	331.7	37.3	72.0
2	217.1	329.3	16.1	71.5
3	136.7	331.9	37.4	252.0
4	267.4	329.2	17.1	251.4
5	12.5	326.6	30.1	161.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	24.0	2.759
140 - 120	31.4	4.069
160 - 140	150.3	23.627
180 - 160	274.3	48.326
200 - 180	305.3	57.877
220 - 200	2.9	0.646
240 - 220	9.6	2.122
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	797.8	139.426

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	37.1	7.160	4	200 - 180	218.3	41.181
	180 - 160	1.6	0.267		180 - 160	49.1	8.707
	Total	38.7	7.427		Total	267.4	49.888
1	160 - 140	125.4	19.804	5	240 - 220	9.6	2.122
	Total	125.4	19.804		220 - 200	2.9	0.646
2	180 - 160	205.1	36.238		Total	12.5	2.768
	160 - 140	11.9	1.890				
	Total	217.1	38.128				
3	200 - 180	49.9	9.536				
	180 - 160	18.5	3.115				
	160 - 140	12.9	1.933				
	140 - 120	31.4	4.069				
	120 - 100	24.0	2.759				
	Total	136.7	21.412				

eP-EAZK-048

Location information

Základní škola, - 49, Velký Ořechov, obec Velký Ořechov

49.10989 N, 17.66940 E

Building area: 368 m²

624 LiDAR points (1.70 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	205.1	399.3	37.5	253.1
1	222.4	399.0	36.8	73.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	222.4	34.747
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	205.1	39.263
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	427.5	74.011

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	205.1	39.263	1	160 - 140	222.4	34.747
Total		205.1	39.263	Total		222.4	34.747

eP-EAZK-049

Location information

Objekt občanske vybavenosti, - 186, Vlčnov, obec Vlčnov

49.01010 N, 17.58025 E

Building area: 1289 m²

1549 LiDAR points (1.20 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	278.8	230.3	0.4	73.2
1	55.7	234.1	3.5	254.2
2	57.7	233.9	16.1	77.8
3	65.7	234.0	16.1	259.5
4	58.1	233.9	15.9	77.7
5	58.6	234.0	16.0	259.7
6	66.9	233.9	16.3	77.5
7	44.1	233.8	14.0	259.4
8	60.5	233.9	16.5	77.3
9	55.3	233.9	15.7	259.2
10	56.6	234.0	16.0	77.6
11	86.1	227.7	16.7	259.2
12	74.2	233.9	16.2	259.4

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	45.0	4.946
140 - 120	9.9	1.307
160 - 140	104.1	16.000
180 - 160	326.4	55.753
200 - 180	532.8	100.684
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1018.2	178.691

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	218.2	40.534	3	200 - 180	62.1	11.895
	180 - 160	48.5	8.425		180 - 160	1.8	0.317
	160 - 140	12.1	1.908		160 - 140	1.8	0.278
	Total	278.8	50.867		Total	65.7	12.490
1	180 - 160	3.2	0.546	4	200 - 180	1.1	0.205
	160 - 140	2.1	0.322		180 - 160	45.6	7.769
	140 - 120	5.4	0.694		160 - 140	11.4	1.748
	120 - 100	45.0	4.946		Total	58.1	9.722
	Total	55.7	6.508	5	200 - 180	9.8	1.837
2	180 - 160	25.6	4.347		180 - 160	36.9	6.270
	160 - 140	32.1	4.850		160 - 140	11.9	1.871
Total	57.7	9.197	Total	58.6	9.977		

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
6	180 - 160	49.7	8.483	10	200 - 180	3.0	0.546
	160 - 140	17.2	2.633		180 - 160	52.5	8.996
	Total	66.9	11.117		160 - 140	1.0	0.161
7	200 - 180	26.1	4.885	Total	56.6	9.704	
	180 - 160	18.0	3.121	11	200 - 180	86.1	16.534
	Total	44.1	8.006		Total	86.1	16.534
8	180 - 160	41.6	6.952		12	200 - 180	74.2
	160 - 140	14.5	2.229	Total		74.2	14.231
	140 - 120	4.5	0.613				
	Total	60.5	9.794				
9	200 - 180	52.2	10.016				
	180 - 160	3.1	0.526				
	Total	55.3	10.543				

eP-EAZK-050

Location information

Radnice, náměstí Míru 12, Zlín, statutární město Zlín

49.22657 N, 17.66615 E

Building area: 983 m²

964 LiDAR points (0.98 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	306.3	239.3	44.0	5.9
1	175.4	240.9	36.1	276.9
2	168.8	241.2	44.6	96.8
3	88.2	240.8	24.6	188.2
4	55.6	241.3	30.6	189.2
5	14.4	237.7	34.6	276.8
6	31.1	241.3	28.9	267.4
7	10.4	240.5	24.7	156.1
8	7.3	240.3	28.1	178.5
9	19.1	240.3	20.6	232.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	306.3	27.908
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	22.3	3.451
180 - 160	356.8	61.886
200 - 180	22.3	4.115
220 - 200	40.8	8.569
240 - 220	128.1	28.729
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	876.6	134.658

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	< 100	306.3	27.908	6	200 - 180	13.5	2.440
	Total	306.3	27.908		180 - 160	16.8	2.918
1	180 - 160	155.4	25.948		160 - 140	0.8	0.132
	160 - 140	20.0	3.090	Total	31.1	5.490	
	Total	175.4	29.037	7	220 - 200	7.6	1.629
2	180 - 160	168.8	30.351		200 - 180	2.1	0.395
	Total	168.8	30.351		180 - 160	0.7	0.123
3	240 - 220	69.7	15.545	Total	10.4	2.147	
	220 - 200	10.9	2.318	8	240 - 220	6.7	1.520
	200 - 180	5.4	1.016		220 - 200	0.6	0.130
	180 - 160	2.2	0.390		Total	7.3	1.650
	Total	88.2	19.268	9	220 - 200	17.7	3.649
4	240 - 220	51.7	11.664		200 - 180	1.4	0.265
	220 - 200	3.9	0.842		Total	19.1	3.914
Total	55.6	12.506	5	180 - 160	13.0	2.157	
5	160 - 140	1.4		0.229	Total	14.4	2.386
	Total	14.4		2.386			

eP-EAZK-051

Location information

Zámek, Soudní 1, Zlín, statutární město Zlín

49.22577 N, 17.66319 E

Building area: 1772 m²

1376 LiDAR points (0.78 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	162.5	237.7	43.5	243.9
1	153.7	237.6	40.9	332.3
2	78.4	238.1	40.5	152.8
3	163.9	237.5	31.8	154.5
4	218.3	237.6	34.4	61.3
5	34.7	224.4	2.4	55.3
6	120.5	237.8	37.3	334.3
7	122.5	237.9	37.0	240.6
8	15.6	234.3	34.1	240.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	274.2	30.035
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	218.3	32.769
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	197.2	38.517
220 - 200	138.1	28.037
240 - 220	242.3	54.345
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1070.1	183.704

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	162.5	32.070	5	200 - 180	34.7	6.447
Total		162.5	32.070	Total		34.7	6.447
1	120 - 100	153.7	16.440	6	120 - 100	120.5	13.596
Total		153.7	16.440	Total		120.5	13.596
2	240 - 220	78.4	17.581	7	220 - 200	122.5	24.852
Total		78.4	17.581	Total		122.5	24.852
3	240 - 220	163.9	36.765	8	220 - 200	15.6	3.185
Total		163.9	36.765	Total		15.6	3.185
4	160 - 140	218.3	32.769				
Total		218.3	32.769				

eP-EAZK-052

Location information

Základní škola, Školní 540, Zubří, město Zubří

49.46982 N, 18.09019 E

Building area: 834 m²

1306 LiDAR points (1.57 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	25.9	382.9	37.9	0.4
1	60.8	380.0	38.4	89.0
2	194.3	380.2	41.0	87.3
3	7.5	373.6	16.5	1.6
4	15.2	373.5	8.6	120.4
5	7.2	379.0	28.2	78.9
6	6.0	381.0	32.7	84.1
7	17.3	378.9	36.0	0.7
8	119.2	380.0	36.9	180.5
9	15.4	369.4	39.6	180.8
10	147.8	384.2	7.7	309.0
11	27.2	383.1	34.7	180.7
12	25.0	383.7	45.6	177.4
13	173.2	383.9	40.0	270.4

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	5.9	0.550
120 - 100	68.6	7.478
140 - 120	123.8	16.286
160 - 140	39.2	6.002
180 - 160	416.9	71.558
200 - 180	0.7	0.120
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	186.8	42.803
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	842.0	144.797

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	22.4	2.328
	< 100	3.6	0.337
	Total	25.9	2.665
1	180 - 160	60.8	10.680
Total		60.8	10.680
2	180 - 160	194.3	33.431
	Total	194.3	33.431
	3	140 - 120	6.3
	120 - 100	1.1	0.130
Total		7.5	0.953

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
4	200 - 180	0.7	0.120
	180 - 160	12.6	2.161
	160 - 140	2.0	0.307
	Total	15.2	2.588
5	180 - 160	1.8	0.290
	160 - 140	3.0	0.473
	140 - 120	2.4	0.310
	Total	7.2	1.073
6	180 - 160	3.8	0.639
	160 - 140	1.6	0.249
	140 - 120	0.5	0.070
	Total	6.0	0.957

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
7	120 - 100	15.0	1.581	11	240 - 220	27.2	6.227
	< 100	2.4	0.213		Total	27.2	6.227
	Total	17.3	1.794		12	240 - 220	25.0
8	240 - 220	119.2	27.328	Total		25.0	5.711
	Total	119.2	27.328	13	180 - 160	143.7	24.357
9	240 - 220	15.4	3.537		160 - 140	27.6	4.190
	Total	15.4	3.537		120 - 100	2.0	0.228
10	160 - 140	5.0	0.783		Total	173.2	28.775
	140 - 120	114.6	15.083				
	120 - 100	28.2	3.212				
	Total	147.8	19.078				

eP-EAZK-053

Location information

Kulturní dům, - 350, Horní Němčiči, obec Horní Němčiči

48.93241 N, 17.62381 E

Building area: 469 m²

863 LiDAR points (1.84 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	99.1	331.0	14.3	243.4
1	43.0	330.8	17.1	333.3
2	42.1	329.6	17.0	334.0
3	135.1	333.4	40.0	333.2
4	142.5	333.2	38.6	153.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	12.7	1.051
120 - 100	148.4	16.050
140 - 120	13.3	1.735
160 - 140	50.6	7.757
180 - 160	12.5	2.165
200 - 180	121.4	23.039
220 - 200	90.2	18.990
240 - 220	12.7	2.831
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	461.9	73.618

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	94.5	17.869	3	120 - 100	132.3	14.290
	180 - 160	4.6	0.817		< 100	2.8	0.241
	Total	99.1	18.685		Total	135.1	14.531
1	160 - 140	41.3	6.374	4	240 - 220	12.7	2.831
	140 - 120	1.7	0.223		220 - 200	90.2	18.990
	Total	43.0	6.596		200 - 180	26.9	5.170
2	160 - 140	4.5	0.653		180 - 160	7.9	1.348
	140 - 120	11.7	1.513		160 - 140	4.7	0.730
	120 - 100	16.1	1.760	Total	142.5	29.069	
	< 100	9.9	0.810				
Total	42.1	4.736					

eP-EAZK-054

Location information

Obecní úřad, - 49, Komárno, obec Komárno

49.43397 N, 17.77876 E

Building area: 149 m²

298 LiDAR points (2.00 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	13.5	365.8	25.2	72.0
1	13.4	365.7	26.9	253.4
2	21.0	370.1	30.6	341.9
3	28.4	370.4	30.9	254.2
4	26.5	370.3	31.2	162.7
5	29.4	370.4	30.6	72.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	2.5	0.277
140 - 120	21.9	2.742
160 - 140	16.4	2.531
180 - 160	29.6	4.978
200 - 180	35.2	6.711
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	26.5	5.977
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	132.3	23.215

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	13.5	2.270	4	240 - 220	26.5	5.977
Total		13.5	2.270	Total		26.5	5.977
1	200 - 180	7.6	1.419	5	180 - 160	9.5	1.557
	180 - 160	5.7	0.998		160 - 140	16.4	2.531
Total		13.4	2.417		140 - 120	3.5	0.462
2	140 - 120	18.5	2.280	Total		29.4	4.550
	120 - 100	2.5	0.277				
Total		21.0	2.557				
3	200 - 180	27.6	5.292				
	180 - 160	0.9	0.153				
Total		28.4	5.445				

eP-EAZK-055

Location information

Kulturní dům, - 104, Bezměrov, obec Bezměrov

49.32888 N, 17.33795 E

Building area: 593 m²

982 LiDAR points (1.66 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	51.1	211.0	11.9	124.9
1	84.1	211.1	11.5	305.0
2	72.0	212.0	0.3	105.0
3	140.7	208.9	0.5	97.8
4	111.2	208.8	0.8	35.4
5	27.3	208.9	5.2	81.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	2.7	0.231
120 - 100	7.3	0.798
140 - 120	27.3	3.534
160 - 140	70.8	10.699
180 - 160	291.4	49.587
200 - 180	87.0	16.295
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	486.4	81.143

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	49.0	9.344	3	180 - 160	113.1	18.964
	180 - 160	1.0	0.183		160 - 140	26.1	4.009
	160 - 140	1.0	0.160		140 - 120	1.5	0.198
	Total	51.1	9.687		Total	140.7	23.172
1	180 - 160	50.5	8.616	4	180 - 160	69.4	11.844
	160 - 140	17.7	2.633		160 - 140	22.0	3.314
	140 - 120	7.1	0.911		140 - 120	18.7	2.425
	120 - 100	6.2	0.675		120 - 100	1.1	0.122
	< 100	2.7	0.231		Total	111.2	17.706
	Total	84.1	13.066	5	200 - 180	1.6	0.281
2	200 - 180	36.5	6.670		180 - 160	21.8	3.783
	180 - 160	35.6	6.197		160 - 140	3.9	0.583
Total	72.0	12.866	Total	27.3	4.646		

eP-EAZK-056

Location information

Kulturní dům, nám. Em. Zahna 682, Strání - Květná, obec Strání

48.88504 N, 17.72131 E

Building area: 940 m²

915 LiDAR points (0.97 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	169.0	368.4	17.7	135.9
1	138.4	368.4	7.6	45.9
2	69.1	363.8	7.1	226.4
3	35.3	363.3	10.5	315.6
4	33.2	367.8	7.7	43.8
5	33.9	367.8	7.8	226.0
6	34.7	367.7	7.4	43.7
7	40.1	367.8	7.2	227.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	3.6	0.406
140 - 120	14.9	1.937
160 - 140	48.4	7.399
180 - 160	191.8	33.112
200 - 180	142.7	27.892
220 - 200	152.4	31.763
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	553.7	102.510

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	152.4	31.763	4	180 - 160	26.9	4.678
	200 - 180	11.6	2.253		160 - 140	4.0	0.626
	140 - 120	5.0	0.650		140 - 120	2.4	0.304
	Total	169.0	34.667		Total	33.2	5.608
1	180 - 160	117.6	20.421	5	200 - 180	21.8	4.237
	160 - 140	15.2	2.297		180 - 160	6.0	1.034
	140 - 120	2.8	0.357		160 - 140	6.0	0.901
	120 - 100	2.8	0.315		Total	33.9	6.172
Total	138.4	23.389	6	180 - 160	29.2	5.032	
2	200 - 180	69.1	13.556	160 - 140	5.5	0.849	
	Total	69.1	13.556	Total	34.7	5.881	
3	180 - 160	12.0	1.948	7	200 - 180	40.1	7.846
	160 - 140	17.7	2.727		Total	40.1	7.846
	140 - 120	4.8	0.626				
	120 - 100	0.8	0.091				
Total	35.3	5.391					

eP-EAZK-057

Location information

Restaurace, nám. Em. Zahna 682, Strání - Květná, obec Strání

48.88507 N, 17.72074 E

Building area: 516 m²

643 LiDAR points (1.25 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	5.1	366.3	4.2	36.0
1	16.3	362.5	10.8	231.4
2	419.3	367.1	1.7	45.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.9	0.121
160 - 140	1.8	0.283
180 - 160	2.3	0.393
200 - 180	435.6	81.110
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	440.7	81.908

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	2.3	0.393
	160 - 140	1.8	0.283
	140 - 120	0.9	0.121
	Total	5.1	0.798
1	200 - 180	16.3	3.204
	Total	16.3	3.204

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	419.3	77.906
	Total	419.3	77.906

eP-EAZK-058

Location information

Víceúčelový objekt, - 1, Březůvky, obec Březůvky

49.15464 N, 17.69871 E

Building area: 994 m²

1165 LiDAR points (1.17 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	131.8	363.1	0.2	190.6
1	7.2	365.5	1.3	73.5
2	200.8	366.6	0.6	55.1
3	428.1	368.4	0.3	210.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	9.0	0.826
120 - 100	6.0	0.664
140 - 120	3.0	0.399
160 - 140	42.5	6.520
180 - 160	106.5	18.417
200 - 180	600.9	112.497
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	767.8	139.322

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	89.8	16.629
	180 - 160	32.5	5.611
	160 - 140	9.5	1.443
	Total	131.8	23.683
1	200 - 180	7.2	1.345
	Total	7.2	1.345
2	200 - 180	80.9	14.955
	180 - 160	68.9	11.899
	160 - 140	33.0	5.077
	140 - 120	3.0	0.399
	120 - 100	6.0	0.664
	< 100	9.0	0.826
Total	200.8	33.820	

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	200 - 180	423.0	79.568
	180 - 160	5.1	0.907
	Total	428.1	80.475

eP-EAZK-059

Location information

Prodejna smíšeného zboží, - 95, Brusné, obec Brusné

49.36332 N, 17.66088 E

Building area: 248 m²

791 LiDAR points (3.19 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	139.2	325.0	14.7	140.3
1	121.6	325.2	14.7	320.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	47.0	7.441
180 - 160	74.6	12.074
200 - 180	2.9	0.560
220 - 200	136.3	28.178
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	260.8	48.253

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	136.3	28.178	1	180 - 160	74.6	12.074
	200 - 180	2.9	0.560		160 - 140	47.0	7.441
	Total	139.2	28.738		Total	121.6	19.515

eP-EAZK-060

Location information

Základní škola, - 290, Huslenky, obec Huslenky

49.30768 N, 18.10906 E

Building area: 573 m²

710 LiDAR points (1.24 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	30.5	406.3	4.7	256.8
1	8.5	406.3	5.9	52.7
2	33.8	409.5	7.2	326.4
3	155.4	414.0	34.1	235.1
4	67.0	413.6	34.5	144.8
5	35.7	413.8	35.2	325.1
6	86.2	411.2	23.3	54.7
7	99.1	414.6	32.3	55.0
8	38.4	413.3	33.3	55.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	21.7	2.004
120 - 100	37.5	4.163
140 - 120	89.6	11.546
160 - 140	175.9	26.129
180 - 160	7.3	1.216
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	157.7	32.747
240 - 220	64.7	14.288
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	554.5	92.093

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	180 - 160	5.2	0.870	5	140 - 120	29.7	3.636	
	160 - 140	10.5	1.570		120 - 100	3.0	0.340	
	140 - 120	8.7	1.130		< 100	3.0	0.288	
	120 - 100	6.1	0.689		Total	35.7	4.265	
	Total	30.5	4.260		6	160 - 140	53.2	8.197
1	180 - 160	2.1	0.345	140 - 120		16.0	2.106	
	160 - 140	1.6	0.244	120 - 100		5.3	0.591	
	140 - 120	1.1	0.139	< 100		11.7	1.031	
	120 - 100	2.1	0.235	Total		86.2	11.925	
	< 100	1.6	0.149	7	160 - 140	76.2	11.132	
Total	8.5	1.112	140 - 120		12.2	1.620		
2	160 - 140	10.5	1.526		120 - 100	7.6	0.827	
	140 - 120	10.5	1.379		< 100	3.0	0.301	
	120 - 100	10.5	1.158		Total	99.1	13.879	
	< 100	2.4	0.235	8	160 - 140	24.0	3.459	
	Total	33.8	4.298		140 - 120	11.5	1.537	
3	220 - 200	155.4	32.239		120 - 100	2.9	0.323	
	Total	155.4	32.239		Total	38.4	5.319	
	4	240 - 220	64.7		14.288	Total	240 - 220	64.7
		220 - 200	2.3	0.508	220 - 200		2.3	0.508
		Total	67.0	14.797	Total		67.0	14.797

eP-EAZK-061

Location information

Víceúčelový objekt, - 129, Dolní Lhota, obec Dolní Lhota

49.13861 N, 17.81127 E

Building area: 612 m²

879 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	102.8	307.1	4.4	354.1
1	117.6	308.0	4.9	83.7
2	102.7	308.0	4.3	263.7
3	54.7	307.7	1.7	183.3
4	67.7	307.6	2.6	347.6
5	71.9	307.6	0.4	259.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	5.5	0.738
160 - 140	3.1	0.487
180 - 160	140.2	24.716
200 - 180	368.6	68.872
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	517.4	94.814

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	95.1	16.825	3	200 - 180	47.0	8.935
	160 - 140	2.2	0.337		180 - 160	6.7	1.164
	140 - 120	5.5	0.738		160 - 140	1.0	0.151
	Total	102.8	17.900		Total	54.7	10.249
1	200 - 180	102.0	19.101	4	200 - 180	61.7	11.304
	180 - 160	15.6	2.744		180 - 160	6.0	1.039
	Total	117.6	21.845		Total	67.7	12.343
2	200 - 180	95.5	17.853	5	200 - 180	62.3	11.681
	180 - 160	7.2	1.273		180 - 160	9.6	1.671
	Total	102.7	19.125		Total	71.9	13.352

eP-EAZK-062

Location information

Obecní úřad, - 292, Horní Lideč, obec Horní Lideč

49.18788 N, 18.05695 E

Building area: 351 m²

568 LiDAR points (1.62 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	187.2	464.1	27.2	7.7
1	175.3	464.6	24.5	185.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	187.2	24.209
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	33.2	7.256
240 - 220	142.1	31.516
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	362.5	62.981

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	187.2	24.209
	Total	187.2	24.209
1	240 - 220	142.1	31.516
	220 - 200	33.2	7.256
	Total	175.3	38.772

eP-EAZK-063

Location information

Depozitář, Jiráskova 1338, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.20914 N, 17.53222 E

Building area: 535 m²

962 LiDAR points (1.80 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	520.5	197.3	0.1	167.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	520.5	97.732
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	520.5	97.732

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	520.5	97.732
Total		520.5	97.732

eP-EAZK-064

Location information

Bytový dům, - 192, Kašava, obec Kašava

49.30078 N, 17.79175 E

Building area: 266 m²

404 LiDAR points (1.52 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	23.8	358.4	32.1	74.2
1	51.3	360.9	11.0	344.2
2	27.1	358.6	36.5	254.7
3	7.6	358.9	35.6	165.5
4	54.3	360.9	10.7	164.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.8	0.091
140 - 120	12.6	1.662
160 - 140	43.3	6.590
180 - 160	42.9	7.113
200 - 180	2.5	0.460
220 - 200	61.3	12.634
240 - 220	0.6	0.141
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	164.1	28.693

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	14.6	2.185	3	240 - 220	0.6	0.141
	140 - 120	9.2	1.221		220 - 200	7.0	1.503
	Total	23.8	3.406		Total	7.6	1.645
1	180 - 160	37.0	6.098	4	220 - 200	54.3	11.131
	160 - 140	10.1	1.533		Total	54.3	11.131
	140 - 120	3.4	0.441				
	120 - 100	0.8	0.091				
Total	51.3	8.163					
2	200 - 180	2.5	0.460				
	180 - 160	5.9	1.016				
	160 - 140	18.6	2.872				
Total	27.1	4.348					

eP-EAZK-065

Location information

Knihovna, - 100, Kašava, obec Kašava

49.29783 N, 17.78726 E

Building area: 278 m²

403 LiDAR points (1.45 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	44.3	338.1	37.0	28.3
1	37.0	338.5	40.1	208.4
2	17.7	342.8	36.2	30.4
3	54.8	343.2	33.7	300.7
4	20.3	343.2	35.5	210.9
5	62.1	343.2	33.1	120.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	7.4	0.627
120 - 100	55.4	6.352
140 - 120	8.1	1.073
160 - 140	47.6	6.966
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	43.7	8.562
220 - 200	22.6	4.644
240 - 220	51.5	11.421
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	236.2	39.646

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	36.9	4.253	3	160 - 140	47.6	6.966
	< 100	7.4	0.627		140 - 120	7.2	0.964
	Total	44.3	4.880		Total	54.8	7.930
1	240 - 220	32.8	7.272	4	240 - 220	18.7	4.149
	220 - 200	1.7	0.362		220 - 200	1.6	0.358
	200 - 180	0.8	0.168		Total	20.3	4.507
	140 - 120	0.8	0.108	5	220 - 200	19.3	3.924
	120 - 100	0.8	0.093		200 - 180	42.8	8.394
Total	37.0	8.003	Total	62.1	12.319		
2	120 - 100	17.7	2.007				
	Total	17.7	2.007				

eP-EAZK-066

Location information

Kulturní dům, - 260, Vlachovice, obec Vlachovice

49.12424 N, 17.93950 E

Building area: 969 m²

1228 LiDAR points (1.27 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	205.9	349.3	1.8	258.5
1	153.7	352.2	3.7	90.3
2	126.8	350.8	10.2	266.3
3	115.9	350.8	10.2	273.2
4	87.6	354.5	1.5	149.3
5	236.7	353.5	13.2	271.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	10.6	0.994
120 - 100	29.0	3.252
140 - 120	26.4	3.424
160 - 140	72.5	10.979
180 - 160	178.8	30.810
200 - 180	609.4	113.646
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	926.6	163.106

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	95.7	17.891
	180 - 160	46.4	7.925
	160 - 140	34.8	5.301
	140 - 120	14.5	1.845
	120 - 100	14.5	1.654
	Total	205.9	34.617
1	200 - 180	115.3	21.420
	180 - 160	34.2	5.935
	160 - 140	4.3	0.640
	Total	153.7	27.996
2	200 - 180	10.6	1.936
	180 - 160	54.2	9.341
	160 - 140	25.1	3.826
	140 - 120	11.9	1.579
	120 - 100	14.5	1.598
	< 100	10.6	0.994
	Total	126.8	19.275

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	200 - 180	112.4	20.809
	180 - 160	3.5	0.608
	Total	115.9	21.417
4	200 - 180	84.1	16.005
	180 - 160	2.3	0.399
	160 - 140	1.1	0.170
Total	87.6	16.574	
5	200 - 180	191.3	35.585
	180 - 160	38.3	6.601
	160 - 140	7.2	1.042
Total	236.7	43.228	

eP-EAZK-067

Location information

Obecní dům, - 217, Kašava, obec Kašava

49.29777 N, 17.78809 E

Building area: 435 m²

731 LiDAR points (1.68 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	80.2	340.2	7.9	117.6
1	41.5	346.0	40.5	211.5
2	42.8	347.6	33.0	30.1
3	39.5	347.4	32.7	210.5
4	51.5	345.5	34.7	137.7
5	6.8	345.5	40.0	29.6
6	13.7	346.1	31.2	207.4
7	39.0	345.7	41.3	211.0
8	13.9	344.5	42.3	211.0
9	51.0	345.4	39.1	29.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	11.2	0.983
120 - 100	51.4	5.746
140 - 120	47.4	5.973
160 - 140	7.1	1.078
180 - 160	62.3	10.662
200 - 180	41.4	7.740
220 - 200	77.0	16.379
240 - 220	82.2	18.207
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	380.0	66.769

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	19.8	3.591	5	120 - 100	6.8	0.739
	180 - 160	52.3	8.959		Total	6.8	0.739
	160 - 140	5.4	0.828	6	240 - 220	1.4	0.304
	140 - 120	2.7	0.369		220 - 200	7.5	1.626
	Total	80.2	13.747		200 - 180	3.4	0.656
1	240 - 220	22.4	4.964	180 - 160	0.7	0.122	
	220 - 200	19.1	4.100	160 - 140	0.7	0.110	
Total	41.5	9.064	Total	13.7	2.817		
2	140 - 120	42.8	5.350	7	240 - 220	14.3	3.155
	Total	42.8	5.350		220 - 200	19.0	4.085
3	240 - 220	39.5	8.755		200 - 180	5.7	1.104
	Total	39.5	8.755	Total	39.0	8.345	
4	220 - 200	28.2	5.917	8	240 - 220	4.6	1.028
	200 - 180	7.8	1.488		220 - 200	3.1	0.651
	180 - 160	7.8	1.314		200 - 180	4.6	0.901
	160 - 140	1.0	0.141		180 - 160	1.5	0.267
	140 - 120	1.9	0.254		Total	13.9	2.847
	120 - 100	1.9	0.217	9	120 - 100	42.7	4.791
	< 100	2.9	0.284		< 100	8.3	0.699
Total	51.5	9.614	Total	51.0	5.491		

eP-EAZK-068

Location information

Mateřská škola, Sídliště 870, Nivnice, obec Nivnice

48.97830 N, 17.64793 E

Building area: 1028 m²

1447 LiDAR points (1.41 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	100.0	256.2	2.5	156.0
1	286.1	257.3	0.2	248.6
2	588.2	260.0	0.1	58.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	27.6	4.260
180 - 160	93.5	16.227
200 - 180	853.3	158.581
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	974.3	179.068

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	32.5	5.947
	180 - 160	54.2	9.380
	160 - 140	13.3	2.031
	Total	100.0	17.358
1	200 - 180	243.2	45.253
	180 - 160	28.6	4.949
	160 - 140	14.3	2.229
	Total	286.1	52.432

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	577.5	107.380
	180 - 160	10.7	1.898
	Total	588.2	109.278

eP-EAZK-069

Location information

Základní škola - 2.stupeň, Komenského 101, Nivnice, obec Nivnice

48.97230 N, 17.64870 E

Building area: 674 m²

1060 LiDAR points (1.57 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	23.3	260.7	33.0	312.5
1	58.1	261.5	34.0	41.7
2	49.7	261.3	34.4	221.7
3	38.0	265.2	33.2	41.8
4	62.9	265.2	34.3	221.2
5	25.4	264.6	31.9	313.0
6	27.1	265.9	30.4	37.5
7	175.2	265.9	34.4	311.3
8	249.1	265.5	34.1	131.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	28.5	2.523
120 - 100	31.7	3.467
140 - 120	289.9	38.603
160 - 140	4.9	0.751
180 - 160	9.8	1.683
200 - 180	27.3	5.258
220 - 200	316.7	66.254
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	708.8	118.538

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	21.8	2.908	5	140 - 120	22.7	3.019
	120 - 100	1.6	0.183		120 - 100	1.8	0.217
	Total	23.3	3.091		< 100	0.9	0.089
1	140 - 120	42.8	5.523	Total	25.4	3.324	
	120 - 100	7.1	0.771	6	140 - 120	6.8	0.865
	< 100	8.2	0.684		120 - 100	5.1	0.556
Total	58.1	6.978	< 100		15.2	1.353	
2	220 - 200	17.9	3.683	Total	27.1	2.773	
	200 - 180	17.9	3.428	7	140 - 120	162.7	21.973
	180 - 160	7.0	1.188		120 - 100	8.3	0.876
	160 - 140	4.0	0.600		< 100	4.2	0.398
	140 - 120	3.0	0.406		Total	175.2	23.246
Total	49.7	9.306	8	220 - 200	243.5	50.890	
3	140 - 120	30.2		3.910	200 - 180	5.6	1.094
	120 - 100	7.8		0.864	Total	249.1	51.985
Total	38.0	4.774	4	220 - 200	55.3	11.681	
4	220 - 200	55.3		11.681	200 - 180	3.8	0.735
	200 - 180	3.8		0.735	180 - 160	2.9	0.494
	180 - 160	2.9		0.494	160 - 140	1.0	0.151
160 - 140	1.0	0.151	Total	62.9	13.061		
Total	62.9	13.061					

eP-EAZK-070

Location information

Základní škola - 1.stupeň, Osvobození 181, Nivnice, obec Nivnice

48.97552 N, 17.64475 E

Building area: 886 m²

1435 LiDAR points (1.62 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	13.2	253.7	39.4	246.9
1	228.7	255.2	40.1	158.4
2	49.8	254.6	36.4	67.4
3	44.0	254.4	36.6	248.0
4	143.3	255.7	39.5	248.3
5	149.4	255.1	39.5	68.4
6	12.5	254.6	34.1	160.8
7	57.2	254.6	40.2	158.4
8	99.3	255.5	34.1	160.9
9	14.9	252.7	13.9	248.8
10	7.2	254.6	39.1	338.0
11	55.3	254.4	40.4	338.1
12	11.3	254.5	38.7	159.0

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	59.3	5.527
120 - 100	61.0	6.372
140 - 120	6.9	0.873
160 - 140	206.8	31.549
180 - 160	51.6	8.724
200 - 180	230.0	44.598
220 - 200	84.5	17.981
240 - 220	186.0	41.939
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	886.2	157.562

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	13.2	2.579	4	200 - 180	125.2	24.452
Total		13.2	2.579		180 - 160	8.2	1.381
1	240 - 220	82.7	18.613		160 - 140	3.3	0.495
	220 - 200	70.6	14.984		140 - 120	4.9	0.619
	200 - 180	41.4	7.963		120 - 100	1.6	0.185
	180 - 160	31.6	5.363	Total		143.3	27.132
	160 - 140	2.4	0.374	5	160 - 140	149.4	22.726
Total		228.7	47.297	Total		149.4	22.726
2	160 - 140	49.8	7.667	6	240 - 220	8.4	1.883
Total		49.8	7.667		220 - 200	2.4	0.506
3	200 - 180	34.6	6.688		200 - 180	1.2	0.232
	180 - 160	6.6	1.097		180 - 160	0.6	0.107
	160 - 140	1.9	0.287	Total		12.5	2.728
	140 - 120	0.9	0.131				
Total		44.0	8.204				

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
7	140 - 120	1.0	0.123	10	120 - 100	5.2	0.545
	120 - 100	23.5	2.508		< 100	2.0	0.189
	< 100	32.7	3.106		Total	7.2	0.735
	Total	57.2	5.737	11	120 - 100	30.6	3.133
8	240 - 220	86.1	19.459		< 100	24.7	2.232
	220 - 200	10.8	2.318		Total	55.3	5.365
	200 - 180	1.2	0.235	12	240 - 220	8.9	1.983
	180 - 160	1.2	0.196		220 - 200	0.8	0.172
	Total	99.3	22.209		200 - 180	1.6	0.310
9	200 - 180	11.5	2.137	Total	11.3	2.466	
	180 - 160	3.4	0.579				
	Total	14.9	2.716				

eP-EAZK-071

Location information

Základní a mateřská škola, - 192, Pozděchov, obec Pozděchov

49.23772 N, 17.95219 E

Building area: 394 m²

613 LiDAR points (1.55 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	23.9	504.3	28.1	12.5
1	23.3	504.5	28.3	193.6
2	173.5	504.7	28.7	103.6
3	210.9	504.9	28.3	283.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	13.2	1.229
120 - 100	8.7	0.990
140 - 120	44.1	5.662
160 - 140	121.3	18.299
180 - 160	47.5	7.909
200 - 180	173.5	33.539
220 - 200	2.4	0.526
240 - 220	20.9	4.652
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	431.6	72.806

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	23.1	2.916	3	180 - 160	47.5	7.909
	120 - 100	0.8	0.094		160 - 140	121.3	18.299
	Total	23.9	3.011		140 - 120	21.1	2.745
1	240 - 220	20.9	4.652		120 - 100	7.9	0.896
	220 - 200	2.4	0.526		< 100	13.2	1.229
	Total	23.3	5.178	Total	210.9	31.078	
2	200 - 180	173.5	33.539				
	Total	173.5	33.539				

eP-EAZK-072

Location information

Hasičská zbrojnice, - 175, Podhradní Lhota, obec Podhradní Lhota

49.41992 N, 17.79526 E

Building area: 236 m²

235 LiDAR points (1.00 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	59.1	398.5	26.4	299.1
1	61.4	398.7	25.7	119.4
2	33.2	398.4	25.5	29.6
3	23.5	398.3	25.7	209.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	10.5	1.431
160 - 140	81.8	12.392
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	84.9	17.702
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	177.2	31.525

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	58.1	9.070	2	160 - 140	23.7	3.322
	140 - 120	1.0	0.126		140 - 120	9.5	1.305
	Total	59.1	9.197		Total	33.2	4.626
1	220 - 200	61.4	12.542	3	220 - 200	23.5	5.160
	Total	61.4	12.542		Total	23.5	5.160

eP-EAZK-073

Location information

Hasičská zbrojnice, - 265, Suchá Loz, obec Suchá Loz

48.97004 N, 17.71374 E

Building area: 103 m²

206 LiDAR points (1.99 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	18.7	303.3	40.4	42.7
1	19.5	303.3	42.3	222.7
2	38.1	303.4	42.0	133.2
3	43.4	303.8	42.9	313.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	19.6	1.715
120 - 100	19.6	2.147
140 - 120	22.9	2.799
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	57.6	12.278
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	119.7	18.938

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	18.7	2.300	3	140 - 120	4.1	0.499
	Total	18.7	2.300		120 - 100	19.6	2.147
1	220 - 200	19.5	4.182		< 100	19.6	1.715
	Total	19.5	4.182		Total	43.4	4.360
2	220 - 200	38.1	8.096				
	Total	38.1	8.096				

eP-EAZK-074

Location information

Obecní úřad a domov pro seniory, - 14, Břestek, obec Břestek

49.09359 N, 17.35440 E

Building area: 338 m²

575 LiDAR points (1.70 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	26.9	244.1	39.8	0.4
1	14.9	244.2	27.3	183.7
2	19.4	244.2	39.6	359.9
3	11.0	244.1	26.9	180.8
4	79.8	244.5	39.7	0.6
5	96.2	244.3	28.0	180.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	57.0	5.318
120 - 100	69.1	6.965
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	4.8	1.035
240 - 220	117.2	26.452
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	248.2	39.771

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	15.2	1.530	3	240 - 220	8.1	1.817
	< 100	11.6	1.078		220 - 200	2.9	0.625
	Total	26.9	2.608		Total	11.0	2.442
1	240 - 220	13.0	2.909	4	120 - 100	41.5	4.179
	220 - 200	1.9	0.411		< 100	38.4	3.609
	Total	14.9	3.320		Total	79.8	7.788
2	120 - 100	12.4	1.257	5	240 - 220	96.2	21.726
	< 100	7.0	0.630		Total	96.2	21.726
	Total	19.4	1.887				

eP-EAZK-075

Location information

Domov pro seniory, - 189, Slavkov pod Hostýnem, obec Slavkov pod Hostýnem

49.37805 N, 17.67116 E

Building area: 788 m²

1217 LiDAR points (1.54 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	387.4	369.0	16.6	279.1
1	26.0	369.2	16.7	190.8
2	41.4	369.2	16.4	189.1
3	141.8	368.9	17.2	99.0
4	140.3	368.8	17.2	99.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	5.1	0.696
160 - 140	17.4	2.539
180 - 160	45.1	7.919
200 - 180	612.4	113.665
220 - 200	56.9	12.086
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	736.9	136.905

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	339.6	61.543	3	200 - 180	129.8	24.877
	180 - 160	37.1	6.554		160 - 140	6.8	1.000
	160 - 140	10.6	1.539		140 - 120	5.1	0.696
	Total	387.4	69.637		Total	141.8	26.574
1	220 - 200	22.2	4.690	4	200 - 180	134.1	25.540
	200 - 180	3.8	0.731		180 - 160	6.2	1.073
	Total	26.0	5.421		Total	140.3	26.612
2	220 - 200	34.6	7.395				
	200 - 180	5.1	0.974				
	180 - 160	1.7	0.292				
	Total	41.4	8.661				

eP-EAZK-076

Location information

Krajská hygienická stanice / ředitelství KNTB a.s., Havlíčkovo nábřeží 600, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22757 N, 17.70223 E

Building area: 873 m²

1009 LiDAR points (1.16 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	511.3	247.6	0.1	150.1
1	322.7	251.2	0.1	291.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	4.8	0.553
140 - 120	14.3	1.938
160 - 140	14.3	2.240
180 - 160	112.7	19.296
200 - 180	687.8	128.536
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	834.0	152.563

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	372.7	69.471	1	200 - 180	315.1	59.064
	180 - 160	105.1	17.943		180 - 160	7.6	1.353
	160 - 140	14.3	2.240	Total	322.7	60.417	
	140 - 120	14.3	1.938				
	120 - 100	4.8	0.553				
Total		511.3	92.146				

eP-EAZK-077

Location information

Obecní úřad, - 272, Prostřední Bečva, obec Prostřední Bečva

49.43689 N, 18.26322 E

Building area: 282 m²

403 LiDAR points (1.43 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	41.3	479.3	7.7	316.6
1	44.1	481.2	1.0	243.8
2	87.4	483.7	28.8	318.9
3	65.8	483.6	28.6	138.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	3.6	0.415
140 - 120	96.4	13.268
160 - 140	14.6	2.201
180 - 160	33.2	5.645
200 - 180	25.0	4.642
220 - 200	65.8	14.104
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	238.5	40.276

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	24.3	4.110
	160 - 140	10.1	1.535
	140 - 120	6.1	0.793
	120 - 100	0.7	0.081
	Total	41.3	6.518
1	200 - 180	25.0	4.642
	180 - 160	8.8	1.535
	160 - 140	4.4	0.667
	140 - 120	2.9	0.386
	120 - 100	2.9	0.334
	Total	44.1	7.564

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	140 - 120	87.4	12.089
	Total	87.4	12.089
3	220 - 200	65.8	14.104
	Total	65.8	14.104

eP-EAZK-078

Location information

Víceúčelový objekt, - 74, Slopné, obec Slopné

49.15536 N, 17.84717 E

Building area: 863 m²

491 LiDAR points (0.57 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	50.1	353.3	24.3	296.3
1	41.7	353.4	22.7	116.0
2	30.6	353.4	24.0	206.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	2.3	0.352
180 - 160	52.5	8.555
200 - 180	23.9	4.659
220 - 200	43.8	9.243
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	122.5	22.808

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	50.1	8.161
	Total	50.1	8.161
1	220 - 200	13.9	2.795
	200 - 180	23.2	4.521
	180 - 160	2.3	0.394
	160 - 140	2.3	0.352
	Total	41.7	8.062

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	220 - 200	29.9	6.448
	200 - 180	0.7	0.138
Total		30.6	6.585

eP-EAZK-079

Location information

Bytový dům, - 64, Bařice - Velké Těšany, obec Bařice-Velké Těšany

49.24525 N, 17.42772 E

Building area: 158 m²

5 LiDAR points (0.03 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-080

Location information

Obecní úřad, - 203, Vigantice, obec Vigantice

49.44056 N, 18.19355 E

Building area: 216 m²

394 LiDAR points (1.82 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	68.1	440.5	30.5	220.8
1	35.4	440.2	30.9	311.5
2	56.9	440.5	30.5	39.8
3	43.0	440.3	30.4	130.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	6.9	0.613
120 - 100	5.9	0.671
140 - 120	77.5	10.457
160 - 140	2.0	0.276
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	3.1	0.613
220 - 200	108.1	22.961
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	203.4	35.591

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	65.1	13.826
	200 - 180	3.1	0.613
	Total	68.1	14.439
1	160 - 140	2.0	0.276
	140 - 120	20.6	2.724
	120 - 100	5.9	0.671
	< 100	6.9	0.613
	Total	35.4	4.284

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	140 - 120	56.9	7.733
	Total	56.9	7.733
3	220 - 200	43.0	9.135
	Total	43.0	9.135

eP-EAZK-081

Location information

Požární stanice, Holešovská 1700, Holešov, Hasičský záchranný sbor Zlínského kraje

49.31959 N, 17.57200 E

Building area: 808 m²

96 LiDAR points (0.12 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-082

Location information

Gymnázium, Palackého 524, Holešov, Zlínský kraj

49.32869 N, 17.57263 E

Building area: 1382 m²

1258 LiDAR points (0.91 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	179.2	246.0	45.5	334.4
1	137.2	245.8	32.2	154.4
2	109.3	246.4	32.1	243.9
3	110.5	246.3	32.0	243.7
4	27.3	245.0	31.8	154.1
5	29.3	245.1	31.7	334.3
6	22.8	244.9	27.5	238.9
7	49.5	245.4	30.9	334.2
8	53.8	246.5	27.6	149.0
9	88.8	247.0	28.7	154.5
10	13.2	245.0	11.4	54.0
11	153.0	245.9	39.3	62.4
12	50.8	245.5	31.9	334.1
13	28.8	245.1	36.8	155.3

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	362.4	32.693
120 - 100	45.8	4.942
140 - 120	77.3	9.627
160 - 140	6.9	1.072
180 - 160	9.4	1.620
200 - 180	108.9	21.205
220 - 200	189.0	38.929
240 - 220	253.9	56.494
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1053.5	166.582

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	< 100	179.2	17.398	3	220 - 200	94.1	18.972
	Total	179.2	17.398		200 - 180	8.2	1.596
1	240 - 220	87.8	19.559		180 - 160	2.7	0.462
	220 - 200	44.7	9.582		160 - 140	1.4	0.213
	200 - 180	3.1	0.581		140 - 120	4.1	0.525
	160 - 140	1.5	0.242	Total	110.5	21.768	
	Total	137.2	29.965	4	240 - 220	2.6	0.583
2	220 - 200	9.6	1.921		220 - 200	10.6	2.232
	200 - 180	91.5	17.853		200 - 180	5.3	1.007
	180 - 160	1.4	0.245		180 - 160	5.3	0.913
	160 - 140	1.4	0.211		160 - 140	2.6	0.405
	140 - 120	4.1	0.540		140 - 120	0.9	0.123
	120 - 100	1.4	0.149	Total	27.3	5.263	
Total	109.3	20.919	5	140 - 120	28.5	3.499	
3	220 - 200	94.1		18.972	120 - 100	0.8	0.097
	200 - 180	8.2		1.596	Total	29.3	3.596
	180 - 160	2.7	0.462				
160 - 140	1.4	0.213					
140 - 120	4.1	0.525					
Total	110.5	21.768					

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
6	220 - 200	21.9	4.482	10	< 100	13.2	1.076
	200 - 180	0.8	0.168		Total	13.2	1.076
	Total	22.8	4.649		11	140 - 120	5.5
7	140 - 120	34.3	4.209	120 - 100		9.1	0.942
	120 - 100	15.2	1.762	< 100		138.4	11.331
	Total	49.5	5.971	Total	153.0	13.006	
8	240 - 220	48.2	10.639	12	120 - 100	19.3	1.991
	220 - 200	5.6	1.215		< 100	31.5	2.889
	Total	53.8	11.854		Total	50.8	4.880
9	240 - 220	86.4	19.261	13	240 - 220	28.8	6.453
	220 - 200	2.5	0.525		Total	28.8	6.453
	Total	88.8	19.786				

eP-EAZK-083

Location information

Ubytovna, Tř. Tomáše Bati 1241, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22536 N, 17.51108 E

Building area: 1054 m²

1932 LiDAR points (1.83 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	576.0	197.5	0.1	300.2
1	384.1	198.8	0.0	257.5
2	8.1	200.7	1.0	45.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	5.9	0.581
120 - 100	5.9	0.686
140 - 120	11.8	1.585
160 - 140	11.8	1.828
180 - 160	297.8	52.596
200 - 180	635.1	117.094
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	968.2	174.369

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	246.8	44.830
	180 - 160	293.9	51.923
	160 - 140	11.8	1.828
	140 - 120	11.8	1.585
	120 - 100	5.9	0.686
	< 100	5.9	0.581
Total		576.0	101.432

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	200 - 180	380.2	70.782
	180 - 160	4.0	0.674
Total		384.1	71.456
2	200 - 180	8.1	1.481
	Total	8.1	1.481

eP-EAZK-084

Location information

Základní škola - budova B, - 437, Nový Hrozenkov, obec Nový Hrozenkov

49.33881 N, 18.19874 E

Building area: 887 m²

1074 LiDAR points (1.21 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	405.2	466.9	33.7	248.5
1	387.4	466.8	29.9	248.5
2	17.4	466.2	33.5	249.2
3	10.6	465.5	33.9	60.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	9.7	1.079
140 - 120	0.7	0.094
160 - 140	14.4	2.160
180 - 160	7.3	1.230
200 - 180	788.5	155.499
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	820.6	160.062

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	389.9	76.644	2	200 - 180	11.1	2.094
	180 - 160	3.8	0.635		180 - 160	3.5	0.594
	160 - 140	3.8	0.579		140 - 120	0.7	0.094
	120 - 100	7.6	0.835		120 - 100	2.1	0.244
	Total	405.2	78.693		Total	17.4	3.026
1	200 - 180	387.4	76.761	3	160 - 140	10.6	1.581
	Total	387.4	76.761		Total	10.6	1.581

eP-EAZK-085

Location information

Baťův institut, Vavrečkova 7040, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22513 N, 17.65876 E

Building area: 5464 m²

3543 LiDAR points (0.65 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	14.4	245.5	10.5	342.9
1	10.6	245.5	8.7	343.5
2	1599.8	242.8	0.2	346.1
3	311.6	246.7	0.3	151.3
4	49.0	251.4	1.1	182.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	32.3	3.752
140 - 120	48.5	6.398
160 - 140	86.7	12.795
180 - 160	123.2	21.106
200 - 180	1694.7	317.638
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1985.4	361.689

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	10.3	1.691	3	200 - 180	304.5	57.262
	160 - 140	4.1	0.651		180 - 160	7.1	1.190
	Total	14.4	2.342		Total	311.6	58.452
1	180 - 160	8.9	1.510	4	200 - 180	49.0	9.328
	160 - 140	1.8	0.272		Total	49.0	9.328
	Total	10.6	1.782				
2	200 - 180	1341.2	251.048				
	180 - 160	97.0	16.715				
	160 - 140	80.8	11.872				
	140 - 120	48.5	6.398				
	120 - 100	32.3	3.752				
Total	1599.8	289.785					

eP-EAZK-086

■ Location information

Požární stanice, Holešovská 1737, Bystřice pod Hostýnem, Hasičský záchranný sbor Zlínského kraje

49.39753 N, 17.66031 E

Building area: 453 m²

76 LiDAR points (0.17 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-087

Location information

Kulturní dům, Husova 432, Bojkovice, město Bojkovice

49.03946 N, 17.80876 E

Building area: 992 m²

1213 LiDAR points (1.22 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	40.1	310.2	4.3	265.4
1	15.0	310.6	27.4	261.3
2	211.7	311.6	30.1	80.9
3	100.7	309.8	3.2	80.2
4	182.4	309.8	58.9	353.2
5	8.2	306.5	1.8	350.2
6	27.6	310.2	2.0	50.3
7	29.5	316.3	7.2	259.5
8	29.0	316.3	6.7	81.7
9	27.7	316.3	9.5	173.0
10	26.8	316.3	8.6	350.6
11	194.4	312.1	30.0	261.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	184.4	12.420
120 - 100	4.0	0.457
140 - 120	27.3	3.569
160 - 140	30.2	4.520
180 - 160	320.0	54.984
200 - 180	299.6	55.794
220 - 200	27.7	5.675
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	893.2	137.419

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	6.7	1.222
	180 - 160	30.1	5.070
	160 - 140	3.3	0.503
	Total	40.1	6.794
1	200 - 180	12.5	2.347
	180 - 160	2.5	0.434
	Total	15.0	2.782
2	180 - 160	201.0	34.745
	160 - 140	10.7	1.597
	Total	211.7	36.342
3	200 - 180	73.1	13.439
	180 - 160	27.7	4.807
	Total	100.7	18.246
4	< 100	182.4	12.235
	Total	182.4	12.235
5	200 - 180	8.2	1.511
	Total	8.2	1.511
6	160 - 140	0.7	0.095
	140 - 120	20.9	2.729
	120 - 100	4.0	0.457
	< 100	2.0	0.185
	Total	27.6	3.465

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
7	200 - 180	27.4	5.168
	180 - 160	2.1	0.360
	Total	29.5	5.528
8	200 - 180	24.3	4.480
	180 - 160	4.7	0.806
	Total	29.0	5.287
9	220 - 200	27.7	5.675
	Total	27.7	5.675
10	180 - 160	22.1	3.723
	160 - 140	4.7	0.745
	Total	26.8	4.468
11	200 - 180	147.4	27.627
	180 - 160	29.9	5.039
	160 - 140	10.7	1.581
	140 - 120	6.4	0.841
	Total	194.4	35.087

eP-EAZK-088

Location information

Kulturní dům, Sidonie 44, Brumov-Bylnice, město Brumov-Bylnice

49.04554 N, 18.07805 E

Building area: 255 m²

361 LiDAR points (1.42 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	142.6	340.8	36.4	327.3
1	136.7	341.0	37.2	147.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	87.0	7.357
120 - 100	55.6	6.150
140 - 120	3.4	0.447
160 - 140	3.4	0.500
180 - 160	5.1	0.857
200 - 180	5.1	0.966
220 - 200	95.7	20.598
240 - 220	23.9	5.282
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	279.3	42.157

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	55.6	6.150
	< 100	87.0	7.357
	Total	142.6	13.508
1	240 - 220	23.9	5.282
	220 - 200	95.7	20.598
	200 - 180	5.1	0.966
	180 - 160	5.1	0.857
	160 - 140	3.4	0.500
	140 - 120	3.4	0.447
	Total	136.7	28.650

eP-EAZK-089

Location information

Katastrální úřad, Československé armády 259, Valašské Klobouky, město Valašské Klobouky

49.13964 N, 18.00928 E

Building area: 300 m²

504 LiDAR points (1.68 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	160.1	404.0	33.4	312.2
1	103.6	404.1	32.8	131.6
2	59.0	404.1	2.7	123.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	160.1	21.829
160 - 140	2.8	0.441
180 - 160	6.7	1.177
200 - 180	62.2	11.583
220 - 200	91.0	19.182
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	322.7	54.213

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	160.1	21.829
	Total	160.1	21.829
1	220 - 200	91.0	19.182
	200 - 180	5.6	1.094
	180 - 160	4.2	0.745
	160 - 140	2.8	0.441
	Total	103.6	21.462

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	56.6	10.489
	180 - 160	2.5	0.432
Total		59.0	10.921

eP-EAZK-090

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, - 176, Boršice, Zlínský kraj

49.06347 N, 17.35377 E

Building area: 149 m²

247 LiDAR points (1.65 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	14.6	239.1	9.6	301.9
1	31.9	237.9	37.5	223.3
2	24.0	238.4	30.8	42.8
3	24.0	237.3	43.2	311.8
4	24.0	237.9	33.3	135.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	19.0	1.617
120 - 100	27.5	3.054
140 - 120	21.1	2.726
160 - 140	7.8	1.170
180 - 160	8.0	1.384
200 - 180	7.0	1.315
220 - 200	28.3	5.981
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	118.6	17.247

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	8.0	1.384	3	140 - 120	2.4	0.291
	160 - 140	6.1	0.927		120 - 100	10.4	1.137
	120 - 100	0.5	0.057		< 100	11.2	0.909
	Total	14.6	2.368		Total	24.0	2.337
1	220 - 200	28.3	5.981	4	200 - 180	3.3	0.641
	200 - 180	3.6	0.675		160 - 140	1.7	0.243
	Total	31.9	6.655		140 - 120	6.6	0.856
2	140 - 120	12.0	1.579		120 - 100	8.3	0.934
	120 - 100	8.3	0.924	< 100	4.1	0.389	
	< 100	3.7	0.319	Total	24.0	3.064	
	Total	24.0	2.823				

eP-EAZK-091, eP-EAZK-092, eP-EAZK-093

Location information

Domov pro seniory, U Domova 470, Buchlovice, Zlínský kraj

49.08647 N, 17.34805 E

Building area: 3528 m²

3641 LiDAR points (1.03 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	262.3	279.2	35.1	156.8
1	394.4	278.0	35.0	336.9
2	32.5	281.3	5.4	67.5
3	455.8	279.3	34.7	246.9
4	11.3	271.8	19.8	156.3
5	8.2	271.8	18.1	157.9
6	18.7	272.7	35.0	246.7
7	166.0	275.0	34.8	246.9
8	376.5	275.5	34.9	336.9
9	375.0	275.6	35.0	156.9
10	12.2	275.5	33.0	67.9
11	11.4	277.0	37.4	159.5
12	6.9	275.1	34.5	173.2
13	5.9	275.4	6.1	11.6
14	10.6	275.8	37.1	158.1
15	8.8	276.2	24.4	83.0
16	18.3	275.9	20.4	336.4
17	17.7	275.0	41.1	335.3
18	39.6	277.6	38.5	336.8
19	50.8	276.2	9.2	30.3
20	206.6	279.7	13.3	157.1

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	208.9	17.992
120 - 100	636.3	72.517
140 - 120	20.6	2.726
160 - 140	68.2	10.334
180 - 160	119.0	20.220
200 - 180	571.7	111.748
220 - 200	236.4	49.668
240 - 220	628.4	141.847
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	2489.5	427.051

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	240 - 220	252.3	56.957	5	200 - 180	1.2	0.221	
	220 - 200	10.0	2.093		180 - 160	3.5	0.600	
	Total	262.3	59.050		160 - 140	2.9	0.428	
1	120 - 100	384.0	44.345	140 - 120	0.6	0.079	Total	
	< 100	10.4	0.957	8.2	1.328			
	Total	394.4	45.301					
2	200 - 180	26.3	4.833	6	200 - 180	3.4	0.636	
	180 - 160	6.2	1.084		180 - 160	6.8	1.150	
	Total	32.5	5.917		160 - 140	5.9	0.914	
3	200 - 180	362.6	70.920	140 - 120	1.7	0.229	Total	
	180 - 160	59.9	10.204	< 100	0.8	0.078		
	160 - 140	23.3	3.535	18.7	3.007			
	140 - 120	3.3	0.450	7	200 - 180	166.0		32.801
	120 - 100	6.7	0.771		Total	166.0		32.801
Total	455.8	85.879	8	120 - 100	224.1	25.104		
4	200 - 180	5.6		1.078	< 100	152.4	12.801	
	180 - 160	2.4	0.412	Total	376.5	37.905		
	160 - 140	1.6	0.236	9	240 - 220	352.7	79.584	
	< 100	1.6	0.146		220 - 200	17.9	3.775	
Total	11.3	1.872	200 - 180		4.5	0.867		
			Total	375.0	84.226			

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
10	160 - 140	12.2	1.903	16	160 - 140	4.6	0.646
	Total	12.2	1.903		140 - 120	9.1	1.192
11	240 - 220	10.8	2.437		120 - 100	2.3	0.263
	220 - 200	0.7	0.147		< 100	2.3	0.198
	Total	11.4	2.584	Total		18.3	2.299
12	240 - 220	2.1	0.470	17	120 - 100	2.5	0.260
	220 - 200	1.4	0.285		< 100	15.2	1.465
	200 - 180	2.1	0.393		Total	17.7	1.724
	180 - 160	0.7	0.121	18	120 - 100	14.0	1.466
	160 - 140	0.7	0.104		< 100	25.6	2.296
	Total	6.9	1.374	Total		39.6	3.763
13	180 - 160	2.2	0.353	19	180 - 160	28.5	4.729
	160 - 140	2.7	0.401		160 - 140	14.3	2.167
	140 - 120	0.5	0.068		140 - 120	5.3	0.707
	< 100	0.5	0.052		120 - 100	2.7	0.309
	Total	5.9	0.874	Total		50.8	7.912
14	240 - 220	10.6	2.399	20	220 - 200	206.6	43.366
	Total	10.6	2.399	Total		206.6	43.366
15	180 - 160	8.8	1.566				
	Total	8.8	1.566				

eP-EAZK-094

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Na Hrádku 100, Fryšták, Zlínský kraj

49.28645 N, 17.68358 E

Building area: 378 m²

314 LiDAR points (0.83 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-095

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, - 136, Hrobice, Zlínský kraj

49.28014 N, 17.79135 E

Building area: 654 m²

941 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	170.1	435.8	0.2	206.5
1	32.3	435.0	1.2	48.3
2	146.9	439.3	12.4	35.0
3	9.5	438.1	12.3	37.5
4	102.2	438.6	28.7	215.3
5	53.8	438.5	11.0	216.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	6.4	0.581
120 - 100	8.5	0.965
140 - 120	24.1	3.152
160 - 140	35.1	5.264
180 - 160	252.8	42.743
200 - 180	34.7	6.367
220 - 200	153.2	32.616
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	514.8	91.688

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	31.9	5.825	3	180 - 160	4.4	0.729
	180 - 160	78.7	13.584		160 - 140	3.8	0.573
	160 - 140	23.4	3.481		140 - 120	1.3	0.161
	140 - 120	21.3	2.770		Total	9.5	1.463
	120 - 100	8.5	0.965	4	220 - 200	99.4	21.627
	< 100	6.4	0.581		200 - 180	2.8	0.542
	Total	170.1	27.206	Total	102.2	22.169	
1	180 - 160	24.3	4.139	5	220 - 200	53.8	10.990
	160 - 140	6.5	0.977		Total	53.8	10.990
	140 - 120	1.6	0.221				
Total	32.3	5.337					
2	180 - 160	145.5	24.291				
	160 - 140	1.5	0.233				
Total	146.9	24.524					

eP-EAZK-096, eP-EAZK-101, eP-EAZK-102, eP-EAZK-103

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Javornická 830, Chvalčov, Zlínský kraj

49.39923 N, 17.69427 E

Building area: 1466 m²

1795 LiDAR points (1.22 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	149.0	353.2	30.6	121.6
1	163.4	356.1	29.4	122.0
2	332.5	357.4	23.2	211.7
3	52.6	358.0	23.6	211.5
4	324.1	354.3	30.5	301.7
5	212.9	356.0	30.1	31.6
6	340.0	357.2	29.9	301.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	60.4	5.452
120 - 100	46.0	5.177
140 - 120	310.6	40.881
160 - 140	488.3	72.629
180 - 160	51.9	8.855
200 - 180	231.5	44.520
220 - 200	385.6	80.882
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1574.5	258.395

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	88.4	18.041	3	220 - 200	49.8	10.714
	200 - 180	52.0	10.129		200 - 180	2.8	0.544
	180 - 160	3.5	0.611		Total	52.6	11.259
	160 - 140	3.5	0.488	4	160 - 140	276.9	41.278
	140 - 120	1.7	0.239		140 - 120	15.7	2.112
	Total	149.0	29.509		120 - 100	12.6	1.398
1	220 - 200	64.9	13.252		< 100	18.9	1.696
	200 - 180	69.1	13.333	Total	324.1	46.484	
	180 - 160	12.6	2.171	5	140 - 120	205.9	27.102
	160 - 140	12.6	1.854		120 - 100	7.0	0.804
	140 - 120	4.2	0.554		Total	212.9	27.906
Total	163.4	31.164	6	160 - 140	188.9	28.032	
2	220 - 200	182.5		38.874	140 - 120	83.1	10.873
	200 - 180	107.6		20.514	120 - 100	26.4	2.975
	180 - 160	35.9		6.072	< 100	41.6	3.757
	160 - 140	6.5	0.976	Total	340.0	45.637	
Total	332.5	66.437					

eP-EAZK-097

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - domeček 1, Javornická 831, Chvalčov, Zlínský kraj

49.39858 N, 17.69476 E

Building area: 286 m²

390 LiDAR points (1.36 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	20.0	348.6	10.0	31.2
1	137.0	350.9	31.4	301.8
2	123.0	351.7	29.6	121.8
3	11.7	351.5	14.6	120.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	2.0	0.176
120 - 100	1.3	0.141
140 - 120	5.5	0.722
160 - 140	146.3	21.713
180 - 160	3.3	0.538
200 - 180	19.2	3.758
220 - 200	114.1	23.437
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	291.7	50.485

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	3.3	0.538	2	220 - 200	110.0	22.616
	160 - 140	9.3	1.386		200 - 180	11.6	2.263
	140 - 120	4.0	0.514		160 - 140	1.4	0.222
	120 - 100	1.3	0.141		Total	123.0	25.101
	< 100	2.0	0.176	3	220 - 200	4.1	0.821
Total	20.0	2.755	200 - 180		7.6	1.494	
1	160 - 140	135.5	20.105	Total	11.7	2.315	
	140 - 120	1.5	0.208				
Total		137.0	20.313				

eP-EAZK-098

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - domeček 2, Javornická 832, Chvalčov, Zlínský kraj

49.39837 N, 17.69440 E

Building area: 285 m²

383 LiDAR points (1.34 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	16.5	348.5	8.6	29.9
1	142.6	350.8	31.2	301.8
2	117.1	351.6	29.2	121.7
3	17.5	351.5	15.3	120.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	2.6	0.239
120 - 100	5.3	0.595
140 - 120	10.6	1.394
160 - 140	142.5	21.169
180 - 160	3.3	0.550
200 - 180	24.9	4.871
220 - 200	104.4	21.455
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	293.6	50.272

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	0.7	0.106	2	220 - 200	95.0	19.549
	160 - 140	3.3	0.500		200 - 180	16.9	3.291
	140 - 120	4.6	0.589		180 - 160	2.6	0.444
	120 - 100	5.3	0.595		160 - 140	2.6	0.410
	< 100	2.6	0.239		Total	117.1	23.695
	Total	16.5	2.029				
1	160 - 140	136.6	20.258	3	220 - 200	9.5	1.906
	140 - 120	5.9	0.805		200 - 180	8.0	1.579
	Total	142.6	21.063		Total	17.5	3.485

eP-EAZK-099

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - domeček 3, Javornická 833, Chvalčov, Zlínský kraj

49.39815 N, 17.69404 E

Building area: 351 m²

449 LiDAR points (1.28 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	169.5	350.3	31.0	301.9
1	124.4	351.4	29.3	121.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	169.5	25.321
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	124.4	25.724
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	294.0	51.045

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	169.5	25.321	1	220 - 200	124.4	25.724
Total		169.5	25.321	Total		124.4	25.724

eP-EAZK-100

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením - domeček 4, Javornická 834, Chvalčov, Zlínský kraj

49.39846 N, 17.69386 E

Building area: 285 m²

439 LiDAR points (1.54 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	12.8	348.0	8.4	30.7
1	132.4	351.1	29.4	122.3
2	151.3	350.6	31.4	302.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.9	0.084
120 - 100	1.7	0.202
140 - 120	9.5	1.250
160 - 140	151.2	22.466
180 - 160	0.9	0.139
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	132.4	27.360
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	296.5	51.501

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	0.9	0.139	1	220 - 200	132.4	27.360
	160 - 140	3.4	0.503		Total	132.4	27.360
	140 - 120	6.0	0.768		2	160 - 140	147.8
	120 - 100	1.7	0.202	140 - 120		3.5	0.482
	< 100	0.9	0.084	Total	151.3	22.446	
Total		12.8	1.695				

eP-EAZK-104

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, U Cihelny 259, Uherské Hradiště - Jarošov, Zlínský kraj

49.07881 N, 17.48646 E

Building area: 120 m²

167 LiDAR points (1.39 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	53.5	191.1	38.4	302.7
1	51.5	190.8	38.6	122.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	53.5	7.408
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	7.6	1.525
220 - 200	43.9	8.848
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	105.0	17.782

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	53.5	7.408
	Total	53.5	7.408
1	220 - 200	43.9	8.848
	200 - 180	7.6	1.525
	Total	51.5	10.373

eP-EAZK-105, eP-EAZK-106, eP-EAZK-107

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Pod Obecnicu 308, Karolinka, Zlínský kraj

49.35439 N, 18.26472 E

Building area: 503 m²

791 LiDAR points (1.57 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	135.1	508.6	30.1	126.0
1	120.8	508.6	30.4	305.6
2	130.7	511.2	6.6	303.3
3	116.7	511.3	7.9	125.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	120.8	16.594
160 - 140	16.9	2.533
180 - 160	119.5	20.850
200 - 180	144.9	28.375
220 - 200	101.3	20.884
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	503.3	89.236

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	101.3	20.884	2	180 - 160	113.9	19.880
	200 - 180	28.1	5.455		160 - 140	16.9	2.533
	180 - 160	5.6	0.970		Total	130.7	22.413
	Total	135.1	27.309	3	200 - 180	116.7	22.921
1	140 - 120	120.8	16.594		Total	116.7	22.921
Total	120.8	16.594					

eP-EAZK-108, eP-EAZK-109, eP-EAZK-110, eP-EAZK-111

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Kojetinská 1126/54, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30030 N, 17.38658 E

Building area: 182 m²

268 LiDAR points (1.47 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	25.7	197.6	10.2	54.6
1	61.4	204.3	14.4	67.0
2	49.5	203.5	27.0	246.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	2.8	0.237
120 - 100	2.1	0.228
140 - 120	8.7	1.147
160 - 140	14.8	2.283
180 - 160	58.8	10.153
200 - 180	49.5	9.806
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	136.7	23.854

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	7.0	1.137
	160 - 140	7.7	1.174
	140 - 120	6.3	0.838
	120 - 100	2.1	0.228
	< 100	2.8	0.237
Total		25.7	3.613
1	180 - 160	51.8	9.016
	160 - 140	7.2	1.109
	140 - 120	2.4	0.310
	Total	61.4	10.434

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	49.5	9.806
	Total	49.5	9.806

eP-EAZK-112

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Lidická 1502, Kunovice, Zlínský kraj

49.04143 N, 17.46866 E

Building area: 120 m²

253 LiDAR points (2.11 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	68.8	196.9	36.7	16.0
1	62.5	196.8	36.9	195.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	14.6	1.355
120 - 100	54.2	5.828
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	62.5	14.222
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	131.3	21.405

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	54.2	5.828	1	240 - 220	62.5	14.222
	< 100	14.6	1.355		Total	62.5	14.222
	Total	68.8	7.184				

eP-EAZK-113a

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Cihlářská 526, Kunovice, Zlínský kraj

49.03723 N, 17.47422 E

Building area: 1140 m²

2070 LiDAR points (1.82 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	121.1	200.4	14.9	208.0
1	13.2	200.8	15.1	25.2
2	20.9	200.5	13.3	113.6
3	105.2	200.3	14.9	27.9
4	56.2	202.7	0.5	87.9
5	23.0	206.6	16.0	119.1
6	49.7	206.4	14.7	206.8
7	31.8	206.1	14.9	27.9
8	59.5	206.3	15.5	299.3
9	17.6	200.2	14.9	207.1
10	14.7	199.8	10.7	295.3
11	41.0	200.5	0.7	32.7
12	20.4	202.8	1.6	133.3
13	34.8	199.9	7.2	22.6
14	26.6	200.0	12.1	304.0
15	44.3	203.7	14.4	27.2
16	34.5	203.6	14.8	298.4
17	27.3	203.6	14.8	207.9
18	33.4	203.8	12.6	121.4
19	26.2	202.7	1.5	18.0
20	26.5	203.7	15.8	210.8
21	58.2	204.0	14.7	119.6

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	8.8	0.768
120 - 100	11.2	1.248
140 - 120	29.2	3.861
160 - 140	119.9	18.504
180 - 160	267.0	44.333
200 - 180	232.4	44.050
220 - 200	217.8	45.120
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	886.2	157.884

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	106.2	21.968	7	180 - 160	21.5	3.457
	200 - 180	15.0	2.861		160 - 140	10.3	1.586
	Total	121.1	24.828		Total	31.8	5.043
1	160 - 140	13.2	2.067	8	180 - 160	42.4	7.139
	Total	13.2	2.067		160 - 140	11.1	1.700
2	200 - 180	15.8	2.999		140 - 120	5.0	0.661
	180 - 160	3.6	0.609	120 - 100	1.0	0.121	
	160 - 140	1.4	0.225	Total	59.5	9.621	
	Total	20.9	3.833	9	220 - 200	4.7	0.957
3	180 - 160	55.5	8.928		200 - 180	7.4	1.413
	160 - 140	35.1	5.482		180 - 160	5.4	0.932
	140 - 120	11.7	1.578	Total	17.6	3.303	
	120 - 100	2.9	0.333	10	180 - 160	13.3	2.279
Total	105.2	16.321	160 - 140		0.7	0.116	
4	200 - 180	49.9	9.328		140 - 120	0.7	0.094
	180 - 160	6.3	1.112	Total	14.7	2.490	
	Total	56.2	10.440	11	200 - 180	32.5	5.981
5	220 - 200	11.9	2.392		180 - 160	5.4	0.932
	200 - 180	11.1	2.165		160 - 140	0.8	0.118
	Total	23.0	4.557		140 - 120	2.3	0.293
6	220 - 200	49.7	10.481	Total	41.0	7.324	
	Total	49.7	10.481				

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
12	180 - 160	8.4	1.360	17	220 - 200	25.8	5.326
	160 - 140	10.5	1.600		200 - 180	1.6	0.309
	140 - 120	1.4	0.188		Total	27.3	5.634
	Total	20.4	3.148	18	200 - 180	30.2	5.755
13	180 - 160	16.1	2.693		180 - 160	3.2	0.544
	160 - 140	10.2	1.531		Total	33.4	6.298
	140 - 120	3.4	0.444	19	200 - 180	10.2	1.863
	120 - 100	2.5	0.285		180 - 160	9.5	1.631
	< 100	2.5	0.221		160 - 140	5.1	0.759
Total	34.8	5.175	140 - 120		1.5	0.195	
14	180 - 160	3.1	0.515	Total	26.2	4.448	
	160 - 140	9.4	1.442	20	220 - 200	13.6	2.812
	140 - 120	3.1	0.408		200 - 180	11.6	2.218
	120 - 100	4.7	0.509		180 - 160	1.4	0.241
	< 100	6.3	0.547		Total	26.5	5.270
Total	26.6	3.420	21	220 - 200	5.9	1.184	
15	180 - 160	35.6		5.756	200 - 180	47.2	9.159
	160 - 140	8.7		1.377	180 - 160	2.5	0.434
	Total	44.3		7.132	160 - 140	2.5	0.379
16	180 - 160	33.7	5.771	Total	58.2	11.157	
	160 - 140	0.8	0.123				
	Total	34.5	5.894				

eP-EAZK-113b

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Cihlářská 526, Kunovice, Zlínský kraj

49.03696 N, 17.47364 E

Building area: 603 m²

1186 LiDAR points (1.97 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	17.2	205.0	14.9	118.0
1	187.8	205.7	14.8	118.2
2	19.9	205.2	13.3	201.7
3	21.7	205.2	13.4	32.0
4	221.0	205.5	14.8	297.7
5	68.2	205.2	14.9	27.7
6	56.2	204.7	13.8	207.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	2.6	0.227
120 - 100	10.2	1.073
140 - 120	28.8	3.773
160 - 140	108.6	16.661
180 - 160	177.3	29.879
200 - 180	92.1	18.012
220 - 200	172.4	34.938
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	592.1	104.563

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	16.6	3.198	4	180 - 160	142.1	24.116
	180 - 160	0.6	0.109		160 - 140	50.0	7.619
	Total	17.2	3.307		140 - 120	18.4	2.363
1	220 - 200	111.3	22.287		120 - 100	7.9	0.823
	200 - 180	62.6	12.330		< 100	2.6	0.227
	160 - 140	9.3	1.408	Total	221.0	35.148	
	140 - 120	2.3	0.317	5	180 - 160	11.6	1.855
	120 - 100	2.3	0.250		160 - 140	48.5	7.515
Total	187.8	36.592	140 - 120		8.1	1.093	
2	220 - 200	9.9	2.056	Total	68.2	10.463	
	200 - 180	7.8	1.471	6	220 - 200	51.1	10.594
	180 - 160	2.1	0.364		200 - 180	5.1	1.014
	Total	19.9	3.891		Total	56.2	11.609
3	180 - 160	21.0	3.436				
	160 - 140	0.8	0.119				
	Total	21.7	3.555				

eP-EAZK-113c

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Cihlářská 526, Kunovice, Zlínský kraj

49.03684 N, 17.47396 E

Building area: 409 m²

808 LiDAR points (1.97 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	33.7	204.2	0.6	50.9
1	35.6	202.0	17.0	27.8
2	26.4	204.2	0.7	129.9
3	51.8	205.2	15.2	26.9
4	25.7	205.2	15.4	207.4
5	101.5	205.3	15.1	118.2
6	90.3	205.3	15.1	298.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	5.5	0.635
140 - 120	6.9	0.921
160 - 140	47.3	7.198
180 - 160	166.5	28.105
200 - 180	113.4	21.636
220 - 200	25.3	5.260
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	364.9	63.755

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	10.7	1.946	4	220 - 200	23.9	4.989
	180 - 160	18.4	3.166		200 - 180	1.2	0.238
	160 - 140	3.8	0.567		180 - 160	0.6	0.107
	140 - 120	0.8	0.106		Total	25.7	5.335
	Total	33.7	5.784		5	220 - 200	1.4
1	160 - 140	25.3	3.830	200 - 180		90.7	17.477
	140 - 120	4.7	0.628	180 - 160		9.5	1.645
	120 - 100	5.5	0.635	Total	101.5	19.392	
	Total	35.6	5.093	6	180 - 160	82.4	14.095
2	200 - 180	10.8	1.976		160 - 140	7.9	1.231
	180 - 160	11.5	2.007		Total	90.3	15.325
	160 - 140	2.7	0.406				
	140 - 120	1.4	0.187				
Total	26.4	4.576					
3	180 - 160	44.2	7.086				
	160 - 140	7.5	1.164				
	Total	51.8	8.250				

eP-EAZK-113d

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Cihlářská 526, Kunovice, Zlínský kraj

49.03678 N, 17.47426 E

Building area: 604 m²

1162 LiDAR points (1.93 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	180.5	205.6	15.0	297.8
1	69.8	205.3	14.7	27.9
2	13.4	204.6	17.4	301.1
3	27.3	205.1	10.8	355.4
4	21.0	205.2	10.2	240.7
5	225.2	205.6	14.8	117.9
6	55.9	204.8	14.7	208.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	4.2	0.477
140 - 120	9.3	1.233
160 - 140	85.7	13.159
180 - 160	191.8	32.292
200 - 180	65.9	13.037
220 - 200	236.2	47.800
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	593.0	107.997

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	138.5	23.658	4	200 - 180	21.0	4.098
	160 - 140	33.6	5.084		Total	21.0	4.098
	140 - 120	4.2	0.549	5	220 - 200	182.1	36.442
	120 - 100	4.2	0.477		200 - 180	43.1	8.598
	Total	180.5	29.768		Total	225.2	45.039
1	180 - 160	34.4	5.536	6	220 - 200	54.1	11.358
	160 - 140	33.3	5.164		200 - 180	1.7	0.341
	140 - 120	2.1	0.291		Total	55.9	11.699
	Total	69.8	10.992				
2	180 - 160	8.6	1.417				
	160 - 140	4.8	0.752				
	Total	13.4	2.170				
3	180 - 160	10.3	1.681				
	160 - 140	14.0	2.158				
	140 - 120	3.0	0.393				
	Total	27.3	4.231				

eP-EAZK-114

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Na Bělince 1492, Kunovice, Zlínský kraj

49.04469 N, 17.45819 E

Building area: 1002 m²

1209 LiDAR points (1.21 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	416.9	182.1	0.7	102.2
1	154.6	189.8	21.2	348.4
2	68.7	186.3	40.8	348.5
3	75.5	189.3	21.3	167.1
4	48.7	189.7	21.3	167.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	87.4	7.903
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	11.5	1.469
160 - 140	150.6	21.636
180 - 160	7.4	1.298
200 - 180	383.4	70.931
220 - 200	3.1	0.682
240 - 220	121.1	26.711
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	764.4	130.629

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	383.4	70.931	2	< 100	68.7	6.202
	180 - 160	7.4	1.298		Total	68.7	6.202
	160 - 140	3.7	0.524	3	240 - 220	73.4	16.189
	140 - 120	3.7	0.452		220 - 200	2.1	0.466
	< 100	18.6	1.701		Total	75.5	16.655
Total	416.9	74.906	4	240 - 220	47.7	10.522	
1	160 - 140	146.8		21.112	220 - 200	1.0	0.216
	140 - 120	7.7		1.017	Total	48.7	10.738
Total	154.6	22.129					

eP-EAZK-115

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Cukrovar 304, Kvasice, Zlínský kraj

49.24399 N, 17.46535 E

Building area: 593 m²

606 LiDAR points (1.02 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	26.1	206.3	36.0	319.7
1	50.1	206.8	33.2	43.9
2	33.4	206.6	35.6	137.3
3	11.8	208.6	32.4	227.8
4	37.0	207.7	36.5	317.7
5	29.7	207.4	36.2	136.6
6	26.4	207.4	34.8	227.0
7	22.0	195.3	0.1	110.5
8	40.3	198.9	1.1	96.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	6.7	0.574
120 - 100	28.6	3.214
140 - 120	92.1	11.843
160 - 140	13.7	2.035
180 - 160	13.5	2.351
200 - 180	24.5	4.556
220 - 200	97.7	20.888
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	276.9	45.461

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	22.8	2.841	5	220 - 200	27.8	5.967
	120 - 100	3.4	0.389		200 - 180	1.0	0.180
	Total	26.1	3.230		180 - 160	1.0	0.173
1	140 - 120	42.1	5.537		Total	29.7	6.319
	120 - 100	5.0	0.564	6	220 - 200	24.7	5.203
	< 100	3.0	0.269		200 - 180	1.7	0.335
Total	50.1	6.370	Total		26.4	5.538	
2	220 - 200	33.4	7.204	7	160 - 140	8.7	1.279
	Total	33.4	7.204		140 - 120	10.7	1.394
3	220 - 200	11.8	2.515		120 - 100	2.7	0.284
	Total	11.8	2.515	Total	22.0	2.957	
4	140 - 120	15.7	1.961	8	200 - 180	21.8	4.041
	120 - 100	17.6	1.978		180 - 160	12.6	2.179
	< 100	3.7	0.305		160 - 140	5.0	0.756
	Total	37.0	4.243		140 - 120	0.8	0.109
					Total	40.3	7.085

eP-EAZK-116

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Parková 21, Kvasice, Zlínský kraj

49.24312 N, 17.47396 E

Building area: 1488 m²

608 LiDAR points (0.41 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	62.3	208.5	0.6	345.1
1	86.7	195.0	1.6	85.8
2	64.6	208.5	0.6	325.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.9	0.130
160 - 140	48.5	7.417
180 - 160	37.3	6.142
200 - 180	126.9	23.719
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	213.6	37.408

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	62.3	11.631	2	200 - 180	64.6	12.088
Total		62.3	11.631	Total		64.6	12.088
1	180 - 160	37.3	6.142				
	160 - 140	48.5	7.417				
	140 - 120	0.9	0.130				
Total		86.7	13.689				

eP-EAZK-117

Location information

Domov pro seniory, - 128, Loučka, Zlínský kraj

49.17004 N, 17.88305 E

Building area: 1761 m²

1805 LiDAR points (1.02 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	30.5	452.4	7.4	3.9
1	65.8	452.1	2.7	335.5
2	55.8	452.4	3.8	74.6
3	115.9	455.5	0.6	316.1
4	160.6	455.6	2.1	133.6
5	35.3	453.3	16.1	166.5
6	22.8	452.8	15.0	217.7
7	20.7	455.2	22.0	161.3
8	318.4	459.3	16.3	74.4
9	301.6	462.2	12.5	253.3
10	271.3	462.2	14.0	75.2
11	305.7	459.2	16.3	254.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	11.4	0.993
120 - 100	20.2	2.234
140 - 120	49.3	6.561
160 - 140	80.3	11.884
180 - 160	520.9	91.372
200 - 180	944.3	178.871
220 - 200	78.1	16.577
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1704.4	308.494

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	24.1	4.083	5	220 - 200	35.3	7.539
	160 - 140	6.4	0.974		Total	35.3	7.539
	Total	30.5	5.058		6	220 - 200	22.1
1	160 - 140	4.1	0.576	200 - 180		0.7	0.139
	140 - 120	31.7	4.163	Total		22.8	4.700
	120 - 100	18.7	2.059	7	220 - 200	20.7	4.477
	< 100	11.4	0.993		Total	20.7	4.477
Total	65.8	7.790	8	180 - 160	318.4	56.430	
2	160 - 140	47.3		6.939	Total	318.4	56.430
	140 - 120	8.6	1.189	9	200 - 180	287.7	55.284
	Total	55.8	8.128		180 - 160	13.9	2.435
3	200 - 180	34.6	6.318		Total	301.6	57.719
	180 - 160	48.2	8.197	10	200 - 180	186.4	33.672
	160 - 140	22.6	3.395		180 - 160	84.9	14.701
	140 - 120	9.0	1.210		Total	271.3	48.374
	120 - 100	1.5	0.175	11	200 - 180	293.7	56.815
	Total	115.9	19.296		180 - 160	12.0	2.135
4	200 - 180	141.1	26.642		Total	305.7	58.950
	180 - 160	19.4	3.390				
	Total	160.6	30.032				

eP-EAZK-118

Location information

Domov se zvláštním režimem, - 119, Loučka, Zlínský kraj

49.17001 N, 17.88390 E

Building area: 618 m²

120 LiDAR points (0.19 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-119

Location information

Domov pro seniory, V Drahách 1105, Luhačovice, Zlínský kraj

49.09650 N, 17.74402 E

Building area: 724 m²

88 LiDAR points (0.12 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-120, eP-EAZK-121, eP-EAZK-122

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Mlýnská 560, Luhačovice, Zlínský kraj

49.09786 N, 17.74668 E

Building area: 254 m²

329 LiDAR points (1.29 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	48.1	251.2	4.1	44.3
1	22.9	256.6	27.5	308.4
2	31.3	256.0	33.3	235.6
3	43.4	256.3	34.9	145.8
4	17.0	257.0	19.6	42.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.8	0.085
140 - 120	15.9	2.120
160 - 140	42.7	6.382
180 - 160	28.5	4.886
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	32.3	6.658
240 - 220	42.5	9.370
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	162.7	29.500

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	28.5	4.886	3	240 - 220	42.5	9.370
	160 - 140	11.4	1.731		220 - 200	1.0	0.212
	140 - 120	7.3	0.980		Total	43.4	9.582
	120 - 100	0.8	0.085	4	160 - 140	11.6	1.759
	Total	48.1	7.681		140 - 120	5.4	0.718
1	160 - 140	19.7	2.892	Total	17.0	2.478	
	140 - 120	3.2	0.421				
2	220 - 200	31.3	6.445				
	Total	31.3	6.445				

eP-EAZK-123a

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Hradská 82, Lukov, Zlínský kraj

49.29086 N, 17.73066 E

Building area: 361 m²

501 LiDAR points (1.39 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	95.8	324.9	32.8	10.4
1	32.7	324.0	28.4	283.3
2	25.3	324.3	33.7	103.2
3	104.1	324.6	33.2	190.5
4	19.0	321.6	27.4	292.1
5	16.6	322.1	32.8	83.0
6	18.3	321.7	33.8	11.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	14.7	1.409
120 - 100	109.0	12.194
140 - 120	13.6	1.772
160 - 140	20.6	3.109
180 - 160	47.9	8.036
200 - 180	14.8	2.791
220 - 200	25.7	5.473
240 - 220	65.6	14.735
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	311.8	49.519

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	95.8	10.772	4	160 - 140	13.2	1.973
	Total	95.8	10.772		140 - 120	4.1	0.531
1	180 - 160	28.7	4.804		120 - 100	0.8	0.092
	160 - 140	4.0	0.606	< 100	0.8	0.069	
Total	32.7	5.410	Total	19.0	2.665		
2	200 - 180	4.5	0.820	5	160 - 140	0.6	0.090
	180 - 160	17.9	3.008		140 - 120	8.0	1.041
	160 - 140	1.5	0.235		120 - 100	8.0	0.886
	140 - 120	1.5	0.199		Total	16.6	2.017
	Total	25.3	4.262	6	120 - 100	4.4	0.444
3	240 - 220	65.6	14.735		< 100	13.9	1.340
	220 - 200	25.7	5.473		Total	18.3	1.785
	200 - 180	10.3	1.971				
	180 - 160	1.3	0.223				
	160 - 140	1.3	0.205				
Total	104.1	22.608					

eP-EAZK-123b

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Hradská 82, Lukov, Zlínský kraj

49.29075 N, 17.73008 E

Building area: 972 m²

1257 LiDAR points (1.29 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	237.7	322.4	30.2	280.3
1	299.7	321.9	30.5	100.4
2	48.0	322.0	28.0	10.3
3	69.4	321.6	27.8	10.9
4	184.9	322.1	28.0	191.0
5	28.7	323.4	4.2	28.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	27.3	2.428
120 - 100	57.3	6.302
140 - 120	68.0	8.666
160 - 140	77.3	11.757
180 - 160	201.8	33.957
200 - 180	311.7	58.823
220 - 200	85.9	18.184
240 - 220	39.2	8.712
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	868.4	148.830

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	145.7	24.202	3	140 - 120	36.2	4.582
	160 - 140	58.8	8.923		120 - 100	24.1	2.679
	140 - 120	25.6	3.283		< 100	9.1	0.862
	120 - 100	2.6	0.301	Total	69.4	8.123	
	< 100	5.1	0.431	4	240 - 220	39.2	8.712
Total	237.7	37.141	220 - 200		85.9	18.184	
1	200 - 180	259.5	49.099		200 - 180	29.9	5.690
	180 - 160	32.9	5.751		180 - 160	16.8	2.873
	160 - 140	7.3	1.146		160 - 140	11.2	1.688
	Total	299.7	55.997	140 - 120	1.9	0.253	
2	140 - 120	4.4	0.548	Total	184.9	37.400	
	120 - 100	30.6	3.321	5	200 - 180	22.3	4.034
	< 100	13.1	1.135		180 - 160	6.4	1.130
Total	48.0	5.005	Total	28.7	5.164		

eP-EAZK-123c

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Hradská 82, Lukov, Zlínský kraj

49.29055 N, 17.72992 E

Building area: 1999 m²

2219 LiDAR points (1.11 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	137.5	325.9	35.4	122.9
1	77.7	327.4	19.3	303.0
2	76.8	324.3	33.7	9.8
3	28.9	324.0	35.9	304.2
4	234.1	327.3	35.3	10.3
5	301.1	326.3	35.2	190.3
6	38.2	328.6	2.8	9.3
7	47.8	326.4	40.5	10.0
8	184.6	326.6	46.0	280.4
9	54.4	324.2	42.6	101.1
10	50.3	328.3	39.2	100.1
11	18.1	319.8	1.4	16.5
12	174.2	326.6	34.3	10.2
13	45.1	324.5	34.1	190.6
14	108.6	328.2	34.4	190.5
15	27.2	326.6	30.0	189.7
16	43.9	326.6	30.6	99.8
17	46.7	326.2	44.5	278.1

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	144.5	12.817
120 - 100	479.9	52.487
140 - 120	46.4	6.137
160 - 140	129.5	19.214
180 - 160	224.4	37.729
200 - 180	141.3	26.648
220 - 200	176.8	36.872
240 - 220	352.3	79.798
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1695.1	271.701

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	103.1	21.229	5	240 - 220	198.3	44.773
	200 - 180	32.7	6.316		220 - 200	56.7	12.048
	180 - 160	1.7	0.289		200 - 180	24.8	4.748
	Total	137.5	27.834		180 - 160	14.2	2.429
1	180 - 160	73.9	12.175	160 - 140	7.1	1.097	Total
	160 - 140	3.8	0.593	301.1	65.095		
	Total	77.7	12.768				
2	120 - 100	62.7	7.031	6	200 - 180	22.6	4.108
	< 100	14.1	1.280		180 - 160	13.0	2.272
	Total	76.8	8.311		160 - 140	0.9	0.130
			140 - 120		1.7	0.224	
3	140 - 120	12.7	1.656	Total	38.2	6.734	
	120 - 100	8.5	0.940	7	120 - 100	39.5	3.982
	< 100	7.6	0.675		< 100	8.3	0.782
	Total	28.9	3.271		Total	47.8	4.764
4	120 - 100	224.3	24.812	8	160 - 140	97.6	14.292
	< 100	9.8	0.841		140 - 120	29.7	3.958
	Total	234.1	25.654		120 - 100	14.9	1.615
					< 100	42.4	3.550
			Total		184.6	23.414	

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
9	200 - 180	5.1	0.928	14	240 - 220	85.1	19.366
	180 - 160	45.6	7.862		220 - 200	13.6	2.862
	160 - 140	3.8	0.568		200 - 180	6.2	1.157
	Total	54.4	9.358		180 - 160	3.7	0.615
10	200 - 180	13.1	2.425	Total	108.6	24.001	
	180 - 160	28.5	4.933	15	240 - 220	23.8	5.369
	160 - 140	7.7	1.168		220 - 200	3.4	0.733
	140 - 120	1.1	0.150		Total	27.2	6.101
	Total	50.3	8.676	16	200 - 180	36.9	6.965
11	120 - 100	0.8	0.081		180 - 160	7.0	1.225
	< 100	17.3	1.461		Total	43.9	8.191
	Total	18.1	1.541	17	180 - 160	36.9	5.928
12	120 - 100	129.2	14.027		160 - 140	8.7	1.365
	< 100	45.0	4.228		140 - 120	1.1	0.149
	Total	174.2	18.255		Total	46.7	7.442
13	240 - 220	45.1	10.290				
	Total	45.1	10.290				

eP-EAZK-123d

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Hradská 82, Lukov, Zlínský kraj

49.29055 N, 17.73067 E

Building area: 1037 m²

1384 LiDAR points (1.33 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	146.6	326.4	33.4	341.9
1	202.3	326.6	35.1	161.9
2	37.4	325.9	34.5	71.6
3	248.0	325.7	35.8	261.6
4	112.5	327.2	34.1	81.5
5	37.1	326.3	35.1	172.0
6	57.2	325.9	34.0	188.9
7	8.0	325.9	29.6	161.4
8	11.2	326.3	33.1	82.1
9	13.1	325.4	33.1	81.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	148.1	17.405
140 - 120	1.5	0.207
160 - 140	36.5	5.788
180 - 160	139.9	23.930
200 - 180	252.2	46.546
220 - 200	20.0	4.252
240 - 220	275.3	62.310
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	873.4	160.437

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	146.6	17.248	5	240 - 220	37.1	8.496
	Total	146.6	17.248		Total	37.1	8.496
1	240 - 220	183.5	41.370	6	240 - 220	47.7	10.880
	220 - 200	10.4	2.204		220 - 200	8.5	1.813
	200 - 180	6.3	1.177		200 - 180	1.1	0.194
	180 - 160	2.1	0.373		Total	57.2	12.887
	Total	202.3	45.124		7	240 - 220	7.0
2	180 - 160	0.9	0.150		220 - 200	1.1	0.234
	160 - 140	36.5	5.788	Total	8.0	1.799	
	Total	37.4	5.937	8	180 - 160	11.2	1.912
3	200 - 180	244.9	45.175	Total	11.2	1.912	
	180 - 160	3.1	0.554	9	180 - 160	13.1	2.229
	Total	248.0	45.729	Total	13.1	2.229	
4	180 - 160	109.4	18.712				
	140 - 120	1.5	0.207				
	120 - 100	1.5	0.157				
	Total	112.5	19.076				

eP-EAZK-124

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, - 90, Medlovice, Zlínský kraj

49.05031 N, 17.27106 E

Building area: 250 m²

514 LiDAR points (2.06 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	126.4	339.8	26.4	256.4
1	37.7	339.9	27.7	77.5
2	42.4	340.6	14.0	77.0
3	26.5	339.6	27.4	76.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.9	0.077
120 - 100	1.7	0.200
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	3.4	0.522
180 - 160	77.4	13.253
200 - 180	149.7	28.241
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	233.0	42.293

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	126.4	24.022	2	200 - 180	23.3	4.218
	Total	126.4	24.022		180 - 160	16.6	2.882
1	180 - 160	34.3	5.885		160 - 140	2.5	0.388
	160 - 140	0.9	0.135	Total	42.4	7.489	
	120 - 100	1.7	0.200	3	180 - 160	26.5	4.485
	< 100	0.9	0.077		Total	26.5	4.485
	Total	37.7	6.297				

eP-EAZK-125

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Nádražní 144, Morkovice - Slížany, Zlínský kraj

49.24937 N, 17.20922 E

Building area: 131 m²

244 LiDAR points (1.87 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	73.9	303.7	33.6	319.0
1	48.9	303.6	34.3	139.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	11.5	0.940
120 - 100	16.7	1.848
140 - 120	45.8	5.843
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	48.9	10.609
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	122.8	19.239

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	45.8	5.843	1	220 - 200	48.9	10.609
	120 - 100	16.7	1.848		Total	48.9	10.609
	< 100	11.5	0.940				
	Total	73.9	8.630				

eP-EAZK-126

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Husova 1165, Napajedla, Zlínský kraj

49.17820 N, 17.52280 E

Building area: 655 m²

804 LiDAR points (1.23 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	76.6	222.4	9.5	202.8
1	32.4	222.7	5.0	19.7
2	24.5	222.3	11.9	211.9
3	19.4	222.6	7.8	33.3
4	231.1	222.4	35.0	298.0
5	62.5	220.7	35.7	208.8
6	66.2	220.8	36.4	27.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	4.0	0.386
120 - 100	78.3	9.167
140 - 120	49.3	6.454
160 - 140	174.1	25.735
180 - 160	49.3	8.511
200 - 180	15.0	2.895
220 - 200	80.4	16.323
240 - 220	62.5	13.936
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	512.7	83.407

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	66.1	13.432	3	180 - 160	18.7	3.213
	200 - 180	9.4	1.814		160 - 140	0.7	0.118
	180 - 160	1.0	0.176		Total	19.4	3.331
	Total	76.6	15.422	4	160 - 140	168.8	24.933
1	180 - 160	25.6	4.444		140 - 120	46.2	6.046
	160 - 140	4.5	0.684		120 - 100	12.1	1.404
	140 - 120	2.3	0.302		< 100	4.0	0.386
Total	32.4	5.430	Total	231.1	32.769		
2	220 - 200	14.2	2.891	5	240 - 220	62.5	13.936
	200 - 180	5.5	1.081		Total	62.5	13.936
	180 - 160	4.0	0.678	6	120 - 100	66.2	7.763
	140 - 120	0.8	0.106		Total	66.2	7.763
Total	24.5	4.755					

eP-EAZK-127

■ Location information

Domov se zvláštním režimem, - 100, Návojná, Zlínský kraj

49.10973 N, 18.05334 E

Building area: 878 m²

241 LiDAR points (0.27 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-128

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, - 589, Nedakonice, Zlínský kraj

49.02852 N, 17.38605 E

Building area: 88 m²

238 LiDAR points (2.72 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-129

■ Location information

Chráněné bydlení, - 590, Nedakonice, Zlínský kraj

49.02849 N, 17.38607 E

Building area: 114 m²

356 LiDAR points (3.11 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-130

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, - 600, Nedakonice, Zlínský kraj

49.02875 N, 17.38596 E

Building area: 177 m²

39 LiDAR points (0.22 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-131

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, - 601, Nedakonice, Zlínský kraj

49.02866 N, 17.38609 E

Building area: 177 m²

39 LiDAR points (0.22 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-132

Location information

Domov se zvláštním režimem, - 9, Pržno, Zlínský kraj

49.38775 N, 17.94226 E

Building area: 295 m²

417 LiDAR points (1.41 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	33.5	339.2	29.1	128.8
1	17.8	337.8	2.0	53.0
2	20.5	338.9	30.6	39.1
3	63.8	340.4	7.3	221.7
4	23.0	341.2	28.0	219.0
5	62.9	340.6	4.2	39.2
6	10.2	341.5	1.6	15.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	4.5	0.384
120 - 100	7.4	0.838
140 - 120	29.2	3.846
160 - 140	18.5	2.783
180 - 160	42.3	7.331
200 - 180	76.1	14.724
220 - 200	53.7	11.402
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	231.8	41.307

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	33.5	7.058	4	220 - 200	20.2	4.344
	Total	33.5	7.058		200 - 180	2.8	0.513
1	160 - 140	3.2	0.475		Total	23.0	4.857
	140 - 120	4.5	0.587	5	200 - 180	1.7	0.306
	120 - 100	5.7	0.637		180 - 160	39.9	6.918
	< 100	4.5	0.384		160 - 140	15.3	2.308
	Total	17.8	2.083		140 - 120	4.2	0.583
2	140 - 120	20.5	2.676		120 - 100	1.7	0.201
	Total	20.5	2.676	Total	62.9	10.317	
3	200 - 180	61.5	12.026	6	200 - 180	10.2	1.879
	180 - 160	2.4	0.412		Total	10.2	1.879
	Total	63.8	12.438				

eP-EAZK-133

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Julia Fučíka 1605, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.45807 N, 18.14768 E

Building area: 3758 m²

4712 LiDAR points (1.25 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	185.2	400.4	19.6	293.3
1	302.6	398.7	19.5	112.9
2	356.5	392.0	11.1	35.7
3	608.2	386.2	0.3	261.2
4	349.3	398.7	19.3	270.2
5	168.1	398.7	19.3	89.9
6	199.9	398.8	19.2	90.3
7	190.9	400.3	19.3	270.0
8	338.8	400.4	19.5	112.8
9	360.2	400.4	19.7	292.9
10	50.2	400.2	18.3	288.0
11	124.3	391.9	31.6	216.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	98.4	12.910
160 - 140	206.3	31.485
180 - 160	1349.6	229.348
200 - 180	1458.1	278.479
220 - 200	121.8	26.618
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	3234.2	578.839

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	149.4	25.260	6	200 - 180	193.5	36.065
	160 - 140	21.0	3.205		180 - 160	6.4	1.137
	140 - 120	14.7	1.923		Total	199.9	37.202
	Total	185.2	30.388	7	200 - 180	190.9	35.361
1	200 - 180	302.6	60.402		Total	190.9	35.361
	Total	302.6	60.402	8	200 - 180	335.3	66.515
	2	180 - 160	269.6		44.575	180 - 160	3.5
160 - 140		68.6	10.563		Total	338.8	67.128
140 - 120		18.3	2.330	9	180 - 160	339.0	57.617
Total	356.5	57.468	160 - 140		17.7	2.626	
3	200 - 180	79.9	14.431		140 - 120	3.5	0.481
	180 - 160	387.0	66.645		Total	360.2	60.724
	160 - 140	86.0	13.054	10	180 - 160	50.2	8.767
	140 - 120	55.3	7.308		Total	50.2	8.767
Total	608.2	101.438	11	220 - 200	121.8	26.618	
4	200 - 180	212.2		39.093	200 - 180	2.5	0.500
	180 - 160	117.5		20.080	Total	124.3	27.118
	160 - 140	13.1		2.037	5	200 - 180	141.1
	140 - 120	6.5	0.868	180 - 160		27.0	4.654
Total	349.3	62.078	Total	168.1		30.764	

eP-EAZK-134

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Zemědělská 573, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46093 N, 18.13550 E

Building area: 181 m²

44 LiDAR points (0.24 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-135

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Školní 276, Slavičín, Zlínský kraj

49.08949 N, 17.87877 E

Building area: 112 m²

187 LiDAR points (1.67 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	15.3	367.9	38.3	277.2
1	40.1	367.8	38.3	7.6
2	21.4	367.8	39.4	98.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	40.1	4.199
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	15.3	2.544
200 - 180	21.4	3.932
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	76.8	10.675

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	15.3	2.544
Total		15.3	2.544
1	120 - 100	40.1	4.199
Total		40.1	4.199

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	21.4	3.932
Total		21.4	3.932

eP-EAZK-136

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Tyršova 1626, Staré Město, Zlínský kraj

49.07348 N, 17.44179 E

Building area: 100 m²

160 LiDAR points (1.60 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	20.8	186.8	41.4	255.0
1	14.3	187.4	38.2	73.2
2	14.0	187.6	38.1	163.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	14.3	2.268
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	20.8	3.906
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	14.0	3.190
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	49.1	9.364

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	20.8	3.906	2	240 - 220	14.0	3.190
Total		20.8	3.906	Total		14.0	3.190
1	160 - 140	14.3	2.268				
Total		14.3	2.268				

eP-EAZK-137

■ Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Velehradská 2169, Staré Město, Zlínský kraj

49.08190 N, 17.43729 E

Building area: 202 m²

45 LiDAR points (0.22 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-138

Location information

Domov se zvláštním režimem, Okružní 1519, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02701 N, 17.66150 E

Building area: 1676 m²

3054 LiDAR points (1.82 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	1069.3	219.2	0.7	231.3
1	180.0	223.0	0.8	67.6
2	178.6	223.0	0.6	332.9
3	155.2	223.1	0.8	162.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	41.5	3.872
120 - 100	93.4	10.379
140 - 120	135.0	17.845
160 - 140	124.6	18.637
180 - 160	176.5	30.684
200 - 180	1012.0	188.730
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1583.0	270.148

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	498.3	92.387	2	200 - 180	178.6	33.213
	180 - 160	176.5	30.684		Total	178.6	33.213
	160 - 140	124.6	18.637	3	200 - 180	155.2	29.381
	140 - 120	135.0	17.845		Total	155.2	29.381
	120 - 100	93.4	10.379				
	< 100	41.5	3.872				
	Total	1069.3	173.805				
1	200 - 180	180.0	33.749				
	Total	180.0	33.749				

eP-EAZK-139

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Antonína Dvořáka 1248, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02757 N, 17.63854 E

Building area: 97 m²

216 LiDAR points (2.22 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	12.7	250.7	44.9	319.9
1	23.0	250.5	42.4	228.6
2	25.7	250.6	44.8	138.6
3	16.7	250.2	42.2	48.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	16.9	1.878
140 - 120	12.5	1.560
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	2.8	0.545
220 - 200	46.0	9.695
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	78.2	13.678

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	12.7	1.401
	Total	12.7	1.401
1	220 - 200	23.0	4.847
	Total	23.0	4.847
2	220 - 200	23.0	4.848
	200 - 180	2.8	0.545
	Total	25.7	5.393

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	140 - 120	12.5	1.560
	120 - 100	4.2	0.477
	Total	16.7	2.037

eP-EAZK-140

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Na Dlouhých 1205, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02841 N, 17.63678 E

Building area: 98 m²

206 LiDAR points (2.09 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-141

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Slovákcké náměstí 2034, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.01961 N, 17.64853 E

Building area: 115 m²

240 LiDAR points (2.10 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	24.5	216.9	35.7	344.6
1	20.6	217.6	40.3	164.0
2	12.3	216.7	38.7	254.0
3	17.7	217.2	38.8	74.0
4	3.8	214.3	38.5	74.0
5	4.6	217.3	38.1	72.9
6	9.1	216.5	41.2	253.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	2.4	0.212
120 - 100	22.0	2.423
140 - 120	0.8	0.115
160 - 140	23.0	3.650
180 - 160	8.5	1.401
200 - 180	21.0	3.965
220 - 200	5.8	1.203
240 - 220	9.1	2.042
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	92.6	15.011

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	22.0	2.423	3	160 - 140	17.7	2.811
	< 100	2.4	0.212		Total	17.7	2.811
	Total	24.5	2.635	4	180 - 160	3.8	0.616
1	240 - 220	9.1	2.042		Total	3.8	0.616
	220 - 200	5.8	1.203	5	160 - 140	4.6	0.731
	200 - 180	1.6	0.317		Total	4.6	0.731
	180 - 160	3.3	0.554	6	200 - 180	7.7	1.448
	140 - 120	0.8	0.115		180 - 160	0.7	0.118
Total	20.6	4.230	160 - 140		0.7	0.108	
2	200 - 180	11.6	2.200	Total	9.1	1.674	
	180 - 160	0.6	0.113				
	Total	12.3	2.313				

eP-EAZK-142, eP-EAZK-143

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Štěpnická 1139, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06418 N, 17.44780 E

Building area: 1105 m²

1392 LiDAR points (1.26 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	924.7	193.4	0.0	184.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	924.7	173.812
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	924.7	173.812

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	924.7	173.812
Total		924.7	173.812

eP-EAZK-144

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Rostislavova 686, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06425 N, 17.46849 E

Building area: 198 m²

372 LiDAR points (1.88 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	83.4	187.5	31.6	4.6
1	9.3	186.7	11.4	79.6
2	21.2	187.3	31.2	184.4
3	21.6	187.3	31.7	184.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	83.4	9.895
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	2.7	0.425
180 - 160	6.6	1.075
200 - 180	0.8	0.167
220 - 200	18.5	4.008
240 - 220	23.4	5.235
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	135.4	20.804

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	83.4	9.895
	Total	83.4	9.895
1	180 - 160	6.6	1.075
	160 - 140	2.7	0.425
	Total	9.3	1.499
2	240 - 220	9.3	2.082
	220 - 200	11.0	2.373
	200 - 180	0.8	0.167
Total	21.2	4.623	

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	240 - 220	14.1	3.153
	220 - 200	7.5	1.635
Total	21.6	4.787	

eP-EAZK-145, eP-EAZK-146, eP-EAZK-147, eP-EAZK-148, eP-EAZK-149

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Rostislavova 671, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06459 N, 17.47088 E

Building area: 163 m²

309 LiDAR points (1.90 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-150

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Školní 774, Uherský Ostroh, Zlínský kraj

48.98722 N, 17.39801 E

Building area: 909 m²

1465 LiDAR points (1.61 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	12.7	177.2	7.0	215.9
1	307.3	179.0	0.3	95.9
2	74.6	183.5	0.6	24.7
3	286.0	183.4	0.7	35.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	60.3	10.640
200 - 180	620.3	115.073
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	680.6	125.712

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	6.1	1.101
	180 - 160	6.7	1.185
	Total	12.7	2.286
1	200 - 180	254.9	47.051
	180 - 160	52.4	9.240
	Total	307.3	56.291

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	73.4	13.612
	180 - 160	1.2	0.214
	Total	74.6	13.826
3	200 - 180	286.0	53.309
	Total	286.0	53.309

eP-EAZK-151, eP-EAZK-152

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Václavkova 919, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.48273 N, 17.96456 E

Building area: 262 m²

38 LiDAR points (0.14 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-153

Location information

Poradna - hlavní budova, Husova 402/15, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.46910 N, 17.96544 E

Building area: 262 m²

335 LiDAR points (1.28 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	50.3	310.6	47.0	256.3
1	7.1	312.4	36.0	62.7
2	24.4	311.3	34.0	345.4
3	48.6	311.3	30.6	165.2
4	8.6	307.8	2.4	183.1
5	19.4	304.3	6.8	174.4
6	6.4	308.5	10.6	170.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	12.6	1.119
120 - 100	11.8	1.222
140 - 120	6.4	0.878
160 - 140	1.2	0.181
180 - 160	41.6	7.268
200 - 180	62.7	11.784
220 - 200	28.2	5.839
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	164.7	28.291

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	16.0	2.921
	180 - 160	34.2	6.015
	Total	50.3	8.936
1	160 - 140	0.6	0.091
	140 - 120	6.4	0.878
	Total	7.1	0.968
2	120 - 100	11.8	1.222
	< 100	12.6	1.119
	Total	24.4	2.341
3	220 - 200	21.8	4.507
	200 - 180	20.8	3.943
	180 - 160	5.9	1.004
	Total	48.6	9.454

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
4	200 - 180	8.6	1.627
	Total	8.6	1.627
5	200 - 180	17.3	3.293
	180 - 160	1.5	0.249
	160 - 140	0.6	0.090
Total	19.4	3.632	
6	220 - 200	6.4	1.332
	Total	6.4	1.332

eP-EAZK-154

Location information

Poradna - kuchyně, Husova 404/17, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.46906 N, 17.96494 E

Building area: 181 m²

333 LiDAR points (1.84 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	48.9	304.4	31.1	165.9
1	7.8	303.9	29.4	253.4
2	8.7	304.0	31.0	78.0
3	56.3	304.2	30.2	346.9
4	18.4	303.7	36.1	255.9
5	16.4	303.6	35.3	74.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.7	0.067
120 - 100	13.3	1.569
140 - 120	46.6	5.698
160 - 140	22.1	3.362
180 - 160	20.0	3.473
200 - 180	11.1	2.068
220 - 200	19.3	4.117
240 - 220	23.4	5.219
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	156.5	25.573

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	240 - 220	23.4	5.219	3	140 - 120	45.0	5.489
	220 - 200	19.3	4.117		120 - 100	11.3	1.343
	200 - 180	2.8	0.531		Total	56.3	6.832
	180 - 160	0.7	0.120	4	200 - 180	6.7	1.228
	120 - 100	2.1	0.227		180 - 160	11.7	2.068
	< 100	0.7	0.067		Total	18.4	3.296
	Total	48.9	10.281	5	160 - 140	14.9	2.211
1	200 - 180	1.7	0.309		140 - 120	1.6	0.209
	180 - 160	5.6	0.968		Total	16.4	2.420
	160 - 140	0.6	0.088				
Total	7.8	1.365					
2	180 - 160	2.0	0.317				
	160 - 140	6.7	1.063				
	Total	8.7	1.380				

eP-EAZK-155

■ Location information

Domov pro seniory, Žerotínova 1568, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47174 N, 17.97807 E

Building area: 1336 m²

237 LiDAR points (0.18 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-156

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Buchlovská 301, Velehrad, Zlínský kraj

49.10591 N, 17.38944 E

Building area: 1005 m²

1545 LiDAR points (1.54 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	27.7	216.2	10.4	235.8
1	131.5	219.5	9.5	54.8
2	45.2	219.3	24.8	145.2
3	41.5	219.3	25.2	235.1
4	37.8	219.2	25.1	324.8
5	46.4	219.1	24.4	55.0
6	76.7	219.3	24.6	324.9
7	79.4	219.5	25.2	55.0
8	191.5	219.2	24.6	234.9
9	25.6	216.2	25.0	144.9
10	45.3	219.4	24.8	324.9
11	48.5	219.3	25.2	145.0
12	47.6	219.4	24.8	55.2
13	46.8	219.6	23.9	234.7

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	8.4	0.767
120 - 100	51.5	5.786
140 - 120	66.5	8.787
160 - 140	283.8	42.979
180 - 160	100.7	17.220
200 - 180	71.2	13.678
220 - 200	309.4	63.997
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	891.5	153.213

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	27.7	5.374	4	160 - 140	3.7	0.517
	Total	27.7	5.374		140 - 120	21.2	2.811
1	180 - 160	66.5	11.425	120 - 100	7.4	0.811	
	160 - 140	23.2	3.525	< 100	5.5	0.512	
	140 - 120	20.1	2.607	Total	37.8	4.651	
	120 - 100	21.7	2.477	5	160 - 140	39.6	6.153
	Total	131.5	20.034		140 - 120	1.9	0.258
2	220 - 200	25.7	5.404		120 - 100	4.8	0.526
	200 - 180	9.8	1.820	Total	46.4	6.937	
	180 - 160	7.1	1.203	6	160 - 140	73.2	10.510
	160 - 140	2.7	0.405		140 - 120	1.2	0.160
	Total	45.2	8.832		120 - 100	2.4	0.281
3	220 - 200	26.0	5.302		Total	76.7	10.951
	200 - 180	9.6	1.861				
	180 - 160	1.9	0.325				
	160 - 140	2.9	0.453				
	140 - 120	1.0	0.131				
	Total	41.5	8.072				

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
7	160 - 140	79.4	12.422	11	220 - 200	18.3	3.819
Total		79.4	12.422		200 - 180	8.2	1.557
8	220 - 200	188.9	39.055		180 - 160	18.3	3.106
	200 - 180	2.7	0.519		160 - 140	3.7	0.536
Total		191.5	39.575	Total		48.5	9.018
9	220 - 200	16.8	3.528	12	160 - 140	41.0	6.409
	200 - 180	4.8	0.910		140 - 120	2.8	0.384
	180 - 160	4.0	0.683		120 - 100	3.7	0.403
Total		25.6	5.121	Total		47.6	7.197
10	160 - 140	12.5	1.769	13	220 - 200	33.7	6.889
	140 - 120	18.3	2.435		200 - 180	8.4	1.637
	120 - 100	11.6	1.288		180 - 160	2.8	0.478
	< 100	2.9	0.255		160 - 140	1.9	0.280
Total		45.3	5.747	Total		46.8	9.284

eP-EAZK-157

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Nádvoří 305, Velehrad, Zlínský kraj

49.10260 N, 17.39660 E

Building area: 314 m²

415 LiDAR points (1.32 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	69.4	212.8	6.9	283.2
1	27.5	221.2	27.1	104.8
2	15.0	218.0	38.5	289.2
3	26.7	221.8	28.5	279.4
4	17.1	218.1	45.4	102.1
5	16.0	220.4	30.5	255.4
6	14.6	217.7	40.3	194.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	6.7	0.619
120 - 100	5.2	0.582
140 - 120	8.0	1.062
160 - 140	21.3	3.206
180 - 160	74.3	12.728
200 - 180	56.2	10.665
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	14.6	3.318
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	186.3	32.180

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	44.9	7.657	3	180 - 160	25.1	4.304
	160 - 140	11.8	1.792		160 - 140	1.6	0.241
	140 - 120	5.3	0.710	Total	26.7	4.546	
	120 - 100	4.3	0.478	4	200 - 180	14.2	2.612
	< 100	3.2	0.310		180 - 160	2.8	0.503
	Total	69.4	10.948	Total	17.1	3.115	
1	200 - 180	27.5	5.352	5	200 - 180	14.4	2.701
	Total	27.5	5.352		180 - 160	1.5	0.263
2	160 - 140	7.9	1.172	Total	16.0	2.964	
	140 - 120	2.6	0.352	6	240 - 220	14.6	3.318
	120 - 100	0.9	0.104		Total	14.6	3.318
	< 100	3.5	0.309				
Total	15.0	1.937					

eP-EAZK-158

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Rokytnice 48, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.32771 N, 17.98302 E

Building area: 395 m²

552 LiDAR points (1.40 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	149.4	361.3	8.7	24.9
1	17.7	361.0	11.9	26.3
2	158.1	361.1	9.4	203.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.7	0.070
120 - 100	7.6	0.812
140 - 120	14.3	1.858
160 - 140	96.0	14.509
180 - 160	133.0	22.087
200 - 180	73.7	13.759
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	325.2	53.096

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	80.8	13.182	2	200 - 180	73.7	13.759
	160 - 140	65.6	9.955		180 - 160	52.2	8.906
	140 - 120	3.0	0.407		160 - 140	18.4	2.791
	Total	149.4	23.544		140 - 120	7.7	0.995
1	160 - 140	12.0	1.764	120 - 100	6.1	0.646	
	140 - 120	3.5	0.456	Total	158.1	27.097	
	120 - 100	1.4	0.166				
	< 100	0.7	0.070				
	Total	17.7	2.456				

eP-EAZK-159

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Dolní Jasenka 2274, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.34692 N, 17.99596 E

Building area: 830 m²

192 LiDAR points (0.23 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-160

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, - 825, Zašová, Zlínský kraj

49.47936 N, 18.04331 E

Building area: 142 m²

23 LiDAR points (0.16 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-161

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Hlavní 1, Zborovice, Zlínský kraj

49.25162 N, 17.28155 E

Building area: 1293 m²

2629 LiDAR points (2.03 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	187.9	259.9	33.9	52.0
1	191.4	260.0	33.1	231.2
2	196.1	260.4	36.0	322.2
3	46.4	259.4	20.2	232.2
4	303.6	260.2	34.5	142.5
5	250.8	260.0	32.1	50.3
6	224.0	259.9	33.9	232.0
7	29.8	259.2	32.6	321.3
8	23.3	259.0	33.9	321.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	121.0	10.316
120 - 100	109.6	12.313
140 - 120	369.7	46.725
160 - 140	100.4	14.294
180 - 160	5.6	0.936
200 - 180	22.2	4.364
220 - 200	724.7	154.519
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1453.2	243.467

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	21.9	3.083	4	220 - 200	303.6	66.678
	140 - 120	63.4	8.223		Total	303.6	66.678
	120 - 100	35.0	3.872	5	160 - 140	66.5	9.434
	< 100	67.7	5.587		140 - 120	92.1	12.031
	Total	187.9	20.765		120 - 100	51.2	5.751
1	220 - 200	179.2	37.658	< 100	40.9	3.571	
	180 - 160	2.4	0.403	Total	250.8	30.788	
	160 - 140	9.7	1.421	6	220 - 200	216.7	45.056
	Total	191.4	39.482		200 - 180	7.3	1.450
2	140 - 120	174.0	21.451		Total	224.0	46.506
	120 - 100	13.2	1.521		7	140 - 120	19.3
	< 100	8.8	0.818	120 - 100		7.0	0.792
	Total	196.1	23.790	< 100		3.5	0.340
3	220 - 200	25.1	5.126	Total	29.8	3.549	
	200 - 180	14.9	2.914	8	140 - 120	20.1	2.495
	180 - 160	3.1	0.533		120 - 100	3.2	0.376
	160 - 140	2.4	0.356		Total	23.3	2.871
	140 - 120	0.8	0.109				
	Total	46.4	9.038				

eP-EAZK-162

Location information

Dětské centrum, Burešov 3675, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.23531 N, 17.69035 E

Building area: 389 m²

646 LiDAR points (1.66 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	199.3	267.7	33.7	256.5
1	7.9	266.6	23.9	171.1
2	10.8	266.8	33.4	76.4
3	100.8	267.8	33.9	76.7
4	36.3	267.1	34.2	346.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	7.0	0.631
120 - 100	39.1	4.413
140 - 120	12.6	1.653
160 - 140	82.1	12.409
180 - 160	176.6	30.566
200 - 180	37.6	6.932
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	355.1	56.605

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	29.8	5.402	3	180 - 160	14.0	2.270
	180 - 160	162.6	28.296		160 - 140	64.4	9.717
	160 - 140	6.9	1.091		140 - 120	12.6	1.653
	Total	199.3	34.790		120 - 100	2.8	0.306
			< 100		7.0	0.631	
1	200 - 180	7.9	1.530	Total	100.8	14.577	
Total	7.9	1.530					
2	160 - 140	10.8	1.601	4	120 - 100	36.3	4.108
Total	10.8	1.601	Total		36.3	4.108	

eP-EAZK-163, eP-EAZK-164

Location information

Domov pro seniory, Burešov 4884, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.23465 N, 17.68968 E

Building area: 2178 m²

2354 LiDAR points (1.08 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	6.9	250.4	0.9	46.4
1	361.7	250.8	0.4	96.4
2	139.0	255.2	0.2	353.1
3	370.6	255.3	0.2	311.2
4	59.9	258.3	1.4	114.0
5	424.3	266.0	14.9	98.7
6	194.1	269.1	9.4	278.3
7	103.5	265.6	41.8	278.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	11.1	0.998
120 - 100	7.4	0.833
140 - 120	16.1	2.154
160 - 140	88.6	13.551
180 - 160	512.5	87.631
200 - 180	1024.3	190.050
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1660.0	295.217

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	2.8	0.452	4	200 - 180	59.9	11.309
	160 - 140	2.8	0.423		Total	59.9	11.309
	140 - 120	1.4	0.190	5	200 - 180	307.7	57.678
	Total	6.9	1.065		180 - 160	97.9	17.008
1	200 - 180	103.3	19.016		160 - 140	18.6	2.872
	180 - 160	195.6	33.715		Total	424.3	77.559
	160 - 140	29.5	4.487	6	200 - 180	184.5	34.175
	140 - 120	14.8	1.964		180 - 160	9.6	1.688
	120 - 100	7.4	0.833		Total	194.1	35.863
	< 100	11.1	0.998	7	180 - 160	97.4	15.828
	Total	361.7	61.012		160 - 140	6.1	0.967
Total	103.5	16.794					
2	200 - 180	93.8	17.369				
	180 - 160	25.1	4.289				
	160 - 140	20.1	3.032				
	Total	139.0	24.691				
3	200 - 180	275.1	50.503				
	180 - 160	84.1	14.651				
	160 - 140	11.5	1.770				
	Total	370.6	66.923				

eP-EAZK-165

Location information

Centrum poradenství, U Náhonu 5208, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22924 N, 17.67604 E

Building area: 506 m²

737 LiDAR points (1.46 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	245.2	232.5	37.0	24.6
1	110.6	231.9	38.0	205.1
2	108.1	231.8	38.1	204.4
3	7.8	231.4	9.2	112.5
4	10.1	233.0	9.7	21.9
5	25.5	234.6	0.4	342.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	245.2	27.633
140 - 120	1.2	0.154
160 - 140	4.8	0.727
180 - 160	10.2	1.735
200 - 180	33.3	6.247
220 - 200	28.8	6.103
240 - 220	184.0	41.181
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	507.5	83.781

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	245.2	27.633	3	200 - 180	6.9	1.312
	Total	245.2	27.633		180 - 160	0.9	0.163
1	240 - 220	85.8	19.140	4	Total	7.8	1.475
	220 - 200	22.6	4.778		180 - 160	4.2	0.686
	200 - 180	2.3	0.441		160 - 140	4.8	0.727
	Total	110.6	24.358		140 - 120	1.2	0.154
2	240 - 220	98.2	22.042	5	Total	10.1	1.567
	220 - 200	6.2	1.326		200 - 180	24.1	4.494
	180 - 160	3.7	0.633		180 - 160	1.4	0.253
	Total	108.1	24.000		Total	25.5	4.747

eP-EAZK-166

Location information

Týdenní stacionář, Pod Vodojemem 3651, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22292 N, 17.67716 E

Building area: 196 m²

242 LiDAR points (1.24 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	176.9	278.9	0.2	145.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	176.9	33.244
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	176.9	33.244

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	176.9	33.244
Total		176.9	33.244

eP-EAZK-167

Location information

Chráněné bydlení, Hamerská 715, Zubří, Zlínský kraj

49.46368 N, 18.08703 E

Building area: 152 m²

218 LiDAR points (1.43 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	23.1	361.3	33.1	9.3
1	9.4	361.5	31.5	100.5
2	22.9	361.9	29.8	197.9
3	21.4	361.6	32.5	280.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	23.1	2.597
140 - 120	0.7	0.097
160 - 140	5.0	0.773
180 - 160	16.3	2.719
200 - 180	8.8	1.656
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	22.9	5.165
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	76.9	13.008

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	23.1	2.597	3	180 - 160	15.7	2.615
Total		23.1	2.597		160 - 140	5.0	0.773
1	200 - 180	8.8	1.656		140 - 120	0.7	0.097
	180 - 160	0.6	0.104	Total		21.4	3.485
Total		9.4	1.761				
2	240 - 220	22.9	5.165				
Total		22.9	5.165				

eP-EAZK-168

Location information

Domov pro seniory, - 233, Nezdenice, Zlínský kraj

49.01940 N, 17.75472 E

Building area: 2695 m²

5325 LiDAR points (1.98 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	95.7	243.3	15.7	95.5
1	296.4	248.6	15.8	276.2
2	22.2	248.1	32.6	294.3
3	95.5	243.3	13.8	17.8
4	5.5	248.0	11.1	41.4
5	13.0	247.9	16.3	273.5
6	50.3	247.7	14.1	23.5
7	7.2	249.9	16.4	96.0
8	214.8	248.9	13.8	275.0
9	129.4	249.1	16.0	96.3
10	113.3	249.2	16.2	6.4
11	51.2	249.7	29.3	186.7
12	37.1	249.8	29.2	186.8
13	226.6	248.5	14.8	6.0
14	47.5	249.0	15.3	188.7
15	286.3	248.6	14.9	95.9
16	288.7	248.5	15.0	275.9
17	16.9	247.8	15.0	185.9
18	22.3	248.4	16.8	8.4
19	31.6	247.9	20.5	287.7
20	174.2	248.3	18.1	275.3
21	190.2	248.7	14.8	105.7
22	30.6	248.0	14.3	275.9
23	17.4	247.7	14.9	194.6

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	100.7	8.816
120 - 100	149.2	16.515
140 - 120	160.0	20.847
160 - 140	393.7	60.762
180 - 160	293.3	51.178
200 - 180	1244.1	231.399
220 - 200	60.3	12.562
240 - 220	62.6	14.128
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	2463.9	416.207

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	33.9	6.187	6	160 - 140	4.4	0.626
	180 - 160	46.0	7.952		140 - 120	39.4	5.234
	160 - 140	8.5	1.262		120 - 100	2.9	0.322
	140 - 120	2.4	0.335		< 100	3.6	0.315
	120 - 100	1.2	0.123		Total	50.3	6.496
	< 100	3.6	0.356		7	200 - 180	0.9
Total	95.7	16.216	1	180 - 160	4.5	0.792	
1	200 - 180	282.0	51.665	160 - 140	1.8	0.276	
	180 - 160	8.6	1.502	Total	7.2	1.232	
	160 - 140	2.9	0.441	8	140 - 120	81.9	10.470
	140 - 120	2.9	0.365		120 - 100	75.3	8.512
Total	296.4	53.973	< 100		57.6	5.160	
2	160 - 140	3.7	0.542	Total	214.8	24.142	
	140 - 120	10.2	1.325	9	200 - 180	77.7	14.496
	120 - 100	7.4	0.819		180 - 160	33.3	5.734
	< 100	0.9	0.084		160 - 140	7.4	1.118
Total	22.2	2.770	140 - 120		9.2	1.244	
3	120 - 100	60.5	6.518	120 - 100	1.8	0.222	
	< 100	34.9	2.902	Total	129.4	22.815	
Total	95.5	9.419	10	160 - 140	103.4	15.592	
4	160 - 140	3.7		0.552	140 - 120	9.8	1.344
	140 - 120	1.8		0.235	Total	113.3	16.935
Total	5.5	0.787	5	200 - 180	13.0	2.397	
Total	13.0	2.397		Total	13.0	2.397	

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)		
11	240 - 220	39.3	8.866	17	220 - 200	16.1	3.316		
	220 - 200	8.2	1.720		200 - 180	0.8	0.161		
	200 - 180	2.7	0.536		Total	16.9	3.477		
	180 - 160	0.9	0.164		18	160 - 140	22.3	3.341	
	Total	51.2	11.285			Total	22.3	3.341	
12	240 - 220	23.3	5.262	19		180 - 160	23.3	3.978	
	220 - 200	6.0	1.265			160 - 140	6.0	0.899	
	200 - 180	6.0	1.158			140 - 120	2.3	0.294	
	180 - 160	1.7	0.291		Total	31.6	5.171		
	Total	37.1	7.977		20	200 - 180	137.4	25.007	
13	160 - 140	226.6	35.646	180 - 160		36.8	6.519		
	Total	226.6	35.646	Total		174.2	31.527		
	14	220 - 200	29.3	6.136		21	200 - 180	190.2	37.017
		200 - 180	17.4	3.303			Total	190.2	37.017
		180 - 160	0.8	0.141	22		180 - 160	27.6	4.735
Total		47.5	9.580	160 - 140			3.1	0.467	
15		200 - 180	253.4	47.492			Total	30.6	5.202
	180 - 160	32.9	5.785	23		220 - 200	0.6	0.125	
	Total	286.3	53.277			200 - 180	13.6	2.616	
	16	200 - 180	214.9		39.199	180 - 160	3.1	0.545	
		180 - 160	73.8		13.039	Total	17.4	3.285	
Total		288.7	52.238						

eP-EAZK-169, eP-EAZK-170

Location information

Domov pro osoby se zdravotním postižením, Kopánky 2052, Staré Město, Zlínský kraj

49.07902 N, 17.43126 E

Building area: 2836 m²

3962 LiDAR points (1.40 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	552.8	194.4	2.9	299.1
1	202.2	190.9	6.5	211.9
2	77.6	190.9	5.1	208.9
3	250.0	190.9	5.1	119.9
4	65.1	191.0	4.9	30.4
5	99.6	190.7	5.1	13.9
6	291.6	191.0	5.0	209.5
7	221.7	191.1	4.4	288.2
8	462.7	194.5	5.5	98.1
9	6.0	195.8	32.9	209.9
10	13.4	187.0	31.9	122.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	34.1	3.038
120 - 100	38.7	4.247
140 - 120	57.9	7.495
160 - 140	169.3	25.825
180 - 160	465.9	80.364
200 - 180	1457.4	274.620
220 - 200	13.4	2.784
240 - 220	6.0	1.343
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	2242.7	399.717

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	552.8	102.488	5	180 - 160	81.8	14.161
	Total	552.8	102.488		160 - 140	11.5	1.731
1	200 - 180	67.4	12.572	140 - 120	5.2	0.699	
	180 - 160	35.0	5.985	120 - 100	1.0	0.114	
	160 - 140	27.0	4.069	Total	99.6	16.705	
	140 - 120	24.3	3.124	6	200 - 180	273.2	53.537
	120 - 100	18.9	2.062		180 - 160	18.5	3.229
	< 100	29.7	2.605	Total	291.6	56.766	
Total	202.2	30.416	7	200 - 180	173.6	32.075	
2	200 - 180	72.0		14.041	180 - 160	34.7	6.016
	180 - 160	3.7		0.650	160 - 140	13.4	2.094
	160 - 140	0.9	0.135	Total	221.7	40.185	
	140 - 120	0.9	0.127	8	200 - 180	110.2	20.129
Total	77.6	14.952	180 - 160		224.8	38.734	
3	200 - 180	208.3	39.779		160 - 140	92.5	14.187
	180 - 160	28.8	5.035		140 - 120	17.6	2.285
	160 - 140	9.6	1.434		120 - 100	13.2	1.439
	140 - 120	3.2	0.405	< 100	4.4	0.433	
Total	250.0	46.654	Total	462.7	77.206		
4	180 - 160	38.6	6.556	9	240 - 220	6.0	1.343
	160 - 140	14.3	2.176		Total	6.0	1.343
	140 - 120	6.6	0.854	10	220 - 200	13.4	2.784
	120 - 100	5.5	0.633		Total	13.4	2.784
Total	65.1	10.218					

eP-EAZK-171

Location information

Odborné učiliště, Nádražní 525, Holešov, Zlínský kraj

49.32769 N, 17.57009 E

Building area: 751 m²

969 LiDAR points (1.29 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	98.0	235.7	40.4	347.7
1	10.7	234.6	34.6	257.9
2	77.3	235.6	40.0	167.2
3	129.1	237.1	44.2	257.8
4	12.9	235.0	34.8	169.8
5	21.9	235.1	39.2	256.6
6	149.1	236.2	41.5	168.8
7	93.3	235.9	41.1	347.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	105.5	10.399
120 - 100	87.3	8.795
140 - 120	2.7	0.363
160 - 140	7.7	1.157
180 - 160	21.2	3.662
200 - 180	141.0	26.019
220 - 200	41.4	8.805
240 - 220	185.6	42.049
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	592.4	101.250

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	85.9	8.658	4	240 - 220	1.4	0.303
	< 100	12.1	1.182		220 - 200	8.8	1.870
	Total	98.0	9.840		200 - 180	2.0	0.388
1	200 - 180	10.7	2.008	180 - 160	0.7	0.114	
	Total	10.7	2.008	Total	12.9	2.674	
2	240 - 220	60.0	13.577	5	200 - 180	8.2	1.530
	220 - 200	11.5	2.466		180 - 160	13.7	2.365
	200 - 180	3.5	0.645		Total	21.9	3.895
	160 - 140	2.3	0.355	6	240 - 220	124.3	28.169
	Total	77.3	17.044		220 - 200	21.0	4.470
3	200 - 180	112.8	20.704	200 - 180	3.8	0.744	
	180 - 160	6.8	1.184	Total	149.1	33.382	
	160 - 140	5.4	0.802	7	< 100	93.3	9.218
	140 - 120	2.7	0.363		Total	93.3	9.218
	120 - 100	1.4	0.137				
	Total	129.1	23.190				

eP-EAZK-172

Location information

Základní praktická škola, Palackého 437, Holešov, Zlínský kraj

49.32877 N, 17.57123 E

Building area: 361 m²

402 LiDAR points (1.11 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	77.2	238.0	32.7	153.4
1	16.1	237.0	34.9	330.4
2	3.1	235.2	32.7	330.3
3	4.9	236.5	34.3	330.1
4	25.3	233.1	21.5	338.0
5	22.3	234.2	13.9	332.0
6	2.6	236.0	34.1	334.0
7	30.6	236.8	32.8	63.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.7	0.066
120 - 100	26.4	3.066
140 - 120	12.5	1.600
160 - 140	65.3	9.691
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	3.0	0.586
220 - 200	12.2	2.626
240 - 220	62.0	13.818
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	182.1	31.454

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	240 - 220	62.0	13.818	5	160 - 140	11.5	1.756
	220 - 200	12.2	2.626		140 - 120	4.1	0.541
	200 - 180	3.0	0.586		120 - 100	6.1	0.671
	Total	77.2	17.030		< 100	0.7	0.066
1	120 - 100	16.1	1.911	Total	22.3	3.034	
	Total	16.1	1.911	6	120 - 100	2.6	0.292
2	140 - 120	1.4	0.169		Total	2.6	0.292
	120 - 100	1.7	0.192	7	160 - 140	30.6	4.627
	Total	3.1	0.361		Total	30.6	4.627
3	140 - 120	4.9	0.592				
	Total	4.9	0.592				
4	160 - 140	23.1	3.308				
	140 - 120	2.2	0.299				
	Total	25.3	3.607				

eP-EAZK-173

Location information

Základní umělecká škola, Bezručova 675/7, Holešov, Zlínský kraj

49.33066 N, 17.58616 E

Building area: 544 m²

904 LiDAR points (1.66 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	14.7	243.7	32.3	315.6
1	15.0	245.4	34.1	48.6
2	15.2	245.3	36.0	229.1
3	14.4	244.5	26.1	272.1
4	35.7	235.7	5.4	322.0
5	13.5	243.9	3.9	323.2
6	44.4	244.1	31.3	319.2
7	132.0	244.4	30.6	48.8
8	56.5	244.2	31.4	139.3
9	13.0	244.3	29.4	41.6
10	30.5	244.7	31.2	319.9
11	25.0	244.4	31.6	319.2
12	5.6	242.1	14.3	50.5

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	33.4	2.959
120 - 100	34.4	3.810
140 - 120	125.6	16.523
160 - 140	138.7	19.936
180 - 160	13.3	2.326
200 - 180	1.8	0.340
220 - 200	68.2	14.673
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	415.4	60.568

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	11.0	1.454	3	180 - 160	12.4	2.178
	120 - 100	2.2	0.247		160 - 140	2.0	0.293
	< 100	1.5	0.137		Total	14.4	2.471
	Total	14.7	1.838		4	160 - 140	7.3
1	140 - 120	9.5	1.291	140 - 120		14.6	1.899
	120 - 100	2.7	0.312	120 - 100		13.0	1.443
	< 100	2.7	0.244	< 100		0.8	0.074
	Total	15.0	1.847	Total	35.7	4.504	
2	220 - 200	12.6	2.655	5	< 100	13.5	1.153
	200 - 180	0.8	0.153		Total	13.5	1.153
	180 - 160	0.8	0.149	6	140 - 120	41.4	5.443
	160 - 140	0.8	0.127		120 - 100	3.0	0.333
	Total	15.2	3.084		Total	44.4	5.776

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
7	160 - 140	128.1	18.357	11	140 - 120	21.5	2.816
	140 - 120	3.9	0.547		120 - 100	1.7	0.190
	Total	132.0	18.904		< 100	1.7	0.156
8	220 - 200	55.5	12.018	Total	25.0	3.162	
	200 - 180	1.0	0.187	12	160 - 140	0.5	0.071
	Total	56.5	12.206		140 - 120	1.5	0.198
9	140 - 120	4.5	0.584		120 - 100	2.0	0.226
	120 - 100	3.2	0.349	< 100	1.5	0.125	
	< 100	5.2	0.469	Total	5.6	0.620	
	Total	13.0	1.402				
10	140 - 120	17.6	2.291				
	120 - 100	6.5	0.710				
	< 100	6.5	0.601				
	Total	30.5	3.602				

eP-EAZK-174

Location information

Odborné učiliště - kotelna, tělocvična, nám. Osvoboditelů -, Kelč, Zlínský kraj

49.47660 N, 17.81664 E

Building area: 990 m²

1257 LiDAR points (1.27 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	68.4	333.2	0.5	33.6
1	207.1	333.8	1.4	13.7
2	174.3	337.1	1.1	285.0
3	176.8	338.9	19.7	94.3
4	165.7	338.8	19.7	274.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	10.1	1.072
140 - 120	16.6	2.144
160 - 140	63.3	9.781
180 - 160	249.6	43.348
200 - 180	452.6	83.883
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	792.2	140.228

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	3.7	0.666	3	200 - 180	151.6	28.471
	180 - 160	40.6	6.982		180 - 160	25.3	4.496
	160 - 140	12.0	1.820		Total	176.8	32.967
	140 - 120	11.1	1.411	4	200 - 180	55.8	10.073
	120 - 100	0.9	0.099		180 - 160	84.5	14.884
	Total	68.4	10.978		160 - 140	25.4	4.011
1	200 - 180	113.2	20.777	Total	165.7	28.968	
	180 - 160	69.8	11.948				
	160 - 140	24.1	3.672				
	Total	207.1	36.397				
	2	200 - 180	128.4	23.897			
180 - 160		29.4	5.037				
160 - 140		1.8	0.277				
140 - 120		5.5	0.733				
120 - 100		9.2	0.973				
Total	174.3	30.917					

eP-EAZK-175

Location information

Odborné učiliště - zahrada, nám. Osvoboditelů -, Kelč, Zlínský kraj

49.47748 N, 17.81578 E

Building area: 126 m²

295 LiDAR points (2.35 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	8.5	338.9	30.9	284.1
1	55.8	339.2	31.6	13.6
2	13.4	338.8	23.9	104.1
3	59.7	339.3	31.0	193.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	20.8	1.929
120 - 100	39.7	4.364
140 - 120	7.0	0.896
160 - 140	6.3	0.955
180 - 160	5.8	0.963
200 - 180	7.5	1.448
220 - 200	49.5	10.639
240 - 220	0.9	0.205
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	137.4	21.398

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	3.9	0.631	3	240 - 220	0.9	0.205
	160 - 140	4.6	0.706		220 - 200	49.5	10.639
	Total	8.5	1.337		200 - 180	7.5	1.448
1	120 - 100	35.0	3.833		180 - 160	1.9	0.332
	< 100	20.8	1.929	Total	59.7	12.624	
	Total	55.8	5.761				
2	160 - 140	1.7	0.248				
	140 - 120	7.0	0.896				
	120 - 100	4.7	0.531				
	Total	13.4	1.676				

eP-EAZK-176

Location information

Odborné učiliště - dílny, nám. Osvoboditelů -, Kelč, Zlínský kraj

49.47735 N, 17.81359 E

Building area: 134 m²

246 LiDAR points (1.84 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	126.5	351.5	11.4	171.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	8.0	1.386
200 - 180	93.2	18.124
220 - 200	25.3	5.088
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	126.5	24.598

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	25.3	5.088
	200 - 180	93.2	18.124
	180 - 160	8.0	1.386
Total		126.5	24.598

eP-EAZK-177

Location information

Odborné učiliště - zámek, nám. Osvoboditelů 1, Kelč, Zlínský kraj

49.47795 N, 17.81583 E

Building area: 1021 m²

1400 LiDAR points (1.37 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	32.5	364.1	42.4	275.4
1	30.5	364.9	40.1	275.2
2	125.2	364.3	41.4	95.9
3	75.3	364.0	41.5	274.1
4	96.1	363.5	35.9	94.6
5	13.2	363.4	36.5	178.7
6	95.3	364.1	43.8	280.8
7	7.6	363.2	41.1	196.7
8	81.9	363.6	43.7	100.1
9	235.0	363.6	41.8	8.4
10	124.6	364.1	46.0	187.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	244.5	23.766
120 - 100	20.7	2.256
140 - 120	34.3	4.498
160 - 140	138.7	20.880
180 - 160	155.5	26.885
200 - 180	197.9	36.125
220 - 200	72.9	15.629
240 - 220	52.7	11.818
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	917.1	141.857

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	4.5	0.726	5	240 - 220	13.2	3.007
	160 - 140	16.3	2.480		Total	13.2	3.007
	140 - 120	4.5	0.575	6	160 - 140	75.9	11.514
	120 - 100	1.8	0.196		140 - 120	5.5	0.732
	< 100	5.4	0.500		120 - 100	9.7	1.037
Total	32.5	4.477	< 100	4.1	0.385		
1	180 - 160	26.8	4.482	Total	95.3	13.668	
	160 - 140	3.7	0.577	7	240 - 220	7.6	1.731
	Total	30.5	5.058		Total	7.6	1.731
2	200 - 180	52.7	9.534	8	200 - 180	58.1	10.592
	180 - 160	65.9	11.490		180 - 160	23.8	4.228
	160 - 140	2.6	0.398		Total	81.9	14.820
	140 - 120	1.3	0.163	9	< 100	235.0	22.880
	120 - 100	2.6	0.308		Total	235.0	22.880
Total	125.2	21.893	10	240 - 220	31.9	7.079	
3	180 - 160	8.7		1.437	220 - 200	72.9	15.629
	160 - 140	37.1		5.476	200 - 180	12.2	2.347
	140 - 120	22.9		3.029	180 - 160	4.6	0.768
	120 - 100	6.5		0.715	160 - 140	3.0	0.435
Total	75.3	10.657	Total	124.6	26.257		
4	200 - 180	74.9	13.652				
	180 - 160	21.2	3.755				
	Total	96.1	17.407				

eP-EAZK-178

Location information

Dětský domov, U Sýpek 1306/3, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29870 N, 17.38453 E

Building area: 271 m²

180 LiDAR points (0.67 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	134.7	218.4	33.6	335.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	122.2	14.493
140 - 120	12.5	1.497
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	134.7	15.991

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	12.5	1.497
	120 - 100	122.2	14.493
	Total	134.7	15.991

eP-EAZK-179

Location information

Gymnázium, Masarykovo náměstí 496/13, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29707 N, 17.38993 E

Building area: 1716 m²

493 LiDAR points (0.29 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-180

Location information

Konzervatoř, Pilařova 7, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29817 N, 17.39047 E

Building area: 1926 m²

664 LiDAR points (0.34 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	5.6	217.0	24.7	342.9
1	12.2	217.0	24.0	340.0
2	52.5	220.7	38.8	250.8
3	29.3	219.6	18.3	247.6
4	91.9	218.5	4.8	328.6
5	49.8	216.7	23.3	247.8
6	10.1	222.0	24.8	248.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	12.1	1.370
140 - 120	19.2	2.458
160 - 140	24.7	3.788
180 - 160	108.1	18.086
200 - 180	87.3	16.920
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	251.5	42.622

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	3.3	0.407	5	180 - 160	40.4	6.654
	120 - 100	2.3	0.264		160 - 140	7.9	1.216
	Total	5.6	0.672		140 - 120	1.6	0.214
			Total		49.8	8.085	
1	140 - 120	7.4	0.937	6	200 - 180	5.5	1.022
	120 - 100	4.7	0.555		180 - 160	1.8	0.324
	Total	12.2	1.492		160 - 140	1.8	0.287
			140 - 120		0.9	0.126	
2	200 - 180	52.5	10.137	Total	10.1	1.759	
	Total	52.5	10.137				
3	200 - 180	29.3	5.761				
	Total	29.3	5.761				
4	180 - 160	66.0	11.107				
	160 - 140	15.0	2.284				
	140 - 120	6.0	0.774				
	120 - 100	5.0	0.550				
	Total	91.9	14.716				

eP-EAZK-181

Location information

Obchodní akademie, Obvodová 3503/7, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29530 N, 17.40760 E

Building area: 1329 m²

2095 LiDAR points (1.58 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	179.6	200.9	9.4	353.8
1	13.2	201.1	15.5	263.7
2	20.3	201.1	15.3	79.7
3	87.5	200.8	9.6	350.7
4	314.6	200.8	9.5	170.5
5	327.1	200.7	11.1	210.5
6	333.0	200.7	11.3	30.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	4.9	0.650
160 - 140	55.3	8.580
180 - 160	576.9	97.238
200 - 180	76.7	14.756
220 - 200	561.6	115.063
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1275.5	236.287

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	153.5	25.952	4	220 - 200	287.2	58.991
	160 - 140	26.2	4.081		200 - 180	20.5	3.906
	Total	179.6	30.034		180 - 160	6.8	1.207
1	200 - 180	10.5	1.959	Total	314.6	64.103	
	160 - 140	2.1	0.308	5	220 - 200	274.4	56.072
	140 - 120	0.7	0.097		200 - 180	45.7	8.892
Total	13.2	2.364	180 - 160		7.0	1.206	
2	180 - 160	9.1	1.539	Total	327.1	66.170	
	160 - 140	7.0	1.057	6	180 - 160	322.3	54.258
	140 - 120	4.2	0.552		160 - 140	10.7	1.676
Total	20.3	3.148	Total		333.0	55.935	
3	180 - 160	78.2	13.077				
	160 - 140	9.3	1.457				
	Total	87.5	14.534				

eP-EAZK-182

Location information

Centrum odborné přípravy technické, Nábělkova 539/3, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29425 N, 17.39679 E

Building area: 540 m²

863 LiDAR points (1.60 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	304.1	221.0	28.7	68.9
1	300.6	220.2	29.2	249.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	14.3	1.290
120 - 100	7.1	0.799
140 - 120	11.9	1.506
160 - 140	38.7	5.943
180 - 160	259.3	42.611
200 - 180	273.5	52.745
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	604.7	104.895

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	237.6	38.795	1	200 - 180	273.5	52.745
	160 - 140	33.3	5.103		180 - 160	21.7	3.816
	140 - 120	11.9	1.506		160 - 140	5.4	0.841
	120 - 100	7.1	0.799		Total	300.6	57.402
	< 100	14.3	1.290				
Total		304.1	47.493				

eP-EAZK-183

Location information

Střední škola hotelová a služeb - restaurace, Nádražní 3550, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30170 N, 17.40270 E

Building area: 355 m²

531 LiDAR points (1.49 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	346.1	199.2	0.1	296.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	346.1	64.973
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	346.1	64.973

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	346.1	64.973
Total		346.1	64.973

eP-EAZK-184

Location information

Střední škola hotelová a služeb - budova A, Kojetínská -, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30535 N, 17.38245 E

Building area: 174 m²

240 LiDAR points (1.38 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	31.9	198.5	26.4	241.9
1	39.3	198.5	25.7	328.3
2	16.5	198.5	25.0	149.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	39.3	5.489
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	48.4	10.093
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	87.7	15.582

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	31.9	6.477	2	220 - 200	16.5	3.616
Total		31.9	6.477	Total		16.5	3.616
1	140 - 120	39.3	5.489				
Total		39.3	5.489				

eP-EAZK-185

Location information

Střední škola hotelová a služeb - kotelna, Kojetínská -, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30520 N, 17.38324 E

Building area: 167 m²

240 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	16.7	198.6	27.0	151.0
1	38.2	198.6	25.6	327.8
2	39.6	198.7	26.3	242.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	5.3	0.506
120 - 100	7.8	0.884
140 - 120	36.1	4.880
160 - 140	5.5	0.823
180 - 160	12.9	2.198
200 - 180	23.3	4.459
220 - 200	3.5	0.699
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	94.5	14.448

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	3.5	0.699	2	200 - 180	10.1	1.900
	200 - 180	13.2	2.558		180 - 160	12.9	2.198
	Total	16.7	3.257		160 - 140	5.5	0.823
1	140 - 120	32.4	4.395	140 - 120	3.7	0.485	
	120 - 100	4.2	0.471	120 - 100	3.7	0.413	
	< 100	1.7	0.160	< 100	3.7	0.345	
	Total	38.2	5.026	Total	39.6	6.164	

eP-EAZK-186

Location information

Střední škola hotelová a služeb - stáje, Kojetínská -, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30520 N, 17.38324 E

Building area: 814 m²

1084 LiDAR points (1.33 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	368.3	201.5	20.9	150.1
1	349.3	201.3	20.6	330.7
2	80.2	200.9	27.7	240.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	37.2	3.173
120 - 100	34.0	3.775
140 - 120	141.8	19.004
160 - 140	137.5	19.751
180 - 160	16.3	2.764
200 - 180	66.7	12.606
220 - 200	364.4	78.784
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	797.9	139.857

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	364.4	78.784	2	200 - 180	66.7	12.606
	180 - 160	4.0	0.708		180 - 160	12.3	2.055
	Total	368.3	79.492		140 - 120	0.6	0.077
1	160 - 140	137.5	19.751	120 - 100	0.6	0.070	
	140 - 120	141.2	18.928	Total	80.2	14.808	
	120 - 100	33.4	3.705				
	< 100	37.2	3.173				
Total	349.3	45.557					

eP-EAZK-187

Location information

Střední škola hotelová a služeb, Na Lindovce 1463/1, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30214 N, 17.38010 E

Building area: 1142 m²

1587 LiDAR points (1.39 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	237.7	222.0	34.1	329.7
1	243.8	222.0	33.8	329.7
2	148.9	221.2	53.8	239.8
3	470.6	221.8	33.9	149.7
4	46.3	221.1	34.1	59.5
5	54.1	221.2	34.0	239.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	14.2	1.285
120 - 100	30.7	3.526
140 - 120	453.3	55.497
160 - 140	34.9	5.097
180 - 160	8.9	1.544
200 - 180	157.7	30.596
220 - 200	321.8	68.478
240 - 220	179.8	39.915
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1201.3	205.939

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	231.5	28.214	4	160 - 140	34.9	5.097
	120 - 100	6.2	0.735		140 - 120	9.4	1.258
	Total	237.7	28.949		120 - 100	1.9	0.219
1	140 - 120	206.9	25.316	Total	46.3	6.575	
	120 - 100	22.7	2.572	5	220 - 200	52.1	10.625
	< 100	14.2	1.285		200 - 180	2.0	0.393
	Total	243.8	29.173		Total	54.1	11.018
2	200 - 180	139.8	27.101				
	180 - 160	3.6	0.616				
	140 - 120	5.4	0.709				
	Total	148.9	28.425				
3	240 - 220	179.8	39.915				
	220 - 200	269.7	57.853				
	200 - 180	15.9	3.102				
	180 - 160	5.3	0.928				
	Total	470.6	101.799				

eP-EAZK-188

Location information

Střední škola hotelová a služeb - kotelná, Pavlákova 3942, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30128 N, 17.38147 E

Building area: 1302 m²

1670 LiDAR points (1.28 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	1269.2	227.5	0.1	298.2
1	22.7	229.8	1.1	51.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	11.0	1.710
180 - 160	11.0	1.870
200 - 180	1269.8	238.108
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1291.9	241.687

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	1247.1	233.889
	180 - 160	11.0	1.870
	160 - 140	11.0	1.710
Total		1269.2	237.468

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	200 - 180	22.7	4.219
Total		22.7	4.219

eP-EAZK-189

Location information

Střední škola hotelová a služeb - kuchyně, Pavlákova -, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30147 N, 17.38189 E

Building area: 835 m²

1078 LiDAR points (1.29 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	345.5	212.8	0.3	142.2
1	404.0	214.3	0.1	191.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	6.8	1.058
180 - 160	149.6	26.697
200 - 180	593.0	108.946
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	749.4	136.702

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	242.9	44.446
	180 - 160	95.8	17.082
	160 - 140	6.8	1.058
Total		345.5	62.586

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	200 - 180	350.1	64.501
	180 - 160	53.9	9.615
Total		404.0	74.116

eP-EAZK-190

Location information

Střední škola hotelová a služeb - škola, Pavlákova -, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30169 N, 17.38228 E

Building area: 852 m²

1151 LiDAR points (1.35 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	809.7	214.3	0.0	176.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	809.7	152.100
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	809.7	152.100

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	809.7	152.100
Total		809.7	152.100

eP-EAZK-191

Location information

Střední škola hotelová a služeb - sportovní areál, Kojetinská 2679/84, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30365 N, 17.38362 E

Building area: 179 m²

286 LiDAR points (1.60 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	172.6	197.3	1.4	150.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	35.2	6.195
200 - 180	137.3	25.255
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	172.6	31.450

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	137.3	25.255
	180 - 160	35.2	6.195
	Total	172.6	31.450

eP-EAZK-192

Location information

Střední zdravotnická škola, Albertova 4261/25a, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29105 N, 17.38138 E

Building area: 2388 m²

1427 LiDAR points (0.60 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	278.0	205.5	0.3	69.3
1	18.2	205.2	22.2	57.2
2	16.3	205.5	20.8	61.2
3	152.3	219.3	12.4	332.1
4	169.4	219.2	12.7	150.3
5	291.6	212.1	5.3	237.6
6	287.5	211.1	11.5	59.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	71.7	9.433
160 - 140	121.6	18.270
180 - 160	460.1	78.912
200 - 180	390.5	74.076
220 - 200	169.4	35.203
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1213.4	215.894

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	98.9	18.093	3	180 - 160	139.8	23.040
	180 - 160	37.1	6.388		160 - 140	12.5	1.955
	160 - 140	71.1	10.459		Total	152.3	24.996
	140 - 120	71.1	9.340	4	220 - 200	169.4	35.203
	Total	278.0	44.281		Total	169.4	35.203
1	160 - 140	17.5	2.699	5	200 - 180	291.6	55.983
	140 - 120	0.7	0.093		Total	291.6	55.983
	Total	18.2	2.792	6	180 - 160	273.1	47.836
2	180 - 160	10.2	1.647		160 - 140	14.4	2.228
	160 - 140	6.1	0.929		Total	287.5	50.064
Total	16.3	2.576					

eP-EAZK-193, eP-EAZK-194, eP-EAZK-195

Location information

Vyšší odborná škola pedagogická a sociální a Střední pedagogická škola A, 1. máje 221/10, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29619 N, 17.39385 E

Building area: 1632 m²

2124 LiDAR points (1.30 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	25.5	224.6	2.5	102.8
1	6.5	229.5	5.6	154.4
2	107.5	221.9	12.9	105.6
3	47.8	229.3	30.2	276.8
4	69.4	228.9	14.3	277.8
5	45.4	228.8	1.1	28.0
6	89.2	222.1	4.3	101.6
7	60.0	208.8	3.4	6.0
8	137.7	224.4	32.3	7.3
9	52.8	224.5	32.6	269.6
10	163.4	224.4	32.1	187.9
11	30.0	223.7	33.6	270.2
12	45.6	224.5	33.4	0.1
13	84.0	224.7	33.7	180.2
14	81.4	224.5	32.2	270.3
15	136.0	224.1	32.5	7.6
16	197.8	224.2	31.6	187.6
17	15.8	229.7	31.7	90.6
18	45.7	229.7	13.4	278.0

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	31.1	2.856
120 - 100	362.2	42.049
140 - 120	79.2	10.208
160 - 140	58.5	8.830
180 - 160	120.7	20.589
200 - 180	408.0	76.812
220 - 200	55.2	11.688
240 - 220	326.7	74.127
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1441.6	247.160

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	12.0	2.194	6	200 - 180	85.1	16.065
	180 - 160	11.2	1.935		180 - 160	3.0	0.515
	160 - 140	2.4	0.345		160 - 140	1.0	0.157
	Total	25.5	4.474		Total	89.2	16.737
1	200 - 180	1.0	0.187	7	140 - 120	28.8	3.658
	180 - 160	3.0	0.507		120 - 100	31.3	3.540
	160 - 140	2.5	0.381		Total	60.0	7.198
2	200 - 180	107.5	20.895	8	120 - 100	126.6	14.755
	Total	107.5	20.895		< 100	11.1	1.018
3	180 - 160	27.7	4.689		9	180 - 160	24.9
	160 - 140	8.6	1.291	160 - 140		8.3	1.271
	140 - 120	2.9	0.386	140 - 120		8.3	1.087
	120 - 100	2.9	0.324	120 - 100		3.1	0.333
	< 100	5.7	0.520	< 100		8.3	0.734
	Total	47.8	7.210	Total		52.8	7.687
4	200 - 180	69.4	12.706	10	240 - 220	80.9	18.238
	Total	69.4	12.706		220 - 200	37.2	7.850
5	200 - 180	45.4	8.460		200 - 180	22.7	4.358
	Total	45.4	8.460		180 - 160	8.1	1.374
			160 - 140		3.2	0.490	
			140 - 120		3.2	0.433	
			120 - 100		8.1	0.876	
			Total		163.4	33.618	

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
11	180 - 160	26.4	4.556	14	180 - 160	9.6	1.587
	160 - 140	1.8	0.284		160 - 140	28.9	4.356
	140 - 120	0.9	0.121		140 - 120	32.1	4.145
	< 100	0.9	0.089		120 - 100	9.6	1.100
	Total	30.0	5.049		< 100	1.1	0.106
12	120 - 100	44.6	5.112	Total	81.4	11.295	
	< 100	1.0	0.099	15	120 - 100	136.0	16.008
	Total	45.6	5.211		Total	136.0	16.008
13	240 - 220	48.0	10.824		16	240 - 220	197.8
	220 - 200	18.0	3.838	Total		197.8	45.065
	200 - 180	6.0	1.169	17	200 - 180	15.8	2.856
	180 - 160	6.0	1.019		Total	15.8	2.856
	140 - 120	3.0	0.378	18	200 - 180	43.2	7.924
	< 100	3.0	0.290		180 - 160	0.8	0.147
	Total	84.0	17.519		160 - 140	1.7	0.254
				Total	45.7	8.324	

eP-EAZK-196, eP-EAZK-197

Location information

Vyšší odborná škola potravinářská a Střední průmyslová škola mlékárenská, Štěchovice 1358/16, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29996 N, 17.38380 E

Building area: 242 m²

248 LiDAR points (1.02 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	30.4	212.7	43.8	328.0
1	50.5	210.9	43.9	57.4
2	28.6	211.2	45.0	237.1
3	30.3	210.5	43.8	328.3
4	18.7	213.3	40.4	240.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	60.7	6.360
140 - 120	50.5	6.801
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	2.0	0.342
200 - 180	19.4	3.789
220 - 200	25.9	5.228
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	158.5	22.521

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	30.4	3.193
	Total	30.4	3.193
1	140 - 120	50.5	6.801
	Total	50.5	6.801
2	220 - 200	13.7	2.777
	200 - 180	13.7	2.681
	180 - 160	1.1	0.202
	Total	28.6	5.659

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	120 - 100	30.3	3.167
	Total	30.3	3.167
4	220 - 200	12.2	2.451
	200 - 180	5.7	1.108
	180 - 160	0.8	0.140
	Total	18.7	3.700

eP-EAZK-198, eP-EAZK-199

Location information

Základní škola, 1. máje 209/14, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29637 N, 17.39271 E

Building area: 699 m²

1116 LiDAR points (1.60 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	11.0	221.3	24.9	10.4
1	9.7	221.8	27.4	280.0
2	14.6	221.4	26.0	98.2
3	61.5	221.5	23.8	279.9
4	18.0	221.5	0.0	270.0
5	166.7	221.9	24.3	98.2
6	155.2	210.7	7.3	6.5
7	44.0	221.7	25.2	97.2
8	127.7	222.2	24.7	8.3
9	9.1	220.5	31.1	280.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	13.0	1.225
120 - 100	45.5	5.036
140 - 120	197.0	26.383
160 - 140	84.2	12.691
180 - 160	59.9	10.186
200 - 180	217.7	41.356
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	617.4	96.877

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	11.0	1.473	6	160 - 140	65.4	9.816
Total		11.0	1.473		140 - 120	52.3	6.873
1	180 - 160	4.2	0.696		120 - 100	28.0	3.118
	160 - 140	3.5	0.532		< 100	9.3	0.870
	140 - 120	1.4	0.169	Total		155.2	20.678
	120 - 100	0.7	0.083	7	200 - 180	39.1	7.385
Total		9.7	1.480		160 - 140	2.5	0.370
2	200 - 180	11.9	2.251		140 - 120	1.7	0.211
	180 - 160	1.3	0.224		120 - 100	0.8	0.095
	160 - 140	0.7	0.097	Total		44.0	8.061
	140 - 120	0.7	0.083	8	140 - 120	127.7	17.272
Total		14.6	2.655	Total		127.7	17.272
3	180 - 160	53.3	9.080	9	180 - 160	1.1	0.186
	160 - 140	8.2	1.274		160 - 140	4.0	0.602
Total		61.5	10.354		140 - 120	2.3	0.301
4	120 - 100	15.4	1.675		120 - 100	0.6	0.066
	< 100	2.6	0.252	Total		9.1	1.257
Total		18.0	1.927				
5	200 - 180	166.7	31.720				
Total		166.7	31.720				

eP-EAZK-200

Location information

Základní škola a Mateřská škola, Františka Vančury 3695/2, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30090 N, 17.37742 E

Building area: 1030 m²

1310 LiDAR points (1.27 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	11.7	215.1	1.8	305.8
1	19.4	216.0	4.2	126.4
2	42.6	215.0	1.7	312.1
3	55.9	216.8	4.5	131.9
4	174.0	216.7	3.0	309.9
5	539.8	220.2	0.3	265.8
6	11.9	222.5	3.6	138.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	1.9	0.166
120 - 100	3.1	0.361
140 - 120	12.2	1.609
160 - 140	54.9	8.269
180 - 160	66.2	11.347
200 - 180	716.9	133.992
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	855.2	155.743

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	180 - 160	3.5	0.579	3	200 - 180	54.2	10.477	
	160 - 140	4.1	0.606		180 - 160	1.7	0.291	
	140 - 120	2.9	0.383		Total	55.9	10.768	
	< 100	1.2	0.097		4	200 - 180	169.1	31.119
	Total	11.7	1.664			180 - 160	4.9	0.859
			Total	174.0		31.977		
1	200 - 180	11.8	2.165	5	200 - 180	469.9	87.931	
	180 - 160	4.2	0.705		180 - 160	38.8	6.717	
	160 - 140	3.5	0.529		160 - 140	31.1	4.719	
	Total	19.4	3.400		Total	539.8	99.368	
2	180 - 160	13.2	2.196	6	200 - 180	11.9	2.300	
	160 - 140	16.2	2.415		Total	11.9	2.300	
	140 - 120	9.3	1.226					
	120 - 100	3.1	0.361					
	< 100	0.8	0.069					
Total	42.6	6.267						

eP-EAZK-201

Location information

Základní škola a dětský domov - Základní škola, - 233, Liptál, Zlínský kraj

49.29299 N, 17.93071 E

Building area: 571 m²

1007 LiDAR points (1.76 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	133.1	427.4	28.0	12.3
1	12.8	424.3	28.7	294.0
2	7.8	424.3	32.7	114.5
3	30.9	424.4	7.8	287.7
4	41.2	424.6	33.1	24.4
5	157.8	427.4	27.6	191.7
6	89.6	424.9	14.6	192.0
7	74.3	420.8	1.5	114.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	9.8	0.917
120 - 100	18.2	2.047
140 - 120	185.4	23.589
160 - 140	24.1	3.706
180 - 160	25.4	4.413
200 - 180	31.6	5.820
220 - 200	99.8	21.157
240 - 220	153.2	34.480
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	547.6	96.129

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	133.1	17.118
	Total	133.1	17.118
1	160 - 140	12.8	1.991
	Total	12.8	1.991
2	220 - 200	5.6	1.127
	200 - 180	2.2	0.444
	Total	7.8	1.571
3	160 - 140	1.5	0.227
	140 - 120	5.3	0.667
	120 - 100	14.3	1.604
	< 100	9.8	0.917
Total	30.9	3.415	
4	140 - 120	41.2	5.027
	Total	41.2	5.027

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
5	240 - 220	153.2	34.480
	220 - 200	4.6	0.973
	Total	157.8	35.454
6	220 - 200	89.6	19.056
	Total	89.6	19.056
7	200 - 180	29.3	5.376
	180 - 160	25.4	4.413
	160 - 140	9.8	1.487
	140 - 120	5.9	0.775
120 - 100	3.9	0.444	
Total	74.3	12.497	

eP-EAZK-202

Location information

Základní škola a dětský domov - Hospodářská budova, --, Liptál, Zlínský kraj

49.29256 N, 17.92862 E

Building area: 556 m²

806 LiDAR points (1.45 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	139.1	424.0	1.2	148.1
1	319.9	425.9	0.2	277.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	6.2	1.035
200 - 180	452.8	84.214
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	459.0	85.250

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	139.1	26.000
	Total	139.1	26.000
1	200 - 180	313.7	58.214
	180 - 160	6.2	1.035
	Total	319.9	59.249

eP-EAZK-203

Location information

Základní škola a dětský domov - Dětský domov, - 91, Liptál, Zlínský kraj

49.29236 N, 17.92795 E

Building area: 728 m²

1232 LiDAR points (1.69 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	221.7	433.1	31.8	329.3
1	12.4	432.8	34.2	238.7
2	105.8	433.1	32.5	59.8
3	98.2	433.2	34.3	149.3
4	72.0	433.4	35.0	59.2
5	18.6	432.6	34.9	148.9
6	44.8	434.1	35.0	150.8
7	36.0	433.9	35.3	148.6
8	10.6	433.9	34.2	237.2
9	39.6	434.4	2.1	231.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	11.0	1.306
140 - 120	211.4	26.732
160 - 140	183.4	27.383
180 - 160	12.8	2.188
200 - 180	51.1	9.708
220 - 200	46.6	9.811
240 - 220	143.4	31.938
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	659.7	109.066

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	211.4	26.732	7	240 - 220	0.9	0.205
	120 - 100	10.3	1.232		220 - 200	21.3	4.480
	Total	221.7	27.964		200 - 180	3.7	0.713
1	220 - 200	12.4	2.541		180 - 160	5.5	0.952
	Total	12.4	2.541	160 - 140	4.6	0.695	
2	160 - 140	105.8	15.943	Total	36.0	7.045	
	Total	105.8	15.943	8	220 - 200	0.7	0.145
3	240 - 220	98.2	21.873		200 - 180	5.6	1.101
	Total	98.2	21.873		180 - 160	3.5	0.592
4	160 - 140	72.0	10.586		120 - 100	0.7	0.074
	Total	72.0	10.586	Total	10.6	1.912	
5	240 - 220	15.4	3.416	9	200 - 180	38.8	7.316
	220 - 200	3.2	0.701		180 - 160	0.7	0.134
	Total	18.6	4.116		Total	39.6	7.450
6	240 - 220	28.9	6.445				
	220 - 200	9.0	1.945				
	200 - 180	3.0	0.578				
	180 - 160	3.0	0.510				
	160 - 140	1.0	0.159				
	Total	44.8	9.636				

eP-EAZK-204

Location information

Střední odborná škola - dílny, Hradisko 290, Luhačovice, Zlínský kraj

49.09434 N, 17.74995 E

Building area: 273 m²

453 LiDAR points (1.66 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	95.1	290.8	34.7	37.7
1	22.8	290.7	40.7	307.7
2	13.3	291.0	43.0	124.7
3	29.4	288.5	7.9	218.4
4	9.2	291.3	43.7	308.0
5	49.4	290.9	35.7	217.7
6	24.0	290.7	40.3	127.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	22.0	2.008
120 - 100	10.0	1.155
140 - 120	99.7	12.728
160 - 140	6.1	0.934
180 - 160	34.2	5.860
200 - 180	30.4	5.832
220 - 200	40.7	8.360
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	243.1	36.878

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	95.1	12.129	4	120 - 100	9.2	1.068
	Total	95.1	12.129		Total	9.2	1.068
1	120 - 100	0.8	0.086	5	220 - 200	6.9	1.400
	< 100	22.0	2.008		200 - 180	27.6	5.284
	Total	22.8	2.094		180 - 160	6.9	1.170
2	220 - 200	9.8	2.010		160 - 140	3.4	0.523
	200 - 180	2.8	0.548		140 - 120	4.6	0.599
	160 - 140	0.7	0.107		Total	49.4	8.976
	Total	13.3	2.665	6	220 - 200	24.0	4.950
3	180 - 160	27.4	4.690		Total	24.0	4.950
	160 - 140	2.0	0.304				
	Total	29.4	4.994				

eP-EAZK-205

Location information

Střední odborná škola - internát, Masarykova 999, Luhačovice, Zlínský kraj

49.09893 N, 17.75478 E

Building area: 717 m²

680 LiDAR points (0.95 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	20.2	251.7	0.5	192.3
1	54.0	255.4	6.2	191.8
2	8.0	255.4	4.5	73.4
3	22.0	254.7	12.1	152.0
4	13.9	255.3	20.9	151.4
5	24.2	261.0	3.4	77.0
6	18.3	260.9	8.0	67.2
7	142.4	262.1	9.9	331.1
8	41.8	261.9	9.8	152.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	11.7	1.322
140 - 120	16.1	2.087
160 - 140	24.1	3.606
180 - 160	188.1	32.212
200 - 180	42.2	7.929
220 - 200	62.5	12.847
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	344.7	60.002

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	5.6	1.021	5	200 - 180	4.7	0.853
	180 - 160	9.1	1.532		180 - 160	16.4	2.874
	160 - 140	5.6	0.856		160 - 140	2.3	0.336
	Total	20.2	3.409		140 - 120	0.8	0.096
1	180 - 160	10.8	1.789	Total	24.2	4.160	
	160 - 140	16.2	2.414	6	200 - 180	8.8	1.594
	140 - 120	15.3	1.991		180 - 160	9.5	1.698
	120 - 100	11.7	1.322		Total	18.3	3.291
	Total	54.0	7.515	7	180 - 160	142.4	24.319
2	200 - 180	8.0	1.475		Total	142.4	24.319
	Total	8.0	1.475	8	220 - 200	41.8	8.530
3	220 - 200	6.9	1.380		Total	41.8	8.530
	200 - 180	15.1	2.985	4	220 - 200	13.9	2.936
Total	22.0	4.366	Total		13.9	2.936	

eP-EAZK-206

Location information

Střední odborná škola - škola, Masarykova 101, Luhačovice, Zlínský kraj

49.09587 N, 17.74767 E

Building area: 428 m²

616 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	216.6	266.0	2.8	145.7
1	139.6	263.5	43.3	326.5
2	88.0	263.5	43.7	236.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	139.6	14.967
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	6.3	1.102
200 - 180	253.8	48.849
220 - 200	44.6	9.022
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	444.3	73.940

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	210.4	40.283	2	220 - 200	44.6	9.022
	180 - 160	6.3	1.102		200 - 180	43.4	8.566
	Total	216.6	41.385		Total	88.0	17.588
1	120 - 100	139.6	14.967				
Total		139.6	14.967				

eP-EAZK-207

Location information

Základní umělecká škola, Komenského 305, Napajedla, Zlínský kraj

49.17181 N, 17.51487 E

Building area: 574 m²

69 LiDAR points (0.12 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-208, eP-EAZK-210

Location information

Gymnázium, tř. Spojenců 907, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.21725 N, 17.51228 E

Building area: 785 m²

1205 LiDAR points (1.54 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	778.8	196.8	0.1	301.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	778.8	146.321
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	778.8	146.321

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	778.8	146.321
Total		778.8	146.321

eP-EAZK-209

Location information

Gymnázium - budova B, Školní 726, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.21673 N, 17.51240 E

Building area: 276 m²

460 LiDAR points (1.67 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	264.7	191.4	0.3	129.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	264.7	49.823
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	264.7	49.823

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	264.7	49.823
Total		264.7	49.823

eP-EAZK-211, eP-EAZK-219

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola, Tř. Tomáše Bati 1266, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22439 N, 17.51203 E

Building area: 912 m²

734 LiDAR points (0.80 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	577.3	199.2	0.1	82.6
1	16.6	202.2	0.3	281.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	22.5	3.530
180 - 160	52.5	9.209
200 - 180	518.9	97.203
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	593.8	109.942

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	502.3	94.090
	180 - 160	52.5	9.209
	160 - 140	22.5	3.530
	Total	577.3	106.829

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	200 - 180	16.6	3.113
	Total	16.6	3.113

eP-EAZK-212

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola - autodílna, Tř. Tomáše Bati 1624, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22444 N, 17.51107 E

Building area: 1374 m²

771 LiDAR points (0.56 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	435.1	189.8	0.6	75.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	70.4	12.512
200 - 180	364.8	67.554
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	435.1	80.066

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	364.8	67.554
	180 - 160	70.4	12.512
	Total	435.1	80.066

eP-EAZK-213

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola - budova A, Tř. Tomáše Bati 1581, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22387 N, 17.51088 E

Building area: 1525 m²

2947 LiDAR points (1.93 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	1047.8	198.8	0.1	88.5
1	13.8	201.2	1.0	79.3
2	13.1	201.2	0.4	339.1
3	10.1	201.2	0.5	204.9
4	120.0	201.2	0.3	246.7
5	150.1	201.2	0.2	79.9
6	85.8	201.7	0.7	194.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	20.4	2.273
140 - 120	42.1	5.343
160 - 140	314.3	47.496
180 - 160	230.1	39.508
200 - 180	833.8	154.888
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1440.7	249.508

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	455.9	84.551	4	200 - 180	112.3	20.976
	180 - 160	217.7	37.316		180 - 160	5.2	0.926
	160 - 140	313.0	47.304		160 - 140	1.3	0.192
	140 - 120	40.8	5.185		140 - 120	1.3	0.157
	120 - 100	20.4	2.273		Total	120.0	22.252
	Total	1047.8	176.629				
1	200 - 180	10.5	1.929	5	200 - 180	148.6	27.452
	180 - 160	3.3	0.575		180 - 160	1.5	0.278
	Total	13.8	2.504		Total	150.1	27.730
2	200 - 180	11.4	2.090	6	200 - 180	85.8	16.120
	180 - 160	1.7	0.300		Total	85.8	16.120
	Total	13.1	2.390				
3	200 - 180	9.5	1.770				
	180 - 160	0.6	0.112				
	Total	10.1	1.882				

eP-EAZK-214

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola - budova B, Tř. Tomáše Bati 1269, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22416 N, 17.51124 E

Building area: 529 m²

1062 LiDAR points (2.01 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	526.6	199.0	0.1	156.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	526.6	98.810
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	526.6	98.810

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	526.6	98.810
Total		526.6	98.810

eP-EAZK-215

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola - budova C, Tř. Tomáše Bati 1267, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22378 N, 17.51137 E

Building area: 530 m²

958 LiDAR points (1.81 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	524.3	198.9	0.2	319.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	5.0	0.895
200 - 180	519.3	96.989
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	524.3	97.883

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	519.3	96.989
	180 - 160	5.0	0.895
	Total	524.3	97.883

eP-EAZK-216

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola - domov mládeže 2, Tř. Tomáše Bati 1268, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22516 N, 17.51176 E

Building area: 922 m²

1539 LiDAR points (1.67 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	899.2	199.5	0.1	108.8
1	9.8	202.0	3.1	229.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	14.2	2.387
200 - 180	894.8	167.429
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	909.1	169.817

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	886.1	165.766	1	200 - 180	8.7	1.664
	180 - 160	13.1	2.203		180 - 160	1.1	0.185
	Total	899.2	167.968		Total	9.8	1.848

eP-EAZK-217

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola - kuchyně, Tř. Tomáše Bati 1582, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22482 N, 17.51133 E

Building area: 870 m²

103 LiDAR points (0.12 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-218

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola - sportovní hala, Tř. Tomáše Bati 1270, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22590 N, 17.51160 E

Building area: 1789 m²

645 LiDAR points (0.36 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	527.6	195.9	3.2	83.5
1	436.7	195.8	4.0	267.3
2	185.3	194.7	0.7	359.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	66.6	11.545
200 - 180	1083.0	202.388
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1149.6	213.933

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	514.2	96.323
	180 - 160	13.4	2.375
	Total	527.6	98.698
1	200 - 180	383.5	71.570
	180 - 160	53.3	9.170
	Total	436.7	80.740

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	185.3	34.495
	Total	185.3	34.495

eP-EAZK-220

Location information

Základní škola, Komenského 1855, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.21216 N, 17.53237 E

Building area: 782 m²

1234 LiDAR points (1.58 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	141.8	204.8	0.3	88.2
1	559.8	212.6	0.1	286.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	3.3	0.593
200 - 180	698.2	130.986
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	701.5	131.578

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	138.5	25.794	1	200 - 180	559.8	105.192
	180 - 160	3.3	0.593		Total	559.8	105.192
	Total	141.8	26.387				

eP-EAZK-221

Location information

Základní umělecká škola, Školní 806, Otrokovice, Zlínský kraj

49.21667 N, 17.51214 E

Building area: 270 m²

7 LiDAR points (0.03 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-222

Location information

Gymnázium, Koryčanské Paseky 1725, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46641 N, 18.12900 E

Building area: 2230 m²

2529 LiDAR points (1.13 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	113.4	394.0	0.1	44.0
1	654.7	395.6	0.3	14.5
2	810.5	408.2	0.4	94.7
3	141.2	402.7	0.3	118.5
4	285.1	406.6	0.3	286.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	5.4	0.529
120 - 100	5.4	0.590
140 - 120	5.4	0.727
160 - 140	21.4	3.275
180 - 160	125.3	21.539
200 - 180	1842.0	345.003
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	2004.8	371.663

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	106.0	19.764	3	180 - 160	103.6	17.676
	180 - 160	7.4	1.305		160 - 140	21.4	3.275
	Total	113.4	21.069		140 - 120	5.4	0.727
1	200 - 180	648.0	120.753		120 - 100	5.4	0.590
	180 - 160	6.7	1.196		< 100	5.4	0.529
	Total	654.7	121.949	Total	141.2	22.797	
2	200 - 180	802.8	150.984	4	200 - 180	285.1	53.502
	180 - 160	7.6	1.362		Total	285.1	53.502
	Total	810.5	152.346				

eP-EAZK-223

Location information

Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - domov mládeže, Zemědělská 500, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46097 N, 18.13646 E

Building area: 484 m²

690 LiDAR points (1.42 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	132.1	383.4	2.1	1.7
1	43.4	385.2	33.3	274.7
2	16.8	385.8	33.5	3.6
3	43.2	385.6	32.9	90.2
4	50.7	383.3	2.8	4.3
5	39.4	385.3	33.6	3.5
6	90.2	385.5	32.7	184.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	8.7	0.851
120 - 100	50.2	5.519
140 - 120	4.9	0.644
160 - 140	22.6	3.460
180 - 160	128.8	22.196
200 - 180	110.6	20.196
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	90.2	20.584
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	415.8	73.450

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	110.6	20.196	4	180 - 160	30.9	5.294
	180 - 160	18.7	3.256		160 - 140	13.7	2.086
	160 - 140	1.4	0.221		140 - 120	3.4	0.446
	140 - 120	1.4	0.197		120 - 100	2.6	0.292
	Total	132.1	23.870		Total	50.7	8.119
1	180 - 160	37.9	6.441	5	120 - 100	32.4	3.531
	160 - 140	5.5	0.872		< 100	7.1	0.694
	Total	43.4	7.312		Total	39.4	4.225
2	120 - 100	15.2	1.696	6	240 - 220	90.2	20.584
	< 100	1.6	0.156		Total	90.2	20.584
	Total	16.8	1.853				
3	180 - 160	41.4	7.205				
	160 - 140	1.8	0.282				
	Total	43.2	7.487				

eP-EAZK-224

Location information

Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - kravín, Hradisko -, Vidče, Zlínský kraj

49.45013 N, 18.11695 E

Building area: 1035 m²

1666 LiDAR points (1.61 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	44.2	475.7	17.8	226.7
1	15.3	476.3	5.0	356.8
2	513.1	479.0	42.8	315.9
3	48.4	475.2	8.4	45.5
4	14.3	476.3	26.0	132.3
5	29.0	480.9	32.1	133.3
6	356.2	477.9	42.0	135.9
7	59.0	475.7	18.4	44.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	287.3	22.302
120 - 100	225.8	26.090
140 - 120	4.5	0.591
160 - 140	29.0	4.458
180 - 160	95.7	15.727
200 - 180	13.3	2.575
220 - 200	424.1	90.747
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1079.6	162.491

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	31.1	6.326	4	220 - 200	7.8	1.608
	200 - 180	9.4	1.827		200 - 180	3.9	0.748
	180 - 160	3.8	0.638		180 - 160	2.6	0.450
	Total	44.2	8.791		Total	14.3	2.807
1	180 - 160	14.7	2.521	5	220 - 200	29.0	6.211
	160 - 140	0.7	0.103		Total	29.0	6.211
	Total	15.3	2.624		6	220 - 200	356.2
2	120 - 100	225.8	26.090	Total		356.2	76.602
	< 100	287.3	22.302	7		180 - 160	50.4
	Total	513.1	48.392		160 - 140	8.6	1.358
3	180 - 160	24.2	4.033		Total	59.0	9.444
	160 - 140	19.7	2.996				
	140 - 120	4.5	0.591				
	Total	48.4	7.620				

eP-EAZK-225

Location information

Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - seník, Tvarůžkova -, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.45228 N, 18.14826 E

Building area: 1191 m²

1601 LiDAR points (1.34 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	560.9	411.2	13.6	40.3
1	644.3	411.3	13.3	220.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	6.1	0.943
180 - 160	554.8	92.625
200 - 180	137.2	26.690
220 - 200	507.1	103.432
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1205.2	223.689

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	554.8	92.625	1	220 - 200	507.1	103.432
	160 - 140	6.1	0.943		200 - 180	137.2	26.690
	Total	560.9	93.567		Total	644.3	130.122

eP-EAZK-226

Location information

Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - škola, nábřeží Dukelských hrdinů 570, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46116 N, 18.13895 E

Building area: 1514 m²

2144 LiDAR points (1.42 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	60.1	378.7	1.4	222.1
1	515.3	382.6	0.0	84.7
2	649.7	388.3	1.1	288.2
3	163.5	390.4	2.7	318.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	8.8	1.002
140 - 120	30.9	4.028
160 - 140	50.3	7.773
180 - 160	38.0	6.381
200 - 180	1260.6	235.170
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1388.6	254.355

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	12.4	1.999	2	200 - 180	586.2	109.476
	160 - 140	22.1	3.377		180 - 160	21.2	3.642
	140 - 120	16.8	2.193		160 - 140	28.2	4.396
	120 - 100	8.8	1.002		140 - 120	14.1	1.835
	Total	60.1	8.571		Total	649.7	119.349
1	200 - 180	510.9	95.530	3	200 - 180	163.5	30.164
	180 - 160	4.4	0.741		Total	163.5	30.164
	Total	515.3	96.271				

eP-EAZK-227

Location information

Střední škola zemědělská a přírodovědná - vila, Zemědělská 574, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46096 N, 18.13690 E

Building area: 169 m²

258 LiDAR points (1.53 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	24.8	379.9	46.5	3.8
1	12.5	380.8	46.3	7.0
2	19.1	381.0	46.8	183.3
3	10.3	380.4	45.3	271.9
4	20.7	379.5	32.8	273.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	37.4	2.968
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	13.1	2.015
180 - 160	17.9	2.910
200 - 180	2.6	0.515
220 - 200	13.0	2.815
240 - 220	3.5	0.770
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	87.5	11.994

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	< 100	24.8	2.052	3	180 - 160	9.5	1.539
	Total	24.8	2.052		160 - 140	0.9	0.136
1	< 100	12.5	0.916	Total	10.3	1.675	
	Total	12.5	0.916	4	180 - 160	8.4	1.371
2	240 - 220	3.5	0.770		160 - 140	12.3	1.879
	220 - 200	13.0	2.815		Total	20.7	3.250
	200 - 180	2.6	0.515				
Total	19.1	4.100					

eP-EAZK-228

Location information

Základní škola, Tyršovo nábřeží 649, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.45836 N, 18.13561 E

Building area: 314 m²

433 LiDAR points (1.38 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	175.0	384.1	23.3	317.6
1	133.4	384.2	23.2	137.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	1.7	0.194
140 - 120	9.9	1.325
160 - 140	163.4	24.275
180 - 160	4.2	0.731
200 - 180	105.3	20.600
220 - 200	23.9	4.945
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	308.3	52.069

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	163.4	24.275	1	220 - 200	23.9	4.945
	140 - 120	9.9	1.325		200 - 180	105.3	20.600
	120 - 100	1.7	0.194		180 - 160	4.2	0.731
	Total	175.0	25.794		Total	133.4	26.276

eP-EAZK-229

Location information

Základní umělecká škola, Pionýrská 20, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46094 N, 18.14235 E

Building area: 579 m²

666 LiDAR points (1.15 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	70.3	394.5	42.9	79.7
1	133.1	394.4	42.5	349.6
2	46.0	393.1	41.5	349.4
3	149.0	394.4	42.9	170.0
4	157.8	394.3	42.3	260.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	179.1	17.028
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	3.4	0.458
160 - 140	3.4	0.503
180 - 160	174.9	30.067
200 - 180	52.6	9.574
220 - 200	2.1	0.456
240 - 220	140.6	31.974
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	556.2	90.059

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	70.3	11.386	4	200 - 180	46.3	8.377
Total		70.3	11.386		180 - 160	104.6	18.681
1	< 100	133.1	12.555		160 - 140	3.4	0.503
Total		133.1	12.555		140 - 120	3.4	0.458
2	< 100	46.0	4.473	Total		157.8	28.019
Total		46.0	4.473				
3	240 - 220	140.6	31.974				
	220 - 200	2.1	0.456				
	200 - 180	6.3	1.197				
Total		149.0	33.627				

eP-EAZK-230

Location information

Gymnázium, Školní 822, Slavičín, Zlínský kraj

49.09054 N, 17.88021 E

Building area: 1184 m²

1755 LiDAR points (1.48 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	121.7	374.0	0.4	300.2
1	25.7	374.6	0.4	342.7
2	452.9	385.3	35.4	97.4
3	508.5	385.3	35.4	277.4
4	107.9	384.5	35.9	7.3
5	84.6	384.8	35.4	187.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	13.1	1.225
120 - 100	107.2	11.576
140 - 120	46.6	6.193
160 - 140	158.0	24.307
180 - 160	425.0	71.474
200 - 180	466.8	86.145
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	84.6	19.345
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1301.3	220.265

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	58.1	10.551	3	180 - 160	344.9	57.429
	180 - 160	36.0	6.238		160 - 140	146.1	22.520
	160 - 140	11.1	1.682		140 - 120	17.5	2.340
	140 - 120	4.1	0.546		Total	508.5	82.289
	120 - 100	5.5	0.580	4	120 - 100	101.7	10.997
	< 100	6.9	0.626		< 100	6.2	0.599
	Total	121.7	20.222	Total	107.9	11.596	
1	160 - 140	0.8	0.106	5	240 - 220	84.6	19.345
	140 - 120	24.9	3.307		Total	84.6	19.345
	Total	25.7	3.412				
2	200 - 180	408.7	75.594				
	180 - 160	44.2	7.807				
	Total	452.9	83.401				

eP-EAZK-231

Location information

Střední odborná škola, Divnice 119, Slavičín, Zlínský kraj

49.09922 N, 17.91502 E

Building area: 1997 m²

2811 LiDAR points (1.41 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	424.8	341.0	0.3	122.5
1	676.4	344.7	0.4	126.5
2	787.3	349.1	0.3	147.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	25.7	2.856
140 - 120	21.5	2.825
160 - 140	42.9	6.351
180 - 160	124.4	21.676
200 - 180	1674.0	314.596
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1888.5	348.304

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	210.3	38.872	1	200 - 180	676.4	127.347
	180 - 160	124.4	21.676		Total	676.4	127.347
	160 - 140	42.9	6.351	2	200 - 180	787.3	148.378
	140 - 120	21.5	2.825		Total	787.3	148.378
	120 - 100	25.7	2.856				
Total		424.8	72.579				

eP-EAZK-232, eP-EAZK-233

Location information

Střední odborná škola a Gymnázium, Velehradská 1527, Staré Město, Zlínský kraj

49.08049 N, 17.43830 E

Building area: 1206 m²

1034 LiDAR points (0.86 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	819.0	201.3	0.2	228.6
1	353.3	203.2	12.7	229.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	72.6	9.667
160 - 140	31.1	4.636
180 - 160	155.5	27.209
200 - 180	579.8	108.269
220 - 200	333.3	67.510
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1172.2	217.292

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	559.8	104.331	1	220 - 200	333.3	67.510
	180 - 160	155.5	27.209		200 - 180	20.0	3.938
	160 - 140	31.1	4.636	Total	353.3	71.448	
	140 - 120	72.6	9.667				
Total		819.0	145.843				

eP-EAZK-234

Location information

Střední odborná škola a Gymnázium, Revoluční 747, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06951 N, 17.45043 E

Building area: 1530 m²

2320 LiDAR points (1.52 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	9.3	182.6	1.4	71.8
1	10.2	182.6	4.0	314.7
2	6.0	188.7	32.7	109.3
3	29.2	189.7	34.8	287.5
4	39.5	190.3	35.0	110.0
5	215.9	190.2	34.7	19.1
6	242.1	190.5	35.7	198.9
7	24.2	189.5	17.3	289.5
8	35.6	189.7	34.3	288.2
9	244.7	190.4	34.2	108.9
10	250.9	190.4	34.6	19.0
11	25.8	184.0	2.0	49.7
12	128.5	185.9	0.8	17.0
13	249.7	187.1	0.4	19.5

■ **Energy prediction - Summary**

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	82.6	6.989
120 - 100	402.4	45.922
140 - 120	34.1	4.422
160 - 140	115.8	17.927
180 - 160	135.7	23.348
200 - 180	499.1	95.714
220 - 200	13.5	2.926
240 - 220	228.7	51.562
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1511.8	248.810

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	1.8	0.284	3	160 - 140	29.2	4.589
	160 - 140	2.9	0.449		Total	29.2	4.589
	140 - 120	1.8	0.233	4	200 - 180	39.5	7.796
	120 - 100	2.3	0.256		Total	39.5	7.796
	< 100	0.6	0.051	5	120 - 100	141.2	15.539
Total	9.3	1.273	< 100		74.7	6.255	
1	180 - 160	2.6	0.419	Total	215.9	21.794	
	160 - 140	2.0	0.313	6	240 - 220	228.7	51.562
	140 - 120	2.0	0.267		220 - 200	13.5	2.926
	120 - 100	1.0	0.110	Total	242.1	54.488	
	< 100	2.6	0.237	7	180 - 160	0.9	0.151
Total	10.2	1.345	160 - 140		20.6	3.050	
2	200 - 180	6.0	1.180	140 - 120	2.7	0.362	
	Total	6.0	1.180	Total	24.2	3.563	

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
8	160 - 140	35.6	5.661	12	200 - 180	20.1	3.661
Total		35.6	5.661		180 - 160	65.6	11.284
9	200 - 180	244.7	48.031		160 - 140	12.0	1.834
Total		244.7	48.031		140 - 120	22.8	2.912
10	120 - 100	250.9	29.232		120 - 100	4.0	0.454
Total		250.9	29.232		< 100	4.0	0.383
11	200 - 180	1.5	0.265	Total		128.5	20.527
	180 - 160	15.5	2.672	13	200 - 180	187.3	34.781
	160 - 140	2.9	0.450		180 - 160	49.4	8.539
	140 - 120	2.2	0.288		160 - 140	10.4	1.582
	120 - 100	2.9	0.332		140 - 120	2.6	0.360
	< 100	0.7	0.064	Total		249.7	45.261
Total		25.8	4.072				

eP-EAZK-235

Location information

Dětský domov, Jiřího z Poděbrad 313, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06535 N, 17.46348 E

Building area: 499 m²

733 LiDAR points (1.47 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	90.9	191.3	33.6	97.2
1	152.5	191.7	33.6	277.3
2	41.2	190.7	33.2	97.6
3	46.0	190.5	31.9	278.6
4	68.9	190.2	33.4	7.9
5	42.4	190.3	32.8	186.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	4.0	0.372
120 - 100	72.9	8.419
140 - 120	3.0	0.410
160 - 140	16.3	2.467
180 - 160	203.9	34.775
200 - 180	99.3	18.420
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	42.4	9.683
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	441.9	74.546

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	63.2	11.709	3	180 - 160	36.0	6.069
	180 - 160	26.3	4.556		160 - 140	9.0	1.362
	160 - 140	1.3	0.202		140 - 120	1.0	0.136
	Total	90.9	16.467	Total	46.0	7.568	
1	180 - 160	136.4	23.259	4	120 - 100	68.9	7.987
	160 - 140	6.0	0.904		Total	68.9	7.987
	140 - 120	2.0	0.274	5	240 - 220	42.4	9.683
	120 - 100	4.0	0.432		Total	42.4	9.683
	< 100	4.0	0.372				
Total	152.5	25.240					
2	200 - 180	36.0	6.710				
	180 - 160	5.1	0.890				
	Total	41.2	7.601				

eP-EAZK-236

Location information

Obchodní akademie, Nádražní 22, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06708 N, 17.45919 E

Building area: 1669 m²

389 LiDAR points (0.23 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-237

Location information

Střední škola průmyslová, hotelová a zdravotnická, Jiřího z Poděbrad 822, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06596 N, 17.46342 E

Building area: 1094 m²

232 LiDAR points (0.21 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-238

Location information

Střední škola průmyslová, hotelová a zdravotnická - kuchyně, Kollárova 617, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06640 N, 17.46276 E

Building area: 1870 m²

2317 LiDAR points (1.24 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	312.6	189.0	19.8	357.4
1	183.9	190.9	10.1	351.8
2	59.8	183.1	7.3	173.2
3	169.5	190.9	10.6	352.6
4	172.8	190.9	10.6	172.8
5	149.6	190.8	10.9	171.9
6	332.5	189.1	19.6	177.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.8	0.113
160 - 140	314.3	45.896
180 - 160	369.7	61.795
200 - 180	103.1	19.717
220 - 200	592.7	124.229
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1380.6	251.750

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	312.6	45.639	4	220 - 200	172.8	35.673
Total		312.6	45.639	Total		172.8	35.673
1	180 - 160	183.9	30.845	5	220 - 200	149.6	31.086
Total		183.9	30.845	Total		149.6	31.086
2	200 - 180	47.2	8.937	6	220 - 200	270.3	57.470
	180 - 160	10.1	1.767		200 - 180	55.9	10.780
	160 - 140	1.7	0.257		180 - 160	6.2	1.083
	140 - 120	0.8	0.113	Total		332.5	69.332
Total		59.8	11.074				
3	180 - 160	169.5	28.100				
Total		169.5	28.100				

eP-EAZK-239

Location information

Střední škola průmyslová, hotelová a zdravotnická, Jiřího z Poděbrad 949, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06587 N, 17.46238 E

Building area: 711 m²

155 LiDAR points (0.22 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-240

Location information

Střední škola průmyslová, hotelová a zdravotnická, Kollárova 617, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06632 N, 17.46219 E

Building area: 865 m²

647 LiDAR points (0.75 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	351.4	195.7	7.2	352.6
1	370.0	195.8	7.2	172.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	351.4	61.206
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	370.0	74.717
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	721.3	135.922

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	351.4	61.206	1	220 - 200	370.0	74.717
Total		351.4	61.206	Total		370.0	74.717

eP-EAZK-241, eP-EAZK-242

Location information

Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola, Tř. Maršála Malinovského 368, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06405 N, 17.46676 E

Building area: 437 m²

500 LiDAR points (1.14 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	197.6	191.8	34.2	95.1
1	16.8	189.8	30.9	5.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	13.2	1.554
140 - 120	3.6	0.436
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	197.6	36.399
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	214.4	38.389

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	197.6	36.399
	Total	197.6	36.399
1	140 - 120	3.6	0.436
	120 - 100	13.2	1.554
	Total	16.8	1.990

eP-EAZK-243, eP-EAZK-244

Location information

Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola, Všešrdova 267, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06842 N, 17.46546 E

Building area: 3910 m²

2673 LiDAR points (0.68 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	229.2	198.6	29.9	281.1
1	103.7	198.8	31.2	101.2
2	95.3	192.9	23.4	191.2
3	253.9	198.7	29.5	101.3
4	268.9	198.4	31.3	281.2
5	81.0	184.8	5.0	277.7
6	71.8	185.9	2.6	9.1
7	94.4	198.6	30.4	11.5
8	109.0	198.5	29.4	191.8
9	77.1	198.9	30.3	10.9
10	67.4	203.0	29.2	190.8
11	55.6	203.0	11.2	10.1
12	56.7	203.1	11.9	100.7
13	58.6	203.0	12.0	281.3
14	6.2	199.5	32.6	100.0
15	267.1	198.2	30.9	101.2
16	108.5	192.6	23.9	10.9

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	95.7	8.327
120 - 100	194.6	21.830
140 - 120	259.8	34.101
160 - 140	47.1	7.190
180 - 160	504.1	84.863
200 - 180	638.0	121.369
220 - 200	77.0	16.640
240 - 220	187.9	42.282
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	2004.3	336.602

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	227.0	38.537	5	160 - 140	4.7	0.671
	160 - 140	2.2	0.354		140 - 120	41.4	5.381
	Total	229.2	38.890		120 - 100	31.1	3.511
1	160 - 140	5.5	0.776	< 100	3.8	0.360	
	140 - 120	22.9	3.006	Total	81.0	9.923	
	120 - 100	20.7	2.255	6	120 - 100	34.4	3.752
	< 100	54.6	4.757		< 100	37.4	3.211
Total	103.7	10.793	Total		71.8	6.963	
2	240 - 220	31.1	6.870	7	140 - 120	6.7	0.815
	220 - 200	64.2	13.950		120 - 100	87.8	10.049
	Total	95.3	20.821		Total	94.4	10.864
3	200 - 180	253.9	48.547	8	240 - 220	93.4	21.062
	Total	253.9	48.547		220 - 200	10.8	2.276
4	180 - 160	220.3	36.873		200 - 180	1.2	0.235
	160 - 140	25.7	3.996		180 - 160	3.6	0.637
	140 - 120	11.4	1.503	Total	109.0	24.211	
	120 - 100	11.4	1.217				
Total	268.9	43.589					

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
9	140 - 120	67.8	8.359	12	200 - 180	56.7	10.889
	120 - 100	9.2	1.045		Total	56.7	10.889
	Total	77.1	9.404		13	200 - 180	57.6
10	240 - 220	63.4	14.350	180 - 160		1.0	0.170
	220 - 200	2.0	0.414	Total		58.6	10.703
	180 - 160	1.0	0.166	14	200 - 180	4.5	0.854
	140 - 120	1.0	0.136		180 - 160	1.7	0.291
Total	67.4	15.065	Total	6.2	1.145		
11	180 - 160	46.6	7.668	15	200 - 180	264.1	50.312
	160 - 140	9.0	1.393		180 - 160	3.0	0.520
	Total	55.6	9.061		Total	267.1	50.832
				16	140 - 120	108.5	14.902
				Total	108.5	14.902	

eP-EAZK-245a

Location information

Gymnázium, Komenského 169, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02330 N, 17.64551 E

Building area: 833 m²

1249 LiDAR points (1.50 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	142.1	244.2	35.2	7.4
1	136.2	244.2	36.4	8.5
2	20.0	241.9	36.2	7.7
3	74.3	243.0	40.6	278.8
4	63.7	243.1	41.6	99.0
5	140.9	244.8	36.2	188.7
6	129.8	245.0	35.8	188.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	6.9	0.656
120 - 100	296.8	32.662
140 - 120	10.8	1.436
160 - 140	59.3	9.096
180 - 160	26.1	4.305
200 - 180	36.4	6.669
220 - 200	1.7	0.348
240 - 220	269.0	61.494
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	707.0	116.667

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	142.1	15.868	4	200 - 180	36.4	6.669
	Total	142.1	15.868		180 - 160	9.1	1.558
1	120 - 100	133.6	14.487		160 - 140	7.3	1.103
	< 100	2.6	0.251		140 - 120	5.5	0.717
2	120 - 100	17.5	1.889		120 - 100	3.6	0.417
	< 100	2.5	0.237	< 100	1.8	0.169	
3	180 - 160	17.0	2.747	Total	63.7	10.633	
	160 - 140	52.0	7.993	5	240 - 220	139.2	31.825
	140 - 120	5.3	0.719		220 - 200	1.7	0.348
	Total	74.3	11.459	Total	140.9	32.173	
6	240 - 220	129.8	29.669	Total	129.8	29.669	

eP-EAZK-245b

Location information

Gymnázium, Komenského 169, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02313 N, 17.64487 E

Building area: 1728 m²

2396 LiDAR points (1.39 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	113.3	244.9	31.9	9.2
1	116.1	244.8	30.9	188.3
2	107.4	245.3	26.9	98.9
3	108.9	244.9	40.9	278.8
4	37.9	244.6	23.1	15.5
5	36.1	244.6	25.3	188.1
6	16.1	243.8	26.0	99.3
7	129.7	245.1	26.8	98.2
8	108.1	245.0	31.4	9.5
9	32.6	244.5	30.6	187.7
10	94.4	244.9	32.6	98.6
11	18.2	249.5	40.0	278.7
12	15.5	249.4	5.6	269.8
13	185.6	232.7	6.8	274.8
14	47.4	232.5	0.5	92.5
15	13.5	232.6	1.5	66.0
16	22.8	244.1	22.2	101.3
17	108.2	244.9	32.1	189.0

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	3.1	0.295
120 - 100	159.3	18.809
140 - 120	131.7	16.605
160 - 140	76.5	11.661
180 - 160	136.0	22.742
200 - 180	532.7	99.976
220 - 200	50.7	10.742
240 - 220	221.9	50.313
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1311.9	231.143

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	113.3	13.450
	Total	113.3	13.450
1	240 - 220	108.6	24.615
	220 - 200	7.5	1.598
	Total	116.1	26.213
2	200 - 180	43.2	7.992
	180 - 160	40.6	7.010
	160 - 140	14.4	2.205
	140 - 120	7.9	1.031
	120 - 100	1.3	0.145
	Total	107.4	18.383
3	180 - 160	71.4	11.607
	160 - 140	29.0	4.440
	140 - 120	4.8	0.633
	120 - 100	1.2	0.141
	< 100	2.4	0.233
	Total	108.9	17.054

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
4	140 - 120	37.9	5.073
	Total	37.9	5.073
5	240 - 220	5.6	1.241
	220 - 200	17.7	3.750
	200 - 180	8.8	1.681
	180 - 160	3.2	0.541
	160 - 140	0.8	0.123
	Total	36.1	7.336
6	200 - 180	16.1	3.060
	Total	16.1	3.060
7	200 - 180	117.1	22.148
	180 - 160	6.3	1.091
	140 - 120	1.6	0.208
	120 - 100	4.7	0.533
	Total	129.7	23.980
8	140 - 120	73.9	8.918
	120 - 100	34.1	4.027
	Total	108.1	12.945

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
9	240 - 220	7.0	1.581	14	200 - 180	23.7	4.347
	220 - 200	21.0	4.422		180 - 160	12.3	2.103
	200 - 180	4.7	0.881		160 - 140	11.4	1.755
	Total	32.6	6.884		Total	47.4	8.205
10	200 - 180	94.4	17.752	15	160 - 140	9.4	1.408
	Total	94.4	17.752		140 - 120	2.9	0.396
11	160 - 140	11.4	1.730		120 - 100	1.2	0.141
	140 - 120	2.7	0.347	Total	13.5	1.945	
	120 - 100	3.4	0.372	16	200 - 180	22.1	4.177
	< 100	0.7	0.063		180 - 160	0.7	0.125
Total	18.2	2.512	Total	22.8	4.302		
12	200 - 180	14.0	2.618	17	240 - 220	100.7	22.875
	180 - 160	1.5	0.264		220 - 200	4.5	0.973
	Total	15.5	2.882		200 - 180	3.0	0.578
13	200 - 180	185.6	34.741		Total	108.2	24.426
	Total	185.6	34.741				

eP-EAZK-245c

Location information

Gymnázium, Komenského 169, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02286 N, 17.64554 E

Building area: 2249 m²

2882 LiDAR points (1.28 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	612.2	232.6	0.2	203.7
1	7.1	228.6	32.5	278.2
2	34.4	228.9	1.1	239.1
3	470.7	225.4	0.1	241.1
4	209.9	230.5	1.5	99.7
5	66.3	228.4	9.1	88.9
6	82.3	235.4	24.0	274.1
7	93.7	235.7	48.1	278.7
8	367.8	236.4	48.1	98.7
9	318.8	236.6	36.6	8.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	82.3	6.930
120 - 100	331.5	36.140
140 - 120	33.1	4.397
160 - 140	175.4	27.102
180 - 160	520.7	92.340
200 - 180	1120.4	209.368
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	2263.4	376.277

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	410.7	77.102	5	200 - 180	66.3	12.313
	180 - 160	85.2	14.625		Total	66.3	12.313
	160 - 140	77.5	11.764	6	< 100	82.3	6.930
	140 - 120	31.0	4.103		Total	82.3	6.930
	120 - 100	7.7	0.906	7	160 - 140	93.7	14.703
Total	612.2	108.500	Total		93.7	14.703	
1	180 - 160	2.4	0.383	8	180 - 160	367.8	65.960
	160 - 140	4.1	0.635		Total	367.8	65.960
	120 - 100	0.6	0.068	9	120 - 100	318.8	34.685
Total	7.1	1.086	Total		318.8	34.685	
2	200 - 180	29.4	5.465				
	180 - 160	5.0	0.861				
Total	34.4	6.326					
3	200 - 180	466.2	87.139				
	180 - 160	4.5	0.788				
	Total	470.7	87.928				
4	200 - 180	147.8	27.349				
	180 - 160	55.7	9.722				
	140 - 120	2.1	0.294				
	120 - 100	4.3	0.482				
Total	209.9	37.847					

eP-EAZK-246

Location information

Střední odborné učiliště - dílny, Na Výsluní 813, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02905 N, 17.64102 E

Building area: 462 m²

677 LiDAR points (1.47 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	404.4	269.0	0.1	256.0
1	8.5	271.5	2.0	345.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	7.6	1.182
180 - 160	11.4	1.870
200 - 180	393.9	73.782
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	412.9	76.834

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	385.3	72.212
	180 - 160	11.4	1.870
	160 - 140	7.6	1.182
	Total	404.4	75.264

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	200 - 180	8.5	1.570
	Total	8.5	1.570

eP-EAZK-247

Location information

Střední odborné učiliště - domov mládeže, Na Výsluní 813, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02915 N, 17.64151 E

Building area: 506 m²

1025 LiDAR points (2.02 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	31.9	269.6	15.3	357.7
1	36.3	269.6	15.0	176.0
2	197.4	273.6	12.8	356.3
3	227.6	273.7	13.1	176.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.9	0.097
140 - 120	9.5	1.234
160 - 140	61.0	9.422
180 - 160	157.9	25.561
200 - 180	3.2	0.624
220 - 200	260.6	55.087
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	493.1	92.025

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	21.5	3.176
	140 - 120	9.5	1.234
	120 - 100	0.9	0.097
	Total	31.9	4.507
1	220 - 200	33.1	6.977
	200 - 180	3.2	0.624
	Total	36.3	7.601

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	180 - 160	157.9	25.561
	160 - 140	39.5	6.246
	Total	197.4	31.808
3	220 - 200	227.6	48.110
Total	227.6	48.110	

eP-EAZK-248

Location information

Střední odborné učiliště, Svatopluka Čecha 1110, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02678 N, 17.63954 E

Building area: 1410 m²

2614 LiDAR points (1.85 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	264.6	248.0	1.0	149.3
1	169.7	258.6	35.4	285.5
2	141.4	258.5	35.0	105.6
3	6.8	256.8	9.0	14.7
4	12.2	256.4	9.5	18.8
5	285.3	258.0	40.2	15.7
6	74.1	257.3	34.5	16.2
7	71.8	257.3	35.4	15.3
8	261.4	257.8	40.1	195.7
9	169.2	258.1	34.8	105.5
10	178.2	258.4	35.0	285.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	184.5	15.787
120 - 100	312.9	33.527
140 - 120	44.3	5.897
160 - 140	68.8	10.488
180 - 160	495.6	81.416
200 - 180	315.7	60.499
220 - 200	64.7	13.774
240 - 220	148.2	33.159
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1634.7	254.548

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	133.7	22.909	5	120 - 100	136.9	13.977
	160 - 140	42.7	6.477		< 100	148.5	12.513
	140 - 120	34.1	4.555		Total	285.3	26.490
	120 - 100	25.6	2.704	6	120 - 100	74.1	8.511
	< 100	28.5	2.545		Total	74.1	8.511
Total	264.6	39.190	7	120 - 100	64.8	7.052	
1	180 - 160	157.0		25.229	< 100	7.1	0.687
	160 - 140	6.4		0.980	Total	71.8	7.739
	120 - 100	6.4	0.698	8	240 - 220	148.2	33.159
Total	169.7	26.907	220 - 200		64.7	13.774	
2	200 - 180	125.0	24.049		200 - 180	21.6	4.101
	180 - 160	10.2	1.745		180 - 160	13.5	2.337
	160 - 140	2.0	0.308		160 - 140	10.8	1.654
	120 - 100	4.1	0.469	140 - 120	2.7	0.375	
Total	141.4	26.571	Total	261.4	55.400		
3	160 - 140	0.5	0.074	9	200 - 180	169.2	32.350
	140 - 120	4.7	0.606		Total	169.2	32.350
	120 - 100	1.1	0.118	10	180 - 160	175.8	28.310
	< 100	0.5	0.043		160 - 140	2.4	0.377
Total	6.8	0.840	Total	178.2	28.687		
4	180 - 160	5.4	0.886				
	160 - 140	4.1	0.618				
	140 - 120	2.7	0.361				
	Total	12.2	1.864				

eP-EAZK-249

Location information

Střední odborné učiliště, Svatopluka Čecha 1111, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02674 N, 17.63868 E

Building area: 633 m²

1225 LiDAR points (1.93 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	41.5	255.0	37.4	196.1
1	71.7	254.5	23.2	106.5
2	67.0	254.8	38.2	112.1
3	90.8	249.5	37.5	196.1
4	14.6	245.0	12.2	106.3
5	39.4	254.2	38.8	16.0
6	30.2	254.0	35.7	285.3
7	110.5	254.6	39.1	15.9
8	15.4	249.8	34.7	106.3
9	6.0	247.9	5.1	201.2
10	29.1	249.8	39.5	195.9
11	40.1	248.8	36.7	286.2
12	103.1	249.6	37.9	16.1

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	68.6	6.306
120 - 100	233.3	24.736
140 - 120	17.6	2.297
160 - 140	74.1	11.391
180 - 160	69.4	11.822
200 - 180	84.4	16.424
220 - 200	16.9	3.645
240 - 220	95.3	21.520
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	659.5	98.142

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	1.0	0.125	3	240 - 220	66.2	14.907
	120 - 100	5.9	0.635		220 - 200	16.9	3.645
	< 100	34.6	3.277		200 - 180	7.8	1.513
	Total	41.5	4.036		Total	90.8	20.066
1	200 - 180	9.6	1.744	4	180 - 160	4.1	0.667
	180 - 160	50.6	8.721		160 - 140	2.9	0.443
	160 - 140	11.5	1.749		140 - 120	4.7	0.613
	Total	71.7	12.213		120 - 100	2.3	0.258
2	200 - 180	51.6	10.187		< 100	0.6	0.056
	180 - 160	3.3	0.575		Total	14.6	2.036
	160 - 140	5.5	0.834				
	140 - 120	1.1	0.133				
	120 - 100	1.1	0.124				
	< 100	4.4	0.388				
	Total	67.0	12.243				

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
5	120 - 100	39.4	4.184	10	240 - 220	29.1	6.612
Total		39.4	4.184	Total		29.1	6.612
6	180 - 160	7.3	1.176	11	160 - 140	33.0	5.077
	160 - 140	19.2	2.969		140 - 120	7.1	0.939
	140 - 120	3.7	0.487	Total		40.1	6.016
Total		30.2	4.632	12	120 - 100	74.0	7.827
7	120 - 100	110.5	11.708		< 100	29.1	2.585
Total		110.5	11.708	Total		103.1	10.412
8	200 - 180	15.4	2.980				
Total		15.4	2.980				
9	180 - 160	4.0	0.683				
	160 - 140	2.0	0.320				
Total		6.0	1.003				

eP-EAZK-250

Location information

Střední odborné učiliště, Vazová 2509, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02092 N, 17.63349 E

Building area: 313 m²

15 LiDAR points (0.05 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-251

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola a Obchodní akademie - domov mládeže, Větrná 1370, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.03006 N, 17.65882 E

Building area: 619 m²

1067 LiDAR points (1.72 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	17.6	244.7	2.0	239.3
1	48.4	249.1	30.3	54.7
2	37.7	249.0	30.7	234.9
3	283.6	252.4	30.0	55.0
4	301.9	252.4	30.5	234.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	10.2	0.890
120 - 100	12.4	1.377
140 - 120	164.1	21.554
160 - 140	161.8	23.687
180 - 160	26.5	4.525
200 - 180	98.3	19.141
220 - 200	215.9	44.334
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	689.3	115.508

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	8.0	1.325	3	160 - 140	126.3	18.498
	160 - 140	6.4	0.968		140 - 120	151.6	19.920
	140 - 120	1.6	0.202		120 - 100	5.6	0.630
	120 - 100	0.5	0.059		Total	283.6	39.048
	< 100	1.1	0.102		4	220 - 200	202.2
Total	17.6	2.657	200 - 180	85.4		16.668	
1	160 - 140	25.6	3.702	180 - 160		14.2	2.467
	140 - 120	9.1	1.201	Total	301.9	60.678	
	120 - 100	4.6	0.499				
	< 100	9.1	0.787				
Total	48.4	6.189					
2	220 - 200	13.7	2.790				
	200 - 180	12.9	2.473				
	180 - 160	4.3	0.733				
	160 - 140	3.4	0.519				
	140 - 120	1.7	0.231				
	120 - 100	1.7	0.190				
Total	37.7	6.937					

eP-EAZK-252

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola a Obchodní akademie, Předbranská 415, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02191 N, 17.65098 E

Building area: 595 m²

516 LiDAR points (0.87 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	448.5	227.9	0.2	187.9
1	31.3	231.0	0.6	210.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	4.7	0.541
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	9.4	1.477
180 - 160	42.5	7.370
200 - 180	423.2	79.305
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	479.8	88.694

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	391.8	73.382	1	200 - 180	31.3	5.923
	180 - 160	42.5	7.370		Total		31.3
	160 - 140	9.4	1.477				
	120 - 100	4.7	0.541				
Total		448.5	82.770				

eP-EAZK-253

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola a Obchodní akademie, Nivnická 1781, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.00276 N, 17.65061 E

Building area: 3351 m²

4199 LiDAR points (1.25 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	315.9	225.7	2.2	97.0
1	1930.2	227.9	0.2	50.1
2	614.7	237.0	4.7	185.5
3	359.2	237.1	14.5	4.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	404.7	63.871
180 - 160	383.5	66.529
200 - 180	2431.8	459.537
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	3220.0	589.936

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	195.7	36.020
	180 - 160	113.3	19.745
	160 - 140	6.9	1.079
	Total	315.9	56.844
1	200 - 180	1621.4	302.284
	180 - 160	270.2	46.783
	160 - 140	38.6	5.945
	Total	1930.2	355.012

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	614.7	121.233
	Total	614.7	121.233
3	160 - 140	359.2	56.847
Total	Total	359.2	56.847

eP-EAZK-254

Location information

Střední škola - COPT, Obchodní 2055, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.02559 N, 17.65386 E

Building area: 659 m²

1380 LiDAR points (2.10 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	149.1	243.4	29.7	59.1
1	48.0	240.9	1.9	357.2
2	133.3	243.3	29.9	238.9
3	73.4	247.3	29.9	329.3
4	80.2	247.1	30.0	149.5
5	68.8	247.1	29.8	329.0
6	71.5	247.3	30.3	149.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	10.0	0.940
120 - 100	12.3	1.360
140 - 120	167.1	21.806
160 - 140	101.9	15.095
180 - 160	48.0	8.393
200 - 180	45.1	8.863
220 - 200	160.3	33.511
240 - 220	79.7	17.618
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	624.4	107.585

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	160 - 140	101.9	15.095	4	240 - 220	56.9	12.567	
	140 - 120	39.9	5.282		220 - 200	23.4	5.112	
	120 - 100	5.9	0.657		Total	80.2	17.678	
	< 100	1.5	0.147		5	140 - 120	68.8	8.989
	Total	149.1	21.182			Total	68.8	8.989
1	180 - 160	48.0	8.393	6		240 - 220	22.9	5.051
	Total	48.0	8.393		220 - 200	46.7	10.108	
	2	220 - 200	90.2		18.291	200 - 180	2.0	0.393
200 - 180		43.1	8.470	Total	71.5	15.552		
Total		133.3	26.761	3	140 - 120	58.5	7.535	
3	120 - 100	6.4	0.703		120 - 100	6.4	0.703	
	< 100	8.5	0.793		< 100	8.5	0.793	
	Total	73.4	9.030		Total	73.4	9.030	

eP-EAZK-255

Location information

Dětský domov, Sokolovská 620, Uherský Ostroh, Zlínský kraj

48.98566 N, 17.39819 E

Building area: 402 m²

753 LiDAR points (1.87 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	10.4	183.3	0.4	340.9
1	100.8	189.4	2.2	89.0
2	40.0	189.3	4.2	124.1
3	80.0	189.4	4.0	34.2
4	24.5	186.2	4.1	215.8
5	54.7	189.4	4.2	304.5
6	7.3	189.3	4.8	206.4
7	29.7	179.8	1.1	201.2
8	5.0	189.3	3.7	214.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	11.0	0.955
120 - 100	13.4	1.455
140 - 120	19.7	2.555
160 - 140	38.4	5.814
180 - 160	95.4	16.411
200 - 180	174.4	32.479
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	352.3	59.670

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	0.6	0.087	4	200 - 180	24.5	4.766
	140 - 120	1.2	0.155		Total	24.5	4.766
	120 - 100	1.8	0.199	5	200 - 180	26.9	4.908
	< 100	6.7	0.593		180 - 160	22.7	3.928
	Total	10.4	1.035		160 - 140	5.0	0.790
1	200 - 180	2.9	0.520	Total	54.7	9.626	
	180 - 160	37.5	6.377	6	200 - 180	7.3	1.417
	160 - 140	28.8	4.336		Total	7.3	1.417
	140 - 120	15.8	2.058	7	200 - 180	0.7	0.119
	120 - 100	11.5	1.256		180 - 160	22.4	3.849
	< 100	4.3	0.361		160 - 140	4.0	0.601
Total	100.8	14.909	140 - 120		2.6	0.342	
2	200 - 180	34.6	6.588	Total	29.7	4.912	
	180 - 160	5.3	0.951	8	200 - 180	5.0	0.967
	Total	40.0	7.539		Total	5.0	0.967
3	200 - 180	72.5	13.194				
	180 - 160	7.4	1.306				
	Total	80.0	14.500				

eP-EAZK-256

Location information

Střední odborné učiliště, Brumovská 456, Valašské Klobouky, Zlínský kraj

49.13205 N, 18.01157 E

Building area: 234 m²

425 LiDAR points (1.81 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	54.4	386.3	45.5	246.2
1	85.3	386.9	45.7	66.6
2	22.0	386.7	45.4	335.0
3	23.8	385.7	44.2	157.0
4	24.2	383.0	28.1	246.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	22.8	2.133
120 - 100	0.8	0.078
140 - 120	79.6	10.803
160 - 140	8.7	1.246
180 - 160	23.1	4.070
200 - 180	59.9	11.265
220 - 200	14.9	3.038
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	209.7	32.633

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	33.6	6.179	4	200 - 180	17.4	3.318
	180 - 160	20.8	3.666		180 - 160	2.3	0.404
	Total	54.4	9.845		160 - 140	1.5	0.231
1	160 - 140	7.2	1.015		140 - 120	1.5	0.189
	140 - 120	78.1	10.613		120 - 100	0.8	0.078
2	< 100	22.0	2.062	< 100	0.8	0.072	
	Total	22.0	2.062	Total	24.2	4.292	
3	220 - 200	14.9	3.038				
	200 - 180	8.9	1.768				
	Total	23.8	4.806				

eP-EAZK-257

Location information

Dětský domov, základní škola a praktická škola, Smolina 16, Valašské Klobouky, Zlínský kraj

49.15484 N, 17.99675 E

Building area: 1379 m²

1981 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	19.1	429.7	6.5	230.3
1	108.6	430.9	42.9	231.8
2	211.3	433.1	11.1	231.3
3	25.7	432.0	42.6	230.4
4	60.3	429.6	15.2	240.9
5	36.1	431.8	43.3	231.4
6	130.1	431.8	42.6	321.6
7	119.0	429.8	7.5	321.5
8	154.2	429.9	7.1	57.4
9	276.5	432.0	43.0	51.3
10	131.7	429.7	10.6	141.6
11	47.2	432.0	42.4	141.8
12	29.5	432.0	43.2	141.4
13	13.6	431.9	44.0	141.4
14	79.5	431.2	43.4	51.6
15	28.5	429.7	12.5	51.9

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	213.1	17.751
120 - 100	203.6	22.706
140 - 120	118.0	15.060
160 - 140	53.0	8.108
180 - 160	243.8	41.489
200 - 180	121.7	23.615
220 - 200	517.4	105.907
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1470.6	234.636

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	11.3	2.116	4	200 - 180	50.4	9.945
	180 - 160	4.3	0.754		180 - 160	7.2	1.228
	160 - 140	2.6	0.406		160 - 140	0.9	0.140
	140 - 120	0.9	0.115		140 - 120	1.8	0.246
	Total	19.1	3.391		Total	60.3	11.559
1	220 - 200	105.5	21.866	5	220 - 200	30.1	6.235
	180 - 160	1.5	0.253		200 - 180	2.4	0.464
	140 - 120	1.5	0.199		180 - 160	3.6	0.614
	Total	108.6	22.318		Total	36.1	7.312
2	220 - 200	198.3	39.809	6	120 - 100	126.9	14.296
	200 - 180	12.9	2.543		< 100	3.2	0.300
	Total	211.3	42.352		Total	130.1	14.596
3	220 - 200	21.7	4.501	7	180 - 160	86.4	14.788
	200 - 180	1.0	0.194		160 - 140	12.5	1.894
	180 - 160	1.0	0.177		140 - 120	18.8	2.451
	160 - 140	1.0	0.146		120 - 100	1.3	0.148
	140 - 120	1.0	0.130		Total	119.0	19.282
Total	25.7	5.147	8	200 - 180	14.2	2.556	
				180 - 160	115.2	19.575	
				160 - 140	23.0	3.582	
				140 - 120	1.8	0.245	
				Total	154.2	25.959	

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
9	140 - 120	64.3	8.128	12	220 - 200	19.3	4.156
	120 - 100	45.0	4.909		200 - 180	3.0	0.584
	< 100	167.2	13.988		180 - 160	2.0	0.343
	Total	276.5	27.026		160 - 140	2.0	0.301
			140 - 120		1.0	0.132	
10	220 - 200	108.6	22.072	120 - 100	2.0	0.237	
	200 - 180	23.1	4.577	Total	29.5	5.753	
	Total	131.7	26.650				
11	220 - 200	21.2	4.571	13	220 - 200	12.6	2.697
	200 - 180	2.4	0.449		200 - 180	1.0	0.186
	180 - 160	2.4	0.404		Total	13.6	2.883
	160 - 140	3.5	0.523	14	140 - 120	20.2	2.555
	140 - 120	5.9	0.747		120 - 100	16.6	1.818
	120 - 100	11.8	1.298		< 100	42.7	3.463
	Total	47.2	7.992		Total	79.5	7.836
			15	180 - 160	20.2	3.353	
				160 - 140	7.4	1.117	
				140 - 120	0.9	0.113	
				Total	28.5	4.582	

eP-EAZK-258

Location information

Základní umělecká škola, Smetanova 116, Valašské Klobouky, Zlínský kraj

49.14171 N, 18.00649 E

Building area: 275 m²

403 LiDAR points (1.46 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	40.0	411.1	29.2	281.4
1	22.3	407.8	11.1	15.9
2	32.1	410.4	28.7	111.7
3	27.5	412.4	10.5	106.5
4	17.6	410.1	28.3	202.4
5	34.2	410.6	31.0	20.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	21.4	2.467
140 - 120	17.7	2.194
160 - 140	11.1	1.695
180 - 160	46.3	7.682
200 - 180	59.6	11.697
220 - 200	17.6	3.776
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	173.7	29.511

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	40.0	6.668	3	200 - 180	27.5	5.294
	Total	40.0	6.668		Total	27.5	5.294
1	180 - 160	6.3	1.014	4	220 - 200	17.6	3.776
	160 - 140	11.1	1.695		Total	17.6	3.776
	140 - 120	2.1	0.274	5	140 - 120	15.6	1.920
	120 - 100	2.8	0.313		120 - 100	18.6	2.154
Total	22.3	3.296	Total	34.2	4.074		
2	200 - 180	32.1	6.403				
Total	32.1	6.403					

eP-EAZK-259

Location information

Dětský domov, Žerotínova 211/22, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47107 N, 17.97630 E

Building area: 746 m²

1068 LiDAR points (1.43 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	17.9	314.2	14.0	86.7
1	48.9	317.2	34.8	356.2
2	19.8	319.3	0.3	313.0
3	24.4	316.8	34.4	84.6
4	15.6	318.9	18.9	218.4
5	49.3	316.6	33.8	221.6
6	49.6	317.1	33.7	131.0
7	41.7	320.9	0.5	214.0
8	165.3	321.6	25.3	86.9
9	171.8	321.4	25.1	266.4
10	96.1	320.9	24.8	355.8
11	79.4	322.2	25.3	177.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	5.2	0.483
120 - 100	52.3	5.637
140 - 120	108.5	14.539
160 - 140	25.4	3.850
180 - 160	262.2	44.752
200 - 180	218.3	40.395
220 - 200	34.0	7.015
240 - 220	73.9	16.390
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	779.8	133.061

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	10.7	1.800	6	200 - 180	29.5	5.528
	160 - 140	2.9	0.439		180 - 160	20.1	3.499
	140 - 120	0.7	0.100		Total	49.6	9.027
	120 - 100	2.1	0.242	7	200 - 180	23.3	4.264
	< 100	1.4	0.125		180 - 160	18.5	3.208
	Total	17.9	2.705		Total	41.7	7.472
1	120 - 100	45.2	4.822	8	180 - 160	155.2	26.181
	< 100	3.8	0.358		160 - 140	8.6	1.326
	Total	48.9	5.180		140 - 120	1.4	0.191
2	200 - 180	16.1	2.925	Total	165.3	27.698	
	180 - 160	3.7	0.652	9	200 - 180	121.7	22.233
	Total	19.8	3.577		180 - 160	45.3	7.860
3	160 - 140	9.1	1.351		160 - 140	4.8	0.734
	140 - 120	14.5	1.943	Total	171.8	30.827	
	120 - 100	0.8	0.089	10	140 - 120	91.9	12.305
	Total	24.4	3.384		120 - 100	4.2	0.484
4	220 - 200	13.4	2.753		Total	96.1	12.789
	200 - 180	1.5	0.284	11	240 - 220	73.9	16.390
	180 - 160	0.7	0.127		220 - 200	5.4	1.193
	Total	15.6	3.164		Total	79.4	17.583
5	220 - 200	15.1	3.069				
	200 - 180	26.3	5.162				
	180 - 160	8.0	1.425				
	Total	49.3	9.656				

eP-EAZK-260

Location information

Gymnázium, Husova 146/2, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47022 N, 17.96888 E

Building area: 1567 m²

1646 LiDAR points (1.05 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	72.3	328.3	35.2	77.6
1	90.0	327.7	35.4	168.3
2	48.0	328.1	35.1	347.6
3	29.5	327.6	30.5	80.3
4	94.3	328.3	33.9	168.3
5	68.2	328.6	35.6	258.0
6	47.3	328.5	35.1	347.2
7	165.0	327.6	34.0	258.2
8	92.6	327.6	33.6	168.0
9	135.5	327.7	34.8	167.9
10	271.6	327.4	34.4	78.1
11	32.8	330.1	34.3	347.7
12	24.1	329.9	31.0	258.3
13	57.8	330.1	31.2	78.0
14	68.8	330.0	32.0	347.5
15	90.4	328.4	31.4	168.0
16	34.6	327.9	32.3	257.4

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	40.3	3.685
120 - 100	172.7	19.579
140 - 120	11.7	1.500
160 - 140	36.8	5.674
180 - 160	417.3	69.929
200 - 180	277.7	52.433
220 - 200	83.5	17.286
240 - 220	382.8	87.157
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1422.8	257.242

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	64.1	10.630	4	240 - 220	71.3	16.180
	160 - 140	2.1	0.315		220 - 200	17.2	3.736
	140 - 120	3.1	0.383		200 - 180	2.3	0.444
	< 100	3.1	0.291		180 - 160	1.1	0.189
	Total	72.3	11.619		160 - 140	2.3	0.362
1	220 - 200	60.7	12.369	Total	94.3	20.911	
	200 - 180	21.4	4.141	5	200 - 180	61.7	11.600
	180 - 160	6.7	1.132		180 - 160	1.1	0.181
	160 - 140	1.1	0.168		160 - 140	2.2	0.338
	Total	90.0	17.810		140 - 120	2.2	0.282
2	120 - 100	27.1	2.819		120 - 100	1.1	0.123
	< 100	20.9	1.896	Total	68.2	12.524	
	Total	48.0	4.714	6	120 - 100	38.3	4.176
3	180 - 160	19.9	3.394		< 100	9.1	0.851
	160 - 140	3.5	0.541		Total	47.3	5.027
	140 - 120	1.7	0.220				
	120 - 100	1.7	0.180				
	< 100	2.6	0.233				
Total	29.5	4.568					

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
7	200 - 180	165.0	31.079	13	180 - 160	55.6	9.436
Total		165.0	31.079		160 - 140	2.2	0.346
8	240 - 220	85.7	19.488	Total		57.8	9.781
	220 - 200	5.5	1.181	14	120 - 100	68.8	8.208
	200 - 180	1.4	0.252	Total		68.8	8.208
Total		92.6	20.922	15	240 - 220	90.4	20.549
9	240 - 220	135.5	30.941	Total		90.4	20.549
Total		135.5	30.941	16	200 - 180	1.9	0.350
10	180 - 160	263.1	44.020		180 - 160	5.6	0.948
	160 - 140	8.5	1.337		160 - 140	15.0	2.266
Total		271.6	45.357		140 - 120	4.7	0.615
11	120 - 100	32.8	3.754		120 - 100	2.8	0.318
Total		32.8	3.754		< 100	4.7	0.414
12	200 - 180	24.1	4.567	Total		34.6	4.912
Total		24.1	4.567				

eP-EAZK-261

Location information

Integrovaná střední škola - COP, Palackého 239/49, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.46367 N, 17.96749 E

Building area: 1742 m²

2707 LiDAR points (1.55 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	223.5	302.0	1.4	76.0
1	29.9	314.1	34.0	77.5
2	408.5	313.9	19.1	346.4
3	477.3	314.9	4.9	346.5
4	27.0	314.0	4.0	202.7
5	64.8	314.0	18.6	165.8
6	28.2	310.1	23.0	255.4
7	65.0	310.7	0.6	303.2
8	36.4	310.3	19.7	76.5
9	145.2	310.1	10.6	253.7
10	66.6	309.7	21.3	256.2
11	19.2	310.1	11.9	84.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	46.8	3.992
120 - 100	31.0	3.500
140 - 120	87.2	11.447
160 - 140	523.9	77.853
180 - 160	568.1	99.911
200 - 180	274.9	52.340
220 - 200	59.4	12.734
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1591.5	261.777

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	160 - 140	78.8	11.755	7	200 - 180	50.7	9.341	
	140 - 120	74.5	9.775		180 - 160	14.4	2.487	
	120 - 100	23.4	2.653		Total	65.0	11.828	
	< 100	46.8	3.992		8	180 - 160	34.8	5.862
	Total	223.5	28.177			160 - 140	1.6	0.247
1	180 - 160	29.9	4.989	Total	36.4	6.109		
	Total	29.9	4.989	9	200 - 180	133.0	25.568	
2	160 - 140	408.5	60.474		180 - 160	5.2	0.905	
	Total	408.5	60.474		140 - 120	1.7	0.221	
3	180 - 160	461.2	81.763		120 - 100	5.2	0.579	
	160 - 140	10.7	1.663		Total	145.2	27.273	
	140 - 120	5.4	0.738	10	200 - 180	54.7	10.444	
	Total	477.3	84.164		180 - 160	5.5	0.949	
4	180 - 160	3.2	0.521		160 - 140	2.7	0.421	
	160 - 140	19.4	2.954		140 - 120	1.8	0.232	
	140 - 120	3.8	0.481		120 - 100	1.8	0.204	
	Total	27.0	4.019	Total	66.6	12.250		
5	220 - 200	59.4	12.734	11	200 - 180	2.9	0.531	
	200 - 180	5.4	1.052		180 - 160	14.0	2.435	
	Total	64.8	13.786		160 - 140	2.2	0.337	
6	200 - 180	28.2	5.404	Total	19.2	3.304		
	Total	28.2	5.404					

eP-EAZK-262

Location information

Obchodní akademie a VOŠ, Jičínská 97, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47719 N, 17.97283 E

Building area: 1221 m²

1670 LiDAR points (1.37 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	616.9	298.9	2.2	28.9
1	345.6	302.3	0.1	45.4
2	173.8	302.3	0.1	60.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	4.7	0.465
120 - 100	23.4	2.601
140 - 120	23.4	3.158
160 - 140	146.0	21.610
180 - 160	403.2	68.740
200 - 180	535.8	98.789
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1136.4	195.364

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	126.2	22.958	2	200 - 180	165.0	30.770
	180 - 160	341.2	57.975		180 - 160	8.8	1.559
	160 - 140	98.1	14.662		Total	173.8	32.329
	140 - 120	23.4	3.158	1	200 - 180	244.6	45.062
	120 - 100	23.4	2.601		180 - 160	53.2	9.206
	< 100	4.7	0.465		160 - 140	47.9	6.948
	Total	616.9	101.819		Total	345.6	61.216

eP-EAZK-263

Location information

Obchodní akademie a VOŠ, Masarykova 101/18, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47603 N, 17.97167 E

Building area: 532 m²

832 LiDAR points (1.56 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	45.1	310.5	38.0	341.6
1	10.5	312.1	8.0	337.9
2	59.5	310.8	33.7	71.2
3	84.2	311.5	26.1	161.8
4	13.8	311.4	26.1	160.9
5	9.7	312.2	33.6	71.8
6	46.3	311.4	35.7	159.3
7	7.0	310.5	10.9	248.4
8	8.6	312.2	38.1	341.4
9	17.0	312.3	16.1	68.1
10	32.5	311.3	37.9	160.7
11	32.8	311.3	34.2	251.1
12	9.8	309.0	34.4	251.9
13	35.8	311.4	28.6	57.2
14	76.7	311.4	26.6	340.8

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	9.8	0.917
120 - 100	63.3	6.841
140 - 120	95.6	12.701
160 - 140	55.4	8.381
180 - 160	42.4	6.857
200 - 180	57.4	11.100
220 - 200	22.9	4.891
240 - 220	142.6	32.005
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	489.3	83.694

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	38.9	4.157	4	240 - 220	9.2	2.054
	< 100	6.1	0.578		220 - 200	2.3	0.489
	Total	45.1	4.735		200 - 180	1.5	0.291
1	180 - 160	0.9	0.140	180 - 160	0.8	0.130	Total
	160 - 140	1.7	0.267	13.8	2.964		
	140 - 120	1.7	0.223	5	180 - 160	9.7	1.573
	120 - 100	4.4	0.483		Total	9.7	1.573
	< 100	1.7	0.157		6	240 - 220	31.1
Total	10.5	1.271	220 - 200	10.4		2.224	
2	180 - 160	25.0	4.012	200 - 180		3.2	0.612
	160 - 140	27.8	4.255	180 - 160	1.6	0.274	
	140 - 120	6.7	0.901	Total	46.3	10.116	
	Total	59.5	9.168	3	240 - 220	69.8	15.570
3	240 - 220	69.8	15.570		220 - 200	10.3	2.178
	220 - 200	10.3	2.178		200 - 180	3.1	0.581
	200 - 180	3.1	0.581		180 - 160	1.0	0.174
	180 - 160	1.0	0.174	Total	84.2	18.503	
Total	84.2	18.503					

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
7	200 - 180	7.0	1.361	11	200 - 180	32.8	6.347
Total		7.0	1.361	Total		32.8	6.347
8	120 - 100	8.6	0.913	12	200 - 180	9.8	1.910
Total		8.6	0.913	Total		9.8	1.910
9	180 - 160	3.4	0.556	13	160 - 140	21.7	3.244
	160 - 140	4.1	0.616		140 - 120	5.7	0.741
	140 - 120	4.8	0.631		120 - 100	6.6	0.753
	120 - 100	4.8	0.535		< 100	1.9	0.182
Total		17.0	2.336	Total		35.8	4.919
10	240 - 220	32.5	7.374	14	140 - 120	76.7	10.205
Total		32.5	7.374	Total		76.7	10.205

eP-EAZK-264

Location information

Obchodní akademie a VOŠ, Jičínská 17, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47712 N, 17.97539 E

Building area: 1141 m²

1432 LiDAR points (1.25 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	83.3	301.5	0.4	267.1
1	383.9	306.3	4.1	346.4
2	6.1	304.6	1.0	346.8
3	58.4	304.6	0.4	77.0
4	505.3	311.3	0.3	342.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.9	0.093
140 - 120	19.4	2.565
160 - 140	56.2	8.530
180 - 160	268.2	46.637
200 - 180	692.5	128.453
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1037.0	186.278

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	64.3	10.900	3	180 - 160	9.4	1.548
	160 - 140	19.0	2.917		160 - 140	29.2	4.389
	Total	83.3	13.817		140 - 120	18.9	2.502
1	200 - 180	192.0	34.617	120 - 100	0.9	0.093	
	180 - 160	185.9	32.742	Total	58.4	8.532	
	160 - 140	6.1	0.944	4	200 - 180	500.5	93.836
	Total	383.9	68.302		180 - 160	4.8	0.818
2	180 - 160	3.7	0.630	Total	505.3	94.653	
	160 - 140	1.9	0.281				
	140 - 120	0.5	0.063				
	Total	6.1	0.973				

eP-EAZK-265

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola stavební, Máchova 628/10, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.46887 N, 17.97586 E

Building area: 2983 m²

3825 LiDAR points (1.28 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	302.5	320.0	0.2	84.3
1	14.0	319.8	0.4	248.9
2	139.8	329.9	4.0	269.2
3	38.8	316.4	27.2	86.8
4	141.6	329.9	0.2	85.1
5	229.2	329.8	23.8	357.0
6	1947.8	329.7	85.7	358.4
7	189.5	329.8	23.7	177.1
8	29.1	329.1	24.2	178.4
9	29.3	331.3	2.6	246.1
10	46.8	329.3	23.7	87.1
11	48.2	329.3	23.9	266.3
12	26.8	331.1	26.8	357.6
13	17.6	331.4	25.7	180.4
14	42.0	331.4	27.6	87.4
15	328.9	329.6	27.9	266.8
16	226.1	329.6	4.7	176.2
17	45.0	329.1	23.8	176.9
18	98.1	329.5	32.2	262.3
19	143.3	329.8	23.2	90.2

■ **Energy prediction - Summary**

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	2121.8	107.588
120 - 100	97.3	10.726
140 - 120	375.6	50.098
160 - 140	111.4	16.887
180 - 160	228.8	38.952
200 - 180	884.2	162.720
220 - 200	22.4	4.723
240 - 220	242.6	54.205
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	4084.1	445.900

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	200.7	36.814	5	140 - 120	224.0	30.452
	180 - 160	84.3	14.582		120 - 100	5.1	0.613
	160 - 140	17.4	2.680		Total	229.2	31.066
	Total	302.5	54.076		6	< 100	1947.8
1	160 - 140	1.2	0.166	Total		1947.8	92.503
	140 - 120	10.5	1.366	7	240 - 220	187.3	41.832
	120 - 100	2.3	0.264		220 - 200	2.3	0.471
Total	14.0	1.796	Total		189.5	42.303	
2	140 - 120	61.4	7.966	8	240 - 220	29.1	6.501
	120 - 100	18.4	2.078		Total	29.1	6.501
	< 100	59.9	5.178	9	120 - 100	19.0	2.020
Total	139.8	15.222	< 100		10.2	0.986	
3	200 - 180	38.8	6.987		Total	29.3	3.005
	Total	38.8	6.987	10	200 - 180	26.8	4.868
4	140 - 120	9.4	1.178		180 - 160	19.1	3.333
	120 - 100	28.3	3.102		160 - 140	1.0	0.149
	< 100	103.9	8.922		Total	46.8	8.350
Total	141.6	13.202					

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
11	200 - 180	37.6	6.932	16	180 - 160	81.8	13.517
	180 - 160	9.6	1.664		160 - 140	79.4	12.016
	160 - 140	1.0	0.151		140 - 120	40.9	5.336
	Total	48.2	8.747		120 - 100	24.1	2.649
12	140 - 120	26.8	3.461	Total	226.1	33.518	
	Total	26.8	3.461	17	240 - 220	12.4	2.747
13	240 - 220	13.9	3.126		220 - 200	19.4	4.099
	220 - 200	0.7	0.153		200 - 180	6.2	1.190
	180 - 160	2.9	0.512		180 - 160	3.5	0.600
	Total	17.6	3.791		160 - 140	1.8	0.251
14	200 - 180	4.0	0.729		140 - 120	1.8	0.228
	180 - 160	27.5	4.743	Total	45.0	9.116	
	160 - 140	9.7	1.474	18	200 - 180	98.1	18.228
	140 - 120	0.8	0.111		Total	98.1	18.228
Total	42.0	7.056	19	200 - 180	143.3	26.498	
15	200 - 180	328.9		60.474	Total	143.3	26.498
	Total	328.9	60.474				

eP-EAZK-266

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola stavební - truhlářská dílna, Vrbenská 234, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47427 N, 17.97684 E

Building area: 1043 m²

1612 LiDAR points (1.55 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	1007.8	301.6	0.1	7.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	41.1	7.294
200 - 180	966.7	180.178
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1007.8	187.472

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	966.7	180.178
	180 - 160	41.1	7.294
	Total	1007.8	187.472

eP-EAZK-267

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola stavební - administrativní část, Vrbenská 234, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47416 N, 17.97552 E

Building area: 1031 m²

1341 LiDAR points (1.30 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	599.7	300.7	1.7	348.9
1	307.7	307.6	0.3	152.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	7.3	0.972
160 - 140	117.0	17.835
180 - 160	76.2	13.417
200 - 180	707.0	131.172
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	907.5	163.396

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	402.3	73.839	1	200 - 180	304.7	57.332
	180 - 160	73.1	12.875		180 - 160	3.0	0.542
	160 - 140	117.0	17.835	Total	307.7	57.874	
	140 - 120	7.3	0.972				
Total		599.7	105.522				

eP-EAZK-268

Location information

Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola sklářská - domov mládeže, Zašovská 100, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47623 N, 17.98002 E

Building area: 341 m²

615 LiDAR points (1.80 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	49.2	301.4	0.4	285.2
1	220.1	326.1	0.1	310.6
2	18.4	326.6	1.8	298.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	21.8	3.812
200 - 180	265.8	49.677
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	287.6	53.489

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	43.7	8.051
	180 - 160	5.5	0.965
	Total	49.2	9.016
1	200 - 180	203.8	38.205
	180 - 160	16.3	2.847
	Total	220.1	41.052

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	18.4	3.421
	Total	18.4	3.421

eP-EAZK-269

Location information

Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola sklářská - huť, U Skláren 842, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47617 N, 17.97947 E

Building area: 662 m²

1057 LiDAR points (1.60 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	17.5	304.3	30.0	5.0
1	17.5	304.3	29.4	197.6
2	43.7	304.6	41.4	280.3
3	274.2	306.0	34.9	10.1
4	6.5	306.1	46.5	276.9
5	10.0	306.3	47.9	98.8
6	22.6	307.2	30.8	282.8
7	23.1	306.9	32.5	99.8
8	278.4	306.2	34.8	190.0
9	15.3	306.0	44.1	101.9
10	13.3	306.8	45.0	281.8
11	15.5	306.3	48.2	100.8
12	13.7	306.6	44.4	280.7
13	17.6	306.2	48.1	100.5
14	11.3	306.3	46.0	276.5

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	95.7	8.593
120 - 100	200.3	21.361
140 - 120	12.3	1.643
160 - 140	104.3	16.056
180 - 160	81.4	13.560
200 - 180	26.2	5.057
220 - 200	73.6	15.595
240 - 220	186.4	42.070
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	780.2	123.935

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	1.3	0.159	4	160 - 140	1.6	0.244
	120 - 100	9.6	1.008		140 - 120	3.3	0.436
	< 100	6.6	0.548		120 - 100	1.6	0.175
	Total	17.5	1.715		Total	6.5	0.855
1	240 - 220	5.8	1.300	5	180 - 160	2.5	0.419
	220 - 200	5.8	1.212		160 - 140	5.0	0.773
	200 - 180	3.6	0.699		140 - 120	1.3	0.168
	180 - 160	2.2	0.385		120 - 100	0.6	0.066
	Total	17.5	3.596		< 100	0.6	0.059
2	180 - 160	23.1	3.707	Total	10.0	1.485	
	160 - 140	19.4	3.023	6	180 - 160	12.7	2.055
	140 - 120	1.2	0.170		160 - 140	7.2	1.120
	Total	43.7	6.900		140 - 120	0.9	0.124
3	120 - 100	185.6	19.793		120 - 100	1.8	0.205
	< 100	88.5	7.987	Total	22.6	3.503	
	Total	274.2	27.780				

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
7	180 - 160	1.0	0.165	11	180 - 160	13.4	2.274
	160 - 140	20.1	3.016		160 - 140	2.1	0.323
	140 - 120	1.0	0.130		Total	15.5	2.597
	120 - 100	1.0	0.115	12	160 - 140	13.7	2.133
	Total	23.1	3.426		Total	13.7	2.133
8	240 - 220	180.6	40.770	13	180 - 160	8.8	1.478
	220 - 200	67.7	14.383		160 - 140	5.5	0.850
	200 - 180	22.6	4.358		140 - 120	3.3	0.456
	180 - 160	2.5	0.448	Total	17.6	2.785	
	160 - 140	5.0	0.793	14	180 - 160	1.7	0.280
Total	278.4	60.751	160 - 140		9.6	1.474	
9	180 - 160	13.5	2.349	Total	11.3	1.755	
	160 - 140	1.8	0.287				
10	160 - 140	13.3	2.020				
	Total	13.3	2.020				

eP-EAZK-270

Location information

Střední uměleckoprůmyslová škola sklářská - škola, Sklářská 603/8, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47659 N, 17.97944 E

Building area: 999 m²

1430 LiDAR points (1.43 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	34.4	302.8	29.7	9.8
1	60.1	302.8	28.9	190.0
2	154.4	309.9	9.8	280.3
3	144.6	307.9	29.6	10.3
4	247.4	308.1	29.6	190.1
5	156.4	309.9	10.5	100.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	19.0	1.796
120 - 100	59.1	6.735
140 - 120	100.9	12.467
160 - 140	12.3	1.852
180 - 160	59.6	10.376
200 - 180	238.8	44.765
220 - 200	58.4	12.668
240 - 220	249.1	55.786
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	797.3	146.446

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	11.8	1.434	3	140 - 120	89.1	11.033
	120 - 100	22.6	2.622		120 - 100	36.5	4.113
	Total	34.4	4.056		< 100	19.0	1.796
1	240 - 220	1.7	0.373	Total	144.6	16.943	
	220 - 200	58.4	12.668	4	240 - 220	247.4	55.413
	Total	60.1	13.041		Total	247.4	55.413
2	200 - 180	82.5	15.062		5	200 - 180	156.4
	180 - 160	59.6	10.376	Total		156.4	29.703
	160 - 140	12.3	1.852				
	Total	154.4	27.290				

eP-EAZK-271

Location information

Základní škola, mateřská škola a praktická škola, Křížná 782, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47221 N, 17.96526 E

Building area: 969 m²

781 LiDAR points (0.81 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	912.3	301.5	0.3	174.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	912.3	171.990
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	912.3	171.990

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	912.3	171.990
Total		912.3	171.990

eP-EAZK-272

Location information

Dětský domov, Chrástěšovská 65, Vizovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22404 N, 17.85560 E

Building area: 235 m²

347 LiDAR points (1.48 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	75.5	303.2	38.8	309.0
1	10.8	303.2	13.6	308.7
2	99.5	304.1	3.4	50.9
3	33.0	301.1	0.1	109.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	81.1	10.667
160 - 140	8.4	1.261
180 - 160	22.0	3.799
200 - 180	107.2	19.700
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	218.8	35.428

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	75.5	9.919	3	200 - 180	10.1	1.846
	Total	75.5	9.919		180 - 160	17.5	3.020
1	180 - 160	2.2	0.357		160 - 140	4.0	0.603
	160 - 140	4.3	0.659		140 - 120	1.3	0.182
	140 - 120	4.3	0.566	Total	33.0	5.650	
	Total	10.8	1.582				
2	200 - 180	97.1	17.854				
	180 - 160	2.4	0.423				
	Total	99.5	18.276				

eP-EAZK-273

Location information

Střední škola oděvní a služeb, Tyršova 874, Vizovice, Zlínský kraj

49.22388 N, 17.84415 E

Building area: 823 m²

1184 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	795.8	309.2	0.3	264.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	795.8	149.516
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	795.8	149.516

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	795.8	149.516
Total		795.8	149.516

eP-EAZK-274

Location information

Dětský domov a základní škola, 3. května 528, Vizovice, Zlínský kraj

49.21836 N, 17.84973 E

Building area: 444 m²

641 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	84.8	319.2	36.0	80.2
1	142.9	319.2	36.0	349.9
2	15.5	319.4	30.2	76.6
3	80.8	320.1	36.1	169.9
4	60.6	319.5	36.3	260.0
5	47.1	319.2	34.1	260.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	29.9	2.652
120 - 100	113.0	12.174
140 - 120	1.0	0.139
160 - 140	11.0	1.677
180 - 160	133.2	22.400
200 - 180	73.7	13.585
220 - 200	19.3	4.103
240 - 220	50.6	11.424
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	431.7	68.155

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	83.9	14.006	4	200 - 180	26.3	4.783
	160 - 140	0.9	0.138		180 - 160	23.2	3.975
	Total	84.8	14.143		160 - 140	10.1	1.540
			140 - 120		1.0	0.139	
1	120 - 100	113.0	12.174	Total	60.6	10.437	
	< 100	29.9	2.652	5	200 - 180	42.6	7.899
	Total	142.9	14.826		180 - 160	4.5	0.794
			Total		47.1	8.693	
2	180 - 160	15.5	2.596	3	240 - 220	50.6	11.424
	Total	15.5	2.596		220 - 200	19.3	4.103
3					200 - 180	4.8	0.902
					180 - 160	6.0	1.029
	Total	80.8	17.458				

eP-EAZK-275

Location information

Masarykovo gymnázium, střední zdravotnická škola a vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická, nám. Svobody 809, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.33784 N, 17.99429 E

Building area: 1016 m²

1701 LiDAR points (1.67 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	29.4	363.1	44.1	215.7
1	119.9	362.6	36.6	194.6
2	9.0	364.6	44.2	188.3
3	148.4	362.7	43.6	35.5
4	9.3	359.1	13.8	27.9
5	17.2	359.0	13.6	277.2
6	70.7	363.2	44.3	35.7
7	30.2	363.0	43.9	36.4
8	112.9	364.2	44.6	125.2
9	123.7	364.1	44.8	305.4
10	109.9	364.1	44.3	126.2
11	67.0	362.8	43.1	214.2
12	137.4	364.1	44.8	215.4
13	35.1	362.7	44.9	306.2
14	27.2	362.9	13.8	305.8
15	24.6	364.3	37.2	51.6

■ **Energy prediction - Summary**

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	159.8	13.816
120 - 100	261.8	28.814
140 - 120	175.5	22.459
160 - 140	34.6	5.152
180 - 160	27.0	4.574
200 - 180	45.6	8.699
220 - 200	353.8	74.715
240 - 220	14.0	3.136
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1072.1	161.365

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	29.4	6.418	5	180 - 160	3.9	0.643
	Total	29.4	6.418		160 - 140	8.6	1.286
1	240 - 220	5.7	1.259	6	140 - 120	4.7	0.596
	220 - 200	92.5	19.833		Total	17.2	2.525
	200 - 180	14.8	2.831	7	120 - 100	27.9	2.944
	180 - 160	5.7	0.965		< 100	42.9	3.383
	160 - 140	1.1	0.171		Total	70.7	6.328
Total	119.9	25.058	8	120 - 100	30.2	3.365	
2	240 - 220	8.3		1.877	Total	30.2	3.365
	220 - 200	0.8	0.154	9	220 - 200	66.8	13.713
Total	9.0	2.031	200 - 180		19.3	3.714	
3	120 - 100	148.4	16.454		180 - 160	14.9	2.543
	Total	148.4	16.454		160 - 140	7.4	1.090
4	140 - 120	2.7	0.343		140 - 120	4.5	0.574
	120 - 100	4.9	0.535	Total	112.9	21.634	
	< 100	1.6	0.134				
	Total	9.3	1.012				

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
9	140 - 120	113.0	14.309	13	120 - 100	8.2	0.873
	120 - 100	4.6	0.529		< 100	26.8	2.111
	< 100	6.1	0.544		Total	35.1	2.984
	Total	123.7	15.382	14	160 - 140	10.4	1.547
10	220 - 200	102.8	21.292		140 - 120	7.1	0.913
	200 - 180	4.3	0.820		120 - 100	5.8	0.653
	180 - 160	1.4	0.242		< 100	3.9	0.358
	160 - 140	1.4	0.224	Total	27.2	3.470	
11	220 - 200	61.5	13.305	15	140 - 120	24.6	3.349
	200 - 180	1.1	0.211		Total	24.6	3.349
	180 - 160	1.1	0.182	12	200 - 180	6.0	1.124
	160 - 140	1.1	0.165		160 - 140	4.5	0.668
	140 - 120	2.2	0.284		140 - 120	16.6	2.091
Total	67.0	14.148	120 - 100		31.7	3.461	
12	200 - 180	6.0	1.124		< 100	78.5	7.286
	160 - 140	4.5	0.668	Total	137.4	14.629	
	140 - 120	16.6	2.091				
	120 - 100	31.7	3.461				
	< 100	78.5	7.286				

eP-EAZK-276

Location information

Masarykovo gymnázium, střední zdravotnická škola a vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická - část B a C, Tyršova 1069, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.33841 N, 17.99576 E

Building area: 2220 m²

3410 LiDAR points (1.54 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	136.7	351.4	5.8	215.8
1	134.5	354.8	8.5	256.1
2	56.7	359.7	6.7	215.3
3	94.9	360.9	8.9	125.6
4	33.4	360.9	8.6	127.8
5	387.4	360.2	33.7	125.9
6	37.3	362.4	6.4	283.4
7	135.5	354.8	4.0	34.7
8	131.8	354.8	4.0	215.9
9	70.7	354.8	11.8	110.0
10	168.2	360.3	34.4	305.6
11	26.9	361.5	24.7	233.4
12	11.8	361.6	33.2	215.5
13	25.7	361.5	22.9	17.3
14	20.3	360.1	34.1	274.7
15	104.9	359.9	37.2	302.3

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	76.5	6.435
120 - 100	64.6	7.213
140 - 120	165.5	21.983
160 - 140	104.1	15.187
180 - 160	278.7	48.140
200 - 180	600.2	114.117
220 - 200	287.3	59.133
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1577.0	272.208

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	68.3	12.710	3	200 - 180	94.9	18.631
	180 - 160	48.6	8.439		Total	94.9	18.631
	160 - 140	15.2	2.278	4	200 - 180	33.4	6.560
	140 - 120	4.6	0.615		Total	33.4	6.560
	Total	136.7	24.042		5	220 - 200	248.5
1	200 - 180	93.0	17.729	200 - 180		62.1	11.658
	180 - 160	23.3	3.996	180 - 160		65.8	11.455
	160 - 140	8.3	1.261	160 - 140		3.7	0.566
	140 - 120	5.0	0.674	120 - 100		7.3	0.853
	120 - 100	5.0	0.580	Total	387.4	75.507	
Total	134.5	24.239	6	200 - 180	37.3	6.914	
2	200 - 180	9.1		1.650	Total	37.3	6.914
	180 - 160	38.5	6.565	7	200 - 180	70.1	12.701
	160 - 140	5.3	0.805		180 - 160	46.2	8.022
	140 - 120	1.5	0.191		160 - 140	6.4	0.950
	120 - 100	0.8	0.086		140 - 120	6.4	0.833
	< 100	1.5	0.139		120 - 100	6.4	0.696
Total	56.7	9.437	Total	135.5	23.201		

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
8	200 - 180	131.8	25.563	12	220 - 200	11.8	2.583
Total		131.8	25.563	Total		11.8	2.583
9	180 - 160	36.0	6.144	13	160 - 140	0.5	0.066
	160 - 140	11.2	1.701		140 - 120	17.8	2.405
	140 - 120	7.4	0.962		120 - 100	3.7	0.419
	120 - 100	7.4	0.813		< 100	3.7	0.331
	< 100	8.7	0.791	Total		25.7	3.220
Total		70.7	10.411	14	180 - 160	20.3	3.518
10	160 - 140	46.9	6.601	Total		20.3	3.518
	140 - 120	68.1	9.110	15	160 - 140	6.8	0.961
	120 - 100	19.2	2.112		140 - 120	54.7	7.194
	< 100	34.1	2.878		120 - 100	14.8	1.653
Total		168.2	20.702		< 100	28.5	2.295
11	220 - 200	26.9	5.575	Total		104.9	12.103
Total		26.9	5.575				

eP-EAZK-277

Location information

Masarykovo gymnázium, střední zdravotnická škola a vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická - část A, Tyršova 1069, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.33880 N, 17.99583 E

Building area: 1099 m²

1566 LiDAR points (1.42 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	49.0	355.8	4.3	135.8
1	19.6	354.4	8.3	246.2
2	12.0	354.4	5.8	127.0
3	89.0	355.3	35.2	36.3
4	225.3	357.1	32.4	305.4
5	268.3	356.7	32.5	35.6
6	300.2	356.9	19.0	215.2
7	146.8	356.6	38.5	212.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	76.5	6.446
120 - 100	53.0	5.861
140 - 120	331.4	42.731
160 - 140	292.0	42.743
180 - 160	128.1	21.555
200 - 180	96.8	17.934
220 - 200	99.3	21.368
240 - 220	33.1	7.289
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1110.2	165.926

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	34.9	5.797	5	140 - 120	267.6	34.557
	160 - 140	10.0	1.521		120 - 100	0.7	0.085
	140 - 120	4.1	0.569		Total	268.3	34.642
	Total	49.0	7.887	6	200 - 180	83.1	15.309
1	200 - 180	0.6	0.114		180 - 160	79.3	13.397
	180 - 160	7.6	1.282		160 - 140	52.9	8.135
	160 - 140	6.3	0.946		140 - 120	24.5	3.212
	140 - 120	3.8	0.498		120 - 100	49.1	5.415
	120 - 100	1.3	0.147		< 100	11.3	1.074
Total	19.6	2.987	Total	300.2	46.542		
2	200 - 180	0.6	0.114	7	240 - 220	33.1	7.289
	180 - 160	5.7	0.967		220 - 200	99.3	21.368
	160 - 140	1.9	0.286		200 - 180	12.5	2.398
	140 - 120	3.8	0.484		180 - 160	0.6	0.112
	Total	12.0	1.852		160 - 140	1.2	0.195
3	140 - 120	23.9	2.928	Total	146.8	31.360	
	< 100	65.1	5.372	4	160 - 140	219.7	31.661
	Total	89.0	8.300		140 - 120	3.8	0.482
4	160 - 140	219.7	31.661		120 - 100	1.9	0.214
	140 - 120	3.8	0.482		Total	225.3	32.357
	120 - 100	1.9	0.214				

eP-EAZK-278

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola strojnická, Pod Strání 1776, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.33562 N, 18.00133 E

Building area: 3663 m²

4750 LiDAR points (1.30 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	116.0	353.3	2.8	279.4
1	121.2	353.3	2.2	271.2
2	480.2	356.1	3.1	7.6
3	879.1	356.7	1.3	182.7
4	824.4	358.8	0.1	253.0
5	841.4	367.4	1.3	96.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	1.3	0.133
120 - 100	9.7	1.077
140 - 120	45.2	6.068
160 - 140	95.5	14.455
180 - 160	271.4	47.541
200 - 180	2839.1	531.291
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	3262.3	600.565

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	59.3	10.210	3	200 - 180	782.1	146.723
	160 - 140	33.7	5.098		180 - 160	32.3	5.491
	140 - 120	14.8	1.908		160 - 140	38.8	5.865
	120 - 100	6.7	0.733		140 - 120	25.9	3.544
	< 100	1.3	0.133		Total	879.1	161.622
	Total	116.0	18.083		4	200 - 180	824.4
1	200 - 180	58.4	10.801	Total	824.4	154.693	
	180 - 160	41.9	7.325	5	200 - 180	841.4	158.602
	160 - 140	13.5	2.065		Total	841.4	158.602
	140 - 120	4.5	0.616				
	120 - 100	3.0	0.343				
	Total	121.2	21.151				
2	200 - 180	332.8	60.472				
	180 - 160	137.9	24.515				
	160 - 140	9.5	1.427				
Total	480.2	86.414					

eP-EAZK-279

Location information

Základní a mateřská škola, Turkmenská 1612, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.33218 N, 18.00149 E

Building area: 1451 m²

1798 LiDAR points (1.24 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	133.7	349.4	1.9	3.7
1	250.3	352.8	1.4	9.7
2	12.3	354.0	11.7	268.0
3	294.3	354.8	0.0	340.1
4	24.1	359.5	2.3	4.7
5	343.8	360.2	0.4	194.3
6	270.8	361.9	2.7	9.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	57.1	5.022
120 - 100	52.0	5.764
140 - 120	54.9	7.092
160 - 140	73.2	10.996
180 - 160	235.4	40.810
200 - 180	856.8	158.655
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1329.3	228.339

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	11.8	1.722	4	180 - 160	16.9	2.880
	140 - 120	31.4	4.042		160 - 140	4.8	0.745
	120 - 100	37.3	4.068		140 - 120	1.6	0.210
	< 100	53.1	4.643		120 - 100	0.8	0.093
	Total	133.7	14.475		Total	24.1	3.928
1	200 - 180	102.3	18.750	5	200 - 180	332.2	62.554
	180 - 160	113.1	19.522		180 - 160	7.7	1.314
	160 - 140	26.9	4.064		160 - 140	3.9	0.562
	140 - 120	8.1	1.104		Total	343.8	64.430
	Total	250.3	43.439	6	200 - 180	267.5	48.993
2	200 - 180	4.3	0.794		180 - 160	3.3	0.583
	180 - 160	2.9	0.497		Total	270.8	49.576
	160 - 140	2.9	0.437				
	140 - 120	0.7	0.089				
	120 - 100	0.7	0.080				
	< 100	0.7	0.071				
Total	12.3	1.969					
3	200 - 180	150.4	27.564				
	180 - 160	91.6	16.013				
	160 - 140	22.9	3.466				
	140 - 120	13.1	1.649				
	120 - 100	13.1	1.523				
	< 100	3.3	0.307				
Total	294.3	50.522					

eP-EAZK-280

Location information

Základní umělecká škola - hlavní budova, Podsedky 285, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.34167 N, 17.99617 E

Building area: 808 m²

1161 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	23.7	382.9	18.8	315.5
1	59.7	383.2	17.8	45.2
2	28.9	383.4	17.9	231.8
3	44.7	383.4	20.0	317.0
4	172.4	383.4	18.8	136.7
5	78.1	383.3	18.3	317.7
6	155.5	383.9	19.1	45.4
7	170.3	383.9	17.4	227.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	301.9	48.024
180 - 160	59.7	9.662
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	371.5	77.514
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	733.1	135.200

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	23.7	3.766	4	220 - 200	172.4	36.260
Total		23.7	3.766	Total		172.4	36.260
1	180 - 160	59.7	9.662	5	160 - 140	78.1	12.428
Total		59.7	9.662	Total		78.1	12.428
2	220 - 200	28.9	5.941	6	160 - 140	155.5	24.843
Total		28.9	5.941	Total		155.5	24.843
3	160 - 140	44.7	6.986	7	220 - 200	170.3	35.312
Total		44.7	6.986	Total		170.3	35.312

eP-EAZK-281

Location information

Základní umělecká škola - přístavek, Podsedky 285, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.34198 N, 17.99633 E

Building area: 275 m²

410 LiDAR points (1.49 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	386.9	373.4	55.7	119.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	386.9	74.999
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	386.9	74.999

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	386.9	74.999
Total		386.9	74.999

eP-EAZK-282, eP-EAZK-283

Location information

Gymnázium, Lesní čtvrť III 1364, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21825 N, 17.69236 E

Building area: 1990 m²

2713 LiDAR points (1.36 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	69.9	334.0	0.2	204.6
1	25.9	341.9	12.4	322.4
2	13.9	334.7	2.2	181.6
3	211.9	345.3	5.2	28.7
4	23.1	343.9	10.4	116.1
5	588.5	341.8	5.1	29.6
6	68.2	334.6	0.2	314.4
7	721.9	341.8	5.0	27.4
8	21.9	341.8	8.1	28.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	27.3	2.454
120 - 100	58.1	6.402
140 - 120	48.2	6.210
160 - 140	60.7	9.206
180 - 160	1527.8	272.898
200 - 180	23.1	4.503
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1745.2	301.674

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	11.1	1.809	6	160 - 140	3.5	0.500
	160 - 140	26.2	3.929		140 - 120	13.9	1.778
	140 - 120	19.1	2.473		120 - 100	37.0	4.098
	120 - 100	12.7	1.404		< 100	13.9	1.291
	< 100	0.8	0.078		Total	68.2	7.667
	Total	69.9	9.693		7	180 - 160	690.3
1	180 - 160	22.4	3.727	160 - 140		18.0	2.829
	160 - 140	2.1	0.320	140 - 120		9.0	1.127
	140 - 120	1.4	0.184	120 - 100		4.5	0.484
Total	25.9	4.230	Total	721.9	127.789		
2	120 - 100	1.9	0.197	8	180 - 160	11.9	1.992
	< 100	12.0	1.026		160 - 140	5.3	0.805
Total	13.9	1.223	140 - 120		2.0	0.263	
3	180 - 160	211.9	38.007		120 - 100	2.0	0.218
	Total	211.9	38.007	< 100	0.7	0.060	
4	200 - 180	23.1	4.503	Total	21.9	3.338	
	Total	23.1	4.503	5	180 - 160	580.1	104.016
5	160 - 140	5.6	0.823		160 - 140	5.6	0.823
	140 - 120	2.8	0.386		140 - 120	2.8	0.386
	Total	588.5	105.225		Total	588.5	105.225

eP-EAZK-284

Location information

Dětský domov, Lazy I 3689, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21892 N, 17.67618 E

Building area: 326 m²

421 LiDAR points (1.29 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	30.8	311.3	28.1	192.9
1	10.7	306.9	11.3	309.5
2	13.8	308.6	1.4	141.1
3	6.6	307.9	23.3	14.2
4	14.5	308.6	28.7	280.6
5	29.6	311.1	27.9	13.5
6	57.3	311.3	28.7	283.6
7	60.2	311.8	30.4	104.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	7.9	0.740
120 - 100	12.8	1.402
140 - 120	51.4	6.680
160 - 140	112.6	17.043
180 - 160	35.9	6.080
200 - 180	3.1	0.569
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	223.7	32.516

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	3.1	0.569	5	140 - 120	26.4	3.350
	180 - 160	19.1	3.297		120 - 100	3.2	0.373
	160 - 140	8.6	1.293		Total	29.6	3.723
	Total	30.8	5.159	6	180 - 160	3.1	0.502
1	120 - 100	5.7	0.589		160 - 140	47.2	7.137
	< 100	5.1	0.480		140 - 120	7.0	0.902
	Total	10.7	1.070		Total	57.3	8.541
2	180 - 160	1.9	0.311	7	180 - 160	10.4	1.736
	160 - 140	6.9	1.044		160 - 140	42.5	6.462
	140 - 120	1.9	0.243		140 - 120	7.3	0.987
	120 - 100	2.5	0.276		Total	60.2	9.185
	< 100	0.6	0.061	3	140 - 120	6.6	0.903
	Total	13.8	1.936		Total	6.6	0.903
4	180 - 160	1.5	0.234	4	180 - 160	1.5	0.234
	160 - 140	7.3	1.107		160 - 140	7.3	1.107
	140 - 120	2.2	0.295		140 - 120	2.2	0.295
	120 - 100	1.5	0.165		120 - 100	1.5	0.165
	< 100	2.2	0.199		< 100	2.2	0.199
	Total	14.5	2.000		Total	14.5	2.000

eP-EAZK-285

Location information

Dětský domov, Mateřská škola, Základní škola a Praktická škola - speciálně pedagogické centrum, Lazy VI 3696, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21979 N, 17.68198 E

Building area: 113 m²

191 LiDAR points (1.69 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	105.9	314.9	0.6	170.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	4.0	0.719
200 - 180	101.8	19.025
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	105.9	19.744

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	101.8	19.025
	180 - 160	4.0	0.719
	Total	105.9	19.744

eP-EAZK-286, eP-EAZK-287

Location information

Dětský domov, Mateřská škola, Základní škola a Praktická škola, Lazy VI 3695, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21968 N, 17.68123 E

Building area: 716 m²

917 LiDAR points (1.28 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	614.5	318.7	0.6	353.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	12.9	2.217
200 - 180	601.5	111.495
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	614.5	113.712

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	601.5	111.495
	180 - 160	12.9	2.217
	Total	614.5	113.712

eP-EAZK-288

Location information

Obchodní akademie Tomáše Bati a Vyšší odborná škola ekonomická, nám. T. G. Masaryka 3669, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22204 N, 17.66506 E

Building area: 1263 m²

1824 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	95.6	243.8	0.5	45.7
1	17.2	255.2	1.5	227.8
2	771.8	257.5	0.3	206.5
3	217.9	259.4	0.1	114.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.6	0.060
120 - 100	2.5	0.279
140 - 120	49.7	6.564
160 - 140	53.5	7.803
180 - 160	20.5	3.455
200 - 180	975.5	183.791
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1102.5	201.950

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	50.4	7.302	2	200 - 180	757.6	142.819
	140 - 120	45.2	5.988		180 - 160	14.2	2.407
	Total	95.6	13.290		Total	771.8	145.226
1	180 - 160	6.4	1.048	3	200 - 180	217.9	40.972
	160 - 140	3.2	0.501		Total	217.9	40.972
	140 - 120	4.5	0.575				
	120 - 100	2.5	0.279				
	< 100	0.6	0.060				
Total	17.2	2.462					

eP-EAZK-289

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum odborné přípravy, Nad Ovčímou IV 2528, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21997 N, 17.66200 E

Building area: 1530 m²

1711 LiDAR points (1.12 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	1481.9	278.2	0.1	98.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	1481.9	278.527
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1481.9	278.527

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	1481.9	278.527
Total		1481.9	278.527

eP-EAZK-290

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum odborné přípravy, Růmy 1548, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21988 N, 17.67015 E

Building area: 365 m²

691 LiDAR points (1.89 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	176.5	272.8	19.5	346.8
1	199.8	272.8	19.0	166.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	9.7	0.901
120 - 100	30.8	3.447
140 - 120	47.0	6.163
160 - 140	93.0	13.387
180 - 160	5.8	1.011
200 - 180	5.8	1.131
220 - 200	184.3	39.403
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	376.3	65.443

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	89.1	12.774	1	220 - 200	184.3	39.403
	140 - 120	47.0	6.163		200 - 180	5.8	1.131
	120 - 100	30.8	3.447		180 - 160	5.8	1.011
	< 100	9.7	0.901		160 - 140	3.9	0.613
	Total	176.5	23.285		Total	199.8	42.158

eP-EAZK-291

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum odborné přípravy, Růmy 4050, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21953 N, 17.66843 E

Building area: 875 m²

987 LiDAR points (1.13 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	506.5	281.2	0.2	7.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	99.4	17.369
200 - 180	407.1	75.315
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	506.5	92.684

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	407.1	75.315
	180 - 160	99.4	17.369
	Total	506.5	92.684

eP-EAZK-292, eP-EAZK-294

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická, nám. T. G. Masaryka 2700, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21965 N, 17.66405 E

Building area: 1520 m²

1560 LiDAR points (1.03 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	1490.7	282.4	0.1	0.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	44.7	6.089
160 - 140	74.5	10.957
180 - 160	134.2	23.371
200 - 180	1237.3	230.530
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1490.7	270.947

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	1237.3	230.530
	180 - 160	134.2	23.371
	160 - 140	74.5	10.957
	140 - 120	44.7	6.089
Total		1490.7	270.947

eP-EAZK-293

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola polytechnická - Centrum odborné přípravy, Růmy 596, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21962 N, 17.67030 E

Building area: 708 m²

1219 LiDAR points (1.72 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	349.4	276.6	12.5	346.2
1	365.4	276.7	12.2	167.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	3.0	0.388
160 - 140	144.6	22.208
180 - 160	201.8	32.747
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	365.4	76.420
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	714.8	131.764

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	201.8	32.747	1	220 - 200	365.4	76.420
	160 - 140	144.6	22.208		Total		365.4
	140 - 120	3.0	0.388				
Total		349.4	55.343				

eP-EAZK-295

Location information

Střední škola gastronomie a obchodu, Univerzitní 3015, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22263 N, 17.66750 E

Building area: 1139 m²

930 LiDAR points (0.82 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	213.8	247.5	0.4	133.8
1	541.3	256.1	0.1	281.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	19.1	3.235
200 - 180	735.9	137.939
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	755.0	141.174

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	207.2	38.817	1	200 - 180	528.7	99.122
	180 - 160	6.5	1.116		180 - 160	12.6	2.119
	Total	213.8	39.933		Total	541.3	101.241

eP-EAZK-296

Location information

Střední průmyslová škola, třída Tomáše Bati 4187, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22019 N, 17.65176 E

Building area: 5283 m²

6007 LiDAR points (1.14 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	564.4	247.4	0.2	347.1
1	14.8	249.9	1.5	301.1
2	138.2	241.5	0.5	83.0
3	13.6	239.5	13.1	83.7
4	678.0	242.5	3.3	353.9
5	631.9	242.5	3.3	174.1
6	2460.0	244.0	0.0	163.1
7	132.9	244.9	0.2	198.7
8	384.8	240.0	0.4	321.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	5.1	0.448
120 - 100	15.4	1.592
140 - 120	20.5	2.786
160 - 140	78.5	12.046
180 - 160	430.5	73.875
200 - 180	4468.6	839.142
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	5018.6	929.890

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	542.3	101.414
	180 - 160	22.1	3.714
	Total	564.4	105.129
1	200 - 180	14.8	2.754
	Total	14.8	2.754
2	200 - 180	51.5	9.442
	180 - 160	73.1	12.722
	160 - 140	13.5	2.128
	Total	138.2	24.292
3	160 - 140	13.6	2.119
	Total	13.6	2.119
4	200 - 180	549.2	99.780
	180 - 160	128.8	22.230
	Total	678.0	122.010

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
5	200 - 180	631.9	122.826
	Total	631.9	122.826
6	200 - 180	2375.2	446.383
	180 - 160	84.8	14.242
	Total	2460.0	460.624
7	200 - 180	129.4	24.336
	180 - 160	3.5	0.633
	Total	132.9	24.969
8	200 - 180	174.5	32.208
	180 - 160	118.0	20.333
	160 - 140	51.3	7.800
	140 - 120	20.5	2.786
	120 - 100	15.4	1.592
< 100	5.1	0.448	
Total	384.8	65.167	

eP-EAZK-297

Location information

Střední škola nábytkářská a obchodní - škola, Holešovská 394, Bystřice pod Hostýnem, Zlínský kraj

49.39890 N, 17.66405 E

Building area: 390 m²

616 LiDAR points (1.58 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	42.5	317.2	36.3	325.2
1	66.1	317.9	30.2	235.9
2	61.5	318.1	36.1	325.5
3	30.0	317.1	34.9	235.0
4	106.1	317.6	35.9	145.2
5	91.4	317.5	30.0	56.0
6	14.7	318.6	6.5	57.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	25.2	2.373
120 - 100	88.8	10.097
140 - 120	38.7	4.816
160 - 140	103.3	15.464
180 - 160	23.7	4.075
200 - 180	91.4	17.543
220 - 200	41.3	8.475
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	412.3	62.843

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	22.7	2.727	4	220 - 200	25.6	5.300
	120 - 100	19.8	2.348		200 - 180	42.2	8.101
	Total	42.5	5.074		180 - 160	12.8	2.180
1	220 - 200	15.7	3.175		160 - 140	8.9	1.340
	200 - 180	46.1	8.888	140 - 120	5.1	0.672	
	180 - 160	1.0	0.176	120 - 100	5.1	0.572	
	140 - 120	3.1	0.415	< 100	6.4	0.599	
	Total	66.1	12.655	Total	106.1	18.764	
2	140 - 120	1.0	0.115	5	160 - 140	90.1	13.483
	120 - 100	48.1	5.404		140 - 120	1.3	0.174
	< 100	12.5	1.184	Total	91.4	13.657	
Total	61.5	6.703	6	200 - 180	3.1	0.554	
3	160 - 140	2.4		0.367	180 - 160	9.8	1.718
	140 - 120	5.5		0.712	160 - 140	1.8	0.274
	120 - 100	15.8		1.774	Total	14.7	2.546
	< 100	6.3	0.590				
Total	30.0	3.443					

eP-EAZK-298

Location information

Střední škola nábytkářská a obchodní - internát, Mlýnská 1425, Bystřice pod Hostýnem, Zlínský kraj

49.39852 N, 17.66651 E

Building area: 1132 m²

1625 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	177.6	314.3	2.2	293.2
1	95.8	314.8	3.6	188.7
2	351.6	315.9	3.4	201.7
3	11.1	318.5	2.8	209.6
4	458.9	320.7	0.7	290.7
5	5.1	323.1	0.6	106.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	3.2	0.357
140 - 120	16.9	2.237
160 - 140	36.9	5.589
180 - 160	119.5	20.519
200 - 180	923.7	173.223
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1100.1	201.925

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	160.6	29.717
	180 - 160	17.0	3.044
	Total	177.6	32.761
1	180 - 160	43.2	7.173
	160 - 140	32.7	4.917
	140 - 120	16.9	2.237
	120 - 100	3.2	0.357
Total	95.8	14.684	
2	200 - 180	288.1	54.351
	180 - 160	59.3	10.302
	160 - 140	4.2	0.672
	Total	351.6	65.324

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	200 - 180	11.1	2.107
	Total	11.1	2.107
4	200 - 180	458.9	86.089
	Total	458.9	86.089
5	200 - 180	5.1	0.960
	Total	5.1	0.960

eP-EAZK-299, eP-EAZK-303, eP-EAZK-304

Location information

Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární, Štěchovice 1315/7a, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29901 N, 17.38301 E

Building area: 473 m²

447 LiDAR points (0.94 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	46.9	222.4	4.6	245.3
1	324.4	222.5	39.6	63.5
2	200.2	223.7	39.9	243.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	6.4	0.842
160 - 140	353.0	51.724
180 - 160	30.5	5.132
200 - 180	181.6	35.434
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	571.5	93.132

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	41.8	7.843	2	200 - 180	139.8	27.591
	180 - 160	5.1	0.896		180 - 160	25.4	4.236
	Total	46.9	8.739		160 - 140	28.6	4.268
1	160 - 140	324.4	47.456		140 - 120	6.4	0.842
	Total	324.4	47.456	Total	200.2	36.937	

eP-EAZK-300, eP-EAZK-302

Location information

Taufertova střední odborná škola veterinární, Štěchovice 1321/7, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29925 N, 17.38330 E

Building area: 300 m²

295 LiDAR points (0.98 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	17.1	221.3	33.9	331.8
1	30.9	221.2	38.9	62.5
2	30.7	221.6	39.7	63.0
3	103.1	220.3	39.9	243.6
4	72.7	220.5	39.1	241.9
5	15.7	221.2	33.1	157.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	3.1	0.362
140 - 120	15.2	1.865
160 - 140	61.6	8.957
180 - 160	7.3	1.249
200 - 180	169.5	33.272
220 - 200	10.3	2.124
240 - 220	3.0	0.667
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	270.1	48.497

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	14.0	1.688	4	220 - 200	4.3	0.870
	120 - 100	3.1	0.362		200 - 180	65.1	12.778
	Total	17.1	2.050		180 - 160	3.3	0.549
1	160 - 140	30.9	4.499	Total	72.7	14.197	
	Total	30.9	4.499	5	240 - 220	3.0	0.667
2	160 - 140	30.7	4.459		220 - 200	6.0	1.254
	Total	30.7	4.459		200 - 180	5.2	1.003
3	200 - 180	99.2	19.491		180 - 160	1.5	0.260
	180 - 160	2.6	0.440	Total	15.7	3.185	
	140 - 120	1.3	0.178				
	Total	103.1	20.108				

eP-EAZK-301

Location information

Taufeřova středn odborn škola veterinrn - tlocvina, Štchovice 1321/7, Kromřž, Zlinsk kraj

49.29887 N, 17.38344 E

Building area: 1052 m²

867 LiDAR points (0.82 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	15.0	215.4	4.0	15.6
1	181.4	218.7	3.3	63.0
2	221.8	218.1	11.8	243.3
3	135.0	216.9	21.7	62.6
4	97.4	213.2	36.8	62.8
5	141.7	214.5	33.1	243.9
6	64.9	210.4	44.7	243.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	1.5	0.136
120 - 100	5.3	0.555
140 - 120	25.6	3.406
160 - 140	80.1	11.651
180 - 160	142.4	23.728
200 - 180	513.6	97.721
220 - 200	88.7	17.847
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	857.2	155.044

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	1.5	0.219	4	160 - 140	78.6	11.432
	140 - 120	6.8	0.844		140 - 120	18.8	2.561
	120 - 100	5.3	0.555	Total	97.4	13.993	
	< 100	1.5	0.136	5	220 - 200	88.7	17.847
	Total	15.0	1.755		200 - 180	52.9	10.407
			Total		141.7	28.254	
1	200 - 180	181.4	33.598	6	200 - 180	59.7	11.315
	Total	181.4	33.598		180 - 160	5.2	0.900
2	200 - 180	219.6	42.401		Total	64.9	12.214
	180 - 160	2.2	0.390				
	Total	221.8	42.791				
3	180 - 160	135.0	22.438				
	Total	135.0	22.438				

eP-EAZK-305, eP-EAZK-306

Location information

Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární, Koperníkova 1435, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30025 N, 17.37997 E

Building area: 539 m²

483 LiDAR points (0.90 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	10.4	223.7	14.8	38.6
1	13.7	223.9	13.8	70.7
2	36.9	223.8	10.1	328.3
3	34.0	223.4	23.7	61.8
4	51.6	222.8	22.8	68.9
5	173.5	223.3	27.6	242.2
6	44.6	222.8	29.0	151.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	146.4	24.741
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	173.5	35.200
240 - 220	44.6	9.913
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	364.6	69.855

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	10.4	1.705	4	180 - 160	51.6	8.733
Total		10.4	1.705	Total		51.6	8.733
1	180 - 160	13.7	2.443	5	220 - 200	173.5	35.200
Total		13.7	2.443	Total		173.5	35.200
2	180 - 160	36.9	6.307	6	240 - 220	44.6	9.913
Total		36.9	6.307	Total		44.6	9.913
3	180 - 160	34.0	5.552				
Total		34.0	5.552				

eP-EAZK-307, eP-EAZK-309

Location information

Taufertova střední odborná škola veterinární, Koperníkova 1429/22, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30108 N, 17.37990 E

Building area: 428 m²

720 LiDAR points (1.68 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	127.1	213.8	28.5	150.5
1	133.7	213.8	28.0	330.9
2	92.5	214.4	27.6	150.9
3	103.4	214.4	28.0	330.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	50.9	4.386
120 - 100	59.0	6.494
140 - 120	127.2	16.415
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	1.5	0.294
220 - 200	202.4	43.678
240 - 220	15.8	3.489
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	456.7	74.756

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	240 - 220	10.3	2.289
	220 - 200	115.3	24.895
	200 - 180	1.5	0.294
	Total	127.1	27.478
1	140 - 120	61.5	7.961
	120 - 100	33.4	3.670
	< 100	38.8	3.256
	Total	133.7	14.888

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	240 - 220	5.4	1.200
	220 - 200	87.1	18.782
	Total	92.5	19.983
3	140 - 120	65.7	8.454
	120 - 100	25.5	2.824
	< 100	12.2	1.129
	Total	103.4	12.407

eP-EAZK-308

Location information

Tauferova střední odborná škola veterinární - stáje, Koperníkova 1429/22, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30067 N, 17.38030 E

Building area: 402 m²

584 LiDAR points (1.45 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	139.9	210.9	30.5	330.6
1	152.3	211.3	28.2	150.8
2	56.1	212.0	29.4	330.5
3	65.0	212.3	28.7	151.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	78.9	6.660
120 - 100	62.8	6.894
140 - 120	54.3	6.831
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	1.8	0.297
200 - 180	3.5	0.681
220 - 200	63.9	13.777
240 - 220	148.1	32.800
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	413.3	67.941

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	23.8	3.007	3	240 - 220	2.6	0.581
	120 - 100	37.2	4.040		220 - 200	57.1	12.299
	< 100	78.9	6.660		200 - 180	3.5	0.681
	Total	139.9	13.707		180 - 160	1.8	0.297
1	240 - 220	145.5	32.219		Total	65.0	13.858
2	220 - 200	6.8	1.479				
	140 - 120	30.5	3.825				
	120 - 100	25.6	2.854				
Total	56.1	6.679					

eP-EAZK-310

Location information

Taufertova střední odborná škola veterinární - škola, Koperníkova 1429/22, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.30062 N, 17.37958 E

Building area: 436 m²

598 LiDAR points (1.37 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	46.1	222.8	29.0	150.6
1	52.4	222.8	29.2	330.2
2	32.1	224.0	29.3	60.0
3	30.1	224.0	29.6	61.7
4	9.0	222.7	29.0	335.0
5	10.2	222.4	30.4	60.7
6	150.3	223.2	29.1	240.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	6.0	0.541
120 - 100	4.3	0.465
140 - 120	61.4	7.996
160 - 140	62.2	9.547
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	1.5	0.296
220 - 200	148.8	30.363
240 - 220	46.1	10.215
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	330.2	59.424

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	240 - 220	46.1	10.215	4	140 - 120	3.9	0.474
	Total	46.1	10.215		120 - 100	2.6	0.283
1	140 - 120	52.4	6.842	5	< 100	2.6	0.228
	Total	52.4	6.842		Total	9.0	0.984
2	160 - 140	22.8	3.466	6	220 - 200	148.8	30.363
	140 - 120	4.2	0.570		200 - 180	1.5	0.296
	120 - 100	1.7	0.183	Total	150.3	30.659	
	< 100	3.4	0.313				
	Total	32.1	4.532				
3	160 - 140	29.2	4.533				
	140 - 120	0.9	0.110				
	Total	30.1	4.643				

eP-EAZK-311

Location information

Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel - domov mládeže 2, Školní 1610, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46402 N, 18.12761 E

Building area: 1307 m²

1443 LiDAR points (1.10 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	1157.7	399.9	0.1	25.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	5.7	0.669
140 - 120	17.2	2.372
160 - 140	28.7	4.289
180 - 160	34.4	6.118
200 - 180	1071.8	200.594
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1157.7	214.042

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	1071.8	200.594
	180 - 160	34.4	6.118
	160 - 140	28.7	4.289
	140 - 120	17.2	2.372
	120 - 100	5.7	0.669
	Total	1157.7	214.042

eP-EAZK-312

Location information

Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel - praktická výuka, Zemědělská 1077, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46105 N, 18.13314 E

Building area: 430 m²

630 LiDAR points (1.46 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	93.6	378.3	1.9	3.4
1	297.5	397.4	0.4	212.6
2	23.9	400.2	1.5	14.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	8.1	0.759
120 - 100	20.6	2.323
140 - 120	34.1	4.480
160 - 140	50.6	7.603
180 - 160	32.1	5.480
200 - 180	269.6	50.377
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	415.0	71.023

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	1.0	0.161
	160 - 140	40.3	5.985
	140 - 120	27.2	3.583
	120 - 100	17.1	1.909
	< 100	8.1	0.759
Total		93.6	12.398
1	200 - 180	245.6	45.941
	180 - 160	31.1	5.319
	160 - 140	10.4	1.618
	140 - 120	6.9	0.897
	120 - 100	3.5	0.414
Total		297.5	54.189

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	23.9	4.436
Total		23.9	4.436

eP-EAZK-313

Location information

Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel - teoretická výuka, Školní 1698, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46461 N, 18.12632 E

Building area: 1337 m²

1248 LiDAR points (0.93 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	446.3	386.2	0.4	22.2
1	703.9	396.2	0.2	9.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	49.8	7.480
180 - 160	182.8	31.978
200 - 180	917.6	170.972
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1150.2	210.430

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	220.5	40.294	1	200 - 180	697.1	130.677
	180 - 160	182.8	31.978		160 - 140	6.8	1.004
	160 - 140	43.0	6.476		Total	703.9	131.681
	Total	446.3	78.749				

eP-EAZK-314

Location information

Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel - domov mládeže 1, Svazarmovská 1508, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46439 N, 18.12900 E

Building area: 404 m²

581 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	390.4	396.2	0.2	339.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	390.4	73.285
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	390.4	73.285

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	390.4	73.285
Total		390.4	73.285

eP-EAZK-315

Location information

Střední škola informatiky, elektrotechniky a řemesel, 1. máje 1220, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46109 N, 18.13092 E

Building area: 438 m²

553 LiDAR points (1.26 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	386.8	400.2	0.1	175.8
1	12.4	402.8	1.0	285.9
2	28.2	403.2	2.7	269.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	7.9	1.213
180 - 160	67.1	11.516
200 - 180	352.3	65.950
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	427.3	78.679

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	311.8	58.323
	180 - 160	67.1	11.516
	160 - 140	7.9	1.213
	Total	386.8	71.053
1	200 - 180	12.4	2.322
	Total	12.4	2.322

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	200 - 180	28.2	5.305
	Total	28.2	5.305

eP-EAZK-316

Location information

Gymnázium - hlavní budova, Komenského 60, Valašské Klobouky, Zlínský kraj

49.14025 N, 18.00459 E

Building area: 1602 m²

2306 LiDAR points (1.44 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	42.0	428.7	46.3	34.0
1	55.5	428.0	47.0	303.2
2	108.9	427.9	46.5	213.9
3	51.0	417.6	28.8	295.9
4	122.2	417.5	43.1	206.4
5	44.0	418.1	44.5	26.6
6	150.4	427.3	46.5	303.6
7	71.3	426.8	44.2	123.8
8	7.8	429.1	44.2	206.4
9	46.6	426.8	41.0	26.2
10	20.2	429.6	44.6	206.1
11	67.5	428.2	42.8	26.2
12	126.8	426.3	44.6	298.3
13	15.9	425.6	36.4	120.7
14	42.4	425.1	1.2	167.3
15	20.0	427.8	42.9	297.6
16	35.4	427.3	42.0	27.4
17	105.6	428.4	44.4	296.8
18	170.0	426.6	39.8	116.9
19	14.4	427.7	45.8	296.3
20	19.4	425.9	38.5	22.2
21	7.4	425.4	35.0	293.9

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	154.1	12.487
120 - 100	238.6	25.404
140 - 120	351.7	46.474
160 - 140	54.3	7.880
180 - 160	44.0	7.637
200 - 180	145.2	28.385
220 - 200	334.8	70.330
240 - 220	22.1	4.907
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1344.8	203.504

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	120 - 100	36.3	3.815	6	140 - 120	53.0	6.603	
	< 100	5.7	0.467		120 - 100	39.3	4.421	
	Total	42.0	4.282		< 100	58.1	4.484	
1	140 - 120	55.5	7.070	Total	150.4	15.508		
2	220 - 200	108.9	23.250	7	220 - 200	31.5	6.426	
	Total	108.9	23.250		200 - 180	32.9	6.376	
3	160 - 140	37.1	5.343		180 - 160	4.1	0.718	
	140 - 120	13.9	1.910		160 - 140	1.4	0.201	
	Total	51.0	7.253	140 - 120	1.4	0.174		
4	240 - 220	6.2	1.367	8	240 - 220	4.2	0.942	
	220 - 200	106.7	22.864		220 - 200	2.8	0.609	
	200 - 180	4.6	0.881		200 - 180	0.7	0.135	
	180 - 160	1.5	0.258		Total	7.8	1.686	
	160 - 140	1.5	0.233	9	120 - 100	9.3	0.974	
	140 - 120	1.5	0.213		< 100	37.2	2.825	
	Total	122.2	25.816		Total	46.6	3.799	
5	120 - 100	25.1	2.542	10	240 - 220	11.7	2.598	
	< 100	18.8	1.736		220 - 200	7.4	1.615	
	Total	44.0	4.278		200 - 180	1.1	0.210	
				Total	20.2	4.423		

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
11	120 - 100	67.5	7.031	16	120 - 100	35.4	3.754
Total		67.5	7.031	Total		35.4	3.754
12	140 - 120	98.7	12.919	17	140 - 120	98.7	13.631
	120 - 100	15.5	1.720		120 - 100	5.5	0.646
	< 100	12.7	1.064		< 100	1.4	0.128
Total		126.8	15.703	Total		105.6	14.405
13	220 - 200	1.8	0.356	18	220 - 200	75.6	15.210
	200 - 180	8.0	1.490		200 - 180	94.5	18.679
	180 - 160	2.7	0.469	Total		170.0	33.889
	160 - 140	3.5	0.534	19	140 - 120	9.9	1.336
Total		15.9	2.850		120 - 100	3.0	0.335
14	200 - 180	3.4	0.613		< 100	1.5	0.143
	180 - 160	35.6	6.191	Total		14.4	1.814
	160 - 140	3.4	0.500	20	120 - 100	1.6	0.166
Total		42.4	7.304		< 100	17.8	1.550
15	140 - 120	19.1	2.619	Total		19.4	1.716
	< 100	0.9	0.090	21	160 - 140	7.4	1.069
Total		20.0	2.709	Total		7.4	1.069

eP-EAZK-317, eP-EAZK-318

Location information

Gymnázium, Komenského 712, Valašské Klobouky, Zlínský kraj

49.13939 N, 18.00373 E

Building area: 668 m²

1075 LiDAR points (1.61 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	137.5	421.2	30.2	320.0
1	52.2	421.3	29.7	230.6
2	109.5	421.7	27.9	137.9
3	36.1	420.9	29.7	50.1
4	29.1	421.2	29.9	47.7
5	107.4	421.0	30.1	320.1
6	26.1	420.5	28.6	230.4
7	153.4	421.2	29.9	140.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	25.0	2.145
120 - 100	51.9	5.801
140 - 120	207.9	27.394
160 - 140	45.4	6.568
180 - 160	34.7	5.926
200 - 180	41.1	7.830
220 - 200	245.4	51.791
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	651.4	107.455

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	140 - 120	68.8	8.880	4	160 - 140	29.1	4.165	
	120 - 100	44.7	4.997		Total	29.1	4.165	
	< 100	24.1	2.056	5	140 - 120	107.4	14.340	
	Total	137.5	15.932		Total	107.4	14.340	
1	220 - 200	48.6	10.185		6	220 - 200	26.1	5.444
	200 - 180	1.8	0.326			Total	26.1	5.444
	160 - 140	1.8	0.266	7	220 - 200	65.8	13.859	
	Total	52.2	10.776		200 - 180	34.7	6.619	
2	220 - 200	104.9	22.302		180 - 160	34.7	5.926	
	200 - 180	4.6	0.885		160 - 140	9.1	1.362	
	Total	109.5	23.187	140 - 120	9.1	1.189		
	3	160 - 140	5.4	0.775	Total	153.4	28.955	
140 - 120		22.6	2.985					
120 - 100		7.2	0.805					
< 100		0.9	0.090					
Total		36.1	4.654					

eP-EAZK-319

Location information

Gymnázium - sportovní hala, Komenského -, Valašské Klobouky, Zlínský kraj

49.13974 N, 18.00409 E

Building area: 1382 m²

1960 LiDAR points (1.42 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	257.0	418.9	8.9	51.4
1	26.4	419.6	10.4	48.9
2	591.6	425.2	9.6	48.1
3	496.3	425.1	10.3	228.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	4.9	0.591
140 - 120	84.1	11.136
160 - 140	188.4	28.548
180 - 160	597.5	102.942
200 - 180	352.4	68.748
220 - 200	143.9	28.841
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1371.2	240.807

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	113.5	19.149	2	180 - 160	484.0	83.794
	160 - 140	116.8	17.893		160 - 140	69.9	10.421
	140 - 120	26.7	3.514		140 - 120	37.6	5.161
	Total	257.0	40.556		Total	591.6	99.376
1	160 - 140	1.6	0.234	3	220 - 200	143.9	28.841
	140 - 120	19.8	2.461		200 - 180	352.4	68.748
	120 - 100	4.9	0.591		Total	496.3	97.589
	Total	26.4	3.286				

eP-EAZK-320

Location information

Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka, Družstevní 1646, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.33898 N, 17.98245 E

Building area: 616 m²

1060 LiDAR points (1.72 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	90.8	353.2	1.1	214.7
1	471.0	356.3	1.2	216.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	4.4	0.592
160 - 140	13.3	1.969
180 - 160	24.4	4.132
200 - 180	519.7	98.584
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	561.8	105.276

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	48.7	9.077
	180 - 160	24.4	4.132
	160 - 140	13.3	1.969
	140 - 120	4.4	0.592
Total		90.8	15.768

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	200 - 180	471.0	89.507
Total		471.0	89.507

eP-EAZK-321

Location information

Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka, Bobrky 466, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.36241 N, 17.96111 E

Building area: 494 m²

1183 LiDAR points (2.39 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	131.4	336.4	20.2	17.0
1	139.9	336.5	20.5	197.3
2	106.5	337.0	13.6	17.0
3	113.4	337.1	13.1	196.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	9.6	0.868
120 - 100	20.7	2.338
140 - 120	34.1	4.525
160 - 140	140.7	21.160
180 - 160	32.8	5.270
200 - 180	3.0	0.584
220 - 200	250.3	53.677
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	491.2	88.423

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	72.1	10.441	3	220 - 200	110.4	23.094
	140 - 120	32.0	4.241		200 - 180	3.0	0.584
	120 - 100	17.6	1.988		Total	113.4	23.679
	< 100	9.6	0.868				
	Total	131.4	17.539				
1	220 - 200	139.9	30.583				
Total	139.9	30.583					
2	180 - 160	32.8	5.270				
	160 - 140	68.6	10.719				
	140 - 120	2.0	0.284				
	120 - 100	3.1	0.350				
	Total	106.5	16.623				

eP-EAZK-322

Location information

Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka, Benátky 1779, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.33810 N, 17.98337 E

Building area: 4676 m²

7347 LiDAR points (1.57 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	275.2	347.9	0.8	217.8
1	205.8	353.1	5.6	214.2
2	254.4	353.1	5.1	34.9
3	244.2	348.3	5.8	36.1
4	151.5	352.9	11.6	125.2
5	160.6	353.0	10.8	304.4
6	39.3	348.0	9.0	124.9
7	55.6	347.8	6.6	305.9
8	50.4	348.1	7.3	306.1
9	225.7	352.5	13.6	124.8
10	239.5	352.6	13.2	304.9
11	204.9	348.3	5.9	34.5
12	117.2	352.7	11.2	124.8
13	176.1	352.8	10.1	305.6
14	30.8	347.8	6.1	305.5
15	221.9	352.4	10.0	124.6
16	243.8	352.5	9.8	305.2
17	206.7	348.3	5.3	34.6
18	24.5	347.8	4.9	306.4
19	85.0	352.4	11.0	125.1
20	169.1	352.5	10.3	304.9
21	138.7	356.8	11.1	124.8
22	206.3	356.9	11.0	304.9
23	13.3	348.6	4.4	113.1
24	128.0	348.4	5.1	38.5
25	70.9	348.3	5.1	37.1
26	41.2	347.7	7.0	305.5
27	119.0	352.4	10.9	124.7
28	181.9	352.5	9.6	305.4

■ **Energy prediction - Summary**

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	17.7	1.552
120 - 100	55.0	6.353
140 - 120	170.1	22.349
160 - 140	307.5	46.475
180 - 160	2309.5	403.012
200 - 180	1231.7	239.755
220 - 200	190.0	38.094
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	4281.5	757.591

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	200 - 180	49.0	8.999	7	180 - 160	17.7	2.918	
	180 - 160	105.6	18.060		160 - 140	26.6	3.977	
	160 - 140	56.6	8.698		140 - 120	11.3	1.490	
	140 - 120	41.5	5.481		Total	55.6	8.385	
	120 - 100	7.5	0.890		8	180 - 160	38.2	6.655
	< 100	15.1	1.302			160 - 140	6.5	0.974
Total	275.2	43.430	140 - 120	0.9		0.113		
1	200 - 180	203.4	39.694	120 - 100		2.8	0.314	
	180 - 160	2.4	0.430	< 100	1.9	0.174		
	Total	205.8	40.124	Total	50.4	8.230		
2	200 - 180	83.9	15.110	9	220 - 200	59.4	11.962	
	180 - 160	143.4	25.272		200 - 180	164.0	31.764	
	160 - 140	27.1	4.038		180 - 160	2.4	0.416	
	Total	254.4	44.420		Total	225.7	44.143	
3	180 - 160	205.3	35.757	10	180 - 160	113.7	19.261	
	160 - 140	16.6	2.569		160 - 140	55.6	8.332	
	140 - 120	13.9	1.879		140 - 120	50.8	6.643	
	120 - 100	8.3	0.953		120 - 100	19.4	2.238	
	Total	244.2	41.159		Total	239.5	36.474	
4	220 - 200	32.5	6.504	11	180 - 160	192.8	33.749	
	200 - 180	119.0	23.207		160 - 140	7.2	1.101	
	Total	151.5	29.711		140 - 120	4.8	0.594	
5	180 - 160	160.6	28.217		Total	204.9	35.444	
	Total	160.6	28.217	12	220 - 200	98.1	19.628	
6	200 - 180	29.9	5.678		200 - 180	19.1	3.803	
	180 - 160	7.7	1.340		Total	117.2	23.431	
	160 - 140	1.7	0.259	13	180 - 160	176.1	31.035	
Total	39.3	7.277	Total		176.1	31.035		

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
14	180 - 160	11.3	1.871	21	200 - 180	138.7	27.667
	160 - 140	16.6	2.476		Total	138.7	27.667
	140 - 120	3.0	0.403	22	180 - 160	206.3	36.184
	Total	30.8	4.750		Total	206.3	36.184
15	200 - 180	221.9	44.101	23	200 - 180	2.3	0.424
	Total	221.9	44.101		180 - 160	10.9	1.905
16	180 - 160	191.0	33.222	Total	13.3	2.328	
	160 - 140	40.2	6.025	24	200 - 180	1.7	0.311
	140 - 120	10.1	1.323		180 - 160	115.9	20.239
	120 - 100	2.5	0.277		160 - 140	3.5	0.531
Total	243.8	40.848	140 - 120		6.9	0.904	
17	180 - 160	191.2	33.723	Total	128.0	21.985	
	160 - 140	12.9	1.996	25	180 - 160	56.1	9.415
	120 - 100	2.6	0.304		160 - 140	13.2	1.989
	Total	206.7	36.022		140 - 120	1.6	0.225
18	180 - 160	5.4	0.901		Total	70.9	11.629
	160 - 140	4.6	0.689	26	180 - 160	8.9	1.480
	140 - 120	9.9	1.304		160 - 140	8.9	1.329
	120 - 100	3.8	0.433		140 - 120	15.3	1.989
	< 100	0.8	0.076		120 - 100	8.1	0.943
Total	24.5	3.404	Total		41.2	5.741	
19	200 - 180	79.7	15.889	27	200 - 180	119.0	23.107
	180 - 160	5.3	0.909		Total	119.0	23.107
	Total	85.0	16.798	28	180 - 160	181.9	32.165
20	180 - 160	159.4	27.887		Total	181.9	32.165
	160 - 140	9.8	1.493				
Total	169.1	29.380					

EAZK-323, eP-EAZK-324, eP-EAZK-325, eP-EAZK-326, eP-EAZK-327, eP-EAZK-328, eP-EAZK-329

Location information

Střední odborná škola Josefa Sousedíka, Školní 1824, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.34062 N, 17.98818 E

Building area: 1359 m²

1492 LiDAR points (1.10 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	991.6	351.6	0.5	36.8
1	121.3	355.9	5.2	33.1
2	31.8	355.8	5.3	217.1
3	27.8	355.1	1.0	312.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	11.5	1.124
120 - 100	23.1	2.726
140 - 120	58.4	7.640
160 - 140	18.3	2.766
180 - 160	341.8	60.539
200 - 180	719.5	133.479
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1172.5	208.274

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	680.3	126.041	2	200 - 180	29.4	5.652
	180 - 160	207.5	36.647		180 - 160	2.4	0.418
	160 - 140	11.5	1.753		Total	31.8	6.070
	140 - 120	57.7	7.536	3	200 - 180	9.8	1.786
	120 - 100	23.1	2.726		180 - 160	10.5	1.797
	< 100	11.5	1.124		160 - 140	6.8	1.013
	Total	991.6	175.827		140 - 120	0.8	0.104
1	180 - 160	121.3	21.677	Total	27.8	4.700	
	Total	121.3	21.677				

eP-EAZK-330, eP-EAZK-331

Location information

Gymnázium a Jazyková škola, nám. T. G. Masaryka 2734, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21946 N, 17.66689 E

Building area: 1527 m²

1834 LiDAR points (1.20 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	1512.3	295.0	0.1	11.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	1512.3	284.011
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1512.3	284.011

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	1512.3	284.011
Total		1512.3	284.011

eP-EAZK-332, eP-EAZK-333

Location information

Gymnázium a Jazyková škola, nám. T. G. Masaryka -, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.21919 N, 17.66719 E

Building area: 1176 m²

488 LiDAR points (0.42 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-334

Location information

Střední zdravotnická škola a Vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická - škola, Broučkova 372, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22476 N, 17.70251 E

Building area: 2102 m²

2488 LiDAR points (1.18 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	376.4	245.4	13.5	248.4
1	410.2	245.3	13.3	67.4
2	132.6	243.6	0.7	302.0
3	21.0	247.0	23.8	293.4
4	23.8	247.4	8.2	123.7
5	25.9	239.6	2.7	12.4
6	132.9	242.2	5.9	292.1
7	136.1	240.7	17.1	293.7
8	140.0	238.1	26.4	293.3
9	167.4	240.5	17.4	114.0
10	171.8	242.2	3.8	118.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	7.3	0.818
140 - 120	39.8	5.354
160 - 140	150.5	22.369
180 - 160	652.2	114.063
200 - 180	888.4	171.121
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1738.3	313.727

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	
0	200 - 180	369.1	71.941	6	200 - 180	119.9	22.059	
	180 - 160	7.4	1.297		180 - 160	13.0	2.256	
	Total	376.4	73.237		Total	132.9	24.315	
1	180 - 160	401.6	71.083	7	180 - 160	134.6	22.948	
	160 - 140	8.6	1.366		160 - 140	1.5	0.237	
	Total	410.2	72.449		Total	136.1	23.185	
2	200 - 180	49.0	9.011	8	160 - 140	111.4	16.396	
	180 - 160	45.4	7.912		140 - 120	28.6	3.864	
	160 - 140	21.8	3.272		Total	140.0	20.260	
	140 - 120	9.1	1.212		9	200 - 180	167.4	33.207
	120 - 100	7.3	0.818			Total	167.4	33.207
Total	132.6	22.226	10	200 - 180	159.2	30.224		
3	180 - 160	20.3		3.337	180 - 160	12.7	2.255	
	160 - 140	0.8		0.120	Total	171.8	32.479	
	Total	21.0	3.457					
4	200 - 180	23.8	4.680					
	Total	23.8	4.680					
5	180 - 160	17.3	2.976					
	160 - 140	6.5	0.978					
	140 - 120	2.2	0.277					
	Total	25.9	4.232					

eP-EAZK-335, eP-EAZK-336

Location information

Střední zdravotnická škola a Vyšší odborná škola zdravotnická, Broučkova 4062, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22489 N, 17.70000 E

Building area: 226 m²

280 LiDAR points (1.24 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	11.6	251.8	1.6	65.9
1	179.3	255.1	0.3	281.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	6.4	1.125
200 - 180	184.5	34.646
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	190.9	35.770

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	5.2	0.960	1	200 - 180	179.3	33.686
	180 - 160	6.4	1.125		Total	179.3	33.686
	Total	11.6	2.085				

eP-EAZK-337

Location information

Zdravotnická záchranná služba Zlínského kraje, Komenského -, Slavičín, Zlínský kraj

49.09026 N, 17.87295 E

Building area: 55 m²

103 LiDAR points (1.86 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	15.3	366.4	24.1	71.3
1	12.9	366.3	24.4	250.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	12.3	1.669
160 - 140	2.9	0.435
180 - 160	0.6	0.106
200 - 180	12.3	2.296
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	28.2	4.505

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	2.9	0.435	1	200 - 180	12.3	2.296
	140 - 120	12.3	1.669		180 - 160	0.6	0.106
Total		15.3	2.104	Total		12.9	2.401

eP-EAZK-338

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje, Peroutkovo nábřeží 434, Zlín, Zlínský kraj

49.22707 N, 17.70320 E

Building area: 3285 m²

4109 LiDAR points (1.25 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	476.6	230.3	3.0	198.9
1	391.0	230.8	2.8	19.5
2	504.9	230.4	0.2	228.5
3	334.1	230.4	1.0	114.2
4	800.6	230.8	0.1	59.9
5	42.1	234.4	0.7	58.5
6	469.3	230.7	0.1	248.2

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	12.3	1.414
140 - 120	4.1	0.522
160 - 140	50.0	7.656
180 - 160	253.4	43.852
200 - 180	2698.7	507.817
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	3018.6	561.262

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	476.6	91.882	4	200 - 180	714.6	133.885
	Total	476.6	91.882		180 - 160	66.2	11.476
1	200 - 180	214.0	39.026		160 - 140	19.8	2.970
	180 - 160	144.1	24.895	Total	800.6	148.332	
	160 - 140	16.5	2.570	5	200 - 180	42.1	7.886
	140 - 120	4.1	0.522		Total	42.1	7.886
	120 - 100	12.3	1.414	6	200 - 180	419.2	78.668
Total	391.0	68.427	180 - 160		36.4	6.361	
2	200 - 180	504.9	94.766		160 - 140	13.7	2.116
	Total	504.9	94.766	Total	469.3	87.145	
3	200 - 180	327.3	61.704				
	180 - 160	6.7	1.120				
	Total	334.1	62.824				

eP-EAZK-339

Location information

Zdravotnická záchranná služba Zlínského kraje, Chrástěšovská 1005, Vizovice, Zlínský kraj

49.23155 N, 17.85734 E

Building area: 644 m²

1180 LiDAR points (1.83 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	352.1	315.1	14.2	264.3
1	296.4	314.9	13.8	84.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	362.7	63.621
200 - 180	285.7	52.480
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	648.5	116.101

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	54.2	9.919	1	200 - 180	231.5	42.561
	180 - 160	297.9	52.282		180 - 160	64.8	11.339
Total		352.1	62.201	Total		296.4	53.900

eP-EAZK-340

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služba Zlínského kraje, Havlíčkova 3549/73, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29140 N, 17.37674 E

Building area: 673 m²

488 LiDAR points (0.73 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	297.4	214.4	13.6	150.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	297.4	62.001
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	297.4	62.001

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	297.4	62.001
Total		297.4	62.001

eP-EAZK-341

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služba Zlínského kraje, Nemocniční 940, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.33219 N, 17.99790 E

Building area: 479 m²

499 LiDAR points (1.04 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	21.4	355.2	24.5	11.0
1	34.6	355.5	24.9	191.1
2	115.4	355.9	24.2	280.8
3	125.2	356.0	24.5	100.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	21.4	2.844
160 - 140	5.4	0.793
180 - 160	110.0	19.111
200 - 180	125.2	23.376
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	34.6	7.720
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	296.6	53.844

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	21.4	2.844
Total		21.4	2.844
1	240 - 220	34.6	7.720
Total		34.6	7.720
2	180 - 160	110.0	19.111
	160 - 140	5.4	0.793
Total		115.4	19.904

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	200 - 180	125.2	23.376
Total		125.2	23.376

eP-EAZK-342

■ Location information

Zdravotnická záchranná služba Zlínského kraje, nábřeží Dukelských hrdinů 2950, Rožnov pod Radhoštěm, Zlínský kraj

49.46174 N, 18.13979 E

Building area: 267 m²

49 LiDAR points (0.18 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-343

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje, Nádražní 871, Morkovice - Slížany, Zlínský kraj

49.25303 N, 17.21127 E

Building area: 236 m²

70 LiDAR points (0.30 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-344

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služba Zlínského kraje, Partyzánů 2364, Uherský Brod, Zlínský kraj

49.03001 N, 17.65344 E

Building area: 387 m²

579 LiDAR points (1.50 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	8.2	267.1	1.7	130.0
1	56.2	267.9	1.4	43.2
2	132.4	268.9	0.9	51.1
3	137.2	269.6	0.8	38.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	14.6	2.573
200 - 180	319.3	59.554
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	333.9	62.127

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	8.2	1.555
	Total	8.2	1.555
1	200 - 180	56.2	10.433
	Total	56.2	10.433
2	200 - 180	127.3	23.744
	180 - 160	5.0	0.882
	Total	132.4	24.626

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	200 - 180	127.6	23.822
	180 - 160	9.6	1.690
	Total	137.2	25.512

eP-EAZK-345

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje, U Nemocnice 1511, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.46325 N, 17.97860 E

Building area: 350 m²

616 LiDAR points (1.76 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	324.3	342.1	0.1	161.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	324.3	60.770
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	324.3	60.770

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	324.3	60.770
Total		324.3	60.770

eP-EAZK-346

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje, Pod Zábřehem 1690, Bystřice pod Hostýnem, Zlínský kraj

49.40275 N, 17.68180 E

Building area: 263 m²

423 LiDAR points (1.61 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	249.3	332.3	0.6	224.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	249.3	46.996
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	249.3	46.996

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	249.3	46.996
Total		249.3	46.996

eP-EAZK-347

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje, J.E.Purkyně 1512, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06481 N, 17.45738 E

Building area: 617 m²

677 LiDAR points (1.10 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	82.5	183.6	0.4	170.9
1	191.1	184.0	0.5	72.4
2	238.7	186.6	0.4	16.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	7.5	0.848
140 - 120	11.7	1.529
160 - 140	15.8	2.398
180 - 160	30.0	5.109
200 - 180	447.3	83.723
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	512.3	93.607

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	17.5	3.199
	180 - 160	30.0	5.109
	160 - 140	15.8	2.398
	140 - 120	11.7	1.529
	120 - 100	7.5	0.848
Total		82.5	13.084

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
1	200 - 180	191.1	35.834
	Total	191.1	35.834
2	200 - 180	238.7	44.690
	Total	238.7	44.690

eP-EAZK-348, eP-EAZK-349

Location information

Zdravotnická záchranná služba Zlínského kraje, náměstí Svobody 881, Buchlovice, Zlínský kraj

49.08684 N, 17.33647 E

Building area: 223 m²

119 LiDAR points (0.53 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	32.2	255.7	1.7	253.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	1.5	0.133
120 - 100	2.2	0.239
140 - 120	1.5	0.191
160 - 140	5.1	0.789
180 - 160	12.4	2.145
200 - 180	9.5	1.738
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	32.2	5.234

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	9.5	1.738
	180 - 160	12.4	2.145
	160 - 140	5.1	0.789
	140 - 120	1.5	0.191
	120 - 100	2.2	0.239
	< 100	1.5	0.133
	Total	32.2	5.234

eP-EAZK-350

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služby Zlínského kraje, Radniční náměstí 42, Karolinka, Zlínský kraj

49.35058 N, 18.23748 E

Building area: 1339 m²

1854 LiDAR points (1.38 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	174.3	484.4	4.0	192.0
1	138.9	485.1	5.5	100.5
2	329.7	485.8	5.8	100.3
3	136.0	485.1	5.2	190.2
4	195.7	486.1	7.0	280.9
5	303.9	486.3	7.4	281.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	18.4	2.544
160 - 140	10.5	1.631
180 - 160	99.5	17.277
200 - 180	1150.1	217.667
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1278.6	239.119

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	163.4	31.862	4	200 - 180	195.7	36.333
	180 - 160	10.9	1.932		Total	195.7	36.333
	Total	174.3	33.794		5	200 - 180	245.6
1	200 - 180	124.0	23.577	180 - 160		33.8	5.840
	180 - 160	14.8	2.640	160 - 140		6.1	0.958
	Total	138.9	26.217	140 - 120		18.4	2.544
2	200 - 180	317.1	60.337	Total	303.9	54.729	
	180 - 160	12.6	2.148	3	200 - 180	104.2	20.170
	Total	329.7	62.486		180 - 160	27.5	4.717
3	200 - 180	104.2	20.170		160 - 140	4.3	0.673
	180 - 160	27.5	4.717		Total	136.0	25.560
	160 - 140	4.3	0.673				

eP-EAZK-351

Location information

Zdravotnická záchraná služba Zlínského kraje, - 396, Suchá Loz, Zlínský kraj

48.97195 N, 17.71545 E

Building area: 287 m²

25 LiDAR points (0.09 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-352

Location information

Hvězdárna - hlavní budova, Vsetínská 941/78, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.46378 N, 17.97366 E

Building area: 298 m²

365 LiDAR points (1.22 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	65.9	336.8	1.2	72.6
1	61.1	336.8	0.2	337.1
2	55.7	338.6	11.1	339.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	1.8	0.242
160 - 140	26.6	4.098
180 - 160	108.7	18.421
200 - 180	45.7	8.397
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	182.8	31.157

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	22.9	4.209	2	180 - 160	44.2	7.303
	180 - 160	33.4	5.762		160 - 140	9.7	1.485
	160 - 140	9.6	1.479		140 - 120	1.8	0.242
	Total	65.9	11.450		Total	55.7	9.030
1	200 - 180	22.8	4.188				
	180 - 160	31.0	5.356				
	160 - 140	7.3	1.133				
	Total	61.1	10.677				

eP-EAZK-353

Location information

Hvězdárna - vedlejší budova, Vsetínská 237/5, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.46421 N, 17.97357 E

Building area: 101 m²

164 LiDAR points (1.62 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	28.1	337.5	37.8	357.1
1	24.8	337.2	39.2	86.9
2	20.7	337.3	38.4	175.8
3	21.0	337.9	38.2	265.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	1.7	0.168
120 - 100	26.4	2.762
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	3.8	0.593
180 - 160	42.0	7.270
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	20.7	4.677
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	94.6	15.470

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	26.4	2.762
	< 100	1.7	0.168
	Total	28.1	2.930
1	180 - 160	21.0	3.543
	160 - 140	3.8	0.593
	Total	24.8	4.136

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	240 - 220	20.7	4.677
	Total	20.7	4.677
3	180 - 160	21.0	3.728
	Total	21.0	3.728

eP-EAZK-354

Location information

Slovácké muzeum - galerie, Otakarova 103, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.07183 N, 17.45778 E

Building area: 600 m²

982 LiDAR points (1.64 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	237.9	191.8	47.5	26.0
1	170.9	190.7	43.4	206.0
2	129.3	189.3	41.6	122.9
3	139.5	189.6	42.1	301.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	237.9	22.833
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	148.5	20.100
160 - 140	4.8	0.729
180 - 160	2.9	0.488
200 - 180	53.3	10.497
220 - 200	80.0	16.300
240 - 220	150.0	33.483
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	677.5	104.429

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	< 100	237.9	22.833	2	220 - 200	70.5	14.349
	Total	237.9	22.833		200 - 180	51.4	10.134
1	240 - 220	150.0	33.483		180 - 160	2.9	0.488
	220 - 200	9.5	1.950		160 - 140	2.9	0.432
	200 - 180	1.9	0.364		140 - 120	1.5	0.199
	160 - 140	1.9	0.296	Total	129.3	25.602	
	140 - 120	7.6	0.973	3	140 - 120	139.5	18.927
Total	170.9	37.067	Total		139.5	18.927	

eP-EAZK-355

Location information

Slovácké muzeum - hlavní budova, Smetanovy sady 179, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06731 N, 17.46784 E

Building area: 919 m²

1212 LiDAR points (1.32 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	79.8	187.9	3.4	0.9
1	7.7	188.0	0.7	336.9
2	18.2	187.9	3.0	57.5
3	7.9	189.8	0.5	38.3
4	36.2	188.0	0.4	105.0
5	26.7	186.9	1.0	45.3
6	21.6	188.0	0.1	209.7
7	80.5	189.7	0.1	118.4
8	12.6	191.2	58.1	330.9
9	6.1	190.8	26.9	326.4
10	8.9	190.9	28.4	238.6
11	51.9	189.8	30.6	153.1
12	60.6	188.0	0.2	17.0
13	235.0	189.8	0.1	16.3

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	14.5	1.205
120 - 100	18.7	2.115
140 - 120	33.7	4.315
160 - 140	60.1	9.148
180 - 160	77.9	13.361
200 - 180	388.5	72.639
220 - 200	8.4	1.718
240 - 220	51.9	11.585
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	653.7	116.086

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	6.4	1.058	4	200 - 180	13.2	2.415
	160 - 140	34.9	5.296		180 - 160	15.9	2.769
	140 - 120	22.0	2.771		160 - 140	3.5	0.546
	120 - 100	14.7	1.652		140 - 120	1.8	0.218
	< 100	1.8	0.177		120 - 100	1.8	0.206
Total	79.8	10.953	Total	36.2	6.154		
1	180 - 160	6.5	1.099	5	180 - 160	16.0	2.751
	160 - 140	1.2	0.188		160 - 140	4.6	0.685
	Total	7.7	1.287		140 - 120	3.8	0.499
2	180 - 160	4.2	0.704	120 - 100	2.3	0.257	
	160 - 140	14.0	2.141	Total	26.7	4.192	
Total	18.2	2.845					
3	200 - 180	4.5	0.830				
	180 - 160	3.4	0.576				
Total	7.9	1.406					

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
6	200 - 180	16.0	2.990	10	220 - 200	8.4	1.718
	180 - 160	5.6	0.971		200 - 180	0.5	0.098
	Total	21.6	3.961		Total	8.9	1.816
7	200 - 180	66.1	12.290	11	240 - 220	51.9	11.585
	180 - 160	12.5	2.153		Total	51.9	11.585
	160 - 140	1.9	0.293	12	200 - 180	58.2	10.872
Total	80.5	14.736	180 - 160		2.5	0.425	
8	< 100	12.6	1.028	Total	60.6	11.297	
	Total	12.6	1.028	13	200 - 180	230.0	43.143
9	140 - 120	6.1	0.827		180 - 160	5.0	0.855
	Total	6.1	0.827		Total	235.0	43.998

eP-EAZK-356

Location information

Slovácké muzeum, Hradební 227, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.06910 N, 17.46321 E

Building area: 175 m²

306 LiDAR points (1.75 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	74.0	190.0	34.0	61.1
1	81.1	190.2	33.5	241.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	74.0	11.108
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	3.0	0.585
220 - 200	78.2	15.813
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	155.2	27.506

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	74.0	11.108
	Total	74.0	11.108
1	220 - 200	78.2	15.813
	200 - 180	3.0	0.585
	Total	81.1	16.398

eP-EAZK-357

Location information

Slovácké muzeum - Památník Velké Moravy, Jezuitská 1885, Staré Město, Zlínský kraj

49.07847 N, 17.44369 E

Building area: 79 m²

58 LiDAR points (0.73 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	16.2	193.2	9.6	352.0
1	24.6	193.2	10.3	170.6

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.7	0.092
160 - 140	4.1	0.604
180 - 160	11.5	1.891
200 - 180	0.7	0.144
220 - 200	23.8	4.874
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	40.8	7.606

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	11.5	1.891	1	220 - 200	23.8	4.874
	160 - 140	4.1	0.604		200 - 180	0.7	0.144
	140 - 120	0.7	0.092		Total	24.6	5.018
Total		16.2	2.588				

eP-EAZK-358

Location information

Slovácké muzeum, Štefánikova 1285, Uherské Hradiště, Zlínský kraj

49.07056 N, 17.46961 E

Building area: 735 m²

747 LiDAR points (1.02 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	350.8	191.9	3.4	6.0
1	378.6	191.9	3.2	184.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	11.4	1.912
200 - 180	718.0	135.216
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	729.4	137.128

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	339.4	61.631	1	200 - 180	378.6	73.585
	180 - 160	11.4	1.912		Total	378.6	73.585
	Total	350.8	63.544				

eP-EAZK-359

Location information

Slovácké muzeum, - 90, Topolná, Zlínský kraj

49.12130 N, 17.54372 E

Building area: 217 m²

449 LiDAR points (2.07 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	55.0	197.2	37.0	343.8
1	50.9	197.4	36.8	164.9
2	86.6	196.7	35.9	68.1
3	29.6	197.4	38.4	249.4

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	4.7	0.436
120 - 100	51.3	5.608
140 - 120	3.0	0.394
160 - 140	91.6	14.179
180 - 160	2.0	0.329
200 - 180	36.6	7.096
220 - 200	7.0	1.491
240 - 220	26.0	5.846
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	222.2	35.380

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	120 - 100	50.3	5.491
	< 100	4.7	0.436
	Total	55.0	5.927
1	240 - 220	26.0	5.846
	220 - 200	7.0	1.491
	200 - 180	7.0	1.333
	180 - 160	2.0	0.329
	160 - 140	5.0	0.740
	140 - 120	3.0	0.394
	120 - 100	1.0	0.117
	Total	50.9	10.250

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	160 - 140	86.6	13.439
	Total	86.6	13.439
3	200 - 180	29.6	5.763
	Total	29.6	5.763

eP-EAZK-360

Location information

Slovácké muzeum, - 93, Topolná, Zlínský kraj

49.12116 N, 17.54321 E

Building area: 190 m²

359 LiDAR points (1.89 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	35.7	194.5	40.7	246.4
1	18.9	194.2	37.9	66.6
2	43.1	195.5	36.5	345.4
3	74.6	195.2	37.7	166.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	12.3	1.143
120 - 100	33.0	3.490
140 - 120	5.5	0.723
160 - 140	22.6	3.343
180 - 160	10.2	1.725
200 - 180	38.1	7.358
220 - 200	10.3	2.201
240 - 220	40.2	9.090
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	172.2	29.072

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	31.3	6.046	3	240 - 220	40.2	9.090
	180 - 160	4.5	0.758		220 - 200	10.3	2.201
	Total	35.7	6.804		200 - 180	6.9	1.313
1	160 - 140	18.0	2.641		180 - 160	5.7	0.967
	140 - 120	0.9	0.123		160 - 140	4.6	0.702
	Total	18.9	2.764	140 - 120	4.6	0.600	
2	120 - 100	30.8	3.230	120 - 100	2.3	0.260	
	< 100	12.3	1.143	Total	74.6	15.132	
	Total	43.1	4.373				

eP-EAZK-361

Location information

Slovácké muzeum - Centrum sv. Cyrila a Metoděje, Jezuitská 1885, Staré Město, Zlínský kraj

49.07805 N, 17.44416 E

Building area: 641 m²

198 LiDAR points (0.31 points/m²)

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-362

Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, Velké náměstí 38/21, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29906 N, 17.39275 E

Building area: 518 m²

578 LiDAR points (1.12 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	220.6	221.8	32.5	125.3
1	111.9	221.7	34.5	213.4
2	49.3	222.3	38.9	216.8
3	19.0	222.1	32.1	303.3
4	161.1	222.0	33.2	307.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	4.5	0.521
140 - 120	43.2	5.837
160 - 140	139.4	19.695
180 - 160	3.5	0.604
200 - 180	44.1	8.488
220 - 200	320.3	67.490
240 - 220	7.0	1.544
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	562.0	104.178

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	188.8	39.135	2	220 - 200	49.3	10.770
	200 - 180	31.8	6.156		Total	49.3	10.770
	Total	220.6	45.291		3	160 - 140	5.4
1	240 - 220	7.0	1.544	140 - 120		9.1	1.224
	220 - 200	82.2	17.584	120 - 100		4.5	0.521
	200 - 180	12.2	2.332	Total		19.0	2.528
	180 - 160	3.5	0.604	4	160 - 140	130.4	18.370
	160 - 140	3.5	0.541		140 - 120	30.7	4.138
140 - 120	3.5	0.476	Total		161.1	22.508	
Total	111.9	23.081					

eP-EAZK-363

Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, Hanácké náměstí 471/5, Kroměříž, Zlínský kraj

49.29316 N, 17.38887 E

Building area: 1087 m²

1519 LiDAR points (1.40 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	18.5	208.9	23.1	250.9
1	27.3	209.2	21.7	68.1
2	62.1	209.1	23.4	341.2
3	31.1	209.1	23.1	70.3
4	56.3	209.0	23.1	159.8
5	66.8	213.8	33.4	160.4
6	65.7	213.9	32.8	339.8
7	412.8	214.3	30.4	250.1
8	397.8	214.2	30.8	70.5

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	6.6	0.612
120 - 100	89.9	10.592
140 - 120	75.6	10.118
160 - 140	176.6	26.962
180 - 160	246.4	40.361
200 - 180	420.0	82.506
220 - 200	29.9	6.563
240 - 220	93.2	20.941
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	1138.4	198.655

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	7.3	1.354	4	240 - 220	26.3	5.803
	180 - 160	3.3	0.573		220 - 200	29.9	6.563
	160 - 140	4.6	0.722		Total	56.3	12.366
	140 - 120	2.0	0.262	5	240 - 220	66.8	15.137
	120 - 100	1.3	0.154		Total	66.8	15.137
	Total	18.5	3.066	6	120 - 100	65.7	7.869
1	180 - 160	8.1	1.333	Total	65.7	7.869	
	160 - 140	6.6	1.007	7	200 - 180	412.8	81.152
	140 - 120	2.9	0.396		Total	412.8	81.152
	120 - 100	5.9	0.649		8	180 - 160	203.9
	< 100	3.7	0.333	160 - 140		160.5	24.541
Total	27.3	3.719	140 - 120	23.4	3.083		
2	160 - 140	4.9	0.690	120 - 100	10.0	1.159	
	140 - 120	47.3	6.377	Total	397.8	61.948	
	120 - 100	6.9	0.760				
	< 100	3.0	0.279				
Total	62.1	8.106					
3	180 - 160	31.1	5.290				
	Total	31.1	5.290				

eP-EAZK-364

Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, - 104, Rymice, Zlínský kraj

49.34273 N, 17.53241 E

Building area: 123 m²

211 LiDAR points (1.71 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	63.1	213.0	53.0	204.1
1	77.3	213.6	37.9	22.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	17.4	1.681
120 - 100	59.9	6.472
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	63.1	13.785
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	140.4	21.938

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	63.1	13.785
	Total	63.1	13.785
1	120 - 100	59.9	6.472
	< 100	17.4	1.681
	Total	77.3	8.154

eP-EAZK-365

■ Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, - 116, Rymice, Zlínský kraj

49.34244 N, 17.52649 E

LiDAR file was empty

LiDAR data does not fulfill quality requirements

eP-EAZK-366

Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, - 14, Rymice, Zlínský kraj

49.34183 N, 17.52498 E

Building area: 214 m²

353 LiDAR points (1.65 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	19.9	217.1	39.6	121.1
1	33.7	215.7	49.0	118.1
2	67.2	215.6	30.1	301.6
3	32.1	215.6	40.4	38.3
4	35.6	215.5	42.4	220.0

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	28.0	2.307
120 - 100	19.2	2.125
140 - 120	10.4	1.371
160 - 140	41.6	6.128
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	33.7	6.485
220 - 200	55.5	11.725
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	188.5	30.141

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	19.9	4.071
Total		19.9	4.071
1	200 - 180	33.7	6.485
Total		33.7	6.485
2	160 - 140	41.6	6.128
	140 - 120	10.4	1.371
	120 - 100	4.7	0.530
	< 100	10.4	0.882
Total		67.2	8.911

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
3	120 - 100	14.5	1.595
	< 100	17.6	1.425
Total		32.1	3.020
4	220 - 200	35.6	7.654
Total		35.6	7.654

eP-EAZK-367

Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, - 3, Rymice, Zlínský kraj

49.34297 N, 17.52799 E

Building area: 402 m²

815 LiDAR points (2.03 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	210.7	223.0	33.8	47.5
1	222.2	223.1	35.0	225.1
2	28.5	222.4	36.1	135.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	19.6	1.694
120 - 100	63.0	7.099
140 - 120	128.2	16.731
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	2.5	0.496
220 - 200	248.2	53.025
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	461.5	79.045

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	128.2	16.731
	120 - 100	63.0	7.099
	< 100	19.6	1.694
	Total	210.7	25.524
1	220 - 200	222.2	47.606
	Total	222.2	47.606

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	220 - 200	26.0	5.419
	200 - 180	2.5	0.496
	Total	28.5	5.915

eP-EAZK-368

Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, - 62, Rymice, Zlínský kraj

49.34339 N, 17.53333 E

Building area: 82 m²

160 LiDAR points (1.96 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	18.8	216.6	27.5	328.4
1	30.3	216.0	44.2	150.6
2	11.3	214.7	46.5	230.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	2.1	0.186
120 - 100	2.8	0.302
140 - 120	13.9	1.839
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	11.3	2.344
240 - 220	30.3	6.743
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	60.4	11.413

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	13.9	1.839
	120 - 100	2.8	0.302
	< 100	2.1	0.186
	Total	18.8	2.326
1	240 - 220	30.3	6.743
	Total	30.3	6.743

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
2	220 - 200	11.3	2.344
	Total	11.3	2.344

eP-EAZK-369

Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, - 65, Rymice, Zlínský kraj

49.34347 N, 17.53384 E

Building area: 59 m²

117 LiDAR points (1.98 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	32.9	215.8	46.1	79.3

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	32.9	5.214
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	32.9	5.214

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	32.9	5.214
Total		32.9	5.214

eP-EAZK-370

Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, - 6, Rymice, Zlínský kraj

49.34335 N, 17.52690 E

Building area: 63 m²

114 LiDAR points (1.80 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	5.5	217.1	37.2	104.1
1	24.7	218.3	48.2	121.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	8.4	1.613
220 - 200	21.9	4.403
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	30.2	6.016

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	5.5	1.044
	Total	5.5	1.044
1	220 - 200	21.9	4.403
	200 - 180	2.9	0.569
	Total	24.7	4.972

eP-EAZK-371

Location information

Muzeum Kroměřížska, - 2, Rymice, Zlínský kraj

49.34284 N, 17.52968 E

Building area: 813 m²

1453 LiDAR points (1.79 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	350.9	219.5	33.0	318.1
1	69.9	219.2	28.0	46.8
2	70.8	219.1	28.4	228.8
3	430.4	219.4	32.7	137.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	34.7	3.216
120 - 100	73.0	8.126
140 - 120	387.8	50.848
160 - 140	67.3	9.873
180 - 160	21.1	3.572
200 - 180	30.5	5.781
220 - 200	307.5	65.385
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	922.0	146.801

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	140 - 120	319.7	42.031	3	220 - 200	240.5	51.267
	120 - 100	7.8	0.855		200 - 180	29.5	5.605
	< 100	23.4	2.199		180 - 160	21.1	3.572
	Total	350.9	45.084		160 - 140	29.5	4.415
1	160 - 140	35.9	5.176		140 - 120	54.9	7.055
	140 - 120	12.3	1.638	120 - 100	54.9	6.130	
	120 - 100	10.4	1.141	Total	430.4	78.044	
	< 100	11.3	1.017				
	Total	69.9	8.973				
2	220 - 200	67.0	14.118				
	200 - 180	0.9	0.176				
	160 - 140	1.9	0.282				
	140 - 120	0.9	0.123				
	Total	70.8	14.699				

eP-EAZK-372

Location information

Muzeum regionu Valašsko - zámek Lešná, - 1, Lešná, Zlínský kraj

49.51968 N, 17.92971 E

Building area: 1059 m²

1133 LiDAR points (1.07 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	14.7	296.1	0.4	96.3
1	132.8	303.9	22.8	319.9
2	70.6	304.1	23.1	138.6
3	69.6	303.9	20.8	228.0
4	64.8	304.0	21.2	226.7
5	102.6	304.1	23.3	46.6
6	97.2	303.9	28.0	131.0
7	55.4	304.1	27.7	312.7
8	103.6	303.9	28.3	47.7
9	71.2	304.1	31.6	227.7

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	30.1	2.636
120 - 100	43.1	4.825
140 - 120	121.4	15.855
160 - 140	202.0	29.662
180 - 160	17.5	3.031
200 - 180	25.4	4.922
220 - 200	343.1	72.368
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	782.5	133.299

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	180 - 160	14.7	2.561	6	220 - 200	97.2	20.619
Total		14.7	2.561	Total		97.2	20.619
1	160 - 140	69.6	10.163	7	160 - 140	32.2	4.645
	140 - 120	44.3	5.779		140 - 120	8.1	1.053
	120 - 100	12.7	1.429		120 - 100	9.1	0.993
	< 100	6.3	0.603		< 100	6.0	0.530
Total		132.8	17.975	Total		55.4	7.221
2	220 - 200	63.2	13.491	8	160 - 140	31.0	4.463
	200 - 180	5.5	1.053		140 - 120	53.8	7.058
	180 - 160	1.8	0.316		120 - 100	9.4	1.093
Total		70.6	14.860		< 100	9.4	0.786
3	220 - 200	65.9	13.763	Total		103.6	13.399
	200 - 180	2.8	0.541	9	220 - 200	66.0	13.975
	180 - 160	0.9	0.154		200 - 180	3.1	0.598
	Total		69.6		14.457	140 - 120	2.1
4	220 - 200	50.8	10.520	Total		71.2	14.846
	200 - 180	14.0	2.731				
Total		64.8	13.251				
5	160 - 140	69.2	10.391				
	140 - 120	13.1	1.692				
	120 - 100	11.9	1.311				
	< 100	8.4	0.717				
Total		102.6	14.111				

eP-EAZK-373

Location information

Muzeum regionu Valašsko - kostel sv. Trojice, Sokolská -, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47068 N, 17.96528 E

Building area: 123 m²

165 LiDAR points (1.34 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	36.3	309.9	55.2	261.7
1	95.6	311.5	60.8	348.1
2	79.7	311.3	59.5	169.8

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	123.2	7.986
120 - 100	6.3	0.666
140 - 120	2.6	0.319
160 - 140	5.1	0.766
180 - 160	8.9	1.514
200 - 180	24.8	4.781
220 - 200	40.7	8.464
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	211.5	24.496

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	160 - 140	1.6	0.240	2	220 - 200	40.7	8.464
	140 - 120	0.8	0.097		200 - 180	24.8	4.781
	120 - 100	6.3	0.666		180 - 160	8.9	1.514
	< 100	27.6	2.299		160 - 140	3.5	0.526
	Total	36.3	3.303		140 - 120	1.8	0.222
1	< 100	95.6	5.687	Total	79.7	15.506	
	Total	95.6	5.687				

eP-EAZK-374, eP-EAZK-375

Location information

Muzeum regionu Valašsko, Zámecká 3/55, Valašské Meziříčí, Zlínský kraj

49.47843 N, 17.96836 E

Building area: 1217 m²

632 LiDAR points (0.52 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	37.1	302.1	2.7	267.3
1	13.9	302.6	21.5	247.3
2	7.0	303.0	1.3	82.3
3	24.6	302.6	19.1	67.9
4	10.0	302.8	24.7	247.2
5	306.2	311.4	35.5	68.1

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	1.1	0.107
120 - 100	12.6	1.431
140 - 120	26.3	3.454
160 - 140	342.7	53.166
180 - 160	16.1	2.703
200 - 180	0.0	0.000
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	398.8	60.860

■ Energy prediction - Detail

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)		
0	180 - 160	0.7	0.117	3	160 - 140	5.2	0.752		
	160 - 140	26.9	4.041		140 - 120	14.2	1.877		
	140 - 120	8.7	1.155		120 - 100	5.2	0.605		
	120 - 100	0.7	0.086		Total	24.6	3.233		
	Total	37.1	5.400	4	140 - 120	2.2	0.275		
1	180 - 160	9.5	1.597		120 - 100	6.7	0.740		
	160 - 140	4.3	0.645		< 100	1.1	0.107		
Total	13.9	2.242	Total	10.0	1.121	5	160 - 140	306.2	47.728
2	180 - 160	5.9	0.989	Total	306.2		47.728		
	140 - 120	1.2	0.147						
Total	7.0	1.136							

eP-EAZK-376

Location information

Muzeum regionu Valašsko - zámek Vsetín, Horní náměstí 2, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.34070 N, 17.99944 E

Building area: 2370 m²

2392 LiDAR points (1.01 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	197.9	395.9	33.4	128.6
1	141.4	395.9	0.4	221.5
2	195.4	392.0	9.0	129.2
3	14.0	392.1	58.8	218.2
4	97.4	392.2	59.6	218.1
5	289.0	395.9	33.2	218.1
6	197.3	395.8	33.3	38.0
7	120.3	396.1	33.6	308.8
8	112.3	391.7	56.7	38.2
9	251.5	395.8	33.5	38.0
10	33.6	396.0	39.5	218.5
11	10.4	391.5	32.6	137.5
12	44.1	395.6	6.6	187.9
13	44.6	396.1	33.9	316.0
14	22.1	392.1	32.1	135.0
15	107.5	395.6	58.2	317.0
16	144.9	391.6	33.6	317.8

■ Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	397.9	34.113
120 - 100	152.6	16.857
140 - 120	605.2	79.264
160 - 140	111.1	16.896
180 - 160	127.1	21.618
200 - 180	88.2	16.774
220 - 200	541.4	114.004
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	2023.5	299.525

■ Energy prediction - Detail (1/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	220 - 200	197.9	41.771	4	220 - 200	93.6	19.082
	Total	197.9	41.771		200 - 180	3.8	0.762
1	180 - 160	15.4	2.485	5	Total	97.4	19.844
	160 - 140	46.2	7.044		220 - 200	184.7	39.123
	140 - 120	25.2	3.283		200 - 180	53.6	10.271
	120 - 100	23.8	2.635		180 - 160	20.9	3.554
	< 100	30.8	2.633		160 - 140	20.9	3.241
	Total	141.4	18.080		140 - 120	6.0	0.791
2	200 - 180	15.8	2.873	120 - 100	3.0	0.337	
	180 - 160	71.1	12.213	Total	289.0	57.316	
	160 - 140	29.6	4.455	6	140 - 120	193.4	25.150
	140 - 120	41.5	5.408		120 - 100	2.0	0.196
	120 - 100	29.6	3.364		< 100	2.0	0.187
	< 100	7.9	0.715		Total	197.3	25.533
Total	195.4	29.029	7	140 - 120	74.5	10.125	
3	220 - 200	4.0		0.803	120 - 100	22.2	2.475
	200 - 180	8.0		1.549	< 100	23.5	2.003
	180 - 160	2.0	0.356	Total	120.3	14.602	
Total	14.0	2.708					

■ Energy prediction - Detail (2/2)

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)	Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
8	< 100	112.3	8.717	12	200 - 180	5.1	0.942
	Total	112.3	8.717		180 - 160	17.8	3.009
9	140 - 120	74.7	9.579	160 - 140	14.4	2.156	
	120 - 100	64.8	7.051	140 - 120	5.9	0.765	
	< 100	112.1	10.079	120 - 100	0.8	0.102	
	Total	251.5	26.709	Total	44.1	6.975	
10	220 - 200	28.8	6.222	13	140 - 120	38.2	5.007
	200 - 180	1.9	0.376		120 - 100	5.5	0.598
	140 - 120	1.0	0.132		< 100	0.9	0.079
	120 - 100	1.0	0.100	Total	44.6	5.684	
	< 100	1.0	0.088	14	220 - 200	22.1	4.750
	Total	33.6	6.918		Total	22.1	4.750
11	220 - 200	10.4	2.253	15	< 100	107.5	9.612
	Total	10.4	2.253		Total	107.5	9.612
				16	140 - 120	144.9	19.023
					Total	144.9	19.023

eP-EAZK-377

Location information

Muzeum regionu Valašsko - hvězdárna, Jabloňová 231, Vsetín, Zlínský kraj

49.34427 N, 17.99627 E

Building area: 196 m²

393 LiDAR points (2.01 points/m²)

Identified rooftops

Plane	Area (m ²)	Avg. height (m)	Tilt(°)	Azimuth(°)
0	162.0	391.0	1.3	1.9

Energy prediction - Summary

PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
< 100	0.0	0.000
120 - 100	0.0	0.000
140 - 120	0.0	0.000
160 - 140	0.0	0.000
180 - 160	0.0	0.000
200 - 180	162.0	30.047
220 - 200	0.0	0.000
240 - 220	0.0	0.000
> 240	0.0	0.000
Total	162.0	30.047

■ **Energy prediction - Detail**

Plane	PV Generation Level (kWh/m ² /year)	Area (m ²)	Total PV Generation (MWh/year)
0	200 - 180	162.0	30.047
Total		162.0	30.047